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About the project

FOODIE project aims at creating a platform hub on the cloud where spatial and non-spatial data related to agricultural sector is available for agri-food stakeholders groups and interoperable. It will offer: an infrastructure for the building of an interacting and collaborative network; the integration of existing open datasets related to agriculture; data publication and data linking of external agriculture data sources, providing specific and high-value applications and services for the support of planning and decision-making processes.

FOODIE project is addressed to four basic groups of users: a) stakeholders from the agriculture sector as end-users of final applications, b) public sector for communication with farmers about taxation, subsidies and regulation, c) researchers for large scale experimentation on real data and d) ICT companies for the development of new applications for agriculture and food sector, mainly using implemented tools

FOODIE specifically works on three pilots:

- Pilot 1: Precision Viticulture (Spain) will focus on the appropriate management of the inherent variability of crops,
- Pilot 2: Open Data for Strategic and Tactical Planning (Czech Republic) will focus on improving future management of agricultural companies (farms) by introducing new tools and management methods,
- Pilot 3: Technology allows integration of logistics via service providers and farm management including traceability (Germany).

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Glossary

The glossary of terms used in this deliverable can be found in the public document “FOODIE_Glossary.pdf” available at: <http://www.foodie-project.eu>

Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviation / Acronym	Description
ARVI	Atmospherically Resistant Vegetation Index
CEP	Complex Event Processing
CSW	Catalogue Service for Web
DRDSI	Danube Reference Data and Service Infrastructure
ESP	Event Stream Processing
EU	European Union
EVI	Enhanced Vegetation Index
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization
FAPAR	Fraction of Absorbed Photosynthetically Active Radiation
GCM	Generic Conceptual Model
GEMET	General Multilingual Environmental Thesaurus
GEO	Group on Earth Observations
GEOSS	Global Earth Observation System of Systems
GMES	Global Monitoring for Environment and Security
GEMI	Global Environment Monitoring Index
GML	Geography Markup Language
GNS	GeoNet Name Server
INSPIRE	Infrastructure for Spatial Information in Europe
MS	Multi Spectral
MSAVI	Modified Soil-Adjusted Vegetation Index
NALT	The National Agricultural Library's Agricultural Thesaurus
NBR	Normalized Burn Ratio
NIR	Near Infra-red
NDVI	Normalized Difference Vegetation Index
O&M	Observations & Measurements (Schema)
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
PAN	Panchromatic
REST	Representational State Transfer
RM-ODP	Reference Model for Object Distributed Processing
SAS	Sensor Alert Service
SAVI	Soil-Adjusted Vegetation Index
SATVI	Soil-Adjusted Total Vegetation Index
SDI	Spatial Data Infrastructure
SensorML	Sensor Model Language

Abbreviation / Acronym	Description
SES	Sensor Event Service
SOA	Service Oriented Architecture
SoiML	Soil Modelling Language
SOAP	Simple Object Access Protocol
SOS	Sensor Observations Service
SoS	System of Systems
SPS	Sensor Planning Service
SWE	Sensor Web Enablement
TGN	Getty Thesaurus of Geographical Names
TML	Transducer Markup Language
UML	Unified Modelling Language
VGI	Volunteered Geographic Information
VP	Viewpoint
W3C	World Wide Web Consortium
WCTS	Web Coordinate Transformation Service
WMS	Web Map Service
WNS	Web Notification Services
WPS	Web Processing Service
WCTS	Web Coordinate Transformation Service
XML	Extensible Mark-up Language
XSD	eXtensible Stylesheet Document

Table 1 Abbreviations and Acronyms

Executive Summary

The agriculture sector is of strategic importance for European society and economy. Due to its complexity, agri-food operators have to manage many different and heterogeneous sources of information. Agriculture requires collection, storage, sharing and analysis of large quantities of spatially and non-spatially referenced data. These data flows currently present a hurdle to uptake of precision agriculture as the multitude of data models, formats, interfaces and reference systems in use result in incompatibilities.

In order to plan and make economically and environmentally sound decisions a combination and management of information is needed. The key point of FOODIE project is creating a platform hub on the cloud where spatial and non-spatial data related to agricultural sector are available for agri-food stakeholders groups and interoperable. It will offer an infrastructure for the building of an interacting and collaborative network; the integration of existing open datasets related to agriculture; data publication and data linking of external agriculture data sources, providing specific and high-value applications and services for the support of planning and decision-making processes.

This document is the “State of the art analysis report” deliverable and its main objective is to collect information about standards, existing technologies, architectures and systems developed in other projects, as well as initiatives and policies and data sources repositories (specially at local, national and European level) which are relevant for defining and implementing the different aspects of the FOODIE platform hub for agricultural services.

The document starts by giving an overview of the informational challenges in the agricultural domain as well as to be objectives to be accomplished by the project in order to address these problems.

The next section focuses on those existing international and European initiatives that aim at facilitating the exchange and access to a wealth of heterogeneous data sets related to the environmental and agricultural domains and generated at different levels by the member states. This section also references to the main European policies that are directly involved in the agriculture sector (e.g., CAP, Water Framework Directive, etc.) and that have to be taken into account in the decision making process of the stakeholders.

Next, the Standards section covers the standards commonly used in the geospatial and environmental domains to encode, visualize and access to the datasets (e.g., sensor information), paying also attention to the specific standards used in the agriculture domain for exchanging information (e.g., agroXML and SoilML) as well as to standards necessary for semanting tagging and publishing the datasets contained in FOODIE platform.

The Results from relevant projects section provides an overview of the different architectural approaches followed by various projects in the environmental and agricultural domain which will provide the basis for designing FOODIE architecture and specifying its building blocks. In addition, this section also has a look at the results obtained by some projects in the areas of Big Data and Future Internet which are interesting from the point of view of the agriculture due the large volumes of data that can be generated over the time (e.g., sensor data from the in-situ sensors deployed on the farms, satellite imagery), its management, visualization and integration as well as in terms of new agriculture services that could be built/offered in the scope of the Future Internet architectures and paradigms respectively.

Then, the Data and knowledge sources section compiles an exhaustive list of openly available datasets and vocabularies that can be used in the scope of the project in order to improve the semanting tagging and publication of datasets within the platform repositories as well as by enabling the provision of improved tools and advisory services for the different stakeholders (by integrating and fusing these external data with the datasets stored in the FOODIE platform).

The Existing technologies and software solutions section focuses on the different available alternatives – many of the coming directly from the opensource geospatial community - that can be used as building blocks of the FOODIE service platform hub.

Finally, the document also includes a specific section related to the analysis of the different sensors and communication protocols used to communicate with/among them and which will be of relevance for deciding which the best option in each pilot is.

Some considerations should be taken into account when reading this document. Either standards or technologies are rapidly evolving and it is complicated to reflect the state-of-the-art of all of them. Therefore, this document comprises only those standards or technologies that the consortium partners have deemed useful at the time of defining the main building blocks of the system as well as based on their experience as ICT providers/integrators. Thus, the final decision about whether a given technology or standard will be used in the project is out of the scope of this document. As a rule the thumb, when considering similar technologies or standards we will try to use those in which we have a previous knowledge or experience. Nevertheless, only when defining thoroughly each component of the system, the best suitable standard or technology will be selected, using this document as a reference and source of information. Obviously, it could be the case that, in the future, we were using a non-previously identified technology or standard which shall be included in the architecture specification deliverable and its following updates.

1 Introduction

The agriculture sector is a unique sector due to its strategic importance for both European citizens (consumers) and economy (regional and global) which, ideally, should make the whole sector a network of interacting organizations. Rural areas are of particular importance with respect to the agri-food sector and should be specifically addressed within this scope.

The different groups of stakeholders involved in the agricultural activities have to manage many different and heterogeneous sources of information that need to be combined in order to make economically and environmentally sound decisions, which include among others the definition of policies (subsidies, standardisation and regulation, national strategies for rural development, climate change), valuation of ecological performances, development of sustainable agriculture, crop recollection, timing and pricing; plagues detection etc. Such processes are very labour intensive because most parts have to be executed manually and the necessary information is not always available or easily accessible.

In this context, future agriculture knowledge management systems have to support not only direct profitability of agriculture or environment protection, but also activities of individuals and groups allowing effective collaboration among groups in the agri-food industry, consumers, public administrations and wider stakeholders communities, especially in the rural domain.

In that sense, FOODIE project aims at

- building an open and interoperable agricultural specialized platform hub on the cloud for the management of spatial and non-spatial agriculture related data from heterogeneous sources;
- integrating of existing and valuable European open datasets related to agriculture;
- data publication and data linking of external agriculture data sources contributed by different public and private stakeholders, through an open and flexible lightweight Application Programming Interface (API), allowing
- providing specific and high-value applications and services for the support in the planning and decision-making processes of different stakeholders groups related to the agricultural and environmental domains,
- providing a marketplace where data can be discovered and exchanged but also external companies can publish their own agricultural application based on the data, services and applications provided by FOODIE.

FOODIE concepts and objectives will be realized by means of the resulting service platform hub, which will be demonstrated in three different pilots' scenarios across Europe, providing each of them thus a set of common and specific requirements:

- **Pilot 1: Precision Viticulture (Spain)** will focus on the appropriate management of the inherent variability of crops, an increase in economic benefits and a reduction of environmental impact.
- **Pilot 2: Open Data for Strategic and Tactical Planning (Czech Republic)** will focus on improving future management of agricultural companies (farms) by introducing new tools and management methods, which will follow the cost optimization path and reduction of environmental burden, improving the energy balance while maintaining the production level.
- **Pilot 3: Technology allows integration of logistics via service providers and farm management including traceability (Germany)**. This pilot will focus on integrating the German machinery cooperatives systems with existing farm management and logistic systems as well as to develop and enlarge existing cooperation and business models with the different chain partners to create win-win situations for all of them with the help of IT solutions.

In order to design and implement the aforementioned service platform proposed by FOODIE project, this document performs an in-depth review of the different aspects that must be considered to be inline with current initiatives and policies relevant in the environmental and agricultural domains as well as commonly and widely used standards, technologies, service oriented architectures and systems developed in other projects, together with the numerous data sources repositories available at local, national and European level that will enable the provision of new and added value agricultural services for the different stakeholders of the platform.

The following sections explain in a more detailed manner all these aspects to be considered.

2 Initiatives and policies

2.1 Initiatives related to the geospatial, environmental and agricultural domains

2.1.1 INSPIRE

The European Commission started the initiative called INSPIRE, INfrastructure for SPatial InfoRmation in Europe, to deal with the issues of efficient discovery and presentation of geographic information. This initiative was transformed in 2007 into the Directive of the European Commission and the Council with designation 2007/2/EC. This Directive was transposed into national legal systems of the EU (European Union) Member states between 2007 and 2009. The Directive itself contains the general concept, while more detailed information may be found in the corresponding Commission Regulations addressing specific issues, as well as in the underlying technical guidelines.

These are, so far, interoperability of spatial data, metadata of spatial data and services, data and service sharing, network services. The directive defines 34 spatial data themes covering a wide range from agriculture, coordinate reference systems, cadastral parcels, transport networks, hydrography, land cover, orthoimagery, soil, human health and safety, natural risk zones, habitats and biotopes, energy resources, buildings, and many others. We may also define interoperability on the conceptual and policy levels. INSPIRE Directive is closely related to other European Directives, international standards and standardization activities, etc. We may find examples in the linkages to European Noise Directive, Water Framework Directive, International Organisation for Standardization (ISO) 19100 series of standards for geographic information or implementation specifications of the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC).

The INSPIRE concept of geographic data follows an object-oriented approach of modelling the entities of the real world. This means that one or more application schemas covering each specific point of view(s) on the domain are created. Each application schema then contains explicit definitions of feature types, their aggregation into classes, attributes of feature types, domains of these attributes, etc. The primary aim is to develop a model which will ensure interoperability and harmonisation within each spatial data topic. Each application schema is offered in a number of ways, such as through a UML (Unified Modelling Language) class diagram, feature catalogue, XSD (eXtensible Stylesheet Document), and, of course, textual descriptions. Besides the application schemas themselves, the concept of INSPIRE geographic data also includes related aspects. These are definitions of the reference systems (coordinate, vertical as well as temporal), quality of geographic data, metadata and many others. On the other hand, common issues for all spatial data topics are written in the Generic Conceptual Model (GCM) document, which comprises definitions of unique identifiers for geographic data, explicit definition of data types, principles of network application schemas, multi-lingual geographic information, etc.

Geographic data, as well as services working with geographic data, always have to be accompanied by INSPIRE metadata. The importance of metadata, in the XML (eXtensible Markup Language) format, is highlighted by its necessity for the discovery process within INSPIRE network services.

INSPIRE network services represent a group of four kinds of services tied the management of geographic data: discovery, view, download and transformation services. Discovery services allow one to search for geographic data and services based on the full-text, spatial and temporal queries that are executed on the above mentioned metadata. The results of searching are again the metadata. It is possible to find information about the data provider, origin, date of creation, keywords, fees, scale, etc. The metadata also contain relevant links for other services. One link may lead to the viewing service that is a modification of OGC (Open Geospatial Consortium) Web Map Service (WMS). As such, a view service may be connected with WMS support by a Geographic Information System. Geographic data in PNG and GIF formats may then be previewed. Another link from the metadata may lead to a download service. This service may be in two main forms; a Web service or direct access, for example, of pre-prepared files of spatial data in an archive. Transformation services described in this article are divided into two main categories; transformation services for coordinate transformations and transformation services for content transformations.

We may define two levels of the INSPIRE documents from a data provider point of view:

- Commission Regulations that are obligatory in all European Member States;
- Implementing Rules that accomplish the Commission Regulations on the technical level, which is not legally obligatory.

The complexity of INSPIRE may be documented by the following numbers: almost 300,000 (April 2014) discoverable spatial data sets and dataset series, as well as more than 25,000 network services for 34 spatial data topics. We may expect that these numbers will increase till year 2020 when is, so far, foreseen the end of the INSPIRE implementation phase.

Metadata

Metadata is a crucial INSPIRE component since the Directive is aimed at the discovery of the geographic information. INSPIRE metadata consist of circa 25 metadata elements that are intended to bring the basic description of a dataset, dataset series and/or a Web service. Such metadata elements are title, abstract, keywords, date of creation, language, lineage, scale denominator, conditions applied to access and use, responsible organisation etc. Each metadata element has strictly defined the value domain to text, integer, coordinates with at least two decimal places, date according to the ISO 8601 etc. Cardinality is defined as well, expressed as, for instance, 1..N, 0..1. XML (eXtensible Markup Language) encoding in the form as defined in EN ISO 19139 is required to support the automatic metadata processing.

Network services

Metadata itself does not assure neither the discoverability nor the access to geographic information. On the other hand, metadata are crucial for both processes in any infrastructure for spatial information. Therefore, metadata are used in all kinds of INSPIRE network services as described below.

Discovery services

These kind of network services are intended for efficient discovery of geographic data and services which is based on metadata. The concept of INSPIRE discovery service is based on the implementation of *Open Geospatial Consortium* (OGC) called *Catalogue Service for Web* (CSW) [98]. There is defined an interface between a server and a client that enables to search for geographic data and services. A user accesses a client application that is mostly in the form of a Web page. Typical client applications are geo-portals that allow to search in several federated catalogues. We may identify geo-portals of data providers (see for instance <http://geoportal.COSMC.cz>), national geo-portals aggregating geographic data and services from one country (as for example <http://geoportal.gov.cz>) as well as European geo-portal integrating catalogues around the Europe (see <http://inspire-geoportal.ec.europa.eu/discovery/>).

Communication to a discovery service begins similarly to other kinds of INSPIRE network services, i.e. through the *Get Discovery Service Metadata* operation (*Capabilities* operation respectively in the OGC concept). The *Get Discovery Service Metadata* operation offers the possibility to obtain the basic information about the requested service, such as owner, which information is available, fees etc. The following operation is called *Discover Metadata* (*GetRecords* according to the OGC). The *Discover Metadata* operation allows combination of logical, mathematical and spatial operators for the efficient discovery. For instance, it enables to ask "I am searching for the geographic data on hydrography that cover the southern part of the Czech Republic, are in a more detailed scale than 1:50.000 and were updated after 2005". Results of such queries are metadata again, with a linkage to a view service, download service and e-shop (in the case of chargeable data). The last operation of a INSPIRE discovery service is called *Publish metadata* (*Harvest* and *Transaction* according to the OGC) that are intended for metadata transmissions between servers providing discovery services (like in the case of geo-portals).

View services

The concept of INSPIRE view services originates in the OGC implementation specification called *Web Map Service* (WMS) in version 1.3.0 (see [99]) that is at the same time the ISO 19128 standard. It is assumed that metadata as result of a discovery service contain a link to a view service. We may then see the preview of geographic data to evaluate whether we would like to obtain data through a download service or not. Preview of geographic data may be in view services degraded.

View services contain two basic operations:

- *Get View Service Metadata (GetCapabilities* in the OGC WMS) with similar structure and functionality as in the case of INSPIRE discovery services,
- *Get Map (GetMap* according to the OGC). First, we need to define parameters of a *Get Map* request like which layers we would like to preview, in which coordinate reference system, width and height of a preview image, etc. We receive an image in the GIF or PNG format as a result to a request with such parameters. It is obliged to publish legends for a preview of geographic data as well.

Please note that the OGC WMS contains the *GetFeatureInfo* operation that is not specified within INSPIRE.

Download services

Each data provider may choose whether (s)he will publish geographic data through so-called direct access or indirect access approach.

The so-called indirect access approach is a Web service very similar to the OGC *Web Feature Service (WFS)*. The basic operations are:

- *Get Download Service Metadata (GetCapabilities* according to the OGC),
- *Get Spatial Object (GetFeature* in the OGC concept) allowing the retrieval of spatial objects based upon a query,
- *Describe Spatial Object Type (DescribeFeature* respectively) that contains the description of spatial objects in the requested dataset.

Data are usually available on a Web page or FTP (File Transfer Protocol) server when using the so-called direct access approach. On the other hand, there shall be established an interface allowing a user to query data through language, identifier of a dataset, coordinate reference system, query on any attribute, spatial data theme and minimum bounding box. Queries like the following one should be therefore supported: "I would like to download spatial data on parcels used for agriculture between Prague and Brno that were updated after 2002, have the area greater than 5 hectares and are in the coordinate reference system WGS-84".

Transformation services

We may identify two main groups of these services: coordinate and content.

The coordinate transformation services are originating from the OGC implementation specification called as *Web Coordinate Transformation Service (WCTS*, see [100]) or from the INSPIRE profile for OGC *Web Processing Service (WPS)* as described by [101]. The aim of coordinate transformation services is a support of data transformation from one coordinate reference system to another. Such motivation originates from the fact that INSPIRE requires ETRS89 coordinate system as the default for all data.

On the other hand, content transformation services are tightly connected to the structure of data; therefore they cannot be as general as coordinate transformation services. Two basic operations of are, so far, assumed:

- *Get Transformation Service Metadata (GetCapabilities* according to the OGC),
- *Transform* defining the input data, source and result data models,

It is obvious that the *Transform* operation is the most complicated one. INSPIRE does not assume the OGC *DescribeProcess* operation that would enable providing the transformation details, such as allowed inputs and outputs (formats, structure, etc.), partial transformation methods and transformation criteria. For that reason, the INSPIRE content transformation services appear as a "black box".

Application schemas

The INSPIRE concept of geographic data follows an object-oriented approach of modelling the entities of the real world. This means that one or more application schemas covering each specific point of view(s) on the domain are created (see Figure 1). Each application schema then contains explicit definitions of feature types, their aggregation into classes, attributes of feature types, domains of these attributes, etc. The primary aim is to develop a model which will ensure interoperability and harmonisation within each spatial data topic. Each application

schema is offered in a number of ways, such as through a UML (*Unified Modelling Language*) class diagram, feature catalogue, XSD (*eXtensible Stylesheet Document*), and, of course, textual descriptions. Besides the application schemas themselves, the concept of INSPIRE geographic data also includes related aspects. These are definitions of the reference systems (coordinate, vertical as well as temporal), quality of geographic data, metadata and many others.

Figure 1 Example on the scope of INSPIRE application schema for hydrography.

(adopted from D2.8.1.7 INSPIRE Data Specification on Hydrography – Guidelines, version 3.1 [102])

Figure 2 Formalised expression of the application schema hydrography through the UML class diagram.

(adopted from D2.8.1.7 INSPIRE Data Specification on Hydrography – Guidelines, version 3.1, modified [102])

Application schema depicted in Figure 1 is then elaborated in the UML (*Unified Modelling Language*) class diagrams. For instance, top right of the Figure 2 depicts the object type *SurfaceWater* that is only an abstraction for two object types, *Watercourse* and *StandingWater*. Each object type contains an explicit attribute definition. For example, the *StandingWater* object type consists of attributes *elevation*, *meanDepth* and *surphaceArea*. The object type *StandingWater* also inherits the attributes from the abstract *SurfaceWater* object type, i.e. from *geometry* to *tidal*. Each attribute has an explicit definition of the data type. For instance, it is *boolean* in the case of the *tidal* attribute that allows only two possible values – true, false. Some attributes originating from code lists, e.g. *widthRange*, may be enhanced for the values of a data provider. INSPIRE application schemas in general may contains a stereotype *voidable*. Such stereotype designates that an attribute shall be provided if available or derivable at reasonable cost. A data provider then adds an explnation why a value cannot be provided, such as unknown, unpopulated or withheld.

The INSPIRE data specification for the spatial data theme *Agricultural and aquaculture facilities* consists of one conceptual model. As stated in this data specification “*The thematic scope of this data specification is aimed to provide a solid framework for mapping, reporting and modelling purposes. This is necessary to support policy formulation through better reporting and management of pan European initiatives, such as waste management, water, animal movements, epidemiological control, food traceability, etc. where Agricultural and Aquaculture Facilities data fulfils a function in relating information to real world objects.*”

Data published under INSPIRE shall be encoded according to the ISO 19118 standard (Geographic information – Encoding). The ISO 19118 standard is tightly related to another ISO standard, ISO 19136 (Geographic information – Geography Markup Language; GML). The GML, the XML-based grammar, is therefore the default encoding for data published under INSPIRE. The XML schemas for all INSPIRE spatial data themes, including agriculture, are provided at the official INSPIRE Website¹.

¹ <http://inspire.jrc.ec.europa.eu>

2.1.2 GMES/Copernicus

Copernicus, previously known and herein-after referred to as Global Monitoring for Environment and Security (GMES), is a European system for monitoring the Earth. The main objective of GMES is to monitor and better understand our environment. GMES serves decision-makers who rely on strategic information with regard to environmental and security issues with an independent and permanent access to reliable data [103].

The purpose of GMES is to deliver information which corresponds to the user needs. The processing and dissemination of this information is carried out within the "GMES service component". The thematic areas within the GMES service component comprise:

- land, marine and atmosphere information – ensuring systematic monitoring and forecasting the state of the Earth's subsystems at regional and global levels;
- climate change information – helping to monitor the effects of climate change, assessing mitigation measures and contributing to the knowledge base for adaptation policies and investments;
- emergency and security information – providing support in the event of emergencies and humanitarian aid needs, in particular to civil protection authorities, also to produce accurate information on security related aspects (e.g. maritime surveillance, border control, global stability, etc.)

The GMES service component depends on Earth observation data collected from space (satellites), air (e.g. airborne instruments, balloons to record stratosphere data), water (e.g. floats, shipboard instruments) or land (e.g. measuring stations, seismographs). These facilities are commonly called as GMES infrastructure component; non-space based installations in the GMES infrastructure component are generally referred to as "in situ component". The GMES architecture is portrayed in Figure 3 [104].

2.1.2.1 GIO GLOBAL LAND COMPONENT

The Global Land (GL) Component in the framework of GMES Initial Operations (GIO) is earmarked as a component of the Land service to operate "a multi-purpose service component" that will provide a series of biogeophysical products on the status and evolution of land surface at global scale. Production and delivery of the parameters are to take place in a timely manner and are complemented by the constitution of long term time series (Global Land Component)².

The Global land service should therefore include the following components:

- a) A global systematic monitoring service (to be deployed as first priority and based on low and medium resolution satellite data) providing near real time biogeophysical parameters at global scale on vegetation state and dynamics and on land cover change
- b) A hot spot ad hoc monitoring service, actionable upon request, for limited geographical coverage in specific regions, with a low revisit frequency, and with high resolution satellite data.
- c) Based on this multi-purpose service component a set of thematic services should be developed to address EU sectoral policies in specific thematic areas.

In line with this consensus working paper, the deployment of the Global Land Component is limited in the framework of GMES Initial Operations (GIO) to the operation of: the "multi-purpose service component" for global systematic monitoring.

² <http://land.copernicus.eu/global/>

Production and delivery of the parameters are to take place in a timely manner and are complemented by the constitution of long term time series. Specific attention is given to continuity and consistency of production with previous pre-operational activities already serving the policies described in the consensus working paper, in particular avoiding gaps in the operational phase and ensuring time consistency of the generated parameters.

The Global Land Component contains a ‘Distribution’ component with an activity line ‘data access’. This activity includes the operation of a data storage capacity with data distribution through the internet (FTP) and through broadcast satellite (EUMETCast). The current FTP distribution system relies on the available infrastructures at the beginning of the Global Land service, being the Geoland2 Spatial Data Infrastructure (SDI) and the DevCoCast website. The FTP distribution service is an important means interacting with the users, and it is commonly known that such an interface can boost (or hamper) the use of the Global Land service products [105].

2.1.3 Shared Environmental Information System (SEIS)

Shared Environmental Information System (SEIS) is based on the following principles [106]:

- Managing all environmental information as closely as possible to its source.
- Collecting environmental information once, and sharing it with others.
- Making environmental information available to public authorities.
- Making environmental information readily accessible to end-users to enable them to assess the state of the environment in a timely fashion.
- Making environmental information accessible to enable comparisons at the appropriate geographical scale.
- Making environmental information fully available to general public.

Figure 4 Shared Environmental Information Systems – peeling the onion (after Weets 2007)

The concept of SEIS is based on information support for implementation of European Environmental Policies. The SEIS is mainly top-down driven and involves participation of mainly public organisations.

The authors consider as important to continue with the SISE vision as a complementary initiative to SEIS. This should ensure [107]:

- bottom up approach;
- participation of public bodies, private initiatives, communities and social networks in SISE building;
- sharing of information, its analysis and modelling;
- education, participation access to information, protection, preparedness;
- sharing not only data but also services.

2.1.4 Single Information Space in Europe for the Environment (SISE)

In 2005 the European Commission launched the i2010 strategy: A European Information Society for Growth and Employment. The Commission defined three pillars for i2010 (Commission of the European Communities 2005):

- Single European Information Space;
- Innovation and Investment;
- Inclusive European Information Society.

The objectives of the Single European Information Space are to offer high-bandwidth communications, rich content and digital services with a market-oriented regulatory framework.

The concept of **Single Information Space in Europe for the Environment (SISE)**³ was formulated for the first time

³ <http://inspire-forum.jrc.ec.europa.eu/pg/groups/10035/single-information-space-in-europe-for-environment-sise/>

in 2005 as part of the Single European Information Space defined in i2010. The idea was that environmental institutions, service providers and citizens can collaborate or use available information without technical restraints. The following schema defines the relation of SISE and other ongoing European initiatives.

The final vision of SISE was defined by the workshop of European experts in February 2008. The main objectives of SISE are as follows [108]:

- **SISE Context**
 - Complexity Management;
 - Environmental Legislation in Europe;
- **Application/Services**
 - SISE Services;
 - Process Chaining & Uncertainties;
 - Real-time Mapping & Modelling;
 - Thesauri;
 - Open Standards & Open Source Software;
- **SISE Open Semantics & Standards**
 - Standardisation & Framework Projects;
 - Standardisation & Community Knowledge;
 - Semantic Web Technologies for the SISE;
 - Ontologies;
- **Data Interoperability & Web Communities**
 - Web 2.0 Technologies;
 - Data Provision in the Semantic Web;
 - SOA/Web Services & Model Driven Communities;
 - Social SISE;
- **Data Visualisation & Modelling including Risk Assessment**
 - Visualisation of Environmental Data;
 - SOA & Semantic Web Services;
 - Simulation & Modelling;
 - Complex 3D/4D Models;
 - Chained Web Services & Legacy Systems;
- **SISE Deployment Models**
 - From Framework Projects to Market Deployment;
 - Project's Knowledge Loss;
 - Regional Application of European Interoperability Standards;
 - SISE & Business Models;
 - Environmental Information Service Economy (EISE).

2.1.5 Global Earth Observation System of Systems (GEOSS)

The vision for Global Earth Observation System of Systems (GEOSS) is to “realize that the originators of future decisions and activities for the benefit of humankind are well informed thanks to coordinated, comprehensive and sustained Earth observations” [109]. GEOSS must provide access and improved interoperability both for the existing and future observation systems. GEOSS is based on voluntary contribution of governments and international organizations.

The Global Earth Observation System of Systems (GEOSS) has been built by the Group on Earth Observations (GEO). There currently exists an implementation plan for the period 2005 to 2015. The GEOSS is a user centric initiative, which is focused on better utilisation of environmental data and decision-support tools by users. The main focus is on Earth observations on global scale. The goal is to deploy global infrastructure, which will be able to supply near-real-time environmental data, information and analyses for a wide range of users. The focus of GEOSS is on nine areas called “Societal Benefit Areas”. They include: **disasters, health, energy, climate, water, weather, ecosystems, agriculture and biodiversity.**

2.1.5.1 Global Agricultural Monitoring System of Systems

The Group on Earth Observations (GEO) / Integrated Global Observing Strategy (IGOL) Agricultural Monitoring Community of Practice was established in July of 2007 at the second IGOL/GEO workshop convened at the headquarters of the UN Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) in Rome. This community of practice represents twenty-five national and international organizations concerned with agricultural monitoring. Its purpose is to develop and implement a strategy for global agricultural monitoring in the framework of GEO.

The GEO acknowledges sustainable agriculture as one of the critical societal benefit areas (SBA) for international cooperation and collaboration. The agriculture SBA calls for an operational system for monitoring global agriculture that includes the following three main functional components:

- Global mapping and monitoring of changes in distribution of cropland area and the associated cropping systems
- Global monitoring of agricultural production leading to accurate and timely reporting of national agricultural statistics and accurate forecasting of shortfalls in crop production and food supply and facilitating reduction of risk and increased productivity at a range of scales; and,
- Effective early warning of famine, enabling the timely mobilization of an international response in food aid [110].

2.1.5.2 GEO Global Agricultural Monitoring (GeoGLAM)

GEOGLAM⁴, the GEO Global Agricultural Monitoring initiative was initially launched by the Group of Twenty (G20) Agriculture Ministers in June 2011, in Paris. The initiative forms part of the G20 Action Plan on Food Price Volatility, which also includes the Agricultural Market Information System (AMIS)⁵, another inter-institutional initiative hosted by the UN Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO). The G20 Ministerial Declaration states that GEOGLAM “will strengthen global agricultural monitoring by improving the use of remote sensing tools for crop production projections and weather forecasting”. By providing coordinated Earth observations from satellites and integrating them with ground-based and other in-situ measurements, the initiative will contribute to generating reliable, accurate, timely and sustained crop monitoring information and yield forecasts.

2.1.5.3 GEOSS Architecture Implementation Pilot

The GEOSS Architecture Implementation Pilot is common initiative of GEOSS and Open Geospatial Consortia (OGC – detail description of OGC is in chapter about standards). The GEOSS Architecture Implementation Pilot (AIP)⁶ develops and deploys new process and infrastructure components for the GEOSS Common Infrastructure (GCI) and the broader GEOSS architecture.

2.1.6 European Union Location Framework (EULF)

The objective of this action is to create a European Union Location Framework (EULF) addressing the EU-wide, cross-sector interoperability framework for the exchange and sharing of location data and services. The EULF will consist of a package of legal acts, methodologies, specifications (and standards), guidelines, and training materials required by public administration and stakeholder communities to facilitate the implementation, use and the generalisation of the Infrastructure for Spatial Information in the European Community (INSPIRE) to a wider location context independently of the thematic sector (as part of e-government programmes).

The activities will contribute to the update of Reference Interoperability Agreements (RIA) and to the definition of a common vision for a European Interoperability Architecture (EIA) based on lessons learnt from sectorial projects or from large scale pilots, to monitoring the contribution of ISA interoperability actions and other projects, to the implementation of the common vision for the EIA. The activities might also include the development of tools, guidelines on how to use the RIA, pro-active participation in standardisation efforts, etc.

To work with the Member States and the concerned Commission services towards a joint vision on the EIA for a

⁴ <http://www.geoglam-crop-monitor.org>

⁵ <http://www.amis-outlook.org>

⁶ http://www.earthobservations.org/geoss_call_aip.shtml

European Public Services (its scope, the articulation of the main architectural building blocks and the need for interface standards between such architectural building blocks). To assess the need and the relevance of having common infrastructure services drafting of the Framework through an iterative process based on workshops with standardization bodies and Member States' representatives.

Benefits:

- Increased awareness of the benefits of using geospatial data and interoperable location base services for innovation and growth.
- A recognized and coherent location framework facilitating the exchange and sharing of location data, as well as the development and interoperable location based services.
- Increased interoperability between public administrations and leverage of investments.
- Enhanced use of standards in Europe and of quality information contributing to the digital single market goals.
- Increased coherence and consistency in EU policies.

2.1.7 Global Open Data for Agriculture and Nutrition (GODAN)

The Global Open Data for Agriculture and Nutrition (GODAN)⁷ initiative seeks to support global efforts to make agricultural and nutritionally relevant data available, accessible, and usable for unrestricted use worldwide. The initiative focuses on building high-level policy and public and private institutional support for open data. The initiative encourages collaboration and cooperation among existing agriculture and open data activities, without duplication, and brings together all stakeholders to solve long-standing global problems.

Open access to research, and open publication of data, are vital resources for food security and nutrition, driven by farmers, farmer organizations, researchers, extension experts, policy makers, governments, and other private sector and civil society stakeholders participating in "innovation systems" and along value chains. Lack of institutional, national, and international policies and openness of data limit the effectiveness of agricultural and nutritional data from research and innovation. Making open data work for agriculture and nutrition requires a shared agenda to increase the supply, quality, and interoperability of data, alongside action to build capacity for the use of data by all stakeholders.

The GODAN initiative is a voluntary association brought together around a shared purpose. Launched in October 2013, the initiative welcomes all those who share this purpose to join as members and to participate in shaping coordinated activities that can deliver on the potential of open data for agriculture and nutrition. Together, initiative partners seek to support this initiative through the following guidelines and principles.

In line with global movements for open data and open access, the initiative seeks to:

- advocate for open data and open access policies by default, in both public and private sectors, whilst respecting and working to balance openness with legitimate concerns in relation to privacy, security, community rights and commercial interests;
- advocate for the release and re-usability of data in support of Innovation and Economic Growth, Improved Service Delivery and Effective Governance, and Improved Environmental and Social Outcomes;

With a focus on open data for agriculture and nutrition, the initiative seeks to:

- advocate for new and existing open data initiatives to set a core focus on agriculture and nutrition data;
- encourage the agreement on and release of a common set of agricultural and nutrition data;
- by increasing widespread awareness of ongoing activities, innovations, and good practices;
- advocate for collaborative efforts on future agriculture and nutrition open data endeavours; and,
- advocate programs, good practices, and lessons learned that enable the use of open data particularly by and for the rural and urban poor.

⁷ <http://godan.info>

2.1.8 Consultative Group on International Agricultural Research (CGIAR)

CGIAR⁸ is a global partnership that unites organizations engaged in research for a food secure future.

The name CGIAR comes from the acronym for the Consultative Group on International Agricultural Research. In 2008 CGIAR underwent a major transformation. To reflect this and yet retain our roots we have kept CGIAR as our name.

CGIAR research is dedicated to reducing rural poverty, increasing food security, improving human health and nutrition, and ensuring more sustainable management of natural resources. It is carried out by 15 centres that are members of the CGIAR Consortium, in close collaboration with hundreds of partner organizations, including national and regional research institutes, civil society organizations, academia, and the private sector.

The 15 research centres generate and disseminate knowledge, technologies, and policies for agricultural development through the CGIAR Research Programs. The CGIAR Fund provides reliable and predictable multi-year funding to enable research planning over the long term, resource allocation based on agreed priorities, and the timely and predictable disbursement of funds. The multi-donor trust fund finances research carried out by the centres through the CGIAR Research Programs.

2.1.9 Digital Earth

A new wave of technological innovation allowing us to capture, store, process and display an unprecedented amount of information about our planet and a wide variety of environmental and cultural phenomena were the main motivations for establishing a concept like the Digital Earth. Such designation of a concept was for the first time given by former United States' vice president Al Gore in 1998.

According to the Gore, A. (1998) *"The hard part of taking advantage of this flood of geospatial information will be making sense of it. - turning raw data into understandable information. Today, we often find that we have more information than we know what to do with. [...] I believe we need a "Digital Earth". A multi-resolution, three-dimensional representation of the planet, into which we can embed vast quantities of geo-referenced data."* We may identify six technologies that were identified as crucial to support the idea of the Digital Earth:

- Computational Science;
- Mass Storage;
- Satellite Imagery;
- Broadband Networks;
- Interoperability;
- Metadata.

At the same time, there were identified **five desired applications** that may broaden in future. **The application called "Increasing agricultural productivity"** is depicted as one of those five applications. There was identified the need to combine satellite imagery and global positioning systems for early detection of diseases and pests, and to target the application of pesticides, fertilizer and water to those parts of their fields that need it the most. In other words, there is emphasized the idea of precision farming.

We may identify four major achievements in the last decade that significantly contribute to the idea of the Digital Earth:

- Geoviewers enabling the public to browse through the virtual globes like Google Earth, NASA World Wind, Bing Maps, etc.;
- Spatial data infrastructures based on standards to achieve interoperability like INSPIRE (see 2.1.1 INSPIRE);
- Sensor networks where the Sensor Web Enablement is one of the most visible standardization activities (see section 3.1.3 Sensor Web Enablement for further details);
- Volunteered geographic information allowing to obtain a huge volume of data from both expert and non-expert groups through the Web (see also section **¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.**);

⁸ <http://www.cgiar.org/who-we-are>

- Big data as the collection of data sets so large and complex that it becomes hard to process them through “traditional” processing applications (see section 4.3 Big data).

Development integrating the above mentioned achievements through the crucial technologies for the agricultural domain may increase the complexity and usefulness of the Digital Earth concept. The whole Digital Earth community may then benefit from such development.

2.2 European policies of relevance

2.2.1 Common Agriculture Policy (CAP)

The Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) is the agricultural policy of the European Union. It implements a system of agricultural subsidies and other programmes (such as the Common_Agricultural_Policy⁹). EU farm policy evolved considerably since the 19th to help farmers face new challenges. Now main priorities are:

- enabling farmers to produce enough safe, high-quality food (cereals, meat, dairy, fruit, vegetables, wine...) for European consumers, contribute to a diversified rural economy and apply the highest standards of care concerning the environment and farm animals
- helping consumers make informed choices about their food, through voluntary EU quality-labelling schemes. These labels – indicating geographical origin, use of traditional ingredients or methods (including organic) – also help make EU farm products competitive on world markets
- promoting innovation in farming and food processing (aided by EU research projects) to increase productivity and reduce environmental impacts, e.g. using crop by-products and waste products to produce energy
- encouraging fair trade relations with developing countries – by suspending export subsidies for farm products and making it easier for developing countries to export their products to the EU [111].

The current CAP reform started in 2010. The decision making process differed from previous reforms, with the European Parliament for the first time acting as co-legislator with the Council.

For more than twenty years, starting in 1992, the CAP has been through successive reforms which have increased market orientation for agriculture while providing income support and safety net mechanisms for producers, improved the integration of environmental requirements and reinforced support for rural development across the EU.

The new policy continues along this reform path, moving from product to producer support and now to a more land – based approach. This is in response to the challenges facing the sector, many of which are driven by factors that are external to agriculture. These have been identified as economic (including food security and globalisation, a declining rate of productivity growth, price volatility, pressures on production costs due to high input prices and the deteriorating position of farmers in the food supply chain), environmental (relating to resource efficiency, soil and water quality and threats to habitats and biodiversity) and territorial (where rural areas are faced with demographic, economic and social developments including depopulation and relocation of businesses) [112].

2.2.2 Water Framework Directive (WFD)

The Water Framework Directive (Directive 2000/60/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 October 2000 establishing a framework for Community action in the field of water policy) is a European Union directive which commits European Union member states to achieve good qualitative and quantitative status of all water bodies (including marine waters up to one nautical mile from shore) by 2015. It is a framework in the sense that it prescribes steps to reach the common goal rather than adopting the more traditional limit value approach.

The Directive aims for 'good status' for all ground and surface waters (rivers, lakes, transitional waters, and coastal waters) in the EU.

⁹ http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Common_Agricultural_Policy

The ecological and chemical status of surface waters is assessed according to the following criteria:

- Biological quality (fish, benthic invertebrates, aquatic flora)
- Hydromorphological quality such as river bank structure, river continuity or substrate of the river bed
- Physical-chemical quality such as temperature, oxygenation and nutrient conditions
- Chemical quality that refers to environmental quality standards for river basin specific pollutants. These standards specify maximum concentrations for specific water pollutants. If even one such concentration is exceeded, the water body will not be classed as having a “good ecological status” [113][114].

Agriculture was recognized as one from key sectors influencing water quality. The main focus is on next points:

- Buffer strips
- Establishment and preservation of wetlands
- Reduce water abstraction
- Reduce fertilization
- Avoiding spreading fertiliser and manure at high risk times and places
- Plant cover in winter
- Catch crops
- Application techniques of manure
- Capacity of manure storage
- Erosion minimising cultivation system [115]

2.2.3 Nitrate Directive

The Nitrates Directive (1991) aims to protect water quality across Europe by preventing nitrates from agricultural sources polluting ground and surface waters and by promoting the use of good farming practices. The Nitrates Directive forms an integral part of the Water Framework Directive and is one of the key instruments in the protection of waters against agricultural pressures. Nitrate directive define next steps for implementation:

- Identification of surface waters and groundwater affected by pollution (or at risk) based on criteria described by the Directive (specifically when the concentration of nitrates in groundwater or surface water (especially those intended for drinking water) reaches more than 50 mg/l or when the surface water found to be eutrophic (or could become eutrophic)
- Designation of Nitrate Vulnerable Zones (Areas of land that become polluted by nitrates - in Europe they are identified as vulnerable when they exceed or being at risk of exceeding 50 mg/l of nitrates)
- Establishment of a code of Good Agricultural Practice to be implemented by farmers on a voluntary basis to prevent nitrate losses to water by leaching and run-off.
- Setting up compulsory action programmes to be implemented by farmers who work in Nitrate Vulnerable Zones (NVZs) based on measures listed in the Good Agricultural Codes and those concerning the limitation of fertilizer application (Nitrates_Directive)¹⁰.

2.2.4 Habitats Directive

Council Directive 92/43/EEC on the Conservation of natural habitats and of wild fauna and flora, known as the Habitats Directive was adopted in 1992. The Directive is the means by which the European Union meets its obligations under the Bern Convention. The Directive applies to the UK and to its Overseas Territory of Gibraltar. The Habitats Directive (together with the Birds Directive) forms the cornerstone of Europe's nature conservation policy. It is built around two pillars: the Natura 2000 network of protected sites and the strict system of species protection (Habitats Directive)¹¹ [116].

The main aim of the Habitats Directive is to promote the maintenance of biodiversity by requiring Member States to take measures to maintain or restore natural habitats and wild species at a favourable conservation status, introducing robust protection for those habitats and species of European importance. In applying these measures Member States are required to take account of economic, social and cultural requirements, as well as

¹⁰ http://www.theseusproject.eu/wiki/Nitrates_Directive

¹¹ http://ec.europa.eu/environment/nature/legislation/habitatsdirective/index_en.htm

regional and local characteristics. The provisions of the Directive require Member States to introduce a range of measures, including:

- Maintain or restore European protected habitats and species listed in the Annexes at a favourable conservation status
- Contribute to a coherent European ecological network of protected sites by designating Special Areas of Conservation (SACs) for habitats and for species. These measures are also to be applied to Special Protection Areas classified under Article 4 of the Birds Directive.
- Ensure conservation measures are in place to appropriately manage SACs and ensure appropriate assessment of plans and projects likely to have a significant effect on the integrity of an SAC. Projects may still be permitted if there are no alternatives, and there are imperative reasons of overriding public interest. In such cases compensatory measures are necessary to ensure the overall coherence of the Natura 2000 network
- Member States shall also endeavour to encourage the management of features of the landscape that support the Natura 2000 network
- Undertake surveillance of habitats and species,
- Ensure strict protection of species.
- Report on the implementation of the Directive every six years, including assessment of the conservation status of species and habitats (Council Directive 92/43/EEC on the Conservation of natural habitats and of wild fauna and flora)¹²

2.2.4.1 Natura 2000

Natura 2000 network¹³ is the centrepiece of EU nature & biodiversity policy. It is a EUwide network of nature protection areas established under the 1992 Habitats Directive. The aim of the network is to assure the long-term survival of Europe's most valuable and threatened species and habitats. It is comprised of Special Areas of Conservation (SAC) designated by Member States under the Habitats Directive, and also incorporates Special Protection Areas (SPAs) which they designate under the 1979 Birds Directive. Natura 2000 is not a system of strict nature reserves where all human activities are excluded. Whereas the network will certainly include nature reserves most of the land is likely to continue to be privately owned and the emphasis will be on ensuring that future management is sustainable, both ecologically and economically. The establishment of this network of protected areas also fulfils a Community obligation under the UN Convention on Biological Diversity. Natura 2000 applies to Birds Sites and to Habitats Sites, which are divided into biogeographical regions. It also applies to the marine environment.

2.2.5 Conclusion

The FOODIE project has a lot of similarities with formal ideas of SISE. SISE intend making Environmental information available to large communities, supporting sharing of information and also decision processes. FOODIE will offer Open Accessibility and sharing of data to agriculture community, with main focus on primary producers, farmers. From this reason will be useful to use SISE recommendation for analysis and architecture design.

From the INSPIRE there are most important recommendation related to data model. Not all data sets, which will be used in FOODIE belongs to some from 34 Data themes described by INSPIRE. But for this, data sets, which belongs to some INSPIRE data themes is important to build FOODIE data model as extension of INSPIRE data models. Other, what has to be taken from INSPIRE are metadata recommendation. It could support easier exchange of data with other organizations and initiatives.

GEOSS and COPERNICUS are on one side two potential sources of information, which could be used and integrated as part of FOODIE Hub. This is mainly data collected by GI- GLOBAL LAND COMPONENT and GODAN. GODAN is only in starting period, but GI- GLOBAL LAND COMPONENT offer operational results from Earth Monitoring. On other side FOODIE is able to contribute mainly towards GEOSS Architecture Implementation Pilot (GEOSS AIP) and also needs to be interoperable with GEO based Monitoring System of Systems.

¹² <http://jncc.defra.gov.uk/page-1374>

¹³ Natura 2000 network

Important for FOODIE implementation is establish link with GODAN initiative, which is trying to define world Wide standards for Agriculture Open Data and CGIAR, which is active in global scale on similar area as FOODIE.

Policies are important for FOODIE from two reasons:

- They define restriction for agriculture productions in European area or in certain regions (for example Natural Protected Areas) and for knowledge management of farm level are important
- They define rules for subsidies, which till now important part of farming incomes and has to be including in any decision processes

To be possible include European directives into farming decision processes, we need to be able to transfer this directives into machine readable forms. It could be for example in the form of maps with certain restrictions (partly already such data exists as for example NATURA 2000), but there is till now a lot of work needed. There already exist some results from past, namely from FUTURE FARM project (see chapter 4.1.15 FutureFarm).

3 Standards

3.1 Common standards in the geospatial and environmental domain

The extensive set of geospatial and environmental (open) standards also covers data models and metadata specifications. These have certainly high relevance for FOODIE.

The main standardization bodies in the geospatial domain are ISO, OGC and CEN. All of these work on wider community standards, some also on domain specific models. Accordingly, FOODIE will use their standards as a baseline – but by far not as the only source – for its developments.

3.1.1 Metadata standards

Metadata is a long-lasting topic in geospatial and environmental data management. Before going into any detail, it should be noted that the distinction between both – data and metadata – strongly depends on the view and intended use of a particular information resource. For many cases it might be sufficient to capture the properties of an object as a simple attribute and then document additional information, such as units or measure, creator etc. separately (as metadata). In other cases, it might be important to directly provide information about used sensing devices, measurement methods and related uncertainties together with the measured value, i.e. all of these items are handled as ‘primary citizen’ (aka data). We will revisit this case also further down, as it is particularly relevant to environmental sciences and related observations.

Detailed overviews of metadata for the geospatial and environmental sciences have been provided previously, for example in [1], [10], [5], or more recently in the data centric view to the Spatial Data Infrastructures (SDI) reference model of CEN/TC287 **¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.**. In essence, a comprehensive conceptual model for metadata for discovery, evaluation and use has been standardized as ISO 19115 [9]. These standards have been widely accepted and used, for example in the context of the INSPIRE Metadata Regulation [7][8] and INSPIRE Data Specifications. Implementations include numerous community specific extensions (aka profiles) **¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.**, for example in domains such as meteorology and biodiversity.

Considering environmental observations and measurement in particular, two standards should be mentioned: The Observations and Measurement (O&M) data model of OGC and ISO, and OGC’s Sensor Mark-up Language (SensorML). Both together provide the mechanisms for encoding sensing information. A brief summary of the latest developments (Version 2.0) is provided below; this also includes recent guidelines and patterns of using the above mentioned standards for particular domains. These guidelines have been provided as part of the data specification work on INSPIRE and complement the relatively generic ISO and OGC standards with blue-prints for community profiling.

Regarding the connection of geospatial and environmental data with other domains, Dublin Core (DC) [2] serves as the common denominator [10]. Beyond that, just recently, a vocabulary for representing location has been developed within the framework of the Interoperability Solutions for European Public Administrations (ISA) Programme of the Commission and was lifted to W3C for consideration [6]. Furthermore, the ISA Programme offers a new conceptual model for metadata describing ‘assets’ including software and data model specifications [3]. Both might also be valuable to describe assets of agricultural communities and in particular FOODIE datasets and services.

These later developments fit directly into the Linked Data movement within and outside the geospatial sector. Here, (HTTP) URI are used for identifying resources, they are further described following standards (most prominently RDF), and these resources are inter-linked. By its generality, the Linked Data phenomenon might set an end to the above mentioned subjective distinction between data and metadata, as well as it removes the borders between environmental data, geographic data and non-geographic data. Linked Data can be seen as the long requested tool augmenting mainstream IT with classical SDI [11].

On the political dimension, apart from the above mentioned works on INSPIRE, at European level, the Shared Environmental Information System (SEIS) is not at a stage that involved metadata standards can be listed,

however, it is likely to use INSPIRE as a basic infrastructure, i.e. also to base on INSPIRE metadata as defined in the guidelines for metadata and the diverse data specifications, together with metadata standards from other domains, such as the Statistical Data and Metadata Exchange (SDMX) for statistics [4]. The Global Monitoring for Environment and Security (GMES) suggests diverse approaches, also due to the sectorial distinction between its space and in-situ components, and the developments within numerous FP7 projects.

3.1.2 Data Models for Brokering Support

In the geospatial and environmental domain several data models/encodings based on specifications from standardization bodies or communities-of-practice are adopted which also applies to the agriculture domain. It is thus understandable that FOODIE addresses this heterogeneity through a brokering approach. The discovery and data access brokers should take into account the following models in order to cover a large degree of interoperability.

Data exchange and serialization formats:

- **OGC/ISO Geography Mark-up Language (GML) – XML encoding¹⁴:** The Geography Markup Language (GML) is an XML grammar for expressing geographical features. GML serves as a modelling language for geographic systems as well as an open interchange format for geographic transactions on the Internet.
- **KML¹⁵:** KML is an XML language focused on geographic visualization, including annotation of maps and images. Geographic visualization includes not only the presentation of graphical data on the globe, but also the control of the user's navigation in the sense of where to go and where to look.

From this perspective, KML is complementary to most of the key existing OGC standards including GML (Geography Markup Language), WFS (Web Feature Service) and WMS (Web Map Service). Currently, KML 2.2 utilizes certain geometry elements derived from GML 2.1.2. These elements include point, line string, linear ring, and polygon.

- **GeoSPARQL¹⁶:** The OGC GeoSPARQL standard supports representing and querying geospatial data on the Semantic Web. GeoSPARQL defines a vocabulary for representing geospatial data in RDF, and it defines an extension to the SPARQL query language for processing geospatial data. In addition, GeoSPARQL is designed to accommodate systems based on qualitative spatial reasoning and systems based on quantitative spatial computations.
- **GeoJSON¹⁷:** GeoJSON is an open standard format for encoding collections of simple geographical features along with their non-spatial attributes using JavaScript Object Notation.
- **ISO19115-2 Geographic information – Metadata¹⁸:** ISO 19115-2:2009 extends the existing geographic metadata standard by defining the schema required for describing imagery and gridded data. It provides information about the properties of the measuring equipment used to acquire the data, the geometry of the measuring process employed by the equipment, and the production process used to digitize the raw data.
- **Network Common Data Form – Climate and Forecast (NetCDF-CF)¹⁹** (version 1.4): netCDF is a set of software libraries and self-describing, machine-independent data formats that support the creation, access, and sharing of array-oriented scientific data. The conventions for climate and forecast (CF) metadata are designed to promote the processing and sharing of netCDF files. The conventions define metadata that provide a definitive description of what the data represents, and the spatial and temporal properties of the data.
- **GeoRSS²⁰** (version 2.0): GeoRSS is an emerging standard for encoding location as part of a Web feed. In

¹⁴ <http://www.opengeospatial.org/standards/gml>

¹⁵ <http://www.opengeospatial.org/standards/kml>

¹⁶ <http://www.opengeospatial.org/standards/geosparql>

¹⁷ <http://geojson.org/geojson-spec.html>

¹⁸ http://www.iso.org/iso/catalogue_detail.htm?csnumber=39229

¹⁹ <http://www.opengeospatial.org/standards/netcdf>

²⁰ <http://www.georss.org/>

GeoRSS, location content consists of geographical points, lines, and polygons of interest and related feature descriptions. GeoRSS feeds are designed to be consumed by geographic software such as map generators.

Services and protocols:

- **OGC Web Map Service²¹** (versions 1.3.0, 1.1.1): The OpenGIS Web Map Service Interface Standard (WMS) provides a simple HTTP interface for requesting geo-registered map images from one or more distributed geospatial databases.
- **OGC Web Feature Service²²** (version 1.0.0, 1.1.0): The OpenGIS Web Feature Service (WFS) specification defines interfaces for describing data manipulation operations of geographic features
- **OGC Web Coverage Service²³** (versions 1.0, 1.1, 1.1.2): The OpenGIS Web Coverage Service (WCS) defines Web-based retrieval of coverages – that is, digital geospatial information representing space/time-varying phenomena.
- **OGC Web Processing Service²⁴** (version 1.0.0, 2.0): The OpenGIS Web Processing Service (WPS) provides rules for standardizing how inputs and outputs (requests and responses) for invoking geospatial processing services, such as polygon overlay, as a Web service. The WPS standard defines how a client can request the execution of a process, and how the output from the process is handled. It defines an interface that facilitates the publishing of geospatial processes and clients' discovery of and binding to those processes.
- **OGC Sensor Observation Service²⁵** (version 1.0.0, 2.0): see next section for a broader explanation of the OGC Sensor Web Enablement standards
- **OGC Catalogue Service Web²⁶** (version 2.0.2 Core with ISO Application Profile 1.0, ebRIM/CIM, ebRIM/EO, CWIC application profiles): The OpenGIS Catalogue Service Web (CSW) specify the interfaces, bindings, and a framework for defining application profiles required to publish and access digital catalogues of metadata for geospatial data, services, and related resource information. Metadata act as generalised properties that can be queried and returned through catalogue services for resource evaluation and, in many cases, invocation or retrieval of the referenced resource. Catalogue services support the use of one of several identified query languages to find and return results using well-known content models (metadata schemas) and encodings.
- **OpenSearch²⁷** (version 1.1): OpenSearch is a collection of technologies that allow publishing of search results in a format suitable for syndication and aggregation. It is a way for websites and search engines to publish search results in a standard and accessible format.
- **Open Archives Initiative - Protocol for Metadata Harvesting²⁸ (OAI-PMH)** (version 2.0 supporting ISO19139 and Dublin core formats)

²¹ <http://www.opengeospatial.org/standards/wms>

²² <http://www.opengeospatial.org/standards/wfs>

²³ <http://www.opengeospatial.org/standards/wcs>

²⁴ <http://www.opengeospatial.org/standards/wps>

²⁵ <http://www.opengeospatial.org/standards/sos>

²⁶ <http://www.opengeospatial.org/standards/cat>

²⁷ <http://www.opensearch.org/>

²⁸ <http://www.openarchives.org/pmh/>

3.1.3 Sensor Web Enablement

At the beginning of the new millennium Sensor Web Enablement (SWE) was established as one of the main initiatives of the Open Geospatial Consortium. As described by Botts, Percivall, Reed and Davidson [117] SWE in the OGC context “refers to Web accessible sensor networks and archived sensor data that can be discovered, accessed and, where applicable, controlled using open standard protocols and interfaces (APIs).” SWE aims to further enhance the concepts of SOA and SDI in the sensors and sensor network domain. Applications vary from agriculture, air remote sensing, pollution monitoring, forest fires to mobile heart monitoring or any other countless number of sensors and sensor systems; as depicted in **Figure 5**

According to Botts, Percivall, Reed and Davidson [118] a sensor network is a computer accessible network of many, spatially distributed devices using sensors to monitor conditions at different locations, such as temperature, sound, vibration, pressure, motion or pollutants.

Botts, Percivall, Reed and Davidson [117] have defined the basic building blocks of the SWE concept. This description reflects the situation as of April 2014:

- **Observations & Measurements Schema (O&M)**, ISO 19156 [119] and OGC Adopted Standard, standard models and XML Schema for encoding observations and measurements from a sensor, both archived and real-time. For more information please see [119] [120] and [121].
- **Sensor Model Language (SensorML)**, OGC Adopted Standard, standard models and XML Schema for describing sensor systems and processes; providing information needed for discovery of sensors, locating sensor observations, processing of low-level sensor observations, and listing taskable properties. For more information please see [122].
- **SweCommon**, OGC Adopted Standard, a low-level data model for exchanging sensor data in a homogenous way across SWE-compliant services and interfaces. For more information please see [123].
- **PUCK Protocol Standard**, OGC Adopted Standard, defines the protocol to retrieve a SensorML description, sensor "driver" code, and other information from the device itself, thus enabling automatic sensor installation, configuration and operation. For more information please see [124].
- **Transducer Markup Language (TransducerML or TML)**, OGC Adopted Standard, the conceptual model and XML Schema for describing transducers and supporting real-time streaming of data to and from sensor systems. For more information please see [125].
- **SWE Service Model**, OGC Adopted Standard, defines data types for common use across OGC Sensor Web Enablement (SWE) services, including operation request and response types.
- **Sensor Observations Service (SOS)**, OGC Adopted Standard, standard Web service interface for requesting, filtering, and retrieving observations and sensor system information. This is the intermediary between a client and an observation repository or near real-time sensor channel. For more information please see [126].
- **Sensor Planning Service (SPS)**, OGC Adopted Standard, standard Web service interface for requesting user-driven acquisitions and observations. This is the intermediary between a client and a sensor collection management environment. For more information please see [127].
- **Sensor Alert Service (SAS)**, OGC Best Practices document, standard Web service interface for publishing

and subscribing to alerts from sensors. For more information please see [128].

- **Web Notification Services (WNS)**, OGC Best Practices document, standard Web service interface for asynchronous delivery of messages or alerts from SAS and SPS Web services and other elements of service workflows. For more information please see [129].

Relation of Internet of Things (IoT) and OGC Sensor Web Enablement (SWE)

In its original definition, the Internet of Things (IoT) referred to uniquely identifiable objects and their virtual representations in an Internet-like structure. Today however, the term Internet of Things is used to denote advanced connectivity of devices, systems and services that goes beyond the traditional machine-to-machine (M2M) and covers a variety of protocols, domains and applications.

The IoT is becoming realized through the ever-increasing embedded computation in common devices, network connectivity reaching to nearly every device, and the success of the web bringing information of all types for our immediate use. IoT allows us to interact with smart objects in a manner similar to how we now interact with web resources in our everyday live.

In this sense, various global initiatives are leading the standardization efforts – such as ITU’s Internet of Things Global Standards Initiative²⁹ and IEEE Internet of Things Initiative^{30 31}, OASIS, W3C³², M2M, ISO, ETSI³³, IERC³⁴, IoTA³⁵, OpenIoT³⁶, etc. - in order to provide a common framework to that enables interoperability among the “things”.

IoT and OGC Sensor Web Enablement interrelation is clear from the perspective that sensors are a key enabler in the realization of an Internet of Things and they empower us to better understand the state of the world around us and to discover and glean information about objects and actions that drive that world. Many of the objects we associate with the Internet of Things are sensor-based systems, contain sensors as key components (e.g. buildings, vehicles, appliances, etc.), or require sensors in order to be discovered and located. The measurements and information from those sensors are what provide much of the Internet of Things with meaningful data.

SWE provides extensive support for describing the location of sensors and their observations, and this location information is a key aspect of data within the Internet of Things, allowing both human users and intelligent objects to know where they are, what they do, and what objects and data are available around them.

In this regard, the Open Geospatial Consortium has set up a specific group – the Sensor Web for IoT SWG³⁷ - which will explore opportunities to extend the SWE framework and to harmonize it with existing open standards to accommodate Web-friendly and efficient implementations of sensor interfaces and sensor networks using the Representational State Transfer (REST) programming model. Sensor Web for IoT SWG members anticipate that REST and sensors will be important factors in the emerging Internet of Things (IoT). To that end, OGC Sensor Web for IoT Working Group is already working on the SensorThings API³⁸, which is a light RESTful API of the SWE service specification standards.

In addition, OGC’s Sensor Web Enablement (SWE) standards are the only ones that focus on the content of sensor information and on making the sensor observations useful to end user applications. SWE standards allow users to assessment the fitness for use of observations and to allow accurate processing on the sensed information to create derived information suitable to the users’ needs in contrast with the other standardization efforts (i.e., ITU and IEEE initiatives for instance) where the focus seems to be more centred in other areas such as compact encodings and protocols for battery-powered wireless sensors, location/navigation in small areas, navigation-to-

²⁹ <http://www.itu.int/en/ITU-T/gsi/iot/Pages/default.aspx>

³⁰ <http://standards.ieee.org/innovate/iot/>

³¹ <http://standards.ieee.org/innovate/iot/stds.html>

³² <http://www.w3.org/community/wot/>

³³ <http://www.etsi.org/technologies-clusters/technologies/m2m>

³⁴ <http://www.internet-of-things-research.eu/>

³⁵ <http://www.iot-a.eu/public>

³⁶ <http://openiot.eu/>

³⁷ <http://www.opengeospatial.org/projects/groups/sweiotswg>

³⁸ <http://ogc-iot.github.io/ogc-iot-api/>

thing, context-specific ‘around me’ use cases, visualisation in 3D city models and indoor models, space-time web navigation, big data, massive transaction rates, semantic translation, privacy and access controls.

3.1.4 Conclusion

OGC standards are key standards for FOODIE project and their deep knowledge and understanding is important for successful implementation of FOODIE project.

In the design and implementation phase we need to have look now only on so called INSPIRE standards like (ISO19115/19119/19139), CSW, WMS, GML, WFS, WCS, WPS), but also on other standards like standards of Sensors Web Enablement (now mainly used in GEOSS and Copernicus), but also on set of new standards, which in some way better respect new general IT trends like KML, OpenSearch, GeoSPARQL, GeoJSON, NetCDF-CF, GeorSS, which are more related to current Web 2.0 trends and which could bring FOODIE better towards non-GI community.

3.2 Standards in the agricultural domain

3.2.1 ISOBUS

ISOBUS is managed by the ISOBUS group in VDMA. The VDMA (VerbandDeutscherMaschinen- und Anlagenbau - German Engineering Federation) is a network of around 3,000 engineering industry companies in Europe and 400 industry experts [130].

The ISOBUS standard specifies a serial data network for control and communications on forestry or agricultural tractors. It consists of several parts: General standard for mobile data communication, Physical layer, Data link layer, Network layer, Network management, Virtual terminal, Implement messages applications layer, Power train messages, Tractor ECU, Task controller and management information system data interchange, Mobile data element dictionary, Diagnostic, File Server. The work for further parts is ongoing. It is currently ISO standard ISO 11783³⁹.

The technical development of ISOBUS began in 1991 when the ISO set up the SC 19 agricultural electronics group. The ISOBUS standard was introduced in tractors and implements in 2001. After seven years of field experience the industry formed the AEF to better support ISOBUS for its members and their customers worldwide. This facilitates precision farming activities such as variable spreading of fertilizer in relation to the position of the spreader in the field. The flow of data takes place in two directions: the task specific data can be transmitted to the task controller and then be analysed using the farm computer, after the work is completed.

A modern ISOBUS system consists of various components, including the tractor, terminal and implement. For system compatibility it is essential what the Universal Terminal and the implement are capable of performing – both separately and together. For increased transparency towards the user the AEF has defined AEF ISOBUS Functionalities that are now also the basis for the certification of ISOBUS products.⁴⁰

3.2.2 agroXML

agroXML is a markup language for agricultural issues providing elements and XML data types for representing data on work processes on the farm including accompanying operating supplies like fertilizers, pesticides, crops and the like. It is defined using W3C's XML Schema. agroRDF is an accompanying semantic model that is at the moment still under heavy development. It is built using RDF.

While there are other standards covering certain areas of agriculture like e. g. the ISOBUS data dictionary for data exchange between tractor and implement or ISOagriNet for communication between livestock farming equipment, the purposes of agroXML and agroRDF are:

- exchange between on-farm systems and external stakeholders
- high level documentation of farming processes

³⁹ http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/ISO_11783

⁴⁰ <http://www.aef-online.org/en/aef-projects/isobus/why-isobus.html>

- data integration between different agricultural production branches
- semantic integration between different standards and vocabularies
- a means for standardized provision of data on operating supplies

A number of use cases have been described and implemented within projects. agroXML however is flexible to allow for usage within other contexts as well [131].

The agroXML schema is based on a model of the real-world processes in agricultural production. They are represented in a tree-like hierarchy. At the moment, agroXML can describe data for plant production. The measure plant protection is anchored in the schema on the left besides other measures like soil tillage, seeding or fertilization, on the right the branches split to characterize the measure plant protection more in detail. The branches describe e. g. fields, machinery and persons executing the pesticide treatment and the deployed supply items. The elements carry additional information, e. g. date, time and the duration of the measure. Profiles define the obligatory elements for a specific data exchange case. To create a profile, elements are copied from the agroXML schema to a separate file and the necessary restrictions applied to the data types in there. Data are transported in an XML instance, a file built according to the rules of the schema and the profile. Using profiles, lean, clear and easily transferable instances can be generated⁴¹.

3.2.3 AgriXchange

A part of the agriXchange^{42 43} work focused on the basic design of the generic integration framework for data, information and knowledge exchange harmonisation and interoperability based on selected use cases. The project worked with two levels of use case descriptions.

- The first is a “wide scope” use case description, covering a whole domain-specific procedure fulfilling the user needs, for example fertilising procedures from planning to execution, consisting of a chain of processes, actors and data-exchange transactions.
- The “narrow scope” description serves as a meta-data model of the interface, where the context of the data transaction of that specific interface is briefly described.

The agriXchange effort focused on two aspects:

- the structure of the framework model serves information sharing and harmonisation development of the data exchange, and
- the implementation of the practical model tool (aXTool) in the agriXchange platform has to be user-friendly.

The agriXchange Reference Framework design contains functionalities such as search, contribute, discussion and evaluation by user experience, and also a mechanism for quality management. The design serves different interest groups with their focus on either wide-scope use cases or narrow-scoped interface solutions, and assists in interactions between the scopes [132].

From the user point of view, the agriXchange Reference Framework should serve four main functions: searching for existing solutions interlinked with any open (standardised) interface, contributing (to) existing solutions, discussion and evaluation of solutions. The Reference Framework tool should provide information in details that suit user’s demand in different phases of a system development process.

Classification of contributed information according to the agriXchange Reference Information Model (aXRIM) is a backbone for the generic integration framework and provides the foundation for the relevant functionalities of the aXTool, like relevant and efficient search functions. The main classes of aXRIM are Process, Actors, Communication protocol and Data. The aXRIM includes elements which concern Technical architecture and Technical communication infrastructure (Class: Communication protocol) and Organisational embedding (Class: Actors).

⁴¹ Martin Kunisch, Jürgen Frisch, Daniel Martini, and Stefan Böttinger agroXML – a standardized language for data exchange in agriculture

⁴² <http://www.agrixchange.org>

⁴³ agriXchange is now mainly active on LinkedIn. Here is growing agriXchange group https://www.linkedin.com/groups?home=&gid=3807971&trk=my_groups-tile-grp and there are also two subgroups: Open Agriculture Data Working Group https://www.linkedin.com/groups?home=&gid=4350866&trk=my_groups-tile-grp and Sensors working group https://www.linkedin.com/groups?home=&gid=4350839&trk=my_groups-tile-grp

Users can be classified as developers, modellers and business users depending on the scope of their interest. The users can represent specific groups of narrow interest areas or wider themes. When contributing, users follow a certain work flow through which the aXTool gives guidance. The quality maintenance requires the contributors to identify their name, the organisation and community they represent, and the contact information. Also, collected user experiences of already existing solutions that are also shared by other contributors, are utilised to describe the quality of a certain solution [133].

Wide-scope use case descriptions serve the development and optimisation of farming, food logistics and trading systems which capture several sub-systems, actors and stakeholders. Narrow-scope interfaces focus on single data exchange interfaces and actors and processes around them, and the level of information detail is higher, including technical details, standards and other implementation instructions. For this level, one of the key factors in data exchange is the sharing of vocabularies. In many cases, each data exchange solution has its own specific vocabulary. To increase cost efficiency in constructing an interoperable system, the harmonising of vocabularies is essential. The aim of the information modelling of the two use cases is to give a high-level understanding of the content of the information to be exchanged between the parties or actors involved. Gathering the data content from different use cases to the agriXchange collection gives a good ground for further analysis and harmonisation of the vocabulary in the agri-food sector [134] [135].

3.2.4 Open Ag Data Alliance

Modern production agriculture has the potential to dramatically improve crop yields and reduce environmental impacts by enabling farmers to properly evaluate past, current and future farm management decisions through analysis of agronomic data generated in the field.

However farmers are currently overwhelmed with walled gardens of incompatible data generated by their existing systems (geodata images, logs, reports, charts). Farmer's want the hardware and software systems they use to interoperate – that is, to share information and be able to adequately rely on each other to help support decision-making.

The most scalable solution for farmers is to enable their hardware and software systems to communicate automatically through secure cloud services or tools. Any system needs to incorporate data from a multitude of sources in order to be useful. However, existing solutions suffer from:

- an inability to gather data from all aspects of any given farm since no one manufacturer accesses all the operational data on a farm,
- farmers' concern about what will happen to their data, and
- questions about data ownership and intellectual property.

In order to enable this next stage in production agriculture productivity, these three issues have to be resolved. Past attempts at solving data sharing and compatibility have revolved around creating monolithic standards that are licensed commercially and selectively. Farmers require an open solution that works with existing standards, adheres to clear privacy and security policies, and doesn't require farmers to pay to access their own data. This is not a unique set of challenges. Other industries have faced a similar stage in their evolution, including financial services, healthcare, and the Internet. In all cases, a distributed, rather than centralized, network model emerged as best for the end users.

With the mission to ensure farmers have full data access, security and privacy, OADA will:

- operate with a farmer-focused approach through a central guiding principle that each farmer owns data generated or entered by the farmer, their employees or by machines performing activities on their farm,
- develop open reference implementations of data storage and transfer mechanisms with security and privacy protocols,
- provide a forum for technical community discussion,
- be led according to the processes of open standards projects that have built much of the Internet's networking, security, web and data standards with multiple university, individual and corporations participating (often while competing in the marketplace). Examples include the Internet Engineering Taskforce (IETF), World Wide Web Consortium (W3C) and The Apache Software Foundation, (which supports over

100 projects).

- direct any financial contributions to a not-for-profit foundation whose purpose will be to enable open source projects in agriculture in service of the OADA mission.

3.2.5 SoilML

The need to exchange soil-domain information independently on the processing environment lead to the desire of establishing the XML dialect for soil data. The concept was initially called as “SoilML”, i.e. a soil equivalent of the much broader “Geoscience Markup Language” also known under the abbreviation “GeoSciML⁴⁴”.

The SoilML was designed to share information on land and soil information within the project called the GlobalSoilMap.net⁴⁵. The representatives of the SoilML initiative met in 2012 with the ISO Working Group on Soil Data Quality standard to assure that both concepts do not overlap. There are intentions to integrate formally the SoilML information modelling work into activities of the International Union of Soil Sciences (IUSS)⁴⁶ Soil Information Working Group, however so far without success.

Since then, the *ISO 28258:2013 – Soil Quality – Digital exchange of soil-related data* was standardized. The ISO 28258 information model offers flexible way to exchange digital soil data in the XML-based format. It is also opened for the possibility to (optionally) combine soil data with the concept of Observations & Measurements, known as ISO 19156. On the other hand, the ISO 28258 information model offers modularity, for instance enables for a soil data provider to include any soil classification (s)he wants.

The recommendation for the development within the Foodie project would therefore be to stick to the information model as standardized within the ISO 28258 document.

3.2.6 Conclusion

In area of agriculture standards is not to clear situation and they doesn't exist one concrete initiative covered all aspects. From existing standards important will be mainly agroXML and SoilML. agriXchange and Open Ag Data Alliance (OADA) are more innitatives. agriXchange project introduced a methodology based on aXTool. This could be topic of interest of FOODIE. OADA is mainly new innitative coming from industry. It is important to establish contacts with this initiative.

3.3 Other relevant standards

3.3.1 HTML5

HTML5⁴⁷ is the fifth major revision of the core markup language of the World Wide Web: the Hypertext Markup Language (HTML). The HTML5 specification is being defined by the HTML Working Group⁴⁸ of W3C⁴⁹ with the support of the Web Hypertext Application Technology Working Group (WHATWG)⁵⁰. At the time of writing this document, HTML5 has the status of W3C Candidate Recommendation and is intended to become a W3C Recommendation in a near future.

With the overload of data on the Web it is commonly very hard for human beings to analyse and interpret such a complex data structures. FOODIE will take advantage of HTML5 technology in order to provide interactive visualizations that facilitate the representation of complex data related to farm and agricultural services. Some of the key features of HTML5 that will allow FOODIE to create advanced visualizations are:

- The canvas element provides scripts with a resolution-dependent bitmap canvas, which can be used for rendering graphs, game graphics, art, or other visual images on the fly.

⁴⁴ <http://www.geosciml.org>

⁴⁵ <http://globalsoilmap.net>

⁴⁶ <http://www.iuss.org>

⁴⁷ <http://www.w3.org/TR/html5>

⁴⁸ <http://www.w3.org/html/wg/>

⁴⁹ <http://www.w3.org>

⁵⁰ <http://www.whatwg.org>

- The SVG element allows developers to include two-dimensional interactive graphics within HTML5 content, according to the SVG specification.

3.3.2 RDF

The data model commonly associated with the linked data publication is RDF (Resource Description Framework)⁵¹. It is possible to do so by the means of other models, like JSON-LD⁵² and Microdata⁵³, but hereby the focus will be the most spread in the community, RDF.

RDF is a data model standardization represented in files with a variety of syntaxes. During the standard's first years, the only syntaxes recommended by the W3C office where RDF/XML and N-Triples, being nowadays widely supported. Due to a series of disadvantages born from the nature of the XML solution, new syntaxes were created to represent RDF in files:

- RDF/XML⁵⁴: It is a syntax recommended by W3C and the most adopted one. Unfortunately it is too complex to be comfortably human-readable and requires XML based technologies to work with it.
- N3 (Notation3)⁵⁵: more than syntax, it is an extension of the RDF model adding variables and logical entailments among other characteristics. It also contributes with a text files based syntax really simplified due to the adoption of prefixes and syntactic abbreviations. Since 2011 it is recognised by W3C as a "Team submission", but not a recommendation.
- N-Triples⁵⁶: It is a subset of N3 syntax based in text files containing a maximum of one RDF triple in each line. It results extremely verbose due to the lack of syntactic abbreviations and simplified URIs through prefixes. However it is not that complex for human-reading and highly machine processable and generated.
- Turtle⁵⁷: It is also a file based syntax. In this case, by the means of syntactic abbreviations, the resulting files look much more compacted and human-readable. It has been accepted as a W3C standard the 25th of February of this year (2014).
- RDF/JSON⁵⁸: It is a RDF syntax that allows representing the data in a compatible form with the JavaScript Object Notation (JSON)⁵⁹.
- RDFa⁶⁰: Since 2008 this syntax is a W3C recommendation. It is based in the idea of including annotations inside a host language like XHTML. The annotations are based on the use of attributes within the XML document elements and designed to be fully compatible with the RDF model.
- TriX⁶¹: syntax proposed by Hewlett Packard, also XML-based. It is not widely adopted, even having the pros of being less complex than RDF/XML.

It could look like a hard choice to select one syntax to represent the RDF but it is not a matter of unique option but a matter of choosing a subset of syntaxes aligned with the kind of consumption we would expect.

It is not practical to offer the full stack of syntaxes so it is common to choose a subset containing at least those recommended by the W3C: RDF/XML, N-Triples y RDFa.

3.3.3 RDFS

RDF Schema (RDFS)⁶² is a semantic extension - a collection of RDF resources - of the RDF data model vocabulary so it can be used for describing taxonomies of classes and properties. By the means of RDFS it is possible to describe groups of related resources and the relationships between them. Moreover, RDFS allows extending defini-

⁵¹ <http://www.w3.org/RDF/>

⁵² <http://json-ld.org/>

⁵³ <http://www.w3.org/TR/microdata>

⁵⁴ <http://www.w3.org/TR/REC-rdf-syntax/>

⁵⁵ <http://www.w3.org/TeamSubmission/n3/>

⁵⁶ <http://www.w3.org/TR/rdf-testcases/#ntriples>

⁵⁷ <http://www.w3.org/TeamSubmission/turtle/>

⁵⁸ <http://www.w3.org/TR/rdf-json>

⁵⁹ <http://www.w3.org/TR/rdf-json/#bib-RFC4627>

⁶⁰ <http://www.w3.org/TR/xhtml-rdfa-primer/>

⁶¹ <http://www.hpl.hp.com/techreports/2004/HPL-2004-56.html>

⁶² <http://www.w3.org/TR/rdf-schema/>

tions for RDF elements, like setting the domain and range of properties or relating classes and properties into taxonomies.

Very close to the object-oriented programming language systems, RDF Schema is based in a class-property system been the main difference between them the properties definition concept. While the OO systems define their properties in terms of the instances properties may have, RDFS describes the properties based on the **domain and range**.

By **domain** of a property it is defined the class whose instances should be subject of the property, i. e., *Prop rdfs:domain Class* defines that *Prop* is an instance of the class **rdf:Property**, that *Class* is an instance of the class **rdfs:Class** and that the resources working as subjects of the property *Prop* **should be instances** of the class *Class*.

Range of a property stands for the subset of resource classes whose instances could work as the object of the property. I. e., *Prop rdfs:range Class* defines that *Prop* is an instance of the class **rdf:Property**, that *Class* is an instance of the class **rdfs:Class** and that the resources working as object of the property *Prop* **should be instances** of the class *Class*.

3.3.4 Web Ontology Language (OWL)

Web Ontology Language (OWL)⁶³ extends RDFS by adding more advanced constructs to describe semantics of RDF statements, facilitating greater machine interpretability of Web content than that supported by XML, RDF, and RDFS. It provides a more extensive vocabulary along with formal semantics for describing properties and classes, including relations between classes (e.g. disjointness), cardinality (e.g. "exactly one"), restriction of values, equality, richer typing of properties, characteristics of properties (e.g. symmetry), and enumerated classes. OWL is based on description logic and thus it brings reasoning power to the semantic web. The initial OWL specification⁶⁴ defined three increasingly expressive sublanguages: (i) OWL-Lite, for users primarily needing a classification hierarchy and simple constraints (e.g., simple cardinality constraints); OWL DL, for users who want the maximum expressiveness while retaining computational completeness (all conclusions are guaranteed to be computable) and decidability (all computations will finish in finite time); (iii) OWL Full, for users who want maximum expressiveness and the syntactic freedom of RDF with no computational guarantees.

The second and current specification OWL 2⁶⁵ adds several new features to OWL 1, some of which are syntactic sugar (e.g., disjoint union of classes) while others offer new expressivity⁶⁶, including increased expressive power for properties (e.g., property chains, qualified cardinality restrictions, asymmetric, reflexive, and disjoint properties), extended support for data types, simple meta-modelling capabilities, extended annotation capabilities, and keys. And at the same time, backwards compatibility with OWL 1 remains to all intents and purposes complete: all OWL 1 Ontologies remain valid OWL 2 Ontologies, with identical inferences in all practical cases.

OWL 2 defines three profiles: OWL 2 EL, OWL 2 QL, and OWL 2 RL. Profiles are sublanguages (syntactic subsets) of OWL 2, each offering useful advantages for particular applications, such as computational properties (e.g., reasoning complexity in range of LOGSPACE to PTIME) or implementation possibilities (e.g., fragments implementable using RDBs). They are defined as syntactic restrictions of OWL 2 Structural Specification, i.e., as a subset of the structural elements that can be used in a conforming ontology, and each is more restrictive than OWL DL. They trade off different aspects of OWL's expressive power in return for different computational and/or implementation benefits.

- OWL 2 EL captures the expressive power common in many large-scale ontology, e.g., SNOMED CT, and the NCI thesaurus. It enables polynomial time algorithms for all the standard reasoning tasks. Thus, it is particularly suitable for applications where very large ontologies are needed, and where expressive power can be traded for performance guarantees.
- OWL 2 QL captures the expressive power that is common in simple ontologies like thesauri, and (most of) the expressive power of ER/UML schemas. It enables conjunctive queries to be answered in Log-Space (AC⁰) using standard relational database technology. Hence, it is particularly suitable for applica-

⁶³ <http://www.w3.org/TR/owl-features/>

⁶⁴ <http://www.w3.org/TR/owl-semantic/>

⁶⁵ <http://www.w3.org/TR/owl2-overview/>

⁶⁶ <http://www.w3.org/TR/owl2-new-features/>

tions where relatively lightweight ontologies are used to organize large numbers of individuals and where it is useful or necessary to access the data directly via relational queries (e.g., SQL)

- OWL 2 RL supports OWL 2 applications that can trade the full expressivity of the language for efficiency, as well as RDFS applications that need some added expressivity from OWL 2. It enables polynomial time reasoning algorithms using rule-extended database technologies operating directly on RDF triples. Thus, it is most suitable for applications where relatively lightweight ontologies are used to organize large numbers of individuals and where it is useful or necessary to operate directly on data in the form of RDF triples.

The primary exchange syntax for OWL 2 is RDF/XML. However, other syntaxes may also be used, including alternative RDF serializations (e.g., Turtle, XML) and a more "readable" syntax, called the Manchester Syntax, which is used in several ontology editing tools.

Hence, OWL 2 as the default ontology language will be used to specify any vocabulary needed to represent and express information in the final platform. This will give us the possibility to express formal semantics of the underlying domain, the possibility to integrate and reuse existing ontologies as well as the ability to exploit existing tools for ontology creation, reasoning, etc.

3.3.5 SPARQL and GeoSPARQL

SPARQL (SPARQL Protocol and RDF Query Language)⁶⁷ is a RDF data query and update language that permits to retrieve and manipulate data stored in a RDF graph model. Its syntax is based in that defined by Turtle and since 2008 has obtained the status of recommendation provided by the W3C.

Query operations, such as SORT, JOIN, AGGREGATE, are fully supported by SPARQL and it offers specifically graph traversal syntax for data represented as a graph.

Regarding data retrieving from a RDF database, there are four options offered by SPARQL:

- SELECT: retrieve data from a SPARQL endpoint as a table format.
- CONSTRUCT: retrieve the data from the SPARQL endpoint and generate a valid RDF graph.
- ASK: obtain True/False result for a query on a SPARQL endpoint.
- DESCRIBE: retrieve an RDF graph from the SPARQL endpoint, which contents are decided by the endpoint based on what is deemed as useful information.

All the queries describe above include a WHERE block to refine the results, although in the case of the DESCRIBE query the WHERE is optional.

GeoSPARQL is a geographic query language for RDF data standardised by the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC). It provides a standard way to express and query spatial elements in RDF, so that users can exchange data easily, and triple store implementers can have a standard format for indexing. GeoSPARQL defines a vocabulary for representing geospatial data in RDF, and it defines an extension to the SPARQL query language for processing geospatial data. In addition, GeoSPARQL is designed to accommodate systems based on qualitative spatial reasoning and systems based on quantitative spatial computations. There are three key classes in the GeoSPARQL ontology:

- geo:Feature – A thing that can have a spatial location; i.e., a park or a monument etc.;
- geo:Geometry – A representation of a spatial location; i.e., a set of coordinates;
- geo:SpatialObject – A superclass of both Features and Geometries.

3.3.6 PROV-O

The PROV Ontology (PROV-O)⁶⁸ is an OWL 2 ontology that encodes the PROV Data Model⁶⁹. It provides a set of classes, properties, and restrictions that can be used to represent, integrate and interchange provenance information generated in different systems and under different contexts. In particular, PROV-O is lightweight ontolo-

⁶⁷ <http://www.w3.org/TR/rdf-sparql-query/>

⁶⁸ <http://www.w3.org/TR/prov-o/>

⁶⁹ <http://www.w3.org/TR/prov-dm/>

gy that can be used to implement a wide range of applications in different domains.

The ontology may be used entirely or partially, depending on the level of detail needed in the particular provenance application. Additionally, PROV-O can be specialized for modelling provenance details that may be specific of particular applications and domains.

PROV-O classifies the specified terms (classes and properties) in three categories to provide an incremental introduction to the ontology: Starting Point terms, Expanded terms, and qualified terms.

Starting point terms are the core classes and properties of the ontology and the basis for other terms. These include three classes (*Entity*, *Activity* and *Agent*), and nine properties (e.g., *wasGeneratedBy*, *wasDerivedFrom*, *startedAtTime*, *used*, *wasAssociatedWith*). The core class *Entity* refers to any physical, digital, conceptual, or other kind of thing (real or imaginary) with some fixed aspects. *Activity* refers to something that occurs over a period of time and acts upon or with entities, such as consuming, processing, transforming, modifying, relocating, using, or generating entities. And the *Agent* is something responsible for an activity taking place, for the existence of an entity, or for another agent's activity.

Expanded terms provide additional classes and properties that can be used to relate term in the Starting Point category. These include seven classes (e.g., *Bundle*, *Person*, *Location*), and 16 properties (e.g., *alternateOf*, *wasRevisionOf*, *hadMember*, *generated*, *value*).

Finally, the qualified terms provide detailed or additional information about binary relations asserted using Starting Point and Expanded properties. These include 20 classes (e.g., *Usage*, *PrimarySource*, *Plan*, *Role*) and 25 properties (e.g., *qualifiedGeneration*, *qualifiedUsage*, *wasInfluencedBy*, *qualifiedRevision*, *hadPlan*, *influencer*, *hadActivity*).

Hence, PROV-O provides a good foundation to represent provenance information about products in the food-supply chain. Most likely, it will be necessary to create a specialization in order to capture all the necessary information for our needs. For instance, we will need to express the raw materials used as source, the logistics activities associated, the packing materials and activities, etc.

3.3.7 SKOS

SKOS (Simple Knowledge Organisation System) core⁷⁰ is a model for expressing basic structures and contents of concept schemes such as thesauri, classification schemes, subject heading lists, taxonomies, 'folksonomies', other types of controlled vocabulary, and also concept schemes embedded in glossaries and terminologies.

The SKOS Core Vocabulary is an application of the Resource Description Framework (RDF), which can be used to express a concept scheme as an RDF graph. Using RDF enables SKOS data to be linked to and/or merged with other RDF data, supporting data sources distributed across the web while remaining meaningfully composed and integrated.

SKOS Core Vocabulary includes five classes: *CollectableProperty*, *Collection*, *Concept*, *ConceptScheme* and *OrderedCollection*. It also defines several properties, such as *broader*, *definition*, *member*, *narrower*, *prefLabel*, *related* and *subject*.

SKOS-XL is an extension of SKOS, which provides additional support for describing and linking lexical entities. It defines the class *Label*, and five properties: *altLabel*, *hiddenLabel*, *labelRelation* and *literalForm* and *prefLabel*. The latest version of SKOS Core already includes three of these properties.

SKOS is a very relevant standard in FOODIE because many knowledge sources such as AGROVOC and GeoNames, use SKOS to express the concept scheme.

3.3.8 DCAT application profile for data portals in Europe

The DCAT Application profile for data portals in Europe (DCAT-AP)⁷¹ is a very new specification based on the Data Catalogue vocabulary (DCAT)⁷² for describing public sector datasets in Europe. Its basic use case is to enable

⁷⁰ <http://www.w3.org/TR/2005/WD-swbp-skos-core-spec-20051102/>

⁷¹ DCAT-AP: https://joinup.ec.europa.eu/asset/dcat_application_profile/description

⁷² DCAT: <http://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat/>

cross-data portal searching for data sets and making public sector data better searchable across borders and sectors. This can be achieved by the exchange of descriptions of data sets among data portals.

Mandatory classes for the profile are:

- Agent (e.g., Organisation)
- Category (Subject of Dataset)
- Category scheme (Controlled vocabulary the theme comes from)
- Catalogue (Repository that hosts the dataset)
- Literal (Literal value)
- Resource (Anything described by RDF)

E.g. for all datasets mandatory properties are title and description, recommended contact point, dataset distribution, keyword/tag, publisher theme/category

3.3.9 CKAN domain model

CKAN Domain Model⁷³ is an open source system for publishing data on the web. It provides tools to streamline publishing, sharing, finding and using data.

The published metadata schema is proprietary and provides some mapping to DC elements. Also adding proprietary user defined elements is allowed. Harvesting of OGC CSW 2.0.2 + ISO 19139 spatial metadata standards is available with extensions.

CKAN metadata profile:

- id: unique id
- name (slug): unique name that is used in urls and for identification
- title (dc:title): short title for dataset
- url (home page): home page for this dataset
- author (dc:creator): original creator of the dataset
- author_email:
- maintainer: current maintainer or publisher of the dataset
- maintainer_email:
- license (dc:rights): license under which the dataset is made available
- version: dataset version
- notes (description) (dc:description): description and other information about the dataset
- tags: arbitrary textual tags for the dataset
- state: state of dataset in CKAN system (active, deleted, pending)
- resources: list of resources
- groups: list of groups this dataset is a member of
- "extras" - arbitrary, unlimited additional key/value fields [52]

3.3.10 R2RML

R2RML⁷⁴ is a language designed to specify mappings from relational databases to RDF datasets. Such mappings enable viewing existing relational data in the RDF data model, expressed in a structure and target vocabulary chosen by the author of the mappings.

Every R2RML mapping is customized to a specific database schema and target vocabulary. Hence, the input to a mapping is a relational database that conforms to that schema, whereas the output is an RDF dataset⁷⁵, as defined in SPARQL, which uses predicates and types from the target vocabulary.

R2RML mappings are themselves RDF graphs, written down in Turtle syntax. R2RML enables different types of mapping implementations. Processors could, for example, offer a virtual SPARQL endpoint over the mapped re-

⁷³ <http://docs.ckan.org/en/ckan-1.8/domain-model.html>

⁷⁴ <http://www.w3.org/TR/r2rml/>

⁷⁵ <http://www.w3.org/TR/2008/REC-rdf-sparql-query-20080115/#rdfDataset>

lational data, or generate RDF dumps, or offer a Linked Data interface.

Although the intended audience of this specification is mainly developers of software that generates or processes R2RML mapping documents, it is a potential relevant standard in FOODIE in the case we will have to deal with legacy databases as data sources. For FOODIE, even though we will not develop such software, we will probably need to use such tools, which are already available (see Section 6.7.2 Semantic tagging and data transformation), and define our own mappings. Hence, this specification will serve as a reference to the R2RML language constructs.

3.3.11 Security and privacy related standards

3.3.11.1 Cloud Security Alliance (CSA)

The Cloud Security Alliance (CSA) is a not-for-profit organization with a mission to promote the use of best practices for providing security assurance within Cloud Computing, and to provide education on the uses of Cloud Computing to help secure all other forms of computing. The Cloud Security Alliance is led by a broad coalition of industry practitioners, corporations, associations and other key stakeholders.

The description of CSA and CSA standards comes from <https://cloudsecurityalliance.org>.

GRC Stack

Achieving Governance, Risk Management and Compliance (GRC) goals requires appropriate assessment criteria, relevant control objectives and timely access to necessary supporting data. Whether implementing private, public or hybrid clouds, the shift to compute as a service presents new challenges across the spectrum of GRC requirements. The Cloud Security Alliance GRC Stack provides a toolkit for enterprises, cloud providers, security solution providers, IT auditors and other key stakeholders to instrument and assess both private and public clouds against industry established best practices, standards and critical compliance requirements. It includes the following initiatives:

- **Cloud Audit:** the goal of this initiative is to provide a common interface and namespace that allows cloud computing providers to automate the Audit, Assertion, Assessment, and Assurance (A6) of their infrastructure (IaaS), platform (PaaS), and application (SaaS) environments and allow authorized consumers of their services to do likewise via an open, extensible and secure interface and methodology. CloudAudit provides the technical foundation to enable transparency and trust in private and public cloud systems.
- **Cloud Controls Matrix (CCM):** this initiative was designed to provide fundamental security principles to guide cloud vendors and to assist prospective cloud customers in assessing the overall security risk of a cloud provider. CCM provides a control framework that gives detailed understanding of security concepts and principles that are aligned to the CSA guidance in 13 domains. The foundations of the CSA CCM rest on its customized relationship to other industry-accepted security standards, regulations, and controls frameworks such as the HITRUST CSF, ISO 27001/27002, ISACA COBIT, PCI, HIPAA and NIST, and will augment or provide internal control direction for service organization control reports provided by cloud providers. As a framework, the CSA CCM provides organizations with the needed structure, detail and clarity relating to information security tailored to the cloud industry. The CSA CCM strengthens existing information security control environments by emphasizing business information security control requirements, reduces and identifies consistent security threats and vulnerabilities in the cloud, provides standardize security and operational risk management, and seeks to normalize security expectations, cloud taxonomy and terminology, and security measures implemented in the cloud.
- **Consensus Assessments Initiative (CAI):** this initiative was launched to perform research, create tools and create industry partnerships to enable cloud computing assessments. We are focused on providing industry-accepted ways to document what security controls exist in IaaS, PaaS, and SaaS offerings, providing security control transparency. This effort by design is integrated with and will support other projects from our research partners. The initial deliverable of this project is the CAI Questionnaire (CAIQ). This questionnaire is available in spreadsheet format, and provides a set of questions a cloud consumer and cloud auditor may wish to ask of a cloud provider. It provides a series of “yes or no” con-

control assertion questions which can then be tailored to suit each unique cloud customer's evidentiary requirements.

- Cloud Trust Protocol (CTP): this protocol is the mechanism by which cloud service consumers (also known as "cloud users" or "cloud service owners") ask for and receive information about the elements of transparency as applied to cloud service providers. The primary purpose of the CTP and the elements of transparency is to generate evidence-based confidence that everything that is claimed to be happening in the cloud is indeed happening as described, and nothing else. This is a classic application of the definition of digital trust. And, assured of such evidence, cloud consumers become liberated to bring more sensitive and valuable business functions to the cloud, and reap even larger payoffs. With the CTP cloud consumers are provided a way to find out important pieces of information concerning the compliance, security, privacy, integrity, and operational security history of service elements being performed "in the cloud".

3.3.11.2 ISO/IEC 27001

Part of the family of standards ISO/IEC 27000-series that deal with information security and which have been published jointly by the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) and the International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC).

The series provides best practice recommendations on information security management, risks and controls within the context of an overall information security management system (ISMS), i.e., a set of policies concerned with information security management or IT related risks. In particular, ISO/IEC 27001 formally specifies a management system that is intended to bring information security under explicit management control. As a formal specification it mandates specific requirements. Organizations that claim to have adopted ISO/IEC 27001 can therefore be formally audited and certified compliant with the standard.

The standard was first published in 2005, and a revised (the current) version was recently released in 2013⁷⁶.

The standard contains 14 domains:

- Information security policies - management direction
- Organization of information security - governance of information security
- Human resources security - security aspects for employees joining, moving and leaving an organization
- Asset management - inventory and classification of information assets
- Access control - restriction of access rights to networks, systems, applications, functions and data
- Cryptography
- Physical and environmental security - protection of the computer facilities
- Operations security - management of technical security controls in systems and networks
- Communications security - management of technical security controls in systems and networks
- Information systems acquisition, development and maintenance - building security into applications
- Supplier relationships
- Information security incident management - anticipating and responding appropriately to information security breaches
- Information security aspects of business continuity management - protecting, maintaining and recovering business-critical processes and systems
- Compliance - ensuring conformance with information security policies, standards, laws and regulations

This standard is potentially useful in FOODIE, as it provides a set of requirements to ensure the security of information assets, which can be assessed in order to ensure compliance.

3.3.12 Conclusion

The standards related to cloud solution will be important to be possible integrate future FOODIE platform with other cloud based application or guarantee easy transferability of FOODIE to other platforms. Standards of

⁷⁶ http://www.iso.org/iso/home/store/catalogue_ics/catalogue_detail_ics.htm?csnumber=54534

Semantic Web are important for integration of non spatial data. These standards are usually relatively new and till now not well approved in practice. Here will be necessary close collaboration with other running initiatives (for example SDI4Apps, SmartOpenData) to cooperate and exchange information about this standards.

4 Results from relevant projects

4.1 Architectural roadmaps from previous related projects in the environmental and agricultural domains

This section provides an overview about the evolution of geospatial reference architectures (and their relevance for the FOODIE architecture). In particular, it gives a justification to apply the viewpoint approach of ISO Reference Model for Open Distributed Processing (ISO/IEC 10746-1:1998) for the documentation of the FOODIE architecture.

Besides, this section also reviews the architectural concepts developed in agriculture specific ICT projects that are also of relevance for FOODIE.

4.1.1 Reference Models

For many years, the European Commission has supported research activities to analyse user and system requirements, to derive architectural principles, and to specify and implement generic components of ICT architectures for large-scale environmental information systems [136]. In parallel, on a world-wide level, various approaches of standardization organizations such as ISO, OGC, OMG, OASIS and The Open Group were launched to stimulate a market based on agreed architectures with the aim of fostering interoperable solutions. Each standardization activity has started by the definition of terms, high-level concepts and their relationships, resulting in a series of reference models (see Figure 6), partly competing and partly complementary.

Figure 6 Evolution of Reference Models

Each standardization activity has started by the definition of terms, high-level concepts and their relationships, resulting in a series of reference models (see Figure 6), partly competing and partly complementary.

OASIS [137] defines a reference model (RM) as an “abstract framework for understanding significant relationships among the entities of some environment. It enables the development of specific reference or concrete architectures using consistent standards or specifications supporting that environment.” These reference models set the conceptual foundation of distributed systems. Originally inspired by the architectural style of interacting objects for distributed processing, they are nowadays discussed in the context of SOAs.

Figure 6 illustrates the two major evolution lines of reference models. The upper line shows the interpretation of the RM-ODP for geospatial distributed processing. It has started with the OGC Reference Model (section 4.1.2) followed by the Reference Model for the ORCHESTRA Architecture (RM-OA) [138] which was developed as a reference architecture for environmental risk management as part of the ORCHESTRA project⁷⁷. The latest extensions include sensors and sensor service networks resulting in the Sensor Service Architecture (SensorSA) [139] based upon OGC Sensor Web Enablement architecture [140]. The RM-OA and the SensorSA were both influenced by the specification of SOA reference models that were drafted by OASIS. Their evolution is shown in the lower line in Figure 6.

4.1.2 OGC Reference Model

The original OGC Reference Model of 2003 [141] laid the basis for the development of a series of OGC standards

⁷⁷ <http://www.eu-orchestra.org/>

for geospatial services and information models. The OGC Reference Model does neither provide any guidance about how to use and order the viewpoints in a design process, nor is the interpretation oriented at the principles of service-oriented computing.

As language for the specification of the information viewpoint it adopted the specification of the General Feature Model (GFM) defined in the ISO rules for application schema (ISO 19109:2005). The GFM is a meta-model for information models using UML extension mechanisms [142]. It defines a feature as an abstraction of a real world phenomenon. A feature is the basic unit for information modelling. Individual feature instances are grouped into feature types where all instances of a certain type are described by common properties such as thematic, temporal or spatial attributes or associations with other feature types.

For the specification of the computational viewpoint the OGC Reference Model identified types and names of geospatial services and categorized them according to ISO 19119:2005. An overview and short introduction to all OGC standards that are derived from the OGC Reference Model (Version 0.1.3) of 2003 is covered by its latest version of 2008 [143].

Hence, starting from a conceptual architectural framework in 2003 that guided a series of OGC standardization work, the OGC Reference Model now provides a kind of structured guidance through the standards developed by OGC. However, the original specification, e.g. the General Feature Model, is still valid and relevant for the FOODIE architecture.

4.1.3 Reference Model of the ORCHESTRA Architecture (RM-OA)

The Reference Model for the ORCHESTRA Architecture (RM-OA) provides a platform-neutral abstract specification of a geospatial service-oriented architecture that responds to the requirements of environmental risk management applications but is not exclusively tied to this application domain. It comprises generic architecture services and information models based on and extending existing OGC specifications [138].

The specification of the RM-OA required a detailed consideration of the work of standardization bodies which resulted in a complex braiding [144] as illustrated in Figure 7 and explained below.

The following ISO and OGC standards heavily influenced the specification of the RM-OA models:

- The ISO/IEC 10746 Reference Model for Open Distributed Processing (RM-ODP) provided the structuring into viewpoints (as explained above).
- The OGC Reference Model (see 4.1.2) influenced the basic structure of the RM-OA document and the usage of the pertinent ISO standards.
- The conceptual modelling of the RM-OA Information Viewpoint was performed according to the basic concepts (such as a “feature”) of ISO 19101:2004 Geographic information - Reference model.
- The meta-model for information is an evolution of the General Feature Model as defined in ISO 19109:2005 Geographic information - Rules for application schema.
- The meta-model for services defined in the RM-OA Service Viewpoint is derived from ISO 19119:2005 Geographic Information - Services but harmonized with the meta-model for information (ISO

19109:2005).

- The OpenGIS Web Service Common Implementation Specification details many of the aspects that are, or will be (because harmonization efforts are under way), common to all OGC Web Service interface Implementation Specifications. This idea was adopted for the specification of common service characteristics in terms of reusable interfaces, for example, for the specification of their capabilities.

In 2007 the RM-OA was accepted as a best-practices architectural framework for geospatial applications by the OGC Technical Committee [138]. Due to its generic and standards-based approach the author proposes it as foundation for system-of-systems engineering projects in the environmental science application domain.

4.1.4 Sensor Service Architecture (SensorSA)

The RM-OA was refined and extended towards a Sensor Service Architecture (SensorSA) [139] in the course of the European Integrated Project SANY⁷⁸ [145]. In addition to the RM-OA, the SensorSA includes the access to sensor observations (e.g. measurement values) and the management of sensors and sensor service networks. Sensors provide the input data for environmental monitoring as well as for risk management of natural, technical and man-made hazards. The SensorSA is based upon the services and information models of the OGC Sensor Web Enablement architecture [140] but puts them into the context of the RM-ODP viewpoints.

The objective of the SensorSA is to motivate and specify the basic design decisions derived from user requirements and generic architectural principles. Its focus is on a platform-neutral specification, i.e. it provides the basic concepts and their interrelationships (conceptual models) and abstract specifications.

Its relevance for FOODIE is derived from the fact that the SensorSA is based upon the OGC Sensor Web Enablement architecture and introduced the notion of a multi-style architecture into the geospatial domain. The SensorSA supports, in addition to the classical architectural style, which is oriented towards remote invocations, an event-driven and a resource-oriented architectural style.

As such, it foresees mechanisms to generate events and distribute them as notifications to interested consumers. This enables spontaneous distribution of information about changing configurations in underlying sensor networks, e.g. the dynamic addition or removal of sensor devices, which is a pre-requisite for the support of the “plug-and-measure” type of operation.

Furthermore, the SensorSA embeds a resource-oriented architectural style. Resource-orientation in the SensorSA refers to unique identification of geospatial resources (e.g. time series of observation results, spatial data sets) and their representations as tables, maps or diagrams. This approach provides more flexibility in the design of an implementation architecture. For instance, it enables the mapping to and the co-existence with so-called RESTful web service environments [146]. By this multi-style approach, it remains a design decision of the system engineer in the engineering step which architectural style best suits the individual purpose and requirements.

4.1.5 EO2HEAVEN Spatial Information Infrastructure

The Spatial Information Infrastructure of the European research project EO2HEAVEN continues the series of architecture specifications of the previous FP6 European projects ORCHESTRA and SANY as described above. EO2HEAVEN (Earth Observation and Environmental Modelling for the Mitigation of Health Risks) contributes to a better understanding of the complex relationships between environmental changes and their impact on human health.

The EO2HEAVEN spatial information infrastructure [147] provides further extensions and refinements to the SensorSA of SANY, e.g. taking into account the requirements to share and process huge amounts of datasets provided by Earth observation agencies and health institutions in order to investigate and assess correlated risks. Furthermore, in its Engineering Viewpoint it discusses how to handle security and uncertainty issues for large datasets and discusses the aspects of moving code versus the transfer of large data sets for geospatial processing chains.

⁷⁸ <http://www.sany-ip.eu/>

Apart from these functional and informational enhancements the EO2HEAVEN spatial information infrastructure is interesting for FOODIE for its iterative approach in refining and upgrading the architectural specification according to emerging technologies and updates of international standards (ISO, OGC).

4.1.6 AFORO

The objective of the AFORO project (running in 2002 and 2003) was to provide a vision and work plan to implement future RTD trends for the transformation of agri-food industries into digital enterprises. The AFORO consortium split the agri-food domain into several more "manageable" sectors. Each of them had its own roadmap. The selected sectors were: (a) primary sources, (b) processed food products, (c) beverages and (d) additives, conservatives & flavours.

For every sector the main objectives were:

- to define business needs,
- to identify the main constraints to be taken into account,
- to define a technology independent roadmap based on business demands.

The AFORO methodology defined an approach to how the business needs of the agri-food domain can be established in an ordered way. The process was divided into the following steps:

- data gathering,
- ascertaining of current and future objectives,
- analysis of these objectives,
- listing of key drivers [148].

The AFORO project defined a roadmapping methodology based on the description of the situation As is and defining the strategic vision To be. The important output from the AFORO roadmap is a consensus of business needs. The following business needs were recognised by AFORO.

- To support food traceability and safety over the whole European market chain.
- To implement interoperability technologies enabling networked organisations and forming a Single Food European Market.
- To develop market knowledge supporting innovative value added products, processes and business strategies.
- To design and develop interoperability tools for European logistic and services.
- To design a European Agri-food Information System including materials, technologies, and results of RTD activities.
- To support the transformation of agri-food business into an effective collaborative organisation.

For every issue the situation AS-IS was analysed and the roadmap TO-BE was defined. For detailed recommendations, see [149].

Figure 8 The AFORO road mapping methodology

4.1.7 ami@netfood

The objective of the AMI@Netfood project (2005 -2006) was to support the implementation of the IST Research Priority and Framework Programme, providing a long-term vision on future trends on scientific and technology research oriented to the development and application of ambient intelligence technologies for the agri-food domain.⁷⁹

The Strategic Research Agenda (SRA) outlined activities necessary to support both rural development and in particular agri-food industries. Concerning agri-food businesses, SRA intended to provide a path to facilitate the sector to retain their position as world leaders in providing safe and healthy food products at a reasonable cost. The approach taken was to draw upon ICT to support businesses and industry in the agri-food sector and transform it into a Collaborative Working Environment (CWE). In relation with rural development domain, the SRA described the needs of the sector and proposed measures to implement ICT solutions in rural areas to support their development. The approach selected not only focused on the development of applications and infrastructures, but also on a means to promote the diversification of rural activities and the promotion of new services through the wide adoption of information and communications technologies.⁸⁰

The ami@netfood SRA defined the following challenges:

- Support the European agri-food industry, especially SMEs, to be a worldwide leader in the supply of high quality and safe food products.
- Increase the level of involvement of consumers in the agri-food value chain by means of the wide adoption of relevant IC technologies and applications.
- Increase the areas in which European citizens find collaborative working environments assisted by ICTs by extending them to agri-food industry and rural domain.
- Open new business opportunities for the European ICT industry through development of new applications and tools to support the European agri-food and rural sector.
- Contribute to trigger the investment in ICT and telecommunications infrastructure by means of creating new business models in rural areas.
- Make rural Europe a more attractive place to live, invest and work, promoting knowledge and innovation for growth and creating more and better jobs.

⁷⁹ <http://www.ami-netfood.com/>

⁸⁰ Dr. Bjarki A Brynjarsson, Dr. Dragan Stokic, Harald Sundmaeker, Jesús de Juan. DRAFT Strategic Research Agenda. Collaborative Work Environments – ICTs supporting Agri-food businesses and Rural development

The research and technology development (RTD) domains selected were:

- ICT applications for the complete traceability of products and services throughout a networked value chain.
- Collaborative environments in agri-food and rural areas.
- ICT applications supporting the management of natural resources and rural development creating value for citizens and businesses.
- Innovative ICT applications in rural areas using broadband infrastructure.

The defined RTD objectives were:

- Developing of interoperable integrated intra- and inter-enterprise applications.
- Improving network collaboration.
- Increasing the effectiveness and efficiency of knowledge sharing.
- Improving the customer orientated business model.
- Supporting the dynamic network management.

4.1.8 Ami4for

The main objective was to establish a new concept of Ambient Mobile Intelligence (AMI) for forest, vinery and agriculture management integrated mobile communication, new methods of navigation (GPS, EGNOS, GALILEO) and integration of spatial information including satellite imaging (SPOT, IKONOS, EROS, PROBA). The specific objectives The integration of a Spatial Data Infrastructure (integrated satellite imagery) as part of a forestry and agriculture knowledge system on the base of standards and recommendations of OGC (Open Geospatial Consortium) with principles of Semantic Web The design and implementation of a communication and navigation system in a heterogeneous network (terrestrial Internet, GPRS, WIFI, satellite) in combination with current and future navigation systems (GPS, EGNOS, GALILEO). The use of new methods for data mining, modelling and analysis for improving forestry and agriculture (in particular precision farming and vinery) management. The new technologies will support the building of the forestry and agriculture knowledge system (forest management, precision farming, and vineyard management)

4.1.9 GIGAS

The objectives of GIGAS project was to ensure architectural coherence between INSPIRE, GMES and GEOSS based on analysis of services and standards. The focus was on full integration of the architectures of these three initiatives. All these initiatives are focused on interoperability of data, informatics and services with focus on environmental monitoring and management in the most open and interoperable way. INSPIRE, GEOSS and GMES apply open service-oriented architecture and software infrastructure using, whenever feasible, already established standards⁸¹.

GIGAS included not only analysis of these three initiatives, but also analysed, how different standardization efforts were covered by these initiatives.

The analysis of GIGAS improved the mutual understanding (technical and procedural) of all these three initiatives. This analysis showed an explicit overlap of their objectives, missions and tasks, but also of the architectural principles, while benefiting from an interoperable approach. The initiatives have similar approaches, but so

Figure 9 GIGAS forum and recommendations

⁸¹ GIGAS Technology Watch Report Architecture Technical Note, <http://www.thegigasforum.eu/cgi-bin/download.pl?f=345.pdf>

far a number of interoperability barriers impede the exploitation of synergies. On the base of this GIGAS design multi-initiative enterprise context, in which interoperability between the different layers enables a common access across the initiatives.

From the user’s perspective, the multi-initiative enterprise context reveals the following advantages:

- Portals search resources over different initiatives and application domains
- Transparent and interoperable access to additional data
- Better reuse of services among different initiatives and application domains
- Development of applications using resources from different initiatives [150].

4.1.10 Humboldt

The Humboldt project focus was on the integration of GEMS and INSPIRE initiative. The Humboldt project aims at helping organisations to enable organisations to document, publish and harmonise their spatial information. The technical goal of Humboldt is to support Spatial Data Infrastructure (SDI) enablement by providing the functionalities for covering the data harmonization process as a whole. The Humboldt Tools and Services are built on current state of the art and standards, designed to provide solutions to all types of users, data custodians as well as private end-users. Humboldt enables the use of single functionalities as part of your own infrastructure⁸².

For the design of software architecture, Humboldt defines as mandatory Distributed Processing-Reference model-RM-ODP and Unified Modelling Language (UML 2).

On the base of scenarios need a common and shared infrastructure was defined [151].

Figure 10 Humboldt scenarios

⁸² <http://www.esdi-humboldt.eu/home.html>

The first components of the Humboldt Framework have been published under the GNU Lesser General Public License version 3 (LGPL v3). They are available for free download at the Humboldt Community Website. This release includes the following software components:

- The Humboldt Model Editor, a UML editor that is specifically geared towards the creation of UML application schemas;
- The Humboldt Alignment Editor, a tool that allows to define conceptual schema transformations;
- The Humboldt Workflow Editor
- The Humboldt Mediator Service, a proxy service that executes transformation chains to provide harmonised geodata;
- The Humboldt Workflow Repository Service, a service that analyses data sets and decides which processing is required to match a target product description;
- The Humboldt Context Service, an easy to use-service that can be used to define transformation products;
- Several transformation services exposed as OGC Web Processing Services, such as Coordinate Transformation Service and an Edge Matching Service⁸³.

4.1.11 AgriXchange

Within the knowledge-based bio-economy, information sharing is an important issue. In agri-food business, this is a complex issue because many aspects and dimensions play a role. An installed base of information systems lack standardization, which hampers efficient exchange of information. This leads to inefficient business processes and hampers adoption of new knowledge and technology. Especially, the exchange of information at whole chain or network level is poorly organized. Although arable and livestock farming have their own specific needs, there are many similarities in the need for an integrated approach. Spatial data increasingly plays an important role in agriculture.

4.1.12 Plan4all

Plan4all in document Data Sharing Requirements⁸⁴ compares classification of services according ISO 19119⁸⁵ with classification of services provided by INSPIRE. ISO19119 classification is much broader than the INSPIRE classification and for purposes of Habitats it will be necessary to also include additional services, then the services required by INSPIRE. So ISO19119 nomenclature of services could be useful for HABITATS architecture design. In the document Data Sharing Requirements the advantage of centralised and decentralised architecture is also compared. The advantages and disadvantages of centralised and decentralised infrastructure include:

- Centralised advantage: - Allows generalization of content to take place at a higher level, whereby making the Plan4all infrastructure. Integration of data allows complex queries, analysis with high speed and performance. Fewer points to implement and maintain services and (custom) protocols
- Centralised disadvantage - Requires a solid server platform from the perspective of the aggregator. Might lead to issues related to intellectual property rights.
- Distributed advantage - All services will be working directly towards authoritative data sources without any time-lag. Allows for local autonomy and institutional involvement
- Distributed disadvantage - Content and schema will have to be generalized at the local level
- Requires skills, experience and resources in running distributed trusted infrastructures

⁸³ <http://www.esdi-humboldt.eu/open-source.html>

⁸⁴ http://wiki.plan4all.eu/wk/images/3/34/Data_sharing_requirements.pdf

⁸⁵ International Organization for Standardization, Geographic information Services, ISO 19119:2005. July 8, 2005

Conclusion of Plan4all is, that future systems will be some way of co-existence of both models.

Plan4all Networking Architecture design⁸⁶ was based on RM-ODP methodology for design. Information viewpoint put in the centre spatial planning data. The spatial plan is consider as a composition of spatial data and document. Information viewpoint describe all operation, which are provided with data. All this parts are described by metadata. The computational viewpoint defines a set of basic services and their relations. On the base of this scheme Engineering viewpoint define generic platform independent architecture of the system. Technology viewpoint give recommendation for potential software tools, which could be used for implementation of Plan4all architecture.

Figure 11 Plan4all architecture diagram

4.1.13 Habitats

HABITATS [152] extends user-centric, co-design approaches into the arena of standards design and adoption processes, considering standards initiatives such as INSPIRE, OGC, UNSDI to be significant social, economic and institutional innovations. The elements of approach are maintained, applying the model at all levels from the global scale of the local and regional policies that frame many HABITATS validation pilots. Community building activities follow a Web 2.0 approach to capture the knowledge in active user communities with a strong interest in contributing to the standards development process. By inviting a broad multi-sectorial and inter-disciplinary range of concerned stakeholders to participate in the HABITATS network, a viral motivation spiral is set off. A peer-to-peer approach to opening up information sources and providing access to content ensure a rapid extension of the critical mass of environmental data established by project partners.

The reference laboratory (RL) allows deploying the current state of the art of technological solution, which will be tested and adopted by Habitats partners and user partners. It allows testing current existing technology and allows generating further research tasks through a user driven process.

Reference laboratory will also collect information coming from other projects, which will be important input for Habitats analysis and Habitats public discussion. Methods of social assessment will be an important part of the reference laboratory.

Habitats RL is based on principles of Geoportal4everybody.

Habitats RL is designed and implemented as a virtual database. It uses principles of web services, URM, social network sites, Geoportal4everybody and semantic web. It integrates different technologies like GIS, e-learning, multimedia, and virtual reality. An important part is the integration of social networking tools supporting social assessment. These services are not implemented on the Habitats portal directly, but they are implemented as virtual services on different places in Europe.

Habitats extended this model and added I consists of several layers, which are:

⁸⁶ <http://www.plan4all.eu/simplecms/?menuID=37&articleID=62&action=article&presenter=ArticleDetail>

- Data layers – management data and files on storage, eventually guarantee access to external sensors
- Server (engine layer) – defines tools, which guarantee basic services on the server side – supplying service
- Client layer – is client side of Web services, which guarantee access of users to services
- Application layer is some form of wrapping elementary client services into application or into such form, which could be used by other Web tools
- Presentation layer contain such web tools, which allow to combine and publish single objects from the application level as part of Web presentation

The illustration below shows the different layers of the HABITATS Networking Architecture.

Figure 12 HABITATS Networking Architecture

4.1.14 Plan4business

Plan4business is a European project running from April 2012 until March 2014 and is co-financed by the 7th Framework Programme of the European Commission. The full title is plan4business – a Service Platform for Aggregation, Processing and Analysing of Urban and Regional Planning Data. Plan4business develops a service platform for aggregation, processing and analyses of urban and regional planning data in Europe. Harmonised data will be integrated into seamless, homogenous, constantly growing and updated trans-border dataset. The platform will enable spatial analyses across European datasets. The platform should serve not only as a catalogue of planning data but also as their integrator enabling users to search, view, analyse and download spatial planning data on European and regional levels. The main project objectives are the automation of harmonisation processes and possibilities of complex analyses.

The design and development of the client side for the plan4business platform should result in the design and development of the client side components of the plan4business service platform including the Authorisation, Authentication, Integration, Analysis and Plan hosting, API (Application Programming Interface) for integration of the Analysis Engine into other portals. On the base of previous experiences it was decided to run the development in parallel to collection of user requirements. It enables to receive feedback from users, but also support user demands on the base of existing tools. The agile approach is also taken to software development, and it is a basic requirement for WP3 (Requirements Management and Service Pricing) that results are delivered early and often. The work is running closely with WP5 Storage, Integration & Analysis Engines, where server side is designed and implemented.

The client components developed are based on existing tools and these tools are modified and extended on the basis of user requirements. For this purpose, a series of workshops aimed to different groups of stakeholders are

being organised and a feedback on the development is tracked using a questionnaire for workshops' participants.

The plan4business team has realised that it has to go for a quick win in a given region or a country with specific applications. The first goal was to simplify the access to information for different types of users which are non-GI experts. The first pilot application that has been implemented is the Location Evaluator. The development of the application was focused on the integration of existing data sources. Data integration and building of data repositories was recognised as a key aspect for success of the plan4business platform. Other pilot applications include Thematic Map Atlas, Harmonise, Embed-Map and others. The complete list of applications is included in the extra document requested after the 1st project review - Business Model – Progress Report.

A specific focus of these Service Levels is on a staged rollout of services to be offered by the *plan4business* platform. By using this staged approach, the platform starts to attract customers with concrete and useable services from the early stage of the development. These early results are valuable in providing feedback and in testing the infrastructure.

The five Service Levels are:

Service Level 1: This level includes examples of various components of the future platform which are not necessarily integrated but they show the basic functions that can be further elaborated and extended. This level includes:

- a data storage for disharmonised spatial and non-spatial data,
- a common data model for harmonised data based on the INSPIRE Directive,
- mechanisms for data integration into the common data model,
- features (platform prototype) for data display and simple navigation,
- utilisation of pan-European datasets related to spatial planning from scattered resources.
- The developed components are used for showcases during workshops, presentations and other meetings in order to provide potential customers an idea of the future platform and its functions and get feedback from end users.

Service Level 2: The main goal for this level is to make the platform prototype publicly available and extend it by the following features:

- analysis of harmonised spatial data based on user requirements (this should include not only predefined queries but also a possibility for user defined queries),
- advanced visualisation tools,
- user customised data mining queries,
- retrieval of the data mining and analysis results for display,
- prototype management tools for data upload, download and publication using OGC Web Services,
- catalogue of spatial planning data,
- creation of user defined map compositions.

Service Level 3: This service level includes improvement of the features from previous service levels and in addition the following features will be utilised:

- mapping functions for maps' customisation based on identified use-cases,
- integration of the harmonisation tools into the platform,
- integrated metadata for analyses, map compositions and integration schemas,
- extended data management tools enabling maintenance of different versions of datasets,
- first releases of pilot applications – Location Evaluator and Thematic Map Viewer.

Service Level 4: This service level includes improvement of the features from previous service levels, their integration into the platform and in addition the following features will be utilised:

- new design of the user interface,
- advanced portrayal of the analysis result in a form of a table, chart or a report.
- support of most of the data formats defined by the users,
- tools for embedding maps into external applications,

- generation of a report from a selected area including information such as data availability, data quality, data source and non-spatial data that are integrated with spatial data.
- integration of single components into an integrated platform.

Service Level 5 – additionally, the Service Level 5 was designed. It includes:

- data download,
- tools for utilising feedback from users of spatial planning data,
- support of more complex queries by using the primary data storage as well as the secondary data storage,
- additional user applications for investors, design and implementation of a brownfield database,
- integration of advertisement into the portal,
- payment module,
- components' update.

The plan4business system is a comprehensive and complex system, built on flexible and scalable layers, interacting through a set of defined services, ensuring performance and security.

Figure 13 plan4business overall architecture

The three layers are:

- **Application** layer, consisting of user portals and interfaces for handling data, administrating the system and for data access, including analyses and data downloading.
- **Service** layer, with services for data integration, analyses, data access, processing and data hosting.
- **Data** layer, with data storage and download services [153].

4.1.15 FutureFarm

FutureFarm was a European project funded by the EU as part of the Seventh Research Framework Programme. The official project start date was 1st January 2008, and the project duration is 3 years. The full project title was "Meeting the challenges of the farm of tomorrow by integrating Farm Management Information Systems to support real-time management decisions and compliance to standards", and the funding is under the Cooperation programme of the FP7 in the Food, Agriculture, Fisheries and Biotechnologies (Knowledge Based Bio-Economy) theme. From FOODIE projects are important two results of FutureFarm project:

- Vision of FutureFarm knowledge management system

- Machine-readable encoding for definitions of data required to assess compliance to agricultural management and crop production standards

Future farm knowledge management systems have to support not only direct profitability of farms or environment protection, but also activities of individuals and groups allowing effective collaboration among groups in agri-food industry, consumers and wider communities, especially in rural domain. Having these considerations in mind, the proposed vision lays the foundation for meeting ambitious but achievable operational objectives that will definitively contribute to fulfil identified needs in the long run.

The farmer has two options. Either he is able to handle easy to use tools that allow with a few clicks to solve all these problems or he gets support by new models of farm advisory systems that are able to solve his needs. The existing extension services are only partly able to keep updated with the farmers' common needs.

Knowledge management systems for generation of homogeneous information for traceability transfer and business as well as integration and management of such information are thus specifically complex issues in this sector. Therefore, the challenging problem is twofold. Firstly, how to assure the full security and safety of products but minimising costs. Secondly, how to provide benefit to the food sector networks of organisations enabling them to interoperate, to exchange information and data and to fully integrate miscellaneous business functions along the value chain. These problems (partly valid for a number of other sectors) are increasingly becoming critical and difficult in the agri-food sector (due to complexity of full traceability and minimal margins) [154].

In order to reliably assess compliance to agricultural management and crop production standards and regulations, a large body of data is required. In order that farmers may gather the correct data to self-check compliance, and that they can produce the necessary data in order to prove compliance to controlling bodies, it is desirable, or even essential, that the exact data required be explicitly and unambiguously defined.

Although this aim is easily defined, no simple solution is available. Two central problems may be identified:

1. Each standard, or rule within that standard, does not in general explicitly state how compliance should be assessed: often there is no clear single data item, or set of data, which is required, or there may be multiple possible alternatives.
2. There is no universal vocabulary or data dictionary for agriculture. Each standard uses its own vocabulary, which may be defined as part of that standard, whilst each FMIS also has an internal data model which may, or more likely may not, correspond to the vocabulary used by any particular standard. Similarly, current data exchange formats for agriculture have a certain vocabulary which does not necessarily correspond to any other. In technical terms, multiple ontologies are in use, which are not always directly comparable.

As a proposed partial solution to this complicated problem, a two-stage system was defined:

1. The machine-readable definition of the rules reference one or more formal ontologies to specify the concepts which are required to define the rule.
2. The FMIS component responsible for evaluating the rules provides a mechanism for translating the concepts from the ontologies to a specific data format which is implemented by the FMIS (e.g. agroXML or a software-internal data structure) [155].

4.1.16 agriXchange

Within the knowledge-based bio-economy, information sharing is an important issue. In agri-food business, this is a complex issue because many aspects and dimensions play a role. An installed base of information systems lack standardization, which hampers efficient exchange of information. This leads to inefficient business processes and hampers adoption of new knowledge and technology. Especially, the exchange of information at whole chain or network level is poorly organized. Although arable and livestock farming have their own specific needs, there are many similarities in the need for an integrated approach. Spatial data increasingly plays an important role in agriculture.

The overall objective of agriXchange project was to coordinate and support the setting up of sustainable network for developing a system for common data exchange in agriculture. This was achieved by:

- Establishing a platform on data exchange in agriculture in the EU

- Developing a reference framework for interoperability of data exchange
- Identifying the main challenges for harmonizing data exchange

First, an in-depth analysis and investigation of the state-of-the art in EU member states was carried out. A platform was built up that facilitates communication and collaborative working groups, that work on several, representative use cases, guided by an integrative reference framework. The framework consists of a sound architecture and infrastructure based on a business process modeling approach integrating existing standards and services.

The development was done in close interaction with relevant stakeholders through the platform and international workshops. The results converge into a strategic research agenda that contains a roadmap for future developments⁸⁷.

4.1.17 Digital Earth Platform

Digital Earth Platform is an initiative of the Joint Research Centre of the European Commission that targets the European branch of the Digital Earth concept as described in section 2.1.9. As such, it (see also European Commission – DG Joint Research Centre, 2014):

- develops components towards an interactive platform for policy analysis and decision making based on the convergence of model web, sensor technologies and online social media with Big Data analytics;
- contributes to Digital Science through targeted pilots grounded by theoretical perspectives, analytical methods and foresight activities;
- develops new technological solutions for innovative data visualisation, experimentation and analysis, whilst addressing also privacy considerations.

The research activity of the Digital Earth Platform is considered for three years, between 2014 and 2016. The main outcome of this research should be to guide the evolution from current systems and technologies towards the 2020 vision of Digital Earth as an interactive platform for policy analysis and evaluation. Furthermore, it should advance the state of the art in the processing of Big Data from heterogeneous sources (citizens, sensors, models, and official public sector data) and their visualization in interactive environments.

4.1.18 GEOLAND2

With the ongoing climate change, the pressure on nature biodiversity and our own living conditions increases steadily. To mitigate these threats by effective adaptation strategies and counter measures a frequent and area-wide monitoring of the environment is crucial to provide decision makers with accurate, up-to-date and reliable information on the changing conditions of our natural resources.

Within the GMES initiative (Global Monitoring for Environment and Security) the Land Services provide cross-border harmonised geo-information at global to local scales in a time- and cost-effective manner. These monitoring services have been defined, developed and implemented within a series of projects funded by the European Commission (e.g., Geoland, BOSS4GMES) and the European Space Agency (e.g., GSE Land and GSE Forest Monitoring).

Building upon their results, geoland2 organised a qualified production network, to build, validate and demonstrate operational processing lines and to set-up a user driven product quality assurance process.

The architecture of geoland2 was made up of two layers: The Core Mapping Services provide land cover, land use and land cover change, as well as a range of bio-physical parameters as an input to more elaborated products while the Core Information Services offer specific information for European Environmental Policies and international treaties on Climate Change, food security and the sustainable development of Africa.⁸⁸

4.1.19 GS Soil

“Assessment and strategic development of INSPIRE compliant Geodata-Services for European Soil Data” with

⁸⁷ <http://www.agrixchange.org/>

⁸⁸ <http://www.gmes-geoland.info/project-background.html>

better known abbreviation “GS Soil” was one of the projects funded between 2009 and 2012 within the European eContent^{plus} framework. The eContent^{plus} framework focused on making the digital content in Europe more accessible, usable and exploitable. For that reason, 34 project partners from 19 European countries connected their forces to collect, harmonise and present the soil information to both – domain experts and non-experts.

The main motivation was that the project reflected the status of soil data at the beginning of the new millennia: comprehensive soil data assets existed within the European Member States:

- although notable amounts of soil data have already been prepared digitally, data accessibility was still extremely limited;
- the inter-organisational and cross-border distribution of soil data was tremendously difficult and in many cases data sets were not interoperable, neither on a technical nor on a semantic level;
- for the huge community of experts and citizens within the European Union soil data therefore were difficult to obtain, to understand and to use.

Figure 14 The organisational structure of the GS Soil project

The GS Soil project aimed at establishing a Best Practice Network focused on soil related issues, through state-of-the-art methodologies and best practice examples, in order to enhance harmonization of national datasets and improving accessibility and exploitability. Thereby it also contributed to the INSPIRE implementation with specific reference to a cluster of data themes on nature conservation.

The main objective of the GS Soil project was to establish the GS Soil Network. As such the project was successful in order to:

- involve new stakeholders;
- share data and best practices;
- improve and stimulate exploitation;
- improve re-use of information on nature conservation.

There were also several technical results of the project, where we would like to highlight:

- best practices for metadata creation and management;
- description of all project partners' datasets within soil domain with INSPIRE-compliant metadata;
- establishment of the soil-domain thesaurus called "SoilThes"⁸⁹;
- publishing the metadata through catalogue services with the main entry point at the GS Soil Portal⁹⁰;
- publishing preview of soil data (maps) at the GS Soil Portal as well;
- establishment of best practice for harmonised soil data exchange through XML-based format.

FOODIE project may therefore re-use the results of the GS Soil project, especially to discover relevant soil-domain data through catalogue services as well as benefit from the harmonised data as inputs for agricultural analyses, modelling, etc.

4.1.20 SmartOpenData

SmartOpenData⁹¹ aims at creating a Linked Open Data infrastructure (including software tools and data) fed by public and freely available data resources, existing sources for biodiversity and environment protection and research in rural and European protected areas and its National Parks.

This will provide opportunities for SMEs to generate new innovative products and services that can lead to new businesses in the environmental, regional decision-making and policy areas among others. The value of the data will be greatly enhanced by making it available through a common query language that gives access to related datasets available in the linked open data cloud.

The commonality of data structure and query language will overcome the monolingual nature of typical datasets, making them available in multiple languages.

4.1.21 SDI4Apps Open Sensor Network and Open Land Use pilots

The main target of SDI4Apps is to bridge the 1) top-down managed world of INSPIRE, Copernicus and GEOSS built by SDI experts and 2) the bottom-up mobile world of voluntary initiatives and thousands of micro SMEs and individuals developing applications (apps). SDI4Apps will secure that users profit from INSPIRE and INSPIRE profits from different voluntary initiatives. SDI4Apps will build a WIN-WIN strategy for building a successful business for hundreds of European SMEs on the basis of INSPIRE, Copernicus and GEOSS.

PILOT III: Open Sensor Network

The aim of **Open Sensors Network** is to create an environment where different groups of volunteers (for example farmers) will be able to integrate low cost sensors (meteorological, quality of air, etc.) into local and regional web sensor networks.

The pilot application will integrate meteorological data and in-situ meteorological sensing networks based on small stations collecting agro-meteorological data to support the crop production systems.

The pilot will define a framework for taking advantage of intelligent sensor webs based on the converging technologies of standard meteorological sensors, micro sensors, computers, and wireless telecommunications with data management and analysis in support of agriculture production activities such as the chemical protection, grape and wine production, fruit protection and production.

Figure 15 Open Sensor Network

⁸⁹ see https://secure.umweltbundesamt.at/soil/en/hierarchical_concepts.html

⁹⁰ <http://www.gssoil-portal.eu>

⁹¹ <http://www.smartopendata.eu/>

The knowledge gained from integrated sensors sensing has the potential to empower managers and decision makers to act on crop and fruit production. The importance of meteorology advisory and measure in agriculture has been increasing during last decades due to emerging need to access appropriate information as a consequence of the increased rapid weather conditions changes. Although the quality of weather forecast has been improved constantly and agriculture is benefiting from this achieved capability, in many European regions, the currently available meteorological data are not sufficient for crop production, as a lot of additional local scale data are needed to be integrated in the specific agro-meteorological models and to take the correct decision in any farm management system.

PILOT IV: Open Land Use Map Through VGI

Land use involves management and modification of natural environment or wilderness into built environment such as fields, pastures, and settlements. It also has been defined as "the arrangements, activities and inputs people undertake in a certain land cover type to produce, change or maintain it" (FAO, 1997a; FAO/UNEP, 1999).

Land use practices vary considerably across the world. The United Nations' Food and Agriculture Organization Water Development Division explains that "Land use concerns the products and/or benefits obtained from use of the land as well as the land management actions (activities) carried out by humans to produce those products and benefits."⁹² As of the early 1990s, about 13% of the Earth was considered arable land, with 26% in pasture, 32% forests and woodland, and 1.5% urban areas.

Land use and land management practices have a major impact on natural resources including water, soil, nutrients, plants and animals. Land use information can be used to develop solutions for natural resource management issues such as salinity and water quality. For instance, water bodies in a region that has been deforested or having erosion will have different water quality than those in areas that are forested. Forest gardening, a plant-based food production system, is believed to be the oldest form of land use in the world

The intention of **SDI4Apps** project is to start support voluntary initiative for Open Land Use Mapping.

4.1.22 AGRO IT - Increasing the efficiency of farming through open standards based AGRO IT platform

AgroIT⁹³ is an EU funded project that will implement an open platform based on open standards. Project will deliver applications and services to various stakeholders: farmers, local communities, state institutions, consulting institutions in farming (government founded and private) and EU institutions.

Main target users are farmers, agricultural organisations, and government and EU institutions from the area of agriculture.

4.2 Future Internet projects with links to the environmental and agricultural domains

The next subsections present a list of projects with focus on the development and provision of Future Internet applications (most projects belong to the FI-PPP programme). In that sense, FOODIE project aims at developing a platform hub that not only offers open data sets but also provides agricultural applications that take into account the latest advancements, concepts and technologies of Future Internet.

As in the former section, the architectural roadmaps of these projects will be of especial relevance for designing the basis of FOODIE architecture in order to build it from a common baseline and be in line with the current trends in the Internet of the Future applications, especially those with links in the environmental and agricultural domain (as for instance in the case of ENVIROFI, SMARTAGRIFOOD or FISpace Future Internet projects).

4.2.1 FI-WARE

The high-level goal of the FI-WARE project⁹⁴ is to build the Core Platform of the Future Internet. This Core Platform, also referred to as the "FI-WARE Platform" or simply "FI-WARE", aiming at increasing the global competi-

⁹² FAO Land and Water Division

⁹³ <http://agro.it.studiomars.si/>

⁹⁴ <http://www.fi-ware.org/>

tiveness of the European ICT economy by introducing an innovative infrastructure for cost-effective creation and delivery of versatile digital services, providing high QoS and security guarantees. As such, it will provide a powerful foundation for the Future Internet, stimulating and cultivating a sustainable ecosystem for (a) innovative service providers delivering new applications and solutions meeting the requirements of established and emerging Usage Areas (e.g., health, environment, smart cities, transport and logistics, etc.); and (b) end users and consumers actively participating in content and service consumption and creation.

FI-WARE is open, based upon elements (called Generic Enablers⁹⁵) which offer reusable and commonly shared functions serving a multiplicity of Usage Areas across various sectors. While not all elements that are suitable to be considered as Generic Enablers will be developed in the FI-WARE project (this would be a goal that the FI-WARE project alone, simply cannot afford), the intention is that all elements developed within FI-WARE can widely be accepted as Generic Enablers, per definition above.

FI-WARE Architecture (and Generic Enablers) is structured along six architectural “chapters”, allowing:

1. Cloud Hosting: Deployment of the Future Internet services on the cloud, i.e. using cloud computing technologies.
2. Data/Context Management Services: Accessing, processing and analysing massive data streams, as well as semantically classifying them into valuable knowledge.
3. Applications and Services Ecosystem and Delivery Framework: Creation, publishing, managing and consuming the Future Internet services.
4. IoT Services Enablement: Leveraging the ubiquity of heterogeneous, resource-constrained devices in the Internet of Things (IoT).
5. Interface to the Network and Devices (I2ND): Accessing the networks and devices through consistent service interfaces.
6. Security: Providing appropriate security mechanisms for all the above.

Each of the six chapters is described in terms of the functional building blocks, i.e., generic enablers (GE), inter- and intra- chapter connections between these GEs and to some level in terms of the standards and preferred technologies.

The following diagram depicts the schema behind the FI-WARE platform the major components (the so called Generic Enablers, or GEs) and the roles interacting with the system. A short introduction to the major building blocks of the FI-WARE, the FI-WARE chapters and their major components can be found in FI-WARE wiki⁹⁶.

⁹⁵ <http://catalogue.fi-ware.org/enablers>

⁹⁶ http://forge.fi-ware.org/plugins/mediawiki/wiki/fiware/index.php/FI-WARE_Architecture

Figure 16 Schematic depiction of FI-WARE platform with all major generic enablers

4.2.2 ENVIROFI

ENVIROFI⁹⁷ is a phase 1 Future Internet Public-Private Partnership (FI-PPP) project. As part of the FI-PPP programme, ENVIROFI consolidates the Future Internet requirements from the Environmental Usage Area perspective and provides technical specifications and prototypes of interoperable geospatial Environmental Enablers⁹⁸. These shall be deployed in the terrestrial, atmospheric and marine environments in collaboration with large stakeholder communities with the perspective of achieving sustainable socio-economic progress in Europe.

Large European communities generate significant amounts of valuable environmental observations at local and regional scales using mobile communication devices, computers and sensors which are mostly connected to the Internet. These communities' environmental observations represent a wealth of information which is currently unused and therefore in need for integration with other fragmented data and information sources, traditionally managed by research and educational institutions and industries.

In order to account for the diversity of existing and potential future solutions, ENVIROFI follows an integrative approach towards its system architecture. This includes a systems of systems approach because the full range of environmental applications cannot be implemented within a single homogeneous structure; and multi-style Service Oriented Architecture (SOA) solution, since the diversity of user requirements implies a rich set of architectures instead of a single one.

The ENVIROFI architecture is based on a set of overarching principles:

- Adoption of a System-of-Systems approach: the systems of systems approach provides a solution for addressing the heterogeneity of systems already implemented in the environmental domain that must

⁹⁷ <http://www.envirofi.eu/>

⁹⁸ <http://catalogue.envirofi.eu/>

be included in the ENVIROFI information system without affecting their normal operations. Moreover, this allows to connect the ENVIROFI information system to relevant systems of systems at European and global level, such as the INSPIRE infrastructure and GEOSS.

- Adoption of a multi-style architecture: relevant environmental resources (data, services, etc.) are currently provided on the Internet adopting different and even mixed architectural styles. Some systems adopt a full SOA, some are based on RESTful approaches, others publish resources as Web 2.0 services, and so on. The ENVIROFI architecture addresses this heterogeneity adopting a multi-style approach to access different systems and resources.
- Orthogonality of the Resource Sharing and Security domains: the ENVIROFI information system provides two general sets of services: resource sharing / interoperability services, and security services. The ENVIROFI architecture handles these two domains as orthogonal. This means that modifications on the security architecture should not affect the resource sharing architecture (and vice-versa). This is actually a common requirement for security architectures, and the majority of the solutions adopted in ENVIROFI respect this assumption.

The following figure shows the ENVIROFI architecture, with seven specific-enabler areas of ENVIROFI and seven generic enabler areas of FI-WARE.

Figure 17 ENVIROFI Specific Enablers Architecture

The specific enablers are broken into six thematic groups based on the type of functionality and role they provide. The specific enabler thematic groups are as follows:

- Harvesters, connectors and mediators: collection of brokers, connectors and mediator services which support protocols and data models found in the environmental domain. This thematic class of specific enabler is there to facilitate easier interoperability between specific enabler services, encouraging agile and flexible service composition in the future internet.
- Geo-referenced data collection applications: geo-referenced observation and sample data is key in the

environmental usage area. The services in this thematic class provide ways to record and archive geo-tagged measurements for later use by other specific enablers such as fusion services. The enablers in this class are designed to support crowd sourcing of environmental measurements, recording multi-author data at a scale to exploit fully the future internet.

- Semantic tagging tools: tools and services that provide support for semantic enrichment of environmental data streams and sources. This thematic class includes environmental domain ontology support, harvester services and linked data services allowing uncertainty annotation of existing measurement resources.
- Fusion tools for heterogeneous data sources: heterogeneous environmental data fusion services operating at different semantic levels. This thematic class includes pre-processing, feature extraction, situation assessment and prediction services, preparing and aggregating environmental data into formats suitable for use by human end users and automated services such as alert services.
- Event detection and notification services: services which provide a variety of notification mechanisms compatible with the environmental geospatial standards and protocols.
- Geospatial data provisioning and storage: services related to the provisioning and storage of environmental observations and measurements. This category includes a number of existing open source environmental services that have gained traction in the environmental geospatial community.

Each specific enabler is essentially a component specification and will allow concrete software to be developed to act as a proof of concept. Although not all, the specific enablers are designed to be environmental application neutral. They offer a variety of environmental services which can be adopted and tailored for domain specific requirements.

The results of ENVIROFI project will be especially relevant for designing FOODIE architecture in terms of requirements and architectural principles and concepts (i.e., RM-ODP architecture viewpoints and enablers categories) given the fact that the environmental and geospatial domains share many commonalities with the agricultural domain, which will support the specification of Future Internet agricultural applications.

4.2.3 SMARTAGRIFOOD

SmartAgriFood⁹⁹ is also a phase 1 Future Internet Public-Private Partnership (FI-PPP) project, which investigated how Future Internet ICT (FI-ICT) could address the global challenges of the agri-food sector, identifying the underlying needs and how FI-Ware Generic Enablers (GEs) could address them by describing potential use cases scenarios in the agri-food sector. It tackled three main areas that covered the complete production chain 'from farm to fork': (i) smart farming, focusing on sensors and traceability; (ii) smart agri-logistics, focusing on real-time virtualization, connectivity and logistics intelligence; (iii) smart food awareness, focusing on transparency of data and knowledge representation. The project use case specification was developed focusing on transparency and interoperability of data and knowledge across the food supply chain, using a user-centered methodology.

Project results include:

- Use Case descriptions for smart farming, including sophisticated and robust broadband sensing and monitoring of animals and plants;
- Use Case descriptions for smart agri-logistics, including intelligent transport and real-time logistics of agri-food products;
- Use Case descriptions of smart food awareness, focusing on enabling the consumer with information concerning safety, health, environmental impact and animal welfare;
- Identification of generic requirements for generic enablers;
- Community and user organization involvement both in requirements gathering, pilot demonstration and evaluation;

⁹⁹ <http://www.smartagrifood.eu/>

- Specification of interfaces and functionalities for integration to Core Platform (FI-Ware¹⁰⁰);
- Contributions to standardization and regulatory bodies in Europe.

Most importantly, SmartAgriFood, together with Finest project¹⁰¹ that did similar work for the Transport and Logistics sector, delivered a conceptual architecture of a FI-Ware cloud-based platform and several prototypes showcasing how it could work for the different sectors (see Figure 18).

Figure 18 Conceptual architecture for Smart Farming as developed in the SmartAgriFood project

SmartAgriFood merged with Finest into the 2nd phase FI-PPP FISpace project (see below) that has recently finished, which in turn evolved into the 3rd phase project SmartAgriFood2 that is about to start this year and where PSNC partner is also involved. SmartAgriFood2 will expand FISpace functionalities by supporting SMEs and web entrepreneurs (SMWEs) to develop approximately 50 new services or Apps in the area of Smart Farming through an open call process. In particular the SmartAgriFood2 call will target applications addressing the three subsectors of arable, livestock and horticulture production.

Figure 19 shows the position of SmartAgriFood project and relations with other phases of FI-PPP program and ICT-Agri ERA-NET project (and its continuation), an FP7 project funded under the ERA-NET scheme¹⁰² for coordination actions spanning three FP7 themes: Agriculture and food supply; Environment and climate; and Information and Communication Technology. The goal of ICT-AGRI was to strengthen research in Europe in those areas and to develop a common European research agenda concerning ICT and robotics in agriculture, and to follow up with calls based on funds from the participating countries' national research programmes.

SmartAgriFood and its follow-up projects provide a good complement to FOODIE approach regarding the architecture and services developed. In FOODIE we may reuse some of these results and we will look forward to the integration and/or communication with those services.

¹⁰⁰ <http://www.fi-ware.org/>

¹⁰¹ <http://www.finest-ppp.eu/>

¹⁰² http://cordis.europa.eu/fp7/coordination/about-era_en.html

Figure 19 SmartAgriFood and related projects

4.2.4 FISpace

FISpace is a 2nd phase FI-PPP project, which was a merger of the Phase 1 projects FInest and SmartAgriFood. The objective of FISpace was to develop a FI-Ware enabled, cloud-based platform for business collaboration using multi-domain trial experiments¹⁰³. Figure 20 shows a high-level picture of the architecture of the FISpace platform. It can be considered as a more developed architecture of the cloud-based platform that was envisioned in SmartAgriFood. As indicated, it sits on top of FI-ware GEs but has two particular extensions for business collaboration: the FISpace Store and the Real-Time B2B collaboration core. These key components are embedded in several other modules to enable system integration (e.g. with IoT), to ensure Security, Privacy and Trust in business collaboration and an Operating Environment and Software Development Kit to support an ecosystem in which Apps for the FISpace store can be developed. The FISpace platform envisioned various types of front-ends (e.g. web or smartphone), but also direct M2M communication is possible. In general, the central features of the FISpace collaboration service include:

- Delivered as Software-as-a-Service (accessed anywhere at any time via any device);
- Delivered as open service that can be extended and customized (e.g., by integrating domains apps)
- A domain app store that facilitates the marketing of targeted applications;
- A collaboration manager for B2B networks supporting planning and execution of business operations from a global perspective with message-based coordination among the involved business partners;
- Integrated techniques for monitoring and tracking on the basis of data integration from the IoT, including sensor systems and smart item technologies accessible via FI-WARE generic enablers;
- Information integration from legacy and third party systems enabled through a service-based integration layer that is enabled and supported by FI-WARE generic enablers;
- Role-based views for the individual participants in the business networks along with integrated security and privacy management for fine-grained access control to confidential information;

In FISpace, eight use case trials were used to develop and test the platform including the FI-Ware GEs that are used, in real experimentation settings. Many of these trials are a follow-up of the trials in SmartAgriFood, so many of the Apps to be developed are focusing on the agri-food sector.

¹⁰³ <http://www.fispace.eu/>

Figure 20 FISpace high-level architecture

4.2.5 c@r

The concept of Future Internet is new, but some ideas of Future Internet were already elaborated, implemented and tested in the c@r project¹⁰⁴ [156].

The C@R architecture is described as:

- CCS – Collaborative Core Services implemented as reusable software;
- SCT – Software Collaboration Tools;
- OC - Orchestration Capabilities;
- LLA – Living Lab Applications cover end user interactions.

The main idea was to develop re-usable components, which could be integrated by developers into final applications. Currently, this concept is extended by more projects e.g. FI-WARE and COIN IP. FI-WARE is focused on architecture design, COIN IP on enterprise collaboration and interoperability services.¹⁰⁵

Figure 21 C@R Reference architecture

¹⁰⁴ www.c-rural.eu

¹⁰⁵ <http://www.coin-ip.eu/>

4.2.6 COIN IP

COIN IP was looking for a concept of Future Internet from the perspective of business collaboration and business interoperability. It defines three types of services:

- Enterprise Collaboration Services supporting collaborative processes in supply chains, collaborative networks or business ecosystems;
- Enterprise Interoperability Services reducing incompatibilities among enterprises;
- Service Platform as integrating services for enterprise collaboration and enterprise interoperability based on semantically-enabled Service Oriented Architectures (SSOA).

COIN IP provided a study of business models. It is working with the concept of SaaS-U (Service Utility) as specific business model. It expects that the utility paradigm will be used for offering services. The model expects that use-value and exchange-value are not identical and that in the future mainly added value services will be sold. The analysis also mentioned the possibility of domination of the market by few organisations, like in real utilities [157]. A part of the COIN IP activities was focused on Open Agriculture Services to define components and interfaces for farm management. The main idea of COIN was again to develop re-usable components, mainly supporting interoperability on the level of data, information, services and business processes.

4.3 Big data

4.3.1 BIG

The BIG Project¹⁰⁶ is an EU coordination and support action to provide a roadmap for Big Data within Europe. The work of the project is split into groups focusing on industrial sectors and technical areas. The BIG project is comprised of:

- Sectorial Forum that gathered Big Data requirements from vertical industrial sectors, including Health, Public Sector, Finance, Insurance, Telecoms, Media, Entertainment, Manufacturing, Retail, Energy, and Transport.
- Technical Working Groups that focused on Big Data technologies for each activity in the data value chain to examine the capabilities and current maturity of technologies in these areas.

Although the agriculture sector is not directly contemplated within the vertical sectors requirements analyses, the results from the analysis performed by the Technical Working groups in the Data Value Chain¹⁰⁷ - describing the state of the art in each part of the chain (i.e., data acquisition, analysis, curation, storage and usage) together with emerging technological trends for coping with Big Data - are still very valuable and applicable for FOODIE (e.g., big data solutions for storage and processing of streams of sensor data).

¹⁰⁶ <http://www.big-project.eu>

¹⁰⁷ http://big-project.eu/sites/default/files/BIG_D2_2_2.pdf

Figure 22 The BIG Project Structure and the Technical Working Group

4.3.2 Optique

Optique¹⁰⁸ is an on-going IP FP7 project that targets some of the bottlenecks limiting the exploitation of “Big Data”, characterized by massive amounts of data accumulated, in real time and over decades, and where accessing relevant parts of the data (i) requires in-depth knowledge of the domain and of the organisation of data repositories, (ii) is limited to a restricted set of predefined queries.

Optique tackle these bottlenecks by:

- Providing a semantic end-to-end connection between users and data sources
- Enabling users to formulate intuitive queries using familiar vocabularies and conceptualisations
- Integrating data spread across multiple distributed data sources
- Exploiting massive parallelism for scalability far beyond traditional RDBMSs, reducing the turnaround time for information requests to minutes rather than days.

The platform uses an ontology to capture (possibly multiple) user conceptualisations, and declarative mappings to transform user queries into complete, correct and highly optimised queries over the data sources. The architecture uses a three layer approach (see Figure 23): (i) the presentation layer consisting of four main user interfaces, which are mainly Web based; (ii) the application layer consisting of several components supporting the system machinery (e.g., query formulation, query answering, ontology and mapping management, etc.); (iii) the data and resource layer consists of the data sources that the system provides access to, that is, relational, semi-structured, temporal databases and data streams. The Optique system is integrated via the Information Workbench (IWB) platform¹⁰⁹, a generic platform for semantic data management that provides a shared triple store for managing the OBDA (Ontology Based Data Access) system assets (e.g., ontologies, mappings, etc.), generic interfaces and APIs for semantic data management (e.g. ontology processing APIs).

The work carried out in Optique is interesting in the context of FOODIE regarding the OBDA approach for management of Big Data. We will take into account the requirements identified in Optique for the design of FOODIE platform.

¹⁰⁸ <http://www.optique-project.eu/>

¹⁰⁹ <http://www.fluidops.com/information-workbench/>

Figure 23 Optique OBDA (Ontology Based Data Access) system architecture

4.3.3 StratusCloud

StratusCloud is an on-going German project implementing a Data as a Service paradigm to allow ad-hoc querying and consumption of company-relevant data sources, whether they are stored in private or public clouds. It aims at delivering a system for horizontal data integration across existing data management services. It will provide a unified API, enabling services and applications to access on-demand and to dynamically integrate data sources of different origin and with different formats. It will also enable migration and replication of data from one cloud to another.

The system will deliver the following benefits to service providers and service consumers:

- Simplified use and reuse of data sources in the enterprise and across the borders of the internal organization through a standardized API enabling the dynamic, ad-hoc integration of structured data sources with various formats
- Simplified exploration, integration, querying and reuse of data components through a central access point to all data components within a company
- Application-independent use of data sets within a company and the ability to connect to external applications based on cloud technologies via logical decoupling of data and applications
- The ability to extend applications ad-hoc supporting the integration of additional data sources or data from public sources (e.g. Linked Open Data)
- Multiple analysis scenarios based on the use of cloud technologies and cloud elasticity

The system is being built on top of FluidOps Platform¹¹⁰, which provides out-of-the box the following features:

- Semantic data management, including semantics and linked-data based integration of private and public data sources, intelligent data access and analytics (semantic search, customizable dashboards, etc.), wiki-based knowledge management with support for collaborative workflows.
- Cloud management, including workflow orchestration and automation, customizable rule engine (event processing, SMS/RSS alerting, etc.), customizable self-service portal (service catalog, service definition and distribution, metering information for billing, etc.)
- Multiple user interfaces, including semantic wiki, customizable UI specification (based on widgets), extensive pool of widgets and templates, dynamic data, visualization, forms, etc.

4.3.4 Data-and-Platform-as-a-Service (DaPaaS)¹¹¹

In the space of just a few years we have seen the transformational power of open data; both for transparency and accountability in public data, and efficiency and innovation with businesses in private data. In its first year, institutions and individuals throughout Europe have supported public sector bodies in releasing data and numerous start-ups, developers and SMEs in reusing this data for economic benefit.

However, we are still at the beginning of the open data movement, and there is still more that can be done to make open data simpler to use and to make it available to a wider audience.

The core goal of the DaPaaS project is to provide a Data- and Platform-as-a-Service environment, where 3rd parties (such as governmental organisations, SMEs, developers and larger companies) can publish and host both data sets and data-intensive applications, which can then be accessed by end-user applications in a cross-platform manner. You can find out more about DaPaaS on the detailed about page.

Essentially, DaPaaS aims to make publishing, consumption, and reuse of open data, as well as deploying open data applications, easier and cheaper for SMEs and small public bodies which otherwise may not have sufficient technical expertise, infrastructure and resources required to do so.

4.3.5 COSMODE

The research and development project COMSODE¹¹² has the following main objectives within its 24 months of duration:

- **Create a publication platform called Open Data Node** that builds on results of previous research and development in the linked data field. Its mission is to bring results from research environment into real-world for people, SMEs and other organizations to use and re-use.
- **Create a methodology framework** for easy use of technology in operating conditions of typical public bodies and rigorously tested for traceability, usability and sustainability in a public body environment. This is going to be verified in three pilot implementations during the project. End user-communities will be involved EU-wide to set a use case framework within which the requirements of heterogeneous organisations can be clearly understood. Provided feedback will be processed into the final methodology and recommendations for re-use applications.

These two results will enable new applications to emerge – some of them will be directly created in the project by consortium members (search service by SPINQUE) or by associated bodies (Semantic Web Company, Austria).

4.3.6 SemaGrow

SemaGrow¹¹³ envisages developing the scalable, efficient, and robust data services needed to take full advantage of the data-intensive and inter-disciplinary Science of 2020 and to re-shape the way that data analysis techniques are applied to the heterogeneous data cloud.

¹¹⁰ <http://www.fluidops.com/fluidops-platform/>

¹¹¹ <http://project.dapaas.eu/>

¹¹² <http://www.comsode.eu/index.php/about/>

¹¹³ <http://www.semagrow.eu/?q=home>

But most of the low-hanging fruit has been picked and it is time to move on to the next step, combining, cross-indexing and, in general, making the best out of all public data, regardless of their schema, size, and update rate; accepting that some schemas might be better suited to a given dataset and application and that there is no consensus about a "universal" schema or vocabulary for any given application, let alone for the Semantic Web and related initiatives such as the LOD cloud. In other words, we need infrastructure that besides being efficient, real-time responsive and scalable is also flexible and robust enough to allow data providers to publish in the manner and form that best suits their processes and purposes and data consumers to query in the manner and form that best suits theirs.

This will be a decisive factor in maintaining the momentum of the linked open data movement by including in the cloud large, live, constantly updated datasets and streams that are published in formats that were not designed with linking across sources in mind. This will not only increase the value of all public data, but can also provide both the incentive and the opportunity to follow Semantic Web standards and linked data best practises for publishers that will not or cannot directly and immediately make this transition.

In order to achieve this ambitious vision and solve a difficult data management problem, we must address the following key challenges:

- Develop novel algorithms and methods for querying distributed triple stores that can overcome the problems stemming from heterogeneity and from the fact that the distribution of data over nodes is not determined by the needs of better load balancing and more efficient resource discovery, but by data providers.
- Develop scalable and robust semantic indexing algorithms that can serve detailed and accurate data summaries and other data source annotations about extremely large datasets. Such annotations are crucial for distributed querying, as they support the decomposition of queries and the selection of the data sources which each query component will be directed to.
- Since it is not possible to align schemas and vocabularies so perfectly that there is no loss of information, investigate how to minimize losses and how to not accumulate them over successive schema translations.

To address these challenges, SemaGrow carries out fundamental databases research and develops methods and infrastructure that will be rigorously tested on three large-scale current use cases as well as on their projected data growth beyond project's end: they are laying the foundations for the scalable, efficient, and robust data services to take full advantage of the data-intensive and inter-disciplinary Science of 2020.

4.3.7 GeoKnow - Geospatial Data and the Semantic Web

Geospatial data or geographic information is the data that identifies a geographic location of natural or constructed features and boundaries on the Earth (e.g. oceans, buildings, countries, rivers, etc). Geographical knowledge bases are among the largest in existence and have high importance in a variety of everyday applications. The data can be mapped and often manipulated with Geographic Information Systems (GIS), however the integration of external data sets into these systems is time-consuming and complex. GeoKnow¹¹⁴ will provide the necessary tools and methods to easily integrate and process data across a wide range of data sources on the web of data.

Possibly one of the most interesting and promising outcomes of the activity surrounding the Web 2.0 evolution has been the large-scale adoption of Linked Data. Among the largest data sets are those with explicit geographic references, e.g. LinkedGeoData (2 billion triples), DBpedia (1 billion triples) and GeoNames (146 million triples). Other data sets carry implicit geographic references such as PubMed (797 million triples) or Freebase (1 billion triples). A problem GeoKnow aims to solve is the lack of rich geospatial links between the data.

4.3.8 SWITCH-ON

The project SWITCH-ON¹¹⁵ addresses water concerns to thoroughly explore and exploit the significant and currently untapped potential of open data. Water information is highly sought after by many kinds of end-users,

¹¹⁴ <http://geoknow.eu/Welcome.html>

¹¹⁵ <http://www.water-switch-on.eu/?q=node/2>

both within government and business as well as within civil society. Water touches virtually all societal and environmental domains and the knowledge domain is largely multidisciplinary. New water information and knowledge can thus lead to more efficient use of environmental services and better handling of environmental problems, including those induced by climate and environmental change. SWITCH-ON will show the benefits achieved through the whole process chain by re-purposing (re-using under different context) open data products into more dedicated and refined water products, which have high value and a broad impact on society. The vision is to improve public services, and to foster business opportunities and growth, by establishing new forms of water research and facilitating the development of new products and services based on principles of sharing. The SWITCH-ON objectives are to use open data for implementing:

- An innovative spatial information platform with open data tailored for direct water assessments.
- An entirely new form of collaborative research for water-related sciences.
- Fourteen new operational products and services dedicated to appointed end-users.
- New business and knowledge to inform individual and collective decisions in line with the Europe's smart
- Growth and environmental objectives.

While focusing on water, the project is expected to inspire a much broader environmental and societal knowledge domain and many different end-users. The SWITCH-ON project will be one trigger in a contemporary global movement to better address environmental and societal challenges through openness and collaboration.

4.3.9 MELODIES

The MELODIES¹¹⁶ project (Maximizing the Exploitation of Linked Open Data In Enterprise and Science) is about using diverse sources of Open Data to develop new applications and technologies that benefit society in a variety of ways. Huge amounts of open data are now freely available and new data sources are appearing all the time. The MELODIES project will apply the latest technologies in cloud computing and data-handling to exploit these data to their best advantage.

4.3.10 Danube Reference Data and Service Infrastructure

The Joint Research Centre of the European Commission leads the project called "The Danube Reference Data and Service Infrastructure (DRDSI). The DRDSI project is based on the EU Strategy for the Danube Region since this region covers significant part of the European Union. The DRDSI project has established four priority domains (see also European Commission – Joint Research Centre, 2013):

- **environment protection** (e.g. data on landscape and biodiversity, flood and droughts risks);
- **navigability** (e.g. data on river morphology and flood risks);
- **irrigation and agricultural development** (e.g. data on soils and crops);
- **energy production** (e.g. data on available energy resources and energy potential).

Similarly to other European activities, the DRDSI project follows the standardization developed in INSPIRE. The outputs of the project are intended to provide a global view of various data covering wide-range of areas such as water and soil quality, population, landscapes etc. for the whole Danube region.

Beside others, any relevant European project may a stakeholder included in the DRDSI project. Such networking between the FOODIE project and the DRDSI project may be twofold:

- development within the Foodie project regarding the (spatial) data may be re-used in the DRDSI project;
- (spatial) data as outputs from the DRDSI project may be re-used in the Foodie project.

¹¹⁶ <http://www.melodiesproject.eu/>

5 Data and knowledge sources

The following subsections present a list of valuable data sources (available at different administrative levels, i.e., regional, national and European level) and vocabularies that can be used to improve the information and services provided by FOODIE platform.

5.1 Open data repositories

5.1.1 European and World level

This section includes some data shared openly at European and World level that must be taken into account in FOODIE project in order to plan economic and environmental decisions.

5.1.1.1 Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO)

AGRIS

AGRIS [55] is one of the most important world-wide information systems in the area of the agricultural sciences. In order to describe AGRIS, some concepts are required:

- The CIARD Routemap to Information Nodes and Gateways (CIARD RING) is a project implemented within the Coherence in Information for Agricultural Research for Development (CIARD) initiative and led by the Global Forum on Agricultural Research (GFAR). The RING is a global directory of web-based information services and datasets for agricultural research for development (ARD). It is the principal tool created through the CIARD initiative to allow information providers to register their services and datasets in various categories and so facilitate the discovery of sources of agriculture-related information across the world [56].
- LODE-BD aims to support the selection of appropriate encoding strategies for producing meaningful Linked Open Data (LOD)-enabled bibliographical data. The LODE-BD recommendations are applicable for structured data describing bibliographic resources such as articles, monographs, theses, conference papers, presentation materials, research reports, learning objects, etc. – in print or electronic format [57].
- AGROVOC is a controlled vocabulary covering all areas of interest to the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) of the United Nations, including food, nutrition, agriculture, fisheries, forestry, and environment as it'll be described in the vocabularies section.

AGRIS uses AGROVOC as backbone to index its records and linked for external resources; aggregates information using the recommendations on metadata standards described on LODE-BD and consumes data exposed by data providers registered on the CIARD RING. To date, it hosts more than 7 million of bibliographic records. AGRIS uses Linked Open Data methodologies to link the bibliographic records with other to related datasets on the web with the objective to enrich the information provided in the AGRIS records. AGRIS interlinks with datasets like World Bank, FAO Geopolitical Ontology, Nature OpenSearch, Global Biodiversity Information Facility and Bioversity International, using AGROVOC. More than 180 million triples have been generated so far [58].

Aquastat Country Profiles

AQUASTAT collects statistics on water resources and data on water resources obtained from national sources. The aim is to describe the particularities of the country, region and river basin and the problems met in the development of the water resources and, in particular, irrigation. Irrigation trends, existing policies and legislation to water use in agriculture, possible treaties and agreements between countries as well as prospects for water management in agriculture are presented, as described in literature. The country profiles, regional and river basin overviews are based on the information available at the time they were written and will be updated every five to ten years. For the most recent reliable country data, reference is made to the AQUASTAT on-line database [59].

FAOSTAT

FAOSTAT is the FAO statistical database. It is an on-line multilingual database currently containing timeseries records from over 210 countries and territories covering agriculture, nutrition, fisheries, forestry and food aid.

FAOSTAT Agriculture provides statistics on crops, livestock, irrigation, land use, fertilizer, pesticide consumption, and agricultural machinery [60].

5.1.1.2 World Bank

The World Bank provides free and open access to a comprehensive set of data about development in countries around the globe, together with other datasets cited in the data catalogue. The data catalogue is a listing of available World Bank datasets, including databases, pre-formatted tables, reports, and other resources. The catalogue includes until twelve Agriculture & Rural Development Datasets [61].

The World Bank currently has three different APIs to provide access to different datasets: one for Indicators (or time series data), one for Projects (or data on the World Bank's operations), and one for the World Bank financial data (World Bank Finances API). All three APIs implement RESTful interfaces to allow users to perform queries of available data using selection parameters. For the Indicators API, XML and JSON representations are available; for the Projects API, Atom representation is also available; for the World Bank Finances API, XML, JSON and RDF representations are available.

5.1.1.3 International Monetary Fund (IMF)

The World Economic Outlook (WEO) database contains selected macroeconomic data series from the statistical appendix of the World Economic Outlook report, which presents the IMF staff's analysis and projections of economic developments at the global level, in major country groups and in many individual countries [62].

5.1.1.4 Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF)

The Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) is an international open data infrastructure, funded by worldwide governments. It allows anyone, anywhere to access data about all types of life on Earth. GBIF operates through a network of nodes, coordinating the biodiversity information facilities of Participant countries and organizations, collaborating with each other and the Secretariat to share skills, experiences and technical capacity. It provides a single point of access (through web services) to more than 400 million records, shared freely by hundreds of institutions worldwide, making it the biggest biodiversity database on the Internet [63].

5.1.1.5 Bioversity International

Bioversity International provides scientific evidence of the role that on-farm and wild agricultural and forest biodiversity can play in a more nutritious, resilient, productive and adaptable food and agricultural system. Bioversity International is home to 3200 unique original field report documents. You can search by species, country, collector's name or mission title, and access directly the original field records plus other information such as where that sample is housed in gene banks worldwide. Other websites and applications can use and integrate data from Bioversity's collecting database through inbuilt web services and a Google map [64].

5.1.1.6 NASA Land Processes Distributed Active Archive Center (LP DAAC)

NASA Land Processes Distributed Active Archive Center (LP DAAC) (1) provides historic data files with the measurements collected from MODIS, a spectroradiometer operated from TERRA and AQUA satellites. MODIS offers valuable data related to precision agriculture such as vegetation index, thermal anomalies and fire, land temperature or land cover characteristics [65].

5.1.1.7 Earthnet Online

Earthnet Online belongs to European Space Agency (ESA) and provides public access to data products of numerous satellite instruments among which are MODIS or CHRIS. The last one, Compact High Resolution Imaging Spectrometer (CHRIS), observes the environment with resolutions of 18m and 36m and five different viewing angles. In particular, its potential for agriculture covers monitoring vegetation growth, crop clustering, Leaf Area Index (LAI), the estimation about chlorophyll content in leaves or the automatic generation of land cover maps [66].

5.1.1.8 The National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA)

NOAA uses satellites which provide data products related with Earth surface observations and count with instruments such as the Advanced Very High Resolution Radiometer (AVHRR). In addition NOAA offers climate models for meteorological forecasting [67].

Some of the NOAA data products related to AP are the following:

- Global Vegetation Index (GVI):
- Fractional Vegetation Index (FVI)
- Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI)
- Precipitable Water Index (PWI)
- Global Vegetation Processing System (GVPS)
- Metop Global Vegetation Index (MGVI)

5.1.1.9 European Environment Agency (EEA)

European Environment Agency (EEA) supplies several data sets, indicators and maps, including related sources on agriculture [68]. The indicators are based on data sources from the EEA as well as EUROSTAT and other organizations.

Some of these data sets and indicators are:

- Emission intensity of agriculture in Europe (WREI 001) - Feb 2014, which uses the data sources:
 - National Accounts by 64 branches - aggregates at current prices (Eurostat)
 - Data on gross nutrient balance Nitrogen and Phosphorus (Eurostat)
 - Data on Economic accounts for agriculture - values at current prices
- Emissions of acidifying substances (CSI 001/APE 007) - Jan 2014, with the data sources:
 - National Emission Ceilings (NEC) Directive Inventory provided by Directorate-General for Environment (DG ENV)
 - National emissions reported to the Convention on Long-range Transboundary Air Pollution (LRTAP Convention) provided by United Nations Economic Commission for Europe (Environment and Human Settlements Division, UNECE)
- Ammonia (NH₃) emissions (APE 003) - Jan 2014, from the data sources:
 - National Emission Ceilings (NEC) Directive Inventory provided by Directorate-General for Environment (DG ENV)
 - National emissions reported to the Convention on Long-range Transboundary Air Pollution (LRTAP Convention) provided by United Nations Economic Commission for Europe (Environment and Human Settlements Division, UNECE)
- Nutrients in freshwater (CSI 020) - Oct 2012
 - Waterbase – Rivers, provided by European Environment Agency (EEA)
 - Waterbase – Lakes, provided by European Environment Agency (EEA)
 - Waterbase – Groundwater, provided by European Environment Agency (EEA)
- European Topic Centre on Biological Diversity (ETC/BD). Natura 2000 data is the European network of protected sites. It is the key instrument to protect biodiversity in the European Union. It is an ecological network of protected areas, set up to ensure the survival of Europe's most valuable species and habitats.
- EUNIS dataset (European Nature Information System). This dataset includes:
 - Data on Species, Habitat types and Sites compiled in the framework of NATURA 2000.
 - Data collected from frameworks, data sources or material published by ETC/BD.
 - Information on Species, Habitat types and Sites.
 - Specific data collected in the framework of the EEA's reporting activities (European Environment Agency).

5.1.1.10 GMES/Copernicus

Copernicus, previously known as GMES (Global Monitoring Environment and Security) is the European Programme for the establishment of a European capacity form Earth Observations. It consists of a complex set of system which collects data from multiple sources: earth observation satellites and in situ sensors [69].

The provision of Copernicus services is based on the processing of environmental data collected from Earth observation satellites and of in situ data.

The Earth observation satellites which provide the data exploited by the Copernicus services are split into two groups of missions:

- The Sentinels, which are currently being developed for the specific needs of the Copernicus Programme. The first satellite (Sentinel-1A) was launched on 3 April 2014.
- The Contributing Missions, which are operated by national, European or international organisations and already provide a wealth of data for Copernicus services. There are around 30 existing or planned Contributing Missions. They fall into the following categories: Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR), optical sensors, altimetry systems, radiometers and spectrometers.

The European Space Agency (ESA) is responsible for the space component of the Copernicus programme and coordinates the delivery of data.

Copernicus services rely on data from in situ monitoring networks (e.g. maps, ground based weather stations, ocean buoys and air quality monitoring networks) to provide robust integrated information and to calibrate and validate the data from satellites.

The in situ networks are managed by Members States and international bodies and make data available to the services by agreement. The European Environment Agency leaded work for Copernicus under the FP7 "GISC" project to catalogue the in situ requirements of the Copernicus services, develop frameworks and pilot agreements to ensure access to all the relevant data in a timely and sustainable way.

Currently, space-based data are provided by the Contributing Missions, which have been classified into five groups that reflect the characteristics of the main types of missions:

- Mission Group 1: High Resolution (HR) and Very High Resolution (VHR) SAR imaging missions with different radar bands for all whether, day/night and interferometry applications.
- Mission Group 2 and 2b: High Resolution (2) and Very High Resolution (2b) multi-spectral imaging missions.
- Mission Group 3: Medium-resolution land and ocean monitoring missions (i.e. wide-swath ocean colour and surface temperature sensors, altimeters).
- Mission Group 4: Geostationary atmospheric missions.
- Mission Group 5: Low Earth Orbit atmospheric missions.

Most data provided by the different missions are distributed by the European Space Agency (ESA). Other space-based data are provided by the French Space Agency (CNES) and the European Organisation for the Exploitation of Meteorological Satellites (EUMETSAT).

Data distributed by ESA take the form of datasets and are delivered to users through data access services. The delivery process relies on an operational system called the "Coordinated Data access System" (CDS).

Two types of datasets are available:

- Core datasets, corresponding to pre-defined large datasets covering the needs of the different users.
- Additional datasets, corresponding to on-demand datasets covering further additional or specific requirements.

Only users who have been declared "eligible" by the European Commission can have access to these datasets. These users must belong to one of the five categories below:

- FP7 Projects
- European Institutions.

- Public Authorities.
- International Organisations and Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs).
- Public.

Access to the datasets is granted according to Copernicus users' categories access rights as defined in the terms and conditions for data access.

The complete list of offered datasets is available in the Data Access Portfolio, describing as well users' categories, data licensing, contributing missions, data access mechanism and delivery timeliness. The DAP V2 is the offer for the second phase of the CSC Data Access (June 2011- May 2014), being V2.8 the last update. It offers different types of core datasets including:

- Optical Pan EU Coverages 2011/2012 Land Monitoring service: seasonal coverages of Optical pan EU HR1/2 (5.8 M Km2) (two coverages during the vegetation season separated by at least 6 weeks).
- European Monthly MR composites 2011-2012: dynamic monitoring of vegetation during the vegetation period (March to October): Monthly optimized coverage of optical MR1 full EU coverage 2011 and 2012.
- Data for atmospheric composition monitoring and forecasting of different types of substances: aerosol, sulphur. dioxide (SO₂), formaldehyde (HCHO), Carbon Monoxide (CO), Carbon Dioxide (CO₂) and Methane (CH₄).

5.1.1.11 EUROSTAT

EUROSTAT provides agriculture statistics that monitor the main objectives of the Common Agricultural Policy, the production and supply of agricultural products and income in the agricultural sector. Also it includes indicators and statistics about the protection of the environment, farming practices, food safety and security and others [70].

The agriculture database covers the next themes:

- Farm structure 2010
- Farm structure: historical data (1990-2007)
- Economic Accounts for Agriculture
- Agricultural Labour Input Statistics
- Unit value statistics for agricultural products
- Selling prices of agricultural products
- Price indices for agricultural products
- Crops products
- Poultry farming
- Area under wine-grape vine varieties by type of production, yield class and regions
- Area under wine-grape vine varieties which have been grubbed, planted or replanted
- Grape must or wine production of the area
- Basic vineyard survey
- Regional Agriculture Statistics
- Greenhouse gas emissions from agriculture
- Gross Nutrient Balance

The part of data is now available already a Linked Open Data. Linked Data is composed of three main components – observations, Data Structure Definition (DSD) and dictionaries. Each component contains a large sets of concepts coded in RDF format. These components are represented by folder with particular RDF files.¹¹⁷

5.1.1.12 U.S. Government's Open Data Portal

U.S. Government's Open Data Portal manages Federal, state and local data, including more than two hundred agricultural datasets [71]. The portal supplies many statistics, data and projections about U.S agriculture, but al-

¹¹⁷ <http://eurostat.linked-statistics.org/>

so international information as:

- International Agricultural Productivity: world total factor productivity growth indices for countries and regions. Most of the data for the analysis comes from FAOSTAT. In some cases Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) input and output data are supplemented with data from national statistical sources.
- International Baseline Data: International baseline projections indicate supply, demand, and trade for major agricultural commodities for selected countries. These projections provide foreign country detail supporting the annual USDA agricultural baseline, which are long run, 10-year projections.

5.1.1.13 Whatstheplan

The WhatsthePlan¹¹⁸ platform developed as part of Plan4business project contains a large data pool of planning data including pan-European datasets Urban Atlas, Corine Land Cover and Natura 2000; statistical information of EUROSTAT and selected countries, national datasets such as cadastral information and flood zones; and regional and local urban planning data. The platform is open for everyone and encourages users to share their data and expand the data coverage on horizontal and vertical levels.

Besides data harmonisation and integration, the platform enables various analyses based on the integrated datasets. The more spatial information is available, the better and more precise analysis results can be retrieved. The platform targets at different user groups. On the one side, there are tools for spatial data experts. The Integration Engine enables harmonisation of your urban plans into the INSPIRE Land Use schema and publish them in an interoperable way using the OGC web services. With the Map Creator you can prepare a map of your choice by making an overlay of data from the database as well of remote data connected using the OGC web services. On the other side, the platform contains a set of spatial apps which are easy to use and show the capabilities of the platform.

5.1.1.14 European Location Framework (ELF)

The goal of this project is to deliver the European Location Framework (ELF)¹¹⁹ required to provide up-to-date, authoritative, interoperable, cross-border, reference geo-information for use by the European public and private sectors. This versatile cloud-based and cascade-supporting architecture provides a platform of INSPIRE compliant geo-information, harmonised at a cross-border and pan-European level.

The three-year project is supported by a consortium of 30 partners across Europe, whose work is co-funded by the European Commission. It will foster the wider use of geo-information and enable the creation of innovative value-added services. The project's proactive stimulation of content markets involves the creation of sample applications using thematic communities to make user-led developments by SMEs (both inside and outside the consortium).

The consortium is committed to continue to provide the ELF Platform beyond the end of the project, thus enabling growth in the use and re-use of trustworthy, accurate and re-usable official reference geo-information. It therefore aims to create a sustainable framework for re-use of authoritative public sector reference geo-information at multiple levels of detail.

5.1.1.15 Open Food Facts

Open Food Facts^{120 121} is a free, open collaborative database of food facts from around the world, which aims to help consumers make better choices about what they put in their body, as well as motivating industry to take more care over the production of food.

Food is becoming an increasingly political issue. Food security has risen up the international agenda to become one of the most talked-about aspects of strategic planning for the future. From questions of who owns the patents on the seeds people need to survive, to questions of the effects of additives in your body, to understanding

¹¹⁸ www.whatstheplan.eu

¹¹⁹ <http://www.elfproject.eu/content/overview>

¹²⁰ <http://blog.okfn.org/2013/03/04/open-food-facts/>

¹²¹ <http://openfoodfacts.org/>

the impact of our consumption habits on the environment, information about food is much-needed and often difficult to come by.

5.1.2 National level

5.1.2.1 Czech Republic

Czech Office for Surveying, Mapping and Cadastre (COSMC)

COSMC, as the central authority of state administration of surveying and land register, ensures the uniform execution of land register administration in the Czech Republic, the construction and maintenance of point fields, the production and publishing of fundamental and thematic state maps and other publications, creation and management of automated surveying and land register information system and documentation of results of land surveying activity.

COSMC also coordinates land survey and land register research and coordinates an international survey and land register cooperation. COSMC directs the Land Survey Office, the surveying and cadastral inspectorates and the cadastral offices. Presently, 115 of the cadastral offices with more than 5000 employees fall under the jurisdiction of COSMC.

ISKN is a comprehensive project that includes development of a new land registration information system for restitution of ownership, compensation and new land purchases. The information system will manage this new infrastructure and become the information source on the legal status and valuation of both public and private property.

The ISKN will contain geographical data and official maps as well as survey data, property attributes, and fund documentation.¹²²

The Base Register of Territorial Identification, Addresses and Real Estates (RUIAN) is one of four core registers in the Czech Republic, which will provide up-to-date reference data to all Czech public authorities and services, and open data for re-use from July 2012. The Czech Office for Surveying, Mapping and Cadastre (COSMC) has been participating as an INSPIRE-LMO since 2005 and in charge of the RUIAN project since 2009. The RUIAN required a large restructuring of country-wide spatial data sets related to several INSPIRE themes: cadastral parcels (CP), addresses (AD), administrative units (AU), buildings and partially also the geonames, transport and protected sites. The timing and significant changes of data sets brought the COSMC into a challenging role to balance the requirements of e-Government and PSI with those of INSPIRE, and to settle them into the everyday practice of Czech public administration already in 2012 [158].

Czech Statistics Office

The Czech Statistical Office (Czech: *Český statistický úřad*) is the main organization which collects, analyses and disseminates statistical information for the benefit of the various parts of the local and national governments of the Czech Republic. It accomplishes this goal through the management of the Czech Statistical Service. Czech Statistical Office starts publishing most of census as open data, but often in proprietary formats. Now they are moving to Linked Open Data. Opening up of the election results data was one of the commitments of the Czech Republic in the OGP Action plan (Government of the Czech Republic, 2012). Czech Statistical Office was able to fulfil this commitment in time. Czech Statistical Office now provides the Data of the 2011 census as OGD as well.¹²³

5.1.2.2 Spain

In Spain, there is a national portal that organizes and manages the Catalog of Public Information, being a single point of access to data sets of the General State Administration [72]. <http://datos.gob.es> came about through an initiative promoted by the Spanish Government's Ministry of Finance and Public Administrations and the Ministry of Industry, Energy and Tourism. The Secretary of State for Telecommunications and the Information Society (SETSI), which is a part of the Ministry of Industry, Energy and Tourism, is responsible for directly managing the

¹²² <http://www.thefreelibrary.com/Czech+Office+for+Surveying,+Mapping+%26+Cadastre+Selects+Bentley.-a053086227>

¹²³ http://www.epsiplatform.eu/sites/default/files/2014-03-Open_Data_CzechRepublic2.pdf

service. Currently, eighty five data sources are available in the rural environment field [73].

In a similar way, several Regional Governments in Spain manages his own Open Data Portal, such as Xunta de Galicia [74] or Junta de Castilla y Leon [75], including Rural & Sea Environment and Meteorological source data.

Some of them include:

- Agro-meteorological stations at Galicia, Spain (MeteoGalicia) [76], which provides the data:
 - Temperature avg
 - Temperature max
 - Temperature min.
 - Relative Humidity avg.
 - Foliar Humidity (Hours)
 - Relative Humidity max.
 - Relative Humidity min.
 - Rain Temperature
 - Soil Temperature
 - Air Temperature
 - Soil Humidity
 - Hours of cold temperature
 - Sunshine hours
 - Global irradiation (daily)
 - Insolation
 - Wind Speed
 - Wind gusts
 - Wind gusts direction
 - Wind Direction
 - Rainfall
 - Hydric balance
 - Evapotranspiration of reference
 - Barometric pressure
 - Reduced pressure at sea level
 - Hours of light

- API MeteoGalicia. Weather Forecast [77]

The numeric forecast information served by the API comes directly from the outputs of the numeric forecast models executed daily by MeteoGalicia.

Specifically, the model of interest is WRF (Weather Research Forecast) with a 1 Km of resolution and 72 hours of forecast horizon.

The forecast include these data:

- Sky state: sunny, high clouds, partly clouds, overcast, cloudy, etc.
 - Temperature
 - Precipitation amount
 - Wind direction
 - Wind module
 - Relative humidity
 - Cloud area fraction
 - Air pressure at sea level
 - Snow level
- THREDDS Server. MeteoGalicia operational modelling data WRF [78]
- This model relays on The Weather Research & Forecasting Model:
- Surface level model variables: NetCDF files with surface variables from WRF model. Model WRF

runs operationally twice a day initialized at 00UTC and 12UTC, the former runs for 96 hours and the later for 84 hours. Three nested domains are configured for 36Km, 12Km and 4km resolution.

- Surface and 3D diagnostic model variables: Grib files (NCEP standard) with forecasted surface and vertical variables. Model WRF runs operationally twice a day initialized at 00UTC and 12UTC, the former runs for 96 hours and the later for 84 hours. Three nested domains are configured for 36Km, 12Km and 4km resolution.
- Model Raw/direct output: NetCDF WRF model output files with model prognostic variables. Model WRF runs operationally twice a day initialized at 00UTC and 12UTC, the former runs for 96 hours and the later for 84 hours. Three nested domains are configured for 36Km, 12Km and 4km resolution. This files files will be generally used to nest other models.

- Weather radar of Xunta Galicia [79]

The meteorological radars generate Plan Position Indicator (PPI) about rainfall. From this data product the following estimations are generated upon the raindrop size distributions and radar reflectivity, according to Marshall-Palmer's formula:

The type and intensity of the rainfall:

- Light rain: intensity lower or equal than 2 mm/h.
- Moderate: intensity greater than 2 mm/h and lower or equal than 15 mm/h.
- Heavy rain: intensity greater than 15 mm/h and lower or equal than 30 mm/h.
- Very heavy rain: intensity greater than 30 mm/h and lower or equal than 60 mm/h.
- Extreme rain: intensity greater than 60 mm/h

Also in Galicia, the Pontevedra Region Government, through the Estación de Fitopatológica do Areeiro [80], supplies Phytosanitary Warnings, Phytosanitary Advices and Meteorological information.

The Instituto Geográfico Nacional of Spain supplies aerial photos and satellite images [81] to public administrations, universities and public research organizations from satellites as Landsat 5, Landsat 7, Spot 4 and Spot 5.

5.1.2.3 Poland

Poland has launched the Central Public Information Repository (CRIP) as a tool to facilitate information access and re-use of information resources. CRIP is defined by the following government orders:

1. Regulation of Polish Ministry regarding CRIP, which deals with the technical standards of the Central Repository (standard metadata) and thus describes how the repository works, how to store and describe the information resources available (so-called metadata standard),
2. Regulation of the Minister of Administration and Digitization on information resource dedicated to sharing in the CRIP. It determines what information resources will be made available in the repository, how frequently they are updated and how they should be prepared before they are made available on the system.

CRIP allows the use of the programming interface (API), which has been made available for professional developers of applications and services. It gives the opportunity to build useful applications that make use of resources in the Central Repository. Applications must comply with the rules of the re-use of information resources and public information unit, whose metadata are stored in the CRIP.

There are several suppliers to the CRIP information resources: government bodies; appropriated funds; The Social Insurance Institution; Agricultural Social Insurance Fund; The National Health Fund; state research institutes and state legal persons.

The Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development provides data to the CRIP (in the form of newsletters, xls and pdf files) concerning prices of agri-food products. The data are collected by the officers of the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development, agricultural advisory centers, and chambers of agriculture.

The Information from the Integrated Agricultural Market Information System relate to the following markets: mutton, oilseeds, cereals, beef and veal, pork, fruit and fresh vegetables, milk, table eggs, poultry, tobacco,

hops, sugar, flowers and ecological eggs.

The Head Office of Geodesy and Cartography (GUGiK) in Poland is carrying on a development plan concerning informatization of geodetic and cartographic based on the Law on Geodesy and Cartography and the Law on spatial information infrastructure. Geodetic Administration has been committed to ensuring interoperability of collections and services, as well as cooperation in their creation and common use. Local zoning plans are developed based on geodetic data: cadastral and master maps, while topographic maps are the basis to evolve the studies of conditions and directions of spatial development of municipalities. Geodetic resources are also used to control the distribution of European funds for farmers. Geodetic data are used in air quality monitoring systems, groundwater and waterways, and to monitor soil erosion and conservation action plan.

GUGiK provides tools to combine and publish data collected at all levels of public administration via the service www.geoportal.gov.pl. The Geoportal Infrastructure for Spatial Information is the central access point based on the interactive map browser containing tools to search and analyze the data. The available and free services offer the following capabilities:

1. a search service – to search spatial data sets and services based on the content of the corresponding metadata as well as services to display the content of the metadata,
2. a viewing service to display, navigate, zoom in and out, move or overlap the visualized sets as well as display the cartographic explanations of symbols and metadata content.

Services available in the portal have been grouped in the following way:

1. the browsing service: Web Map Service (WMS), Web Map Tile Service (WMTS)
2. the search service: Catalogue Service for the Web (CSW)
3. the downloading service: Web Feature Service (WFS), Web Coverage Service (WCS), ATOM
4. the conversion service: Web Coordinate Transformation Server (WCTS)
5. the API service (iMapLiteApi): a javascript library that allows one to embed the map on the HTML page and use the feature that makes it possible to search for the location of the address based on address (or directly specify the point location on the base of the selected coordinate system) and mark it on the map as a marker along with the display text information in a balloon

The Wielkopolska Agricultural Advisory Centre (WODR) in Poznan¹²⁴ is a leader in implementing the EU Directive on integrated pest management in Poland. One of the tools to facilitate implementation of integrated pest management principles are decision support systems (SWD)¹²⁵ in plant protection, which help to determine optimal times of crop protection and thereby allow for superior effectiveness of these treatments while reducing the use of chemical plant protection to a minimum.

A network of 40 meteorological stations located in the WODR demonstration farms in Wielkopolska provides online real data to SWD. The stations collecting data about the current state of weather can be used on farms located 10 km from the device. WODR stations now cover approximately 50% of the area, and taking into account the stations from collaborating institutions, nearly 80% of the agricultural region (see Figure 1). Each station monitors the basic meteorological data: temperature, relative humidity, the amount and intensity of rainfall, atmospheric pressure, wind speed and direction, and dew point. Meteorological stations operate in an autonomous way by passing the data to the server using a cellular network.

Access to weather data from the nearest meteorological station is visible when logging on WODR along with the possibility of downloading a file with weather data.

¹²⁴ PSNC Partner participates in the works of the team to implement integrated pest management at the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development.

¹²⁵ SWD systems are associated with the obligation (introduced as of 1 January 2014) to apply the principles of integrated pest management by all professional users of plant protection products and results from the provisions of Art. 14 Directive 2009/128/EC and art. 55 of Regulation No 1107/2009/WE.

Figure 24 Network of demonstration farms in Wielkopolska (Source:WODR)

The main objectives of the practical use of meteorological stations are the following:

- to create local agro-meteorological forecasts at selected locations in the Wielkopolska region from the local meteorological stations and incorporate them in the existing system of monitoring pests (potato blight, tomato blight, rust of cereals, apple scab, etc.),
- to apply in practice the distribution system of decision support systems on farms with simultaneous verification of their quality,
- to estimate effectiveness of decision support systems by farms of various types,
- to create the agro-meteorological forecasting standard on the local scale, which may allow for wider application and use of decision support systems in agricultural practice if it involves collaboration with other entities in the future.

In 2011 WODR launched the Electronic Platform of Services (EPSU) to connect advisors with farmers. EPSU consists of the following modules:

- a customer base (9704 registered users till 2013)
- a separate section of the website that contains: electronic advice, FAQs, contact to the nearest counselor, information from the nearest meteorological station, e-mail notification about information and news from the areas indicated by the user.

In 2014, as part of EPSU, a system that allows to monitor the results of the model blight of potato and notify farmers via e-mail and SMS was launched. The system forecasts the possible plague and sets the date of the first operation. It can be used by all farmers with potato plantations located within 70 meteorological stations (see Table 2).

No.	Institution / Company	The number of stations
1	Institute of Plant Protection	5
2	The Association of Potato Planters and Producers in Luboń	10

3	Potato Industry in Piła "ZETPEZET"	6
4	Polish Agricultural Consulting Sp z oo	8
5	WODR	40
6	Other	1
Total		70

Table 2 Meteorological stations in the integrated protection of the potato (Source: Own calculations based on data WODR)

WODR plans to develop next IT systems in the areas of:

- irrigation,
- Puccinia recondita
- black cutworms in sugarbeet
- fruit and vegetable (apple scab, tomato blight)
- monitoring of wind resources in the region.

5.2 Open Linked datasets, vocabularies and ontologies

5.2.1 Agriculture domain

5.2.1.1 Agrovoc

AGROVOC is a controlled multilingual vocabulary that covers all the areas of interest of the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO)¹²⁶, including food, nutrition, agriculture, fisheries, forestry, environment etc. It is one of the main knowledge sources for FOODIE, where we plan to reuse it, and extend/complement it when necessary (also trying to reuse as much as possible existing established vocabularies/ontologies), in order to describe and annotate FOODIE data sources, as well as to upgrade or access legacy data sources as RDF graphs.

AGROVOC is published by FAO and edited by a community of experts, and currently it consists of over 32,000 concepts available in up to 20 languages: Arabic, Chinese, Czech, English, French, German, Hindi, Hungarian, Italian, Japanese, Korean, Lao, Persian, Polish, Portuguese, Russian, Slovak, Spanish, Thai, and Turkish.

The users of AGROVOC include researchers, librarians and information managers, who use it mainly for indexing, retrieving and organizing data in agricultural information systems and web pages.

AGROVOC is available as a linked data set in RDF/SKOS-XL, published with a CC3 license¹²⁷, and it is aligned with 13 other multilingual knowledge organization systems related to agriculture, including EUROVOC, GEMET, NALT, GeoNames, etc. It is possible to download AGROVOC, access its data via its Web Services, SPARQL endpoint, or browse its hierarchies via HTML pages.

Among the top concepts of AGROVOC, some of the most particularly relevant for FOODIE include: resources (agricultural resources, biological resources, feed resources, food resources, etc.), features (soil morphological features, etc.), location (production location, soil zonation, etc.), substances (feed and food additives, chemical compounds, sediment, agents, etc.), products (agricultural products, animal products, plant products, foods, etc.).

5.2.1.2 National Agricultural Library's Agricultural Thesaurus (NALT)

The National Agricultural Library's Agricultural Thesaurus (NALT) is a thesaurus and glossary of agricultural terms

¹²⁶ <http://www.fao.org/>

¹²⁷ <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/>

in English and Spanish. It is cooperatively produced by the National Agricultural Library¹²⁸, USDA¹²⁹, and the Inter-American Institute for Cooperation on Agriculture¹³⁰ as well as other Latin American agricultural institutions from the Agriculture Information and Documentation Service of the Americas (SIDALC)¹³¹.

The thesaurus is organized into 17 Subject Categories providing depth coverage of agriculture, biology and related disciplines. In particular, it contains over 98,000 terms, including more than 45,000 cross-references. It also includes a Glossary of definitions for technical terms.

The subject categories that are particularly relevant for FOODIE include Animal Science and Animal Products, Farms and Farming Systems, Food and Human Nutrition, Government, Law and Regulations, Physical and Chemical Sciences.

NALT is used mainly to organize and describe agricultural information, for indexing to improve the retrieval of information.

NALT is available as Linked Open Data, thereby enabling the specification of relationships between isolated data silos. Additionally, as mentioned in section 5.2.1.1, it is connected to AGROVOC linked dataset. The entire NALT can be downloaded in different formats, including RDF/SKOS, XML, MARC 21, PDF and DOC.

5.2.1.3 Agris

Agris¹³² is a multilingual bibliographic database for agricultural science maintained by FAO, which consists of more than 7 million records largely enhanced with AGROVOC. Agris also refers to a collaborative network of more than 150 institutions from around the world, as well as to a mash-up web application that links the bibliographic AGRIS knowledge to related resources on the Web following the Linked Open Data principles.

The AGRIS records contain rich metadata, and are largely indexed by AGROVOC. These records cover publications in the area of agriculture, forestry, animal husbandry, aquatic sciences, fisheries, human nutrition and extension. The publications vary from journal articles, monographs and chapters of books to grey literature, including unpublished scientific and technical reports, theses, dissertations and conference papers. For the majority of records, the full text is made available through the use of a Google gadget.

Agris database may be useful in FOODIE to provide complementary documentation and other bibliographic references related to methods, processes or natural resources that are interesting for their activities.

5.2.1.4 Agrontology

Agrontology¹³³ is an OWL vocabulary providing a compendium to AGROVOC. It specifies a set of domain-specific properties for enriching the description of AGROVOC concepts. Agrontology is enriched with VOAF (Vocabulary of a Friend)¹³⁴ descriptors, mainly for linking it to AGROVOC and to other datasets adopting it, such as FAO Biotech Glossary¹³⁵.

Accordingly, most of the concepts in Agrontology are object properties, such as `isUsedAs`, `hasProperty`, `hasComposition`, `influences`, `usesProcess`, etc. For instance, the description of the concept Soil in Agrovoc (term code 7156¹³⁶), includes the following statements using Agrontology vocabulary:

¹²⁸ <http://www.nal.usda.gov/>

¹²⁹ <http://www.usda.gov/>

¹³⁰ <http://www.iica.int/>

¹³¹ <http://orton.catie.ac.cr/>

¹³² <http://aims.fao.org/agris>

¹³³ <http://aims.fao.org/aos/agrontology>

¹³⁴ <http://purl.org/vocommons/voaf>

¹³⁵ <http://www.fao.org/biotech>

¹³⁶ http://aims.fao.org/aos/agrovoc/data/c_7156

```

<http://aims.fao.org/aos/agrovoc/c_7156>
  <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#type>
    <http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#Concept> ;
  <http://aims.fao.org/aos/agrontology#hasComposition>
    <http://aims.fao.org/aos/agrovoc/c_35657> ;
  <http://aims.fao.org/aos/agrontology#influences>
    <http://aims.fao.org/aos/agrovoc/c_35164>,
    <http://aims.fao.org/aos/agrovoc/c_36778>, <http://aims.fao.org/aos/agrovoc/c_24064>;
  <http://aims.fao.org/aos/agrontology#isComposedOf>
    <http://aims.fao.org/aos/agrovoc/c_4857> ;
  <http://aims.fao.org/aos/agrontology#isUsedAs>
    <http://aims.fao.org/aos/agrovoc/c_3393> ;
  <http://aims.fao.org/aos/agrontology#usesProcess>
    <http://aims.fao.org/aos/agrovoc/c_36315> ;

```

Hence, Agrontology will be also a valuable resource for FOODIE, as it includes extensive vocabulary (mostly properties), to describe concepts related to the agriculture domain, in case we would need to extend AGROVOC with some specialized concepts for FOODIE.

5.2.2 Environment domain

5.2.2.1 General Multilingual Environmental Thesaurus (GEMET)

- Developed by the European Environmental Agency (EEA)
- Founded in 1995, the building stone was *Umwelt Thesaurus* Umweltbundesamt (UBA-A), developer in Vienna, Austria. Afterwards, several other thesauri were integrated
- About 7000 environmental terms in total
- 32 languages
- INSPIRE spatial data themes

5.2.3 Geospatial domain

5.2.3.1 EMERGEL

EMERGEL¹³⁷ (EMERGENCY Elements) is an ontology designed to capture the key aspects dealing with emergency situations. Although some potentially related extreme events, such as floods, droughts, etc. are featured and they could be relevant for FOODIE, that ontology could seem at first glance out of scope for the project.

However, if we have a careful look to the vertical modules of the EMERGEL ontology we can find out that it establishes a remarkable module focusing on geographical contents.

For instance, in the case of countries and regions, several codes are used (IATA, ICAO, ENI and UIC, depending on the airborne, fluvial navigation or railway points of view). But it is from a European Union point of view where EMERGEL offers a useful model for FOODIE. Apart from the ISO 3166 codes for countries and their subdivisions at different levels, the ontology focuses also in modelling the full NUTS and LAU geocodes developed and regulated by Eurostat, the European Union's agency for statistical purposes.

The *Nomenclature des Unités Territoriales Statistiques* (NUTS) is a geocode standard for referencing the subdivisions of countries covering only member states of the EU (also the EFTA countries and the EU candidates though) in detail. For each country, Eurostat establishes a hierarchy of three NUTS levels (NUTS1, NUTS2, NUTS3) and these levels do not necessarily match the particular administrative divisions within the country.

¹³⁷<http://vocab.ctic.es/emergel/>

A NUTS code begins with a two-letter code referencing the country, which is identical to the ISO 3166-1 alpha-2 code. The first subdivision of the country is then supplied with one number and, additionally, a possible second or third subdivision level is referred to with another number each.

On the other hand, LAU (Local administrative unit) is the following level to NUTS3 (formerly they were called NUTS4 and NUTS5). LAUs are low-level administrative divisions of a country, ranked below a province, region or state and they are basic components of the NUTS regions. For each EU member country, two levels of Local Administrative Units (LAU) are defined: LAU1 and LAU2.

NUTS and LAU provides EMERGEL with the necessary granularity to easily *geolocate* under their umbrella not only emergency POIs, such as nuclear/power plants, bodies of water, natural reserves etc., but also agricultural POIs within a given European country. Being possible to query the vertical modules with inquiries like how many accessible bodies of water can be encountered in NUTS3 region X in the Czech Republic, for instance, etc.

5.2.3.2 TELEIOS ontology and linked data

FP7 TELEIOS project¹³⁸ (Virtual Observatory Infrastructure for Earth Observation Data) developed the DLR ontology¹³⁹, which captures the contents of the Virtual Earth Observatory built by the project for data obtained by the satellite TerraSAR-X of TELEIOS partner DLR.

The ontology comprises the following major parts: (i) the part that captures the hierarchical structure of a product and the XML metadata associated with it (e.g., time and area of acquisition, sensor, imaging mode, incidence angle), (ii) the part that defines the RDFS classes and properties that formalize the outputs of the knowledge discovery step (e.g., patch, feature vector), (iii) the part that defines the land cover/use classification scheme for annotating image patches. Hence, some terms from this ontology may be useful in FOODIE to describe satellite data.

In particular, the ontology is expressed in OWL and contains 145 classes and 27 properties (12 object properties and 15 data properties).

Additionally, TELEIOS project published some relevant linked geospatial data for FOODIE, including: (i) the CORINE Land Cover of Europe dataset and (ii) the Urban Atlas of Europe dataset. The first dataset includes different categories of land cover (e.g., forests, semi-natural areas) and specific characterizations (e.g., coniferous forests). The second dataset describes high-resolution land use maps for 305 Large Urban Zones and their surroundings.

5.2.3.3 Getty Thesaurus of Geographical Names (TGN)

- Geographical keywords for a given area of interest and various scales (levels of details) like habitated places, micro-regions, regions, countries, continents
- Developed since 1987, in electronic version since 2000
- <http://www.getty.edu/research/tools/vocabularies/tgn/>
- More than 1 million terms for habituated places, administrative units, infrastructure, hydrography, orography over the world.
- Mostly English and local language
- Well-developed hierarchy

5.2.3.4 GeoNet Name Server (GNS)

- Aggregated databases of the U.S. National Geospatial-Intelligence Agency and U.S. Board on Geographic Names
- World-wide thesaurus, more than 4 million terms
 - Habituated places, administrative units, infrastructure, hydrography, orography, vegetation, oceans
- Wide portfolio of tools for searching in comparison to TGN, up-to-dateness

¹³⁸ <http://www.earthobservatory.eu/>

¹³⁹ <http://www.earthobservatory.eu/ontologies/dlrOntology.owl>

- For instance also synonyms for the regions like in the Czech Republic Vysočina – Jihlavský
- <http://earth-info.nga.mil/gns/html/>

5.2.3.5 GeoWordNet

It is a data-set containing a geospatial ontology composed by three well-known data sources: **WordNet**, **GeoNames** and the Italian part of **MultiWordNet**. It is formed by geo-spatial classes (e.g. mountain), entities (e.g., Naples), their metadata (e.g. latitude and longitude coordinates) and relations between them (e.g., part-of). This knowledge is accessible via RDF file, HTML navigation, PostgreSQL dump and WordNet dict.

GeoWordNet is distributed under the terms and conditions of the license Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License [<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/>].

5.2.3.6 Core Location Vocabulary

The Location Core Vocabulary¹⁴⁰ provides a minimum set of classes and properties for describing any place in terms of its name, address or geometry. The vocabulary is specifically designed to aid the publication of data that is interoperable with EU INSPIRE Directive. It is closely integrated with the Business and Person Core Vocabularies.¹⁴¹

The Core Location Vocabulary is a simplified, reusable and extensible data model that captures the fundamental characteristics of a location, represented as an address, a geographic name, or a geometry.

E-Government Core Vocabularies are the starting point for developing interoperable e-Government systems as it allows mappings with existing data models. This guarantees Public Administrations to attain cross-border and cross-sector interoperability. Please refer to the eGovernment Core Vocabularies paper on the approach and benefits of Core Concepts for further background.¹⁴²

5.2.3.7 LinkedGeoData

LinkedGeoData is a compilation and publication of the geographical information contained in the OpenStreetMap project as an RDF knowledge base following the principles of Linked Data. It also add new relations between OpenStreetMap knowledge and other external information sources belonging to the Linking Open Data initiative, specifically with GeoNames and DBpedia.

It is licensed under the terms of the Open Database License [<http://opendatacommons.org/licenses/odbl/1.0/>] (ODbL).

5.2.3.8 OSM (OpenStreetMap)

The OpenStreetMap initiative has the aim of creating and publishing geographic open data, information like road maps, etc., to everyone.

The information sources used to build this geographic knowledge base are both public (i.e. some governments publish geographical information about their countries), contributed by volunteers or donated by private entities (i.e. *Automotive Navigation Data* (AND))

OpenStreetMaps data is structured in a topological structure. The basic data types conforming the OSM cartography are:

- Nodes: Points for a geographical location.
- Ways: it is an ordered list of nodes representing a polyline or a polygon when the line starts and ends at the same node.
- Relations: groups of nodes, ways and relations which have a common property.
- Tags: a key, value pair assigned to a node, way or relation.

¹⁴⁰ <http://philarcher.org/isa/locn-v1.00.html>

¹⁴¹ <http://www.w3.org/ns/locn.html>

¹⁴² https://joinup.ec.europa.eu/asset/core_location/description

5.2.3.9 GeoNames

GeoNames is a geographical database available for download free of charge and accessible through various web services, under a CC attribution license¹⁴³. It contains over 10 million geographical names corresponding to over 8 million unique features, including 2.8 million populated places and 5.5 million alternate names. All features are categorized into one out of nine feature classes and further subcategorized into one out of 645 feature codes. The main classes include (i) country, state, region; (ii) stream, lake; (iii) parks, areas; (iv) city, villages; (v) road, railroad; (vi) spot, building, farm; (vii) mountain, hill, rock; (viii) undersea; (ix) forest, heath. Beyond names of places in various languages, data stored include latitude, longitude, elevation, population, administrative subdivision and postal codes.

Each GeoNames feature is represented as a web resource identified by a stable URI. This URI provides access, through content negotiation, either to the HTML wiki page, or to a RDF description of the feature, using elements of the GeoNames ontology¹⁴⁴. The ontology describes the GeoNames features properties using OWL, whereas the feature classes and codes are described in the SKOS language. Moreover, GeoNames data is linked to DBpedia data and other RDF Linked Data. The GeoNames RDF data can be accessed, for instance, using a search webservice¹⁴⁵ or by downloading the RDF dump.

GeoNames is a relevant knowledge source for FOODIE regarding geographical data, and especially the GeoNames ontology will be useful for describing and annotating FOODIE datasets with geographical metadata.

5.2.3.10 Other Geospatial Ontologies

Other Geospatial ontologies on the Web that although may not be widely used as the previous ones, but can be relevant in FOODIE for describing and annotating more detailed geospatial metadata include:

- SpatialRelations ontology¹⁴⁶, published by Ordnance Survey for describing basic spatial relations, such as contains, disjoint, equals, partiallyOverlaps, touches, etc.
- NeoGeo Spatial Ontology and NeoGeo Geometry Ontology, provided by GeoVocab.org¹⁴⁷. The former describing topological relations between features, such as connects with, disconnected from, equals, overlaps, contains. The latter enables the description of geographical regions in RDF, including classes such Geometry, BoundingBox, LineString, Polygon, etc., and properties such as boundary, exterior, interior, geometry, polylingMember, etc.

5.2.3.11 W3C Semantic Sensor Network Incubator Group

This W3C groups has produced the Semantic Sensor Network Ontology¹⁴⁸, an ontology for describing sensors, observations, and related concepts. It does not describe domain concepts, time, locations, etc. these are intended to be included from other ontologies via OWL imports. The ontology terms are organized in sections, and modules. Each section has one or more modules, which in turn includes classes and properties. Key modules relevant for FOODIE for the generation of RDF data from sensors include Skeleton (FeatureOfInterest, Observation, Sensor, Sensing, etc.) and MeasuringCapability (Accuracy, DetectionLimit, Drift, Frequency, Latency, etc.).

Before building SSN, the group reviewed several ontologies and data models describing sensors and their capabilities as well as observations. As a result, the group opted to use CSIRO Sensor Ontology as the starting point for the development of the SSN ontology. The CSIRO Sensor Ontology¹⁴⁹ was created for describing particular instances, or classes, of sensors - the functional, physical and measurement aspects. It was used to encode sensors, reason, task, plan, query, do provenance etc., and to enable linking in domain specific concepts, processing concepts, services, etc. Its main classes include sensors, features, operations, results, processes (simple and composite), inputs and outputs, accuracy, resolution, abstract and physical properties, metadata links, power.

¹⁴³ http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Creative_Commons

¹⁴⁴ http://www.geonames.org/ontology/ontology_v3.1.rdf

¹⁴⁵ <http://www.geonames.org/export/geonames-search.html>

¹⁴⁶ <http://www.ordnancesurvey.co.uk/docs/ontologies/spatialrelations.owl>

¹⁴⁷ <http://geovocab.org/>

¹⁴⁸ <http://www.w3.org/2005/incubator/ssn/ssnx/ssn>

¹⁴⁹ <http://www.w3.org/2005/incubator/ssn/wiki/images/4/42/SensorOntology20090320.owl.xml>

Another relevant ontology reviewed by this group, which is more observation-centric, is the SEEK Extensible Observation Ontology (OBOE)¹⁵⁰. It is a suite of OWL-DL ontologies for modeling and representing scientific observations. The OBOE model is designed as a generic data model with a number of constructs for defining observational data. Key features of OBOE include its ability to represent a wide range of measurement types, a mechanism for specifying measurement context, and the ability to associate the type of entity (e.g., sample, organism, etc.) being measured.

This group has also produced, in collaboration with other organizations, the Meteorological sensor ontology¹⁵¹, which is part of the Agriculture Meteorology Sensor Network¹⁵² (also part of this group). The ontology defines several classes to describe more in detail sensor types, including TemperatureSensor, HumiditySensor, AtmosphericPressureSensor, RadiationSensor, PrecipitationSensor, etc.

5.2.4 Temporal

5.2.4.1 data.gov.uk Time Intervals

Intervals present a recopilation URI named calendar intervals with durations of a year, a month... to the granularity of second. The use of these interval resources enables the alignment of the time dimensions between datasets.

Intervals offers three sets of URIs representing time intervals each of them aligned with one of the following calendars:

- The UK/British calendar
- The Gregorian calendar
- The modern UK/British government business calendar

The dataset is accessible in several semantic syntaxes: RDF/XML, Turtle or N3, N-Triple and not semantic as JSON.

5.2.4.2 Time Ontology

This is an OWL ontology¹⁵³ of temporal concepts, originally designed for describing the temporal content of Web pages and the temporal properties of Web services. The ontology provides a vocabulary for expressing facts about topological relations among instants and intervals, together with information about durations, and about datetime information. The key classes include TemporalEntity (Instant, Interval), DurationDescription, DateTimeDescription, TemporalUnit and DayOfWeek.

Hence its applicability may be much more generic than its original intended use, and therefore relevant in FOODIE for annotating temporal content, such as measures, observations, etc.

5.2.4.3 Timeline Ontology

This ontology¹⁵⁴ extends Time Ontology, focussing around the notion of timeline, seen by this ontology as a way to identify a temporal backbone. It can be used to annotate sections of a signal, a video, or any temporal object. In particular, it defines the core concept TimeLine representing a backbone for addressing temporal information. Each temporal object (signal, video, performance, work, etc.) can be associated to such a timeline. Then, a number of Interval and Instant can be defined on this timeline. Other classes defined by this ontology include subclasses of Instant and Interval (from Time Ontology), such as AbstractInstant and DiscreteInterval, and subclasses of TimeInterval (e.g., ContinuousTimeLine, RelativeTimeLine). In FOODIE this ontology can be used to describe more detailed information of temporal content, than the one that can be described with Time Ontology.

¹⁵⁰ <https://semtools.ecoinformatics.org/oboe>

¹⁵¹ <http://www.w3.org/2005/Incubator/ssn/ssnx/meteo/aws>

¹⁵² http://www.w3.org/2005/Incubator/ssn/wiki/Agriculture_Meteorology_Sensor_Network

¹⁵³ <http://www.w3.org/TR/owl-time/>

¹⁵⁴ <http://motools.sourceforge.net/timeline/timeline.html>

5.2.5 Geopolitical and economics

5.2.5.1 Geopolitical Ontology

The Geopolitical Ontology¹⁵⁵, published by FAO, manages information related to (i) area types, including territories, geographic groups, economic groups, organizations and special groups; (ii) data associated to areas, including names in multiple languages, mapping of international codes (UN, ISO, FAOSTAT, AGROVOC), coordinates, currency names and codes, adjectives of nationality, statistical data (land area, agricultural land area, population, GDP); relations between territories (land borders, group membership) and historical changes.

In FOODIE, this ontology may be especially relevant to find relations between territories that may affect, for instance, the production of farmers.

5.2.5.2 STW Thesaurus for Economics

This thesaurus provides vocabulary on any economic subject, including more than 6,000 standardized subject headings and 19,000 entry terms to support individual keywords. It includes also technical terms used in law, sociology, or politics, and geographic names.

It classifies terms in 7 categories: (i) General descriptors, (ii) Business economics, (iii) Geographic names, (iv) Related subject areas, (v) Commodities, (vi) Economics, (vii) Economic sectors.

The thesaurus has been mapped to other vocabularies and thesauri, including AGROVOC and DBpedia. The whole thesaurus and its mappings (as well as individual terms descriptions) can be downloaded in multiple formats, including RDF/XML, Ntriples, Turtle. Additionally, it can be accessed via Web Services for economics terminology supporting resource lookup and query expansion in information retrieval applications, which may be particularly useful in FOODIE.

5.2.6 Lexical and other relevant sources

5.2.6.1 Wordnet

Wordnet¹⁵⁶ is a large lexical database of English. It groups nouns, verbs, adjectives and adverbs into sets of cognitive synonyms (synsets). Each of these synsets expresses a distinct concept. Synsets are interlinked via conceptual-semantic and lexical relations. Wordnet can be roughly seen as a thesaurus, as it groups words together based on their meanings. However, it is more than that because it interlinks not only word forms (strings of letters), but also specific senses of words. Thus, words that are in close proximity to one other can be semantically disambiguated. Additionally, Wordnet labels the semantic relations among words. The main relation among words is synonymy.

Wordnet includes 117 000 synsets, each including links to other synsets by means of a small number of conceptual relations, short description, and in most cases usage examples. The most frequently used relation among synsets is the super-subordinate relation (also called hyperonymy, hyponymy or ISA relation), but Meronymy (the part-whole) relation is also available between synsets.

WordNet is freely and publicly available for download. It is a relevant lexical source for FOODIE, which may be used to find synonym labels for concepts. This is particularly useful in the annotation tasks supported by existing tools such as Gate (see Section 6).

5.2.6.2 Eurovoc

EuroVoc¹⁵⁷ is a multilingual, multidisciplinary thesaurus. It covers the activities of the EU and contains terms in 23 EU languages (Bulgarian, Croatian, Czech, Danish, Dutch, English, Estonian, Finnish, French, German, Greek, Hungarian, Italian, Latvian, Lithuanian, Maltese, Polish, Portuguese, Romanian, Slovak, Slovenian, Spanish and Swedish), plus Serbian. The fields covered are sufficiently wide-ranging to include both Community and national

¹⁵⁵ <http://www.fao.org/countryprofiles/geoinfo/en/>

¹⁵⁶ <http://wordnet.princeton.edu/>

¹⁵⁷ <http://eurovoc.europa.eu/>

points of view, with a certain emphasis on parliamentary activities. These fields include: politics, international relations, European communities, law, economics, trade, agriculture, forestry and fisheries, agri-foodstuffs, etc. Hence, Eurovoc serves as the basis for the domain names used in the European Union's terminology database. However, it is also a controlled set of vocabulary that can be used outside the EU institutions, particularly by parliaments.

Eurovoc was intended to provide a coherent indexing tool for effective management of documentary resources and to enable users to carry out documentary searches using controlled vocabulary. It is available for download in SKOS/RDF and XML format.

Eurovoc is also relevant in FOODIE as it provides the terminology used by the EU about activities that can affect farmers and other stakeholders, such as trade, law, agriculture, agri-food stuff.

5.2.6.3 DBPedia and Freebase

DBPedia¹⁵⁸ is a crowd-sourced community effort to extract structured information from Wikipedia and make this information available on the Web. It provides a huge multi-domain dataset that is published following Linked Data principles with links to external datasets, and represents a backbone in the Linked Open Data (LOD) Cloud. Most datasets of the LOD have links to DBPedia dataset. Hence, it is relevant for FOODIE, as links from our published datasets to DBPedia will enable indirect connections to multiples datasets in the LOD.

The DBpedia dataset uses a large multi-domain ontology, which has been derived from Wikipedia. The English version of the DBpedia 3.9 dataset currently describes 4.0 million Things with 470 million Facts. Out of the 4 million Things, 3.22 million are classified in the ontology, including 832,000 persons, 639,000 places (including 427,000 populated places), 372,000 creative works (including 116,000 music albums, 78,000 films and 18,500 video games), 209,000 organizations (including 49,000 companies and 45,000 educational institutions), 226,000 species and 5,600 diseases. There are also localized versions of DBPedia in 119 languages.

The DBPedia ontology is a simple, cross-domain ontology, which was manually created based on the most commonly used infoboxes in Wikipedia. The ontology consists of 529 classes that form a subsumption hierarchy and are described by 2,333 different properties.

DBPedia is licensed under the terms of the CC Attribution-ShareAlike 3.0 and GNU Free Documentation. It can be downloaded in any of the 119 languages and it can be accessed via its public SPARQL endpoint.

Similarly, Freebase¹⁵⁹ is a community-curated database of well-known people, places, and things. Freebase contains data harvested from sources such as Wikipedia, ChefMoz, NNDB, FMD and MusicBrainz, as well as individually contributed data from its users. Currently it includes more than 43 million topics and more than 2.4 billion facts.

As Dpedia it has links to multiple datasets in the LOD, and is available under a CC Attribution License. It can be accessed via an open API or SPARQL endpoint, and also a database dump is available for download.

¹⁵⁸ <http://wiki.dbpedia.org/>

¹⁵⁹ <http://www.freebase.com/>

6 Existing technologies and software solutions

6.1 General Geographic Information (GI) applications, libraries and tools

6.1.1 GRASS GIS

GRASS GIS¹⁶⁰, commonly referred to as GRASS (Geographic Resources Analysis Support System), is a free and open source Geographic Information System (GIS) software suite used for geospatial data management and analysis, image processing, graphics and maps production, spatial modeling, and visualization. GRASS GIS is currently used in academic and commercial settings around the world, as well as by many governmental agencies and environmental consulting companies.

It has over 350 modules to render maps and images on monitor and paper; manipulate raster, and vector data including vector networks; process multispectral image data; and create, manage, and store spatial data. GRASS GIS offers both an intuitive graphical user interface as well as command line syntax for ease of operations.

Among the most interesting features it provides we can find:

- Raster analysis: Automatic rasterline and area to vector conversion, Buffering of line structures, Cell and profile dataquery, Colortable modifications, Conversion to vector and point data format, Correlation / covariance analysis, Expert system analysis, Map algebra (map calculator), Interpolation for missing values, Neighbourhood matrix analysis, Raster overlay with or without weight, Reclassification of cell labels, Resampling (resolution), Rescaling of cell values, Statistical cell analysis, Surface generation from vector lines.
- Vector analysis: Contour generation from raster surfaces, Conversion to raster and point data format, Reclassification of vector labels, Superpositioning of vector layers
- Point data analysis: Delaunay triangulation, Surface interpolation from spot heights, Thiessen polygons, Topographic analysis (curvature, slope, aspect), LiDAR
- Image processing: Canonical component analysis (CCA), Color composite generation, Edge detection, Frequency filtering (Fourier, convolution matrices), Fourier and inverse fourier transformation, Histogram stretching, IHS transformation to RGB, Image rectification (affine and polynomial transformations on raster and vector targets), Ortho photo rectification, Principal component analysis (PCA), Radiometric corrections (Fourier), Resampling, Resolution enhancement (with RGB/IHS), RGB to IHS transformation, Texture oriented classification (sequential maximum a posteriori classification), Shape detection, Supervised classification (training areas, maximum likelihood classification), Unsupervised classification (minimum distance clustering, maximum likelihood classification)
- DTM-Analysis: Contour generation, Cost / path analysis, Slope / aspect analysis, Surface generation from spot heights or contours
- Geocoding: Geocoding of raster and vector maps including (LiDAR) point clouds
- Map creation: Image maps, Postscript maps, HTML maps
- SQL-support: Database interfaces (DBF, SQLite, PostgreSQL, MySQL, ODBC)
- Geostatistics: Interface to "R" (a statistical analysis environment), Matlab
- Domain specific analysis algorithms: Erosion modelling, Landscape structure analysis, Solution transport, Watershed analysis, etc.

The vast variety of algorithms and analysis tools provided by GRASS GIS make it a very interesting GIS tool than can be used to perform many common operations over the datasets to be stored in FOODIE platform (e.g., data format conversion, raster classification and analysis, etc.). In addition, the possibility of using it as a command-line tool is very convenient in order to offer all those features as web services that can be used by other users/applications.

¹⁶⁰ <http://grass.osgeo.org/>

6.1.2 Geotools

GeoTools¹⁶¹ is an open source (LGPL) Java code library which provides standards compliant methods for the manipulation of geospatial data, for example to implement Geographic Information Systems (GIS). The GeoTools library data structures are based on Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) specifications, such as:

- OGC Style Layer Descriptor / Symbology Encoding data structures and rendering engine
- OGC General Feature Model including Simple Feature support
- OGC Grid Coverage representation of raster information
- OGC Filter and Common Constraint Language (CQL)
- Clients for Web Feature Service, Web Map Service and experimental support for Web Process Service
- ISO 19107 Geometry

It also offers support for using several raster (e.g., arcsde, arcgrid, geotiff, grassraster, gtopo30, image (JPEG, TIFF, GIF, PNG), imageio-ext-gdal, imagemoosaic, imagepyramid, etc.), vector (e.g., shapefile, dxf, excel, geojson, etc.) and xml (e.g., gml2, gml3, kml, etc.) formats. Additional formats can be supported through the use of plugins (e.g., postgis, wms, wfs, wps, etc.).

6.1.3 GDAL/OGR

GDAL¹⁶²/OGR¹⁶³ is an open-source translator library for raster and vectorial geospatial data formats (respectively). As a library, it presents a single abstract data model to the calling application for all supported formats. It also comes with a variety of useful commandline utilities for data translation and processing.

Due to its large support for both raster and vector formats it can be considered the Swiss Army knife in the open source GIS domain in terms of format conversion tools.

6.1.4 R (with spatial extensions)

R¹⁶⁴ is a free software programming language and software environment for statistical computing and graphics. The R language is widely used among statisticians and data miners for developing statistical software and data analysis.

R repositories contain several packages providing modules/plugins offering spatial analysis support and mapping capabilities. Among them it can be found the following:

- Handling spatial data:
 - sp package: provides utility functions, e.g. for plotting data as maps, spatial selection, as well as methods for retrieving coordinates, for subsetting, print, summary, etc.
 - rgeos package: provides an interface to topology functions for sp objects
 - rgdal package: provides bindings to GDAL/OGR library to read/write/transform raster and vector formats as well as access to projection/transformation operations from the PROJ.4 library
 - maptools package: set of tools for manipulating and reading geographic data, in particular ESRI shapefile
 - raster package: a major extension of spatial data classes to virtualise access to large rasters, permitting large objects to be analysed, and extending the analytical tools available for both raster and vector data
- Spatial analysis
 - spatial package: functions for kriging and point pattern analysis.
 - gstat package: provides a wide range of functions for univariate and multivariate geostatistics, also for larger datasets.
 - geoR and geoRglm packages contain functions for model-based geostatistics.
 - vardiac package: interactive variogram diagnostics

¹⁶¹ <http://geotools.org/>

¹⁶² <http://www.gdal.org/>

¹⁶³ <http://www.gdal.org/ogr/>

¹⁶⁴ <http://www.r-project.org/>

6.2 Geospatial databases

6.2.1 Postgresql/PostGIS

PostgreSQL¹⁶⁵ is an open-source object-relational database management system (ORDBMS) It supports a large part of the SQL standard and offers many modern features such as complex queries, foreign keys, triggers, updatable views, transactional integrity and multi-version concurrency control.

PostGIS¹⁶⁶ is a spatial database extender for PostgreSQL object-relational database. It adds support for geographic objects allowing location queries to be run in SQL. In addition to basic location awareness, PostGIS offers many features such as:

- Processing and analytic functions for both vector and raster data for splicing, dicing, morphing, reclassifying, and collecting/unioning with the power of SQL
- raster map algebra for fine-grained raster processing
- Spatial reprojection SQL callable functions for both vector and raster data
- Support for importing / exporting ESRI shapefile vector data via both commandline and GUI packaged tools and support for more formats via other 3rd-party Open Source tools
- Packaged command-line for importing raster data from many standard formats: GeoTiff, NetCDF, PNG, JPG to name a few
- Rendering and importing vector data support functions for standard textual formats such as KML,GML, GeoJSON,GeoHash and WKT using SQL
- Rendering raster data in various standard formats GeoTIFF, PNG, JPG, NetCDF, to name a few using SQL
- Seamless raster/vector SQL callable functions for extrusion of pixel values by geometric region, running stats by region, clipping rasters by a geometry, and vectorizing rasters
- 3D object support, spatial index, and functions
- Network Topology support

6.2.2 Rasdaman

Rasdaman¹⁶⁷ (raster data manager) is an Array DBMS which adds capabilities for storage and retrieval of massive multi-dimensional arrays, such as sensor, image, and statistics data. Rasdaman has no limitation in the number of dimensions - it can serve, for example, 1-D measurement data, 2-D satellite imagery, 3-D x/y/t image time series and x/y/z exploration data, 4-D ocean and climate data, and even beyond spatio-temporal dimensions.

Rasdaman enables Web-based geo data offerings and Big Data Analytics on multi-dimensional raster ("array") data of unlimited size:

- fast: parallel access to Exa-scale archives and Terabyte objects in fractions of a second.
- scalable: seamlessly from laptop to high-parallel, high-availability clouds and server farms.
- flexible: "Array SQL" for navigation, extraction, processing, and ad-hoc analysis.
- open standards as issued by OGC: WMS, WCS, WCS-T, WCPs; rasdaman is WCS Core Reference Implementation.

6.2.3 SQLite¹⁶⁸/Spatialite¹⁶⁹

Spatialite is a spatial extension to SQLite, providing vector geodatabase functionality. It is similar to PostGIS, Oracle Spatial, and SQL Server with spatial extensions, although SQLite/Spatialite aren't based on client-server architecture: they adopt a simpler personal architecture. i.e., the whole SQL engine is directly embedded within the application itself: a complete database simply is an ordinary file which can be freely copied (or even deleted) and transferred from one computer/OS to a different one without any special precaution.

¹⁶⁵ <http://www.postgresql.org>

¹⁶⁶ <http://postgis.refractor.net>

¹⁶⁷ <http://www.rasdaman.com/>

¹⁶⁸ <http://www.sqlite.org/>

¹⁶⁹ <https://www.gaia-gis.it/fossil/libspatialite/index>

Spatialite supports several open standards from the OGC and has been listed as a reference implementation for the proposed GeoPackage standard¹⁷⁰.

6.3 Image processing and data fusion algorithms

6.3.1 Remote sensing applications and software

This section includes existing solutions for remote sensing research area. In the following table, a comparison is applied on these solutions with regards to their some specific features as follows.

Product Name	Open Source	Web Service	Application Type	Language	Support		Platform	Notes
					User	Developer		
PANCROMA	✗	✗	Desktop		✓	✗	Windows	
MicroMSI	✓	✗	Desktop		✓		Windows	Active development ceased a few years ago. Link at NGA is currently dead
Chips	✓	✗ (See notes)	Desktop	C	✓	✓	Windows	Does not directly support web services, but can be used by scripts. Example scripts: http://www.geogr.ku.dk/chips/zip/csl.zip
HighView	✗	✗	Dos / Desktop				Windows	
HyberCube	✓	✗	Desktop	C++	✓	✓	Windows Mac OS/X	
Open Dragon	✓	✓	Desktop	C C++ Java	✓	✓	Windows Mac OS/X Linux	Uses an innovative client-server architecture and is based on platform-independent industry standards including Java, XML and HTML.
OpenEV	✓	✓	Software Library	C Python			Windows Linux	Python scripts allow the use as web service
Optics	✓	✓	Desktop	C Python	✓	✓	Windows Solaris Linux	Can be used in web services through Python scripting extensions
OSSIM	✓	✗ (See notes)	Dos Desktop	C++	✓	✓	Windows Linux	Command-Line Apps may allow use in web services
REGEEMY	✓	✓	Desktop Web	C++	✗	✗	Windows Solaris Linux	Web demo and other web examples (http://regima.dpi.inpe.br/demo/examples.shtml) presents the source package can be used for web services
SamplePoint	✓	✗	Desktop		✓	✗	Windows	
Windisp	✓	✗ (See notes)	Desktop				Windows	Allows programming with DLL. subroutines in DLLs can

¹⁷⁰ <http://www.opengeospatial.org/standards/geopackage>

								be used in web services
MultiSpec	✓		Desktop	See notes	✓	✗	Windows Mac OS/X	

Table 3 Software tools/libraries for satellite image processing

6.3.1.1 PANCROMA

PANCROMA¹⁷¹ is a powerful software application for improving images and extracting information from Landsat, SPOT®, Digital Globe®, GeoEye®, Formosat®, IKONOS®, EO-1 ALI and ASTER satellite multispectral bands. For example it can create colour RGB images and colour pan sharpened images from such data. The program can pan sharpen any file set where the panchromatic band has 2X, 3X, 4X or 6X the resolution of the multispectral bands and that is in a file format that PANCROMATM can read. The program is designed to complement archives such as the free USGS GLOVIS and Earth Explorer Landsat databases and the free Canadian GeoBase archive of SPOT® data.

Free Landsat data is available from other sources as well, and PANCROMATM can handle most of the formats that you will encounter. PANCROMATM is also recognized for its powerful Landsat gap filling capabilities, multi-spectral analysis and image deconvolution.

PANCROMATM uses a technique called pan sharpening to produce a high-resolution colour image from three or four low-resolution multispectral bands plus a high-resolution panchromatic band:

Low Res Colour Bands + High Res Grayscale Band = Hi Res Colour Image

Pan sharpening transforms the high-resolution grayscale band into a high-resolution colour image, doubling or quadrupling the resolution of the colour information in the data set.

6.3.1.2 MicroMSI

MicroMSI¹⁷² for Windows is a remote sensing imagery analysis program designed for use in introductory courses in remote sensing, developed by the National Geospatial-Intelligence Agency. MicroMSI for Windows is a public domain program and can be freely redistributed for non-commercial purposes.

6.3.1.3 Copenhagen Image Processing System (Chips)

Chips¹⁷³ is no longer being supported. Chips for Windows is now freeware product that includes: a standard license, that gives access to all general-purpose image processing capabilities of Chips.

General purpose image processing with Chips for Windows:

- Multiple RGB/pseudocolor image views with both vector and raster overlays (ESRI shapes)
- Vector editing and digitizing
- Image rectification
- Image classification
- Image statistics and visualization of statistics
- Image arithmetic, filtering, profiles, semi-variograms, principal components, scattergram and interpolation
- 3D image visualization
- Built-in scripting language

6.3.1.4 HighView

HighView¹⁷⁴ is based on the state-of-the-art and industry-leading image fusion / pan-sharpening algorithms that were developed by GeoSage in the early 2000s and have been extensively tested with a wide range of imagery

¹⁷¹ <http://www.pancroma.com/>

¹⁷² <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/MicroMSI>

¹⁷³ <http://www.geogr.ku.dk/chips/>

¹⁷⁴ <http://www.geosage.com/highview/download.html>

sources since then. HighView is a unique and highly efficient image fusion tool for both advanced image pan-sharpening and adaptive image stretching.

6.3.1.5 HyperCube

HyperCube¹⁷⁵ is a Macintosh and Windows application program created by ERDC's Topographic Engineering Center (TEC) that analyses and displays multi- and hyper-spectral imagery. This includes the static and dynamic display of the image cube and the generation of spectral classifications using both imagery and spectral libraries.

HyperCube is easy to install and set up. With state-of-the-art functionality, HyperCube can filter, warp, mosaic, reformat, calibrate, combine, photogrammetrically project and perform arithmetic on imagery and data.

Other features include¹⁷⁶:

- Image Loading: Intrinsic and general file types, SRF, TARGA, ERDAS Imagine, ESRI Shape, HDF, JPEG, LASF/ASCII LIDAR, NITF, PNG, TIFF
- Image Operations and Conversions: Zoom, grey and colour mapping, data mapping, flips, rotations, filtering, components to colour, indexed to colour, grey scale/colour tables, replace colour, image to mask, histogram equalization
- Image and Multiband Functions: Statistical measures, histograms, pixel exclusion, scatter plot, image arithmetic, mosaic points and references, warp, plot scaling, band and annotation list, band scrolling, flicker/superimpose, constructing/modifying a cube, colour composite, spectral plots, selection point colours
- Spectral Libraries and Classifications: Format, plotting and superimposing signatures; general and specific algorithms; classify function and options; image product; F(Signatures); ROC curves; attach class map; class map editor; spectral calibration
- Utilities and Applications: Wrap JPEG in NITF; GeoTIFF and JPEG to NITF; Buckeye files to NITF; library; cube ASCII file conversions; concatenate images, cubes and files; apply transformation; merge LAS files; ASCII LIDAR to LASF; shaded relief; contour; stereo mate and compilation; perspective; radiance; lens distortion; point cloud traversal.

6.3.1.6 Open Dragon

The goal of the OpenDragon¹⁷⁷ Project is to provide high-quality, commercial-grade, free remote sensing image processing software to schools and universities.

OpenDragon provides:

- Intuitive, easy-to-use desktop image processing for the study for remote sensing techniques and applications
- Access to optimized source code for the study of image processing software development techniques
- A test bed for students and researchers to explore novel image processing methods.

6.3.1.7 OpenEV

OpenEV¹⁷⁸ is used by private companies, universities, governments and non-profit organizations around the world. OpenEV is both:

- An application for displaying and analysing geospatial data
- A developer library from creating new applications

OpenEV is released under the GNU LGPL license Open Source license. It is available for Windows, Linux, Sun Solaris, and SGI Irix operating systems.

¹⁷⁵ <http://www.erd.usace.army.mil/Media/FactSheets/FactSheetArticleView/tabid/9254/Article/6320/hypercube.aspx>

¹⁷⁶ Manual: <http://www.erd.usace.army.mil/Portals/55/docs/CEERD-TV/HyperCube/HyperCube.pdf>

¹⁷⁷ <http://open-dragon.org/>

¹⁷⁸ <http://openev.sourceforge.net/index.php>

Features:

- Run on popular platforms (Linux, Windows, Solaris, IRIX).
- Handle raster and vector data.
- Support 2D and 3D display.
- Gracefully handle very large (gigabyte) raster datasets.
- Support multi-channel, and complex raster datasets.
- Understand and interpret georeferencing information, and provide on-the-fly reprojection of datasets.
- Provide view manipulation functions (pan, zoom, rotate) at interactive frame rates.
- Provide a powerful image analysis tool.
- Serve as a component in a variety of image analysis applications.

6.3.1.8 Opticks

Opticks¹⁷⁹ ¹⁸⁰ is an expandable remote sensing and imagery analysis software platform that is free and open source.

Features:

- Free and open source
- Supports the following file formats: NITF 2.0/2.1, GeoTIFF, ENVI, ASPAM/PAR, CGM, DTED, Generic RAW, ESRI Shapefile, HDF5, AVI, MPEG, JPEG, GIF, PNG, BMP
- Zoom, pan, rotate spatially large datasets
- Quickly layer GIS features, annotations, results, and other information over your data to provide context
- Many image display controls such as colour map, histogram, transparency, etc.
- Support for datasets larger than four gigabytes
- Analysts can quickly combine steps using graphical wizards
- Support for processing data in its native interleave of BIP, BSQ or BIL

6.3.1.9 OSSIM

OSSIM¹⁸¹ is a powerful suite of geospatial libraries and applications used to process imagery, maps, terrain, and vector data. The software has been under active development since 1996 and is deployed across a number of private, federal and civilian agencies. OSSIM is an open source project. The software is released under LGPL.

Key Features:

- Precision terrain correction and ortho-rectification
- Advanced mosaicking, compositing, and fusion
- Histogram matching and tonal balancing
- Rigorous sensor modelling
- Parameter based image chains
- Native file access to more than 100 raster and vector formats
- Over 4000 projections and datums
- GDAL/OGR Integration

6.3.1.10 REGEEMY

The main goal of REGEEMY¹⁸² work is to bring developed registration methods into one automatic image registration system and make them work operationally.

The developed registration system is a full-featured application intended for operational use by beginners as well as by advanced users. Registration may be achieved by one simple click or may be controlled by several pa-

¹⁷⁹ Extension: <http://opticks.org/confluence/display/opticksExt/All+Opticks+Extensions>

¹⁸⁰ <http://opticks.org/confluence/display/opticks/Welcome+To+Opticks>

¹⁸¹ <http://trac.osgeo.org/ossim/>

¹⁸² <http://regima.dpi.inpe.br/>

rameters. The system contains toolboxes that increase the registration strength using user knowledge.

Three different algorithms¹⁸³ for control point extraction are implemented in the system and other methods can be easily added. One of the algorithms uses optical flow ideas to extract the features in both images. The second method uses spectral information of the images and their local wavelet transform modulus maxima to extract a set of control points. The last one uses centres of gravity of the closed contours and other strong edges as control points.

6.3.1.11 SamplePoint

SamplePoint^{184 185} is a manual image-analysis program designed to facilitate vegetation cover measurements from nadir digital images of any scale. Operating essentially as a digital point frame, the software loads images, places classification points on the image, and stores classification data to a database as the user classes each point.

6.3.1.12 TerraLOOK

TerraLOOK¹⁸⁶ major capabilities include:

- Image find, roam, and zoom
- Image annotation (adding text, arrows, etcetera)
- Image enhancement
- View, edit, and create vector files
- Distance and area measurement
- Image mosaicking
- Multi-lingual support (currently English, Spanish and French)
- Image comparison using 'flicker'
- Multi-band dataset support (many formats)
- Classification
- 3-D viewing capability

6.3.1.13 Windisp

Windisp¹⁸⁷ is a public domain, easy to use software package for the display and analysis of satellite images, maps and associated databases, with an emphasis on early warning for food security. WinDisp was originally developed for the FAO Global Information and Early Warning System. It allows users to:

- Display and analyse satellite images
- Compare two images and analyse trends in a time-series of images
- Extract and graph trends from a number of satellite images such as during the growing season for comparison with other years
- Compute new images from a series of images
- Display tabular data in map format
- Build custom products combining images, maps and specialised legends
- Write and execute batch files to automate routine and tedious tasks
- Build a customized project interface for providing users with detailed menus of available data for a country or a specific area

6.3.2 GIS programs that include significant remote sensing analysis capabilities

There are some GIS (often freeware) programs that include remote sensing capabilities:

¹⁸³ Examples: <http://regima.dpi.inpe.br/examples.html>

¹⁸⁴ <http://www.samplepoint.org/>

¹⁸⁵ Tutorial: <http://www.samplepoint.org/SamplePointTutorial.pdf>

¹⁸⁶ <http://terralook.sourceforge.net/>

¹⁸⁷ <http://www.fao.org/giews/english/windisp/windisp.htm>

Product	Open Source	Web Service	RS	OGC	Application Type	Language	Support		Platform
							User	Dev.	
GRASS GIS	✓	✓	✓	✓	Desktop	C C++ Python	✓	✓	Windows Mac OS/X Linux
QGIS	✓	✓	✓	✓	Desktop	C++ Python	✓	✓	Windows Unix Linux
ILWIS	✓	✓	✓	✓	Desktop	C++	✓	✗	Windows Mac OS/X Linux
MICRODEM	✓	✓		✗	Desktop	Delphi	✗	✗	Windows
SPRING	✓	✓	✓	✓	Desktop Web	Java	✓	✗	Windows Linux
SAGA GIS	✓		✗	✗	Desktop	C++	✓	✓	Windows Linux FreeBSD

Table 4 GIS programs that include significant remote sensing analysis capabilities

6.3.2.1 GRASS GIS

See section 6.3.2.1.

6.3.2.2 QGIS

QGIS¹⁸⁸ is a user friendly Open Source Geographic Information System (GIS) licensed under the GNU General Public License. QGIS is an official project of the Open Source Geospatial Foundation (OSGeo). It runs on Linux, Unix, Mac OSX, Windows and Android and supports numerous vector, raster, and database formats and functionalities.

The Semi-Automatic Classification Plugin is a free plugin for QGIS that allows for the semi-automatic supervised classification of remote sensing images, providing tools to expedite the creation of ROIs, the pre-processing phases (image clipping, Landsat conversion to reflectance), the classification process, and the post processing phases (accuracy assessment, land cover change).

Example¹⁸⁹: estimation of land surface temperature with Landsat thermal infrared band: a tutorial using the semi-automatic classification plugin for QGIS.

6.3.2.3 ILWIS

ILWIS¹⁹⁰ (and the open-source software version called ILWISOpen¹⁹¹) key features are:

- Integrated raster and vector design
- Import and export of widely used data formats
- On-screen and tablet digitizing
- Comprehensive set of image processing tools

¹⁸⁸ <http://qgis.org/en/site/about/index.html>

¹⁸⁹ <http://fromgistors.blogspot.com.es/search/label/Tutorial>

¹⁹⁰ [http://www.itc.nl/Pub/research_programme/Research_output/ILWIS - Remote Sensing and GIS software.html](http://www.itc.nl/Pub/research_programme/Research_output/ILWIS_-_Remote_Sensing_and_GIS_software.html)

¹⁹¹ <http://52north.org/downloads/ilwis>

- Orthophoto, image georeferencing, transformation and mosaicking
- Advanced modelling and spatial data analysis
- 3D visualization with interactive editing for optimal view findings
- Rich projection and coordinate system library
- Geo-statistical analyses, with Kriging for improved interpolation
- Production and visualization of stereo image pairs
- Spatial Multiple Criteria Evaluation
- Set of operations on DEMs/DTMs and hydrological processing
- As per 1 July 2007, ILWIS software is freely available ('as-is' and free of charge) as open source software (binaries and source code) under the 52°North initiative (GPL license).

6.3.2.4 MICRODEM

MICRODEM¹⁹² features are:

- Contrast enhancement
- Filters
- Band histograms
- Correlation (covariance) matrix
- Scattergrams
- Band ratios and normalized indices (e.g. NDVI)
- Principal components analysis
- Multi-band merges
- Image training and classification
- Hyperspectral image analysis (AVIRIS)
- Image averaging
- Pan-sharpening

6.3.2.5 Spring

SPRING¹⁹³ is a state-of-the-art GIS and remote sensing image processing system with an object-oriented data model which provides for the integration of raster and vector data representations in a single environment.

Features:

- LANDSAT, SPOT, ERS-1 and NOAA/AVHRR Data input;
- Registration and Geometric Correction;
- Image Mosaic with grey level equalization;
- Image Enhancement by Histogram Manipulation;
- Spatial Filtering;
- IHS and Principal Components Transformations;
- Arithmetical Operations;
- Pixel Values Reading;
- Maximum-likelihood pixel-based classifier;
- Image Segmentation and Region Classifiers (Supervised and Unsupervised);
- LANDSAT and SPOT Images Restoration;
- Morphological Filters for Images;
- Mixture Models;
- Markov-based Techniques for Image Post-Classification;
- Radar Image Processing.

¹⁹² <http://www.usna.edu/Users/oceano/pguth/website/microdem/microdem.htm>

¹⁹³ <http://www.dpi.inpe.br/spring/english/index.html>

6.3.2.6 SAGA GIS

SAGA (System for Automated Geoscientific Analyses)¹⁹⁴ is a Free and Open Source Software (FOSS) Geographic Information System (GIS) software with immense capabilities for geodata processing and analysis. SAGA is programmed in the object oriented C++ language and supports the implementation of new functions with a very effective Application Programming Interface (API). Functions are organised as modules in framework independent Module Libraries and can be accessed via SAGA's Graphical User Interface (GUI) or various scripting environments (shell scripts, Python, R, etc.).

Features:

- Modular structure allows framework independent function development
- SAGA API with immense support for geodata handling
- GUI for intuitive data management, analysis and visualization
- Runs on Linux as well as on Windows operating systems
- Portable software running without installation even from memory sticks (MSW)
- Scripting via command line, Python, Java, R
- Far more than 450 freely available functions for geodata analysis
- Georeferencing and cartographic projections
- Grid interpolation of scattered point data, triangulation, IDW, splines
- Vector tools: clipping, buffer zones, raster to vector conversion
- Image analysis: filters, supervised classification, PCA, FFT, OBIA
- Geostatistics: GWR, variograms, ordinary & universal Kriging
- Terrain analysis: morphometry, hydrology, illumination, classification

6.3.3 Control and monitoring of the state of crops using multispectral imagery

The concept of precision farming or Precision Agriculture is a farming management concept based on observing, measuring and responding to inter and intra-field variability in crops. Information about the state of crops can be acquired by:

- a. sampling (weighing biomass, measuring leaf chlorophyll content,...)
- b. remote sensing measuring parameters like temperature (air/soil), humidity (air/soil/leaf), wind,
- c. proxy-detection using in-vehicle sensors measure leaf status
- d. aerial or satellite remote sensing where multispectral imagery is acquired and processed to derive maps of crop biophysical parameters.

6.3.3.1 Vegetation indices

Photosynthesis occurs in specialized chlorophyll-containing plant cells called chloroplasts. These cells are most abundant in plant leaves. During photosynthesis, they absorb blue and red light and reflect green light so chlorophyll-containing leaves appear green in color. If the number of chloroplasts should change, the amount of red radiation that the plant absorbs decreases. As plants die, they began to brown and the amount of red radiation that they reflect increases.

Photosynthetically-active plant leaves also strongly reflect radiation between 700 and 1000 nm in the near infrared or NIR portion of the spectrum. If plants are stressed, the amount of NIR that plants reflect decreases.

Therefore, red radiation and NIR can be used as an indicator of plant stress. Following this reasoning the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) was created.

The normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI). It is an index of plant "greenness" or photosynthetic activity [15], [16], [17], [18]. This is one of the main indices used in imagery analysis because of its simplicity; however it has several limitations such as its sensitivity to perturbing factors like atmospheric effects, clouds, soil effects or anisotropy variations.

¹⁹⁴ <http://www.saga-gis.org/>

$$NDVI = \frac{(NIR - VIS)}{(NIR + VIS)}$$

A number of derivatives and alternatives to NDVI have been proposed in the scientific literature to overcome these limitations:

- The Enhanced Vegetation Index (EVI). It was developed to optimize the vegetation signal with improved sensitivity in high biomass regions. EVI was proposed by MODIS Land Discipline Group [37].
- Soil-Adjusted Vegetation Index (SAVI). The soil-adjusted vegetation index was developed as a modification of the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index to correct for the influence of soil brightness when vegetative cover is low. [19], [20], [21].
- Soil-Adjusted Total Vegetation Index (SATVI). It is a modification of several earlier vegetation indices that correlates with the amount of green and senescent vegetation present on the ground [22], [23], [24].
- The Modified Soil-Adjusted Vegetation Index (MSAVI). MSAVI and its later revision, MSAVI2, are soil adjusted vegetation indices that seek to address some of the limitation of NDVI when applied to areas with a high degree of exposed soil surface [25], [26], [27], [28].
- Atmospherically Resistant Vegetation Index (ARVI). This index was defined to overcome the atmospheric effect on the red channel, using a difference in the radiance between the blue and the red channels. ARVI can be used with information coming from a MODIS, LANDSAT TM and EOS-HIRIS sensors [12].
- Global Environment Monitoring Index (GEMI). GEMI is another index created to address perturbations in the atmosphere that could alter the NDVI index [13].
- The Normalized Burn Ratio (NBR). The NBR was defined to highlight areas that have burned and to index the severity of a burn using Landsat TM imagery.
- Fraction of Absorbed Photosynthetically Active Radiation (FAPAR). FAPAR describes the spectral range (wave band) of solar radiation from 400 to 700 nanometers that photosynthetic organisms are able to use in the process of photosynthesis. It can be used as an indicator of the state and evolution of the vegetation cover, replacing the NDVI [14].

These indices can be combined and analysed to extract information about the state of crops.

Figure 25 Variations of crop health within the fields, using QuickBird data

6.3.3.2 Digital aerial imagery and Satellite imagery

The main sources in order to extract vegetation indices and perform crop state analysis are landscape images obtained either from digital aerial imagery or satellite imagery.

Both digital aerial imagery and satellite imagery have greatly benefited from technology improvements in the last decade. Without going into detail of specific sensors, the main parameters that must take into account when making a choice between satellite and aerial imagery are the following:

<p>Resolution of Aerial Imagery:</p> <p>From 90cms to 2.5 cm</p>	<p>Resolution of Satellite Imagery:</p> <p>50cms</p>
<p>Data type of Aerial Imagery:</p> <p>Most aerial cameras offer a fourth near-infrared band + R,G,B bands</p>	<p>Data type of Satellite Imagery:</p> <p>Additional optical bands designed for specific applications (vegetation analysis)</p>
<p>Stereo mapping of Aerial Imagery:</p> <p>Normal aerial surveys will be captured with full stereo mapping capability (60-80% forward overlap between images), and 30% side overlap between runs. This enables a wide range of value-added products to be generated to a high degree of accuracy including Digital Elevation Models (DEMs), Digital Surface Models (DSMs), contours, orthophotos and 3D GIS feature data capture.</p>	<p>Stereo mapping of Satellite Imagery:</p> <p>Stereo imagery is usually not included in satellite image capture.</p>
<p>Weather conditions of Aerial Imagery:</p> <p>Flexibility to plan acquisition according to weather conditions and cloud-free conditions.</p>	<p>Weather conditions of Satellite Imagery:</p> <p>Most satellite providers do not guarantee completely cloud-free imagery .An image is considered valid if cloud cover is less than 10-15%. Cloud free coverage, especially in the tropics, can be very difficult to obtain. Corrections also have to be applied to remove atmospheric effects and haze.</p>
<p>Location accuracy of Aerial Imagery:</p> <p>A typical horizontal accuracy of two pixels can be expected for aerial imagery.</p>	<p>Location accuracy of Satellite Imagery:</p> <p>High resolution satellites location accuracy is usually around 10m to 20m without ground control points</p>
<p>Other considerations of Aerial Imagery:</p> <p>The reach of an aerial acquisition company is usually restricted to a specific area or country due to the fact that aircraft are based in a specific location.</p> <p>The cost of an aerial acquisition survey is not simple as it depends on many variables such as mobilisation cost, resolution, accuracy.</p>	<p>Other considerations of Satellite Imagery:</p> <p>Possibility to acquire data virtually anywhere on the planet without considering border and logistical restrictions.</p> <p>Satellite acquisition costs are usually more straightforward to calculate than aerial imagery costs. (Pricing can directly be found on many satellite data providers' websites.)</p>

Table 5 Typical parameters contained in satellite and aerial imagery

Spatial resolution is an important parameter of the satellite data for the estimation of crop area. Resolution is defined as the ability of the sensor to record smallest details on the ground, which is represented as pixel on the satellite images. For example, if NASA'S MODIS satellite imagery is used to identify crop condition throughout the growing season, it must be taken into account that these images have a spatial resolution of 250m. So each pixel measures 250 sq. meters or 6.25 hectares.

Also, acquisition dates or time of the satellite data are very important for the final crop area estimation by removing the impact of other crops.

Finally, the characteristics of the images can vary depending on the features of the imagers installed on the plane or satellite. The following table describes the characteristics of some of the most used spacecraft-based imagers:

Spacecraft-Based Imagers
Multispectral (MS) and Panchromatic (PAN)
QuickBird (MS, 2.4-m) and (PAN, 0.6-m)
IKONOS MS (4-m) and PAN (1-m)
OrbView 3 MS (4-m) and PAN (1-m)
SPOT 5 MS (10-m) and PAN (5-m or 2.5-m possible from 2 images)
SPOT 4 MS (20-m) and PAN (10-m)
SPOT 1,2,3 MS (20-m) and PAN (10-m)
Indian Remote Sensing System (IRS) MS (23.5-m) and PAN (5-m)
Landsat 8 Operational Land Imager (OLI) PAN (15-m), MS(30-m) THERMAL (100-m)
Landsat 7 Enhanced Thematic Mapper Plus (ETM+, 30-m) and PAN (15-m): Scan Line Correction (SLC) System Broke in May 2003
Landsat 5 Thematic Mapper (TM, 30-m)
Terra ASTER MS (30-m)
DMC MS (31.5-m)
Terra & Aqua MODIS RL NIR (250-m) 36 spectral bands ranging in wavelength from 0.4 μm to 14.4 μm and at varying spatial resolutions (2 bands at 250 m, 5 bands at 500 m and 29 bands at 1 km)

Table 6 Spacecraft-Based Imagers

6.3.3.3 Image acquisition and processing for remote sensing

Image data acquired by airborne and satellites are affected by systematic sensor and platform-induced geometry errors, which introduce terrain distortions when the sensor is not pointing directly at the Nadir location of the sensor (the point on the ground vertically beneath the perspective center of the camera lens).

Some pre-processing operations should be performed in order to get better results prior to image classification.

Imagery mosaicking

The purpose is merging images taken from the same scene at varying times from varying but related view-points and-or by different sensors. Many different techniques are proposed to perform imagery mosaicking. [38] [39] [40] [41] [42].

Figure 26 Imagery mosaicking example

Georeference an image (georectify) and orthorectification

In order to accurately remove the image distortions, a digital elevation model (DEM) is used to perform image orthorectification. The required DEM is generated by feature extraction from high resolution stereo satellite imagery. When DEM is not available, geometric corrections with Ground Control Points becomes an alternative to the orthorectification. This assumes that it is a flat surface.

Georectification means that you must take an image that has not been adjusted to be in a known coordinate system, and put it into a known coordinate system. Usually this means taking an image that is in its original geometry, and putting it into a map projection. There are different ways to do this. The most common way is to identify a set of points in the image for which the latitude and longitude or map coordinates are known, and use them to warp the image into a map projection.

Orthorectification is the process of correcting images so that the scale is uniform: the photo has the same lack of distortions as a map. Therefore, an orthophotograph can be used to measure true distances, because it is an accurate representation of the Earth's surface, having been adjusted for topographic relief, lens distortion and camera tilt.

Georeferenced and Orthorectificated images are commonly used as source for image analysis algorithms [40] [43] [44] [41] [42] [45].

Pan-sharpening multispectral image

“Pan Sharpening” is shorthand for “Panchromatic sharpening”. It means using a panchromatic (single band) image to “sharpen” a multispectral image. In this sense, to “sharpen” means to increase the spatial resolution of a multispectral image.

It is used in many research works [40] [43] [44] and different methods are proposed [46].

The following shows a Pan-sharpened Product, High-Resolution Panchromatic Image Fused with Lower Resolution Multispectral Image. It can be seen that Multispectral data has lower resolution.

Figure 27 Pan-sharpening example

Image enhancement

Correction techniques are routinely used to resolve geometric, radiometric, and other problems found in raw remotely sensed data. Another family of image processing techniques is used to make image data easier to interpret. These so-called image enhancement techniques include contrast stretching, edge enhancement, and deriving new data by calculating differences, ratios, or other quantities from reflectance values in two or more bands, among many others.

Different methods are proposed [47] [48] [49].

Image enhancement can be used to enhance the color component separation of an image [50].

The next images illustrate the increase in contrast in an image before (left) and after (right) a linear contrast

stretch.

Figure 28 Linear contrast stretch example

Image classification

The overall objective of image classification techniques is to automatically categorize all pixels in a digital image into land cover classes or themes. So the target of segmenting an image is to transform the image into a better representation, which is reduced to the essential parts. Furthermore, segmentation can be differed into unsupervised and supervised segmentation.

In unsupervised segmentation, all pixels are grouped into different regions, but there is no meaning annotated to any of them.

The Supervised classification is a standard image processing technique, which is based on clustering of image pixels into known predefined classes.

Examples of predefined classes for land cover categorization can be:

- Tree, water, bare soil, building, grassland, impervious [29]
- Waterbody, vegetated area, non-vegetated area [30]
- Non-shadow, shadow, non vegetation, vegetation [31]
- Agriculture, rural, water, impervious [32]
- Cotton, Corn, fallow farmlands, bare soil [40]
- Wheat, lentil, barley, bare, fallow, urban [43]

There are some features (NDVI for example) that can be extracted from different spectral bands. A summarization of the use of these features can be seen below:

- Mean of pixels in image object, brightness, NDVI, roundness of objects [31]
- 22 attributes (Mean channels, HSI, NDVI, OSAVI,...) [33]
- 31 input features (NDVI, mean blue, mean NIR,...) [34]
- Object area, NDVI, different ratios [45]
- 20 vegetation indices derived from ASTER wavebands [35]

Since many features can be used, some methods can be applied in order to reduce their number or dimensionality [34].

Finally, there are many supervised classification algorithms which have been used for the remote sensing data:

- Decision trees, Random Decision Forests (RDF) [29]
- Maximum Likelihood Classifier, Guassian Maximum Likelihood Classifier [36]
- Nearest Neighbor Classifier [31]
- eCognition Developer using Nearest Neighbor classifier [32]
- Maximum Likelihood (ML), Spectral Angle Mapper (SAM) and Support Vector Machines (SVM) [40]
- Support Vector Machine (SVM), Nearest Neighbour (NN), Maximum likelihood (ML) [33]
- Decision Tree (DT), Random Forest (RF), and Support Vector Machine (SVM) [44]

6.4 Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) service implementations

6.4.1 Metadata catalogue services (OGC CWS)

6.4.1.1 GeoNetwork

GeoNetwork¹⁹⁵ is an open-source complex metadata solution offering advanced metadata editor, catalogue according to the OGC Catalogue Service for Web (CSW) OGC implementation specification including harvesting possibilities. It supports metadata for wide range of standards, from simple Dublin Core metadata, through INSPIRE or Z39.50 metadata to complex metadata according to the ISO standards 19115 and 19119.

Usage of the GeoNetwork begins with the single platform independent installer. It allows installing and running software on a PC or a server with a Windows/Linux and Mac operating systems. It uses the Jetty servlet container since it is the Java based application. So far (May 2014), the latest version is 2.10.3.

The main features of the GeoNetwork application are following:

- Immediate search access to local and distributed geospatial catalogues
- Up- and downloading of data, graphics, documents, pdf files and any other content type
- An interactive Web Map Viewer to combine Web Map Services from distributed servers around the world
- Online editing of metadata with a powerful template system
- Scheduled harvesting and synchronization of metadata between distributed catalogues
- Support for OGC-CSW 2.0.2 ISO Profile, OAI-PMH, Z39.50 protocols
- Fine-grained access control with group and user management
- Multi-lingual user interface

Wide range of standards has been implemented:

- ISO19115/ISO19119/ISO19110 following ISO19139;
- FGDC and Dublin Core;
- Catalogue interfaces
 - OGC-CSW2.0.2 ISO profile client and server,
 - OAI-PMH client and server, GeoRSS server,
 - GEO OpenSearch server,
 - WebDAV harvesting,
 - GeoNetwork to GeoNetwork harvesting support;
- Map Services interfaces (OGC-compliant through the embedded Geoserver map server):
 - WMS,
 - WFS,
 - WCS,
 - KML.

GeoNetwork is based as a decentralized spatial information environment. As such it has been successfully deployed in various institutions when the first was FAO GeoNetwork at its headquarters in Rome. Since then has GeoNetwork been successfully deployed in hundreds of institutions under the GPU/GNL licence.

6.4.1.2 Micka

MICKA¹⁹⁶ is a meta-information catalogue that fully complies with the ISO 19115 standard and is fully compliant with the INSPIRE principles. It can be integrated with map applications. It is multilingual. The web catalogue service uses OGC specifications.

MICKA is a complex system for metadata management used for building Spatial Data Infrastructure (SDI) and geo-portal solutions. It contains tools for editing and management of metadata for spatial information, web ser-

¹⁹⁵ <http://geonetwork-opensource.org/>

¹⁹⁶ <http://www.plan4all.eu/simplecms/?articleID=28&action=article&presenter=ArticleDetail>

vices and other sources (documents, web sites, etc.). It includes online metadata search engine , portrayal of spatial information and download of spatial data to local computer.

MICKA is compatible with obligatory standards for European SDI building (INSPIRE). Therefore it is ready to be connected with other nodes of prepared networked metadata catalogues (its compatibility with pilot European geo-portal is continuously being tested).

Functions include:

- Spatial data metadata (ISO 19115)
- Spatial services metadata (ISO 19119)
- Dublin Core metadata (ISO 15836)
- Feature catalogue support (ISO 19110)
- OGC CSW 2.0.2 support (catalogue service)
- User defined metadata profiles
- INSPIRE metadata profile
- Web interface for metadata editing
- Multilingual (both user interface and metadata records). Currently 16 languages are supported. It is possible to dynamically extend the system for other languages.
- Context help (multilingual)
- Import from the following metadata formats are supported:
 - ESRI ArcCatalog,
 - ISO 19139,
- OGC services (WMS, WFS, WCS, CSW)
- Feature catalogue XML
- Export – ISO 19139, GeorSS
- Support of thesauri and gazetteers.
- Display of changes with GeorSS
- Template base interface with possibilities to change according to user requirements
- Possibility of deep cooperation with any map clients for display of on-line map services.

MICKA stores metadata in a relational database and it is edited by dynamically generated forms. Therefore it is possible to amend other standards or profiles. It is possible to switch between profiles while editing. Individual profiles can be distributed into sections. With the help of control elements it is possible to duplicate individual items, select from code lists or connects to supporting applications. Checking of mandatory items is enabled while editing.

The MICKA integrated application is divided into 3 independent components:

- Metadata creation
- Metadata importing
- Metadata Management

Metadata editing tools and metadata importing tools communicate with Metadata Management through the CSW protocol. This allows use of two tools independently on the one MICKA system (for instance a user could integrate with GeoNetwork)

6.4.2 Download and visualization services (OGC WMS, WFS and WCS)

6.4.2.1 Mapserver

MapServer¹⁹⁷ is a popular Open Source project whose purpose is to display dynamic spatial maps over the Internet. Some of its major features include:

- support for display and querying of hundreds of raster, vector, and database formats
- ability to run on various operating systems (Windows, Linux, Mac OS X, etc.)

¹⁹⁷ <http://mapserver.org/>

- support for popular scripting languages and development environments (PHP, Python, Perl, Ruby, Java, .NET)
- on-the-fly projections
- high quality rendering
- fully customizable application output
- many ready-to-use Open Source application environments

In its most basic form, MapServer is a CGI program that sits inactive on your Web server. When a request is sent to MapServer, it uses information passed in the request URL and the location of the configuration file (Mapfile¹⁹⁸) to create an image of the requested map. The request may also return images for legends, scale bars, reference maps, and values passed as CGI variables.

MapServer can be extended and customized through MapScript¹⁹⁹ or templating. It can be built to support many different vector and raster input data formats, and it can generate a multitude of output formats.

Mapserver supports the following OGC standards: WMS, WFS (there is no support for transactions i.e., WFS-T), WCS, SLD and SOS (the non-transactional part)

6.4.2.2 Geoserver

GeoServer²⁰⁰ is an open source software server written in Java that allows users to share and edit geospatial data. Designed for interoperability, it publishes data from any major spatial data source using open standards.

Being a community-driven project, GeoServer is developed, tested, and supported by a diverse group of individuals and organizations from around the world.

GeoServer is the reference implementation of the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) Web Feature Service (WFS) and Web Coverage Service (WCS) standards – since it fully implements them, including the transactional part -, as well as a high performance certified compliant Web Map Service (WMS).

6.4.2.3 ERDDAP

Environmental Research Division's Data Access Program (ERDDAP²⁰¹) (developed by the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration – NOAA of the USA) is a data server which provides the users with a simple and consistent way to download subsets of scientific datasets in common file formats and make graphs and maps. It can be used as access service for own data, or as a mediator capable of transforming the data and re-publishing it through different types of data servers (OPeNDAP, THREDDS, SOS, WMS, etc.). Coverages can be made available via griddap and WMS, tabular data via tabledap and SOS, and a great variety of data in different formats can be generated and downloaded using the ERDDAP-specific RESTful query interface.

6.4.2.4 Layman

Layer Manager web client allows user to upload files in the user's directory on the server file system and to publish the layers based on these files in the workspace belonging to the group. If the user belongs to several groups, he/she can select which workspace he/she wants to use.

6.4.3 Geospatial processing services (OGC WPS)

6.4.3.1 PyWPS

PyWPS is project, which is developed since 2006, and tries to implement OGC WPS standard. It is written in Python programming language. The main goal of PyWPS is, that it has been written from the beginning, with direct support for GRASS GIS. So, PyWPS can be understood, as kind of translation library, which translates requests compliant with WPS standard, overhands them to GRASS GIS or other command line tool (such as GDAL/OGR,

¹⁹⁸ <http://mapserver.org/mapfile/index.html#mapfile>

¹⁹⁹ <http://mapserver.org/glossary.html#term-mapscript>

²⁰⁰ <http://geoserver.org>

²⁰¹ <http://coastwatch.pfeg.noaa.gov/erddap/index.html>

PROJ.4 or R statistical package), monitors the calculation progress and informs the user and after the calculation is completed, it returns back it's result²⁰².

6.4.3.2 52° North WPS

The 52° North Web Processing Service²⁰³ enables the deployment of geo-processes²⁰³ on the web in a standardized way. It features a pluggable architecture for processes and data encodings. Its focus was the creation of an extensible framework to provide algorithms for generalization on the web.

Features:

- WPS Invocation: Synchronous/Asynchronous invocation; Raw data support; Supports HTTP-GET for Execute; Supports HTTP-POST for Execute; Supports SOAP; Exposes a WSDL document
- Supported WPS Datatypes: GeoTiff Support; ArcGrid Support; Full GML2 support for ComplexData; Full GML3 support for ComplexData; Shapefiles; KML; WKT
- Extensions: WPS4R - R Backend; GRASS out of the box extension; 220+ SEXTANTE Processes; Experimental Transactional Profile (WPS-T); Web GUI to maintain the service; ArcGIS Server Connector
- Result Storage: All Results can be stored as simple web accessible resource with an URL; Raster/Vector results can be stored directly as WMS layer; Vector results can be stored directly as WFS layer; Raster results can be stored directly as WCS layer

6.4.4 Sensor Web Enablement (OGC SWE)

6.4.4.1 Senslog

Senslog implemented SOS service [159] is based on the technology of data binding. It means that classes and interfaces are derived from XML schemes by binding compiler. Java Architecture for XML Binding (JAXB) was used for our purposes [160]. They are used compiled schemes from OGC Schemas and Tools project at this time. OGC Schemas project provides JAXB 2.x bindings for XML Schemas defined by the OGC. These compiled schemes are developed by Aleksei Valikov under 3-clause BSD license²⁰⁴. Binding a schema means generating a set of Java classes that represents the schema. All JAXB implementations provide a tool called a binding compiler to bind a schema (XJC) [Lau08]. After binding we do not have to deal with XML documents ourselves, we deal with programming-language objects, in this case with Java classes. Reading a XML document in JAXB terminology is called unmarshalling. Unmarshalling an XML document means creating a tree of content objects that represents the content and organization of the document. Writing a XML document is called marshalling, it creates a XML document from a content tree.

Implementation is a server-side application that includes core operations of SOS with mandatory parameters at this time.

6.4.4.2 52° North's Sensor Web Enablement Suite

- The **Sensor Observation Service (SOS)** aggregates readings from live, in-situ and remote sensors. The service provides an interface to make sensors and sensor data archives accessible via an interoperable web based interface. Four profiles are defined within the SOS specification: core, transactional, enhanced, and entire.

The current release²⁰⁵ (52N-SOS-4.0.0) implements the core profile comprising the mandatory operations:

- GetCapabilities, for requesting a self-description of the service.

²⁰² <http://pywps.wald.intevation.org/>

²⁰³ <http://52north.org/communities/geoprocessing/wps/>

²⁰⁴ VALIKOV, Aleksei. *OGC Schemas and Tools Project*. 2006 - 2011. Karlsruhe. WWW: <http://confluence.highsource.org/display/OGCS/Home>

²⁰⁵ <http://52north.org/communities/sensorweb/sos/index.html>

- GetObservation, for requesting the pure sensor data encoded in Observations & Measurements (O&M)
- DescribeSensor, for requesting information about the sensor itself, encoded in a Sensor Model Language (SensorML) instance document.

The transactional profile comprising of the following operations is implemented, too:

- RegisterSensor, for signing up new sensors.
- InsertObservation, for inserting new observations for registered sensors.

Additionally, the following operations are implemented:

- GetFeatureOfInterest, for requesting the GML encoded representation of the feature that is the target of the observation.
- GetResult, for periodically polling of sensor data

SOS RESTful Extension

The SOS RESTful Extension²⁰⁶ provides a means for accessing and manipulating SOS resources (i.e., observations, capabilities, offerings, sensors, and features) in a RESTful way - that means, plain HTTP methods (GET, DELETE, POST, PUT) can be used to interact with those resources. Using REST makes client development easy and lightweight.

The implementation of this RESTful extension is based on the 52°North SOS and can be easily added to existing deployments of the SOS 4.0 implementation.

The SOS RESTful add-on is realized as a specific binding for the SOS 4.0 - adding REST functionality beyond the standard KVP and SOAP bindings.

Figure 29 SOS RESTful interface

- The **Sensor Event Service (SES)**²⁰⁷ provides operations to register sensors at the service application and let clients subscribe for observations available at the service. The service performs filtering of sensor data (streams) based upon the filter criteria defined in these subscriptions. Filters can be applied on single observations but also on observation streams, potentially aggregating observations into higher-level information (which itself can be regarded as observation data). Whenever matches are discovered, a notification is sent to the subscriber, using asynchronous, push-based communication mechanisms.
- The **Sensor Planning Service (SPS)**²⁰⁸ is intended to provide a standard interface to collection assets (i.e., sensors, and other information gathering assets) and to support systems that surround them. An SPS not only has to support different kinds of assets with differing capabilities, but also different kinds of request processing systems, which may or may not provide access to the different stages of planning, scheduling, tasking, collection, processing, archiving, and distribution of resulting observation data.

The SPS enables easy integration of new sensors into an SDI by providing a standard interface to a wide variety of collection devices (i.e., sensors, and other information gathering devices) and their support systems. This tasking service makes interoperable sensor control and maintenance possible.

- The 52 North **Sensor Registry** framework²⁰⁹ is not an implementation of a standard from the OGC SWE suite, however it relies on work performed within the EU funded projects OSIRIS and GENESIS. Nonetheless, it is an interesting piece of software that might be of relevance for FOODIE since it provides spe-

²⁰⁶ <http://52north.org/communities/sensorweb/sosREST/index.html>

²⁰⁷ <http://52north.org/communities/sensorweb/ses/0.0.1/index.html>

²⁰⁸ <http://52north.org/communities/sensorweb/sps/1.0.0/index.html>

²⁰⁹ <http://52north.org/communities/sensorweb/discovery/index.html>

cialized sensor and observations metadata storage and query capabilities (as in contrast with the more general purpose OGC Catalogue standards).

The sensor registry framework it is composed of two subcomponents:

- The Sensor Instance Registry (SIR), which deals with sensor metadata (based on SensorML) and metadata of the services that encapsulate the sensors.
 - The Sensor Observable Registry (SOR), which provides an interface for managing the definitions of phenomena measured by sensors as well as exploring semantic relationships between these phenomena.
- The **OX-Framework (short for OGC web service aXess Framework)** is a generic software framework which addresses the needs of application developers who want to access and use OGC Web Services, and in particular Sensor Web services. It can be used as a basis for different application types: this can be thin, thick, or mobile client applications, as well as server applications that need to access OGC Web Services.

The primary aim of the OX-Framework²¹⁰ is to provide an architecture which is flexible and extendable enough so that the various kinds of OGC Web Services (OWS) can be easily accessed and the queried data can be processed. The connection to the OWS is realized by a so-called service-connector component. These components can be implemented for any type of OGC Web Service. New service-connectors can be added to the system as plug-ins. Thus developers are able to dynamically customize and extend the framework. Below, you find a list of the currently available service-connector implementations and their capabilities.

6.4.4.3 OGC SensorThings API

The SensorThings API²¹¹ defines a RESTful web service interface, in which users can perform CREATE, READ, UPDATE, and DELETE (CRUD) actions to any uniquely-identifiable resources in the service.

The OGC SensorThings service interface is different from the other OGC web services, in that it is based on RESTful web service style and JSON encoding. The OGC SensorThings API is inspired by the OASIS Open Data Protocol (OData), which defines a general-purpose RESTful service interface. The SensorThings service interface is very similar to the OData but specifically designed for the IoT.

Besides the OData, the SensorThings service interface also leverages the existing and widely implemented OGC standards. For example, the capabilities part of the OGC SensorThings service interface adapts some elements from the GetCapabilities response defined in the OWS Common by converting the XML encoding into the JSON encoding.

6.4.5 Web 2.0 components

6.4.5.1 Ext JS

Ext JS²¹² is a Javascript development framework created by Sencha to generate web desktop applications executed in user's browser. This platform facilitates the creation of Interactive Web Applications using MVC architecture. Ext JS provides tools to build robust web desktop applications using technologies as AJAX, DHTML and DOM scripting.

The framework provides different features as:

- Modern UI Widgets,
- Plugin-free charting,
- AJAX connections,
- Datastores,
- Standard Events: window, mouse and keyboard

²¹⁰ <http://52north.org/communities/sensorweb/oxf/index.html>

²¹¹ <http://ogc-iot.github.io/ogc-iot-api/index.html>

²¹² <http://www.sencha.com/products/extjs/>

- Powerful theming
- Cross-browser compatibility: this framework delivers the content on a wide variety of browsers and operative systems using the same code. It utilizes HTML5 features and falls back to alternatives on older browsers.

Ext JS is licensed under three different types of licenses depending on the type of project developed: one open source license (GPLv3) and two commercial license options (Commercial Software License and Commercial OEM license).

6.4.5.2 HSLayers

HSLayers²¹³ is an open source Javascript mapping framework for building rich web-based geo applications and it could also be used by parts for improving simple OpenLayers-based maps. HSLayers is released under GNU/GPL license. It is based on top of another two frameworks: OpenLayers and ExtJS.

On one hand, OpenLayers are used for their capabilities of geodata visualization, such as raster maps, web services, vector formats and proprietary formats (e.g.: Google maps). On the other hand, ExtJS is used because it enables to create various elements of UI (panels, tree structures, grids, forms), in a very simple and fast way.

Although HSLayers can be considered as pure JavaScript library, it is designed to work with several server-side components (scripts), which are enabling more advanced features, such as session management, wrapping script for on-the-fly raster data projection, OGC WMC handling, etc.

HSLayers features are coming up from OpenLayers and therefore their characteristics are as follows:

- Portrayal of various types of data:
 - Raster: OGC WMS(-T), Image (PNG, JPEG, GIF), ...
 - Vector: OGC WFS(-T), GML, GeoRSS, KML, GPX, GeoJSON, ...
 - Data sources from commercial servers: Google Maps, Virtual Earth, Yahoo Maps
- The user interface (use control) adheres to current conventions in web map portals.
- Information about queried objects in text bubbles.

HSLayers contains another additional function:

- Dynamic adding of OGC (Open Geospatial Consortium) services into map - clients for WMS and WFS
- Portrayal of independent data sources on the client side. Map composition is composed on the basis of requests to various servers. It is thus not necessary to install a map server.
- Saving of map composition according to WMC (Web Map Context) OGC specification on user computer for repeated future use or for sharing between users.
- Extension of compute functions based on WPS (Web Processing Service) OGC service - according to user needs.
- Multilingual environment.
- Map requests to various types of data stored on various servers, with automatic processing of results.
- Working with micro-formats.
- Searching on the map. Connection of the application with catalogue client (OGC CSW) in the GeoPortal, which enables display of the searched service from catalogue directly on the map.
- Edit function - snapping to chosen layers.
- Possibilities for advanced configuration of user requests.
- Advanced measuring of length and surfaces.
- Print of map compositions - possibility of large print outs (up to A0 format), user configuration of print settings.

²¹³ <http://hslayers.org/>

6.4.5.3 Leaflet

Leaflet²¹⁴ is a lightweight open-source Javascript library for mobile-friendly interactive maps. It is simple and easy to use and works efficiently across the majority of browsers and mobile platforms.. Leaflet focuses on satisfying the principal needs of map applications and it could be easily extended by third-party plugins. Some of the basic features are the support of different types of layers as Web Map Service (WMS) layers, GeoJSON²¹⁵ layers, Vector layers and Tile layers natively; the interaction features as drag and drop, multi-touch, keyboard, scroll and zoom; map controls; visual features and so on. Any map provider can be used with Leaflet (agreeing to its terms of use) as OpenStreetMap, MapBox, Bing Maps, Esri ArcGIS, Nokia Here and MapQuest Open (unlimited requests).

It is used by some companies as Flickr, Foursquare, Wikimedia, CloudMade amongst others.

The code is published under the 2-clause BSD License.

6.5 Volunteered Geographical Information (VGI) tools

Volunteered geographic information (VGI) is the harnessing of tools to create, assemble, and disseminate geographic data provided voluntarily by individuals [82]. Increasingly, VGI is being used to create and analyze spatial information through visualizations, and geospatial models. The geospatial data used, whether publicly provided or offered by volunteers, has been made available more and more through Web 2.0 technologies. Innovators are hosting more web mapping services, and users are sharing more data from GPS capable and affordable units. The best VGI products are reviewed by peers or members that perform quality control checks and updates [83].

Some of the most popular VGI tools are the next ones:

- GeoCommons is an advanced mapping service in which a user can visualize his/her own data to make custom maps including charts without charge. It serves data and maps from its open repository to business, professional and casual users, allowing them to create maps, even if they have little knowledge of GIS software. Citizens may submit their own data and search existing data files for their own reuse [84].
- GeoNode is an Open Source Geospatial Content Management System. GeoNode is a web-based application and platform for developing geospatial information systems (GIS) and for deploying spatial data infrastructures (SDI). It is designed to be extended and modified, and can be integrated into existing platforms [85]. As an example, the World Food Programme manages a corporate web application for creating and sharing geospatial data and maps powered by GeoNode [86].
- Google Map Maker is a service launched by Google in 2008, designed to expand the breadth of the service currently offered by Google Maps. Google has decided to open up Google Maps to a collaborative community effort in certain territories. The ultimate goal of the project is to acquire sufficient high-quality mapping data to be published and used on the existing Google Maps service. Google Map Maker is a separate service than Maps, and changes to Google Map Maker appear on Google Maps only after sufficient review by Google moderators. Users can add all kinds of information including geographic features (e.g., building outlines, roads, rails and bike paths, etc.) [87].
- OpenStreetMap (OSM) [88] is a collaborative project to create a free editable map of the world. Two major driving forces behind the establishment and growth of OSM have been restrictions on use or availability of map information across much of the world and the advent of inexpensive portable satellite navigation devices. It has grown to over 1 million registered users, who can collect data using GPS devices, aerial photography, and other free sources. These crowdsourced data are then made available under the Open Database License. The site is supported by the OpenStreetMap Foundation, a non-profit organization registered in England. Rather than the map itself, the data generated by the OpenStreetMap project are considered its primary output. These data are then available for use in both traditional applications, like their usage by Craigslist, Geocaching, MapQuest Open, JMP statistical software, and Foursquare to replace Google Maps, and more unusual roles, like replacing default data included with GPS receivers.

²¹⁴ <http://leafletjs.com/>

²¹⁵ <http://geojson.org/>

- Wikimapia [89] is a multilingual open-content collaborative map, where anyone can create place tags and share their knowledge. Its goal is to describe the whole world by compiling as much useful information about all geographical objects as possible, organize it and provide free access to the data for public domain. One of the main characteristics of Wikimapia is that it's constantly changing, striving to be always up to date and correct and to collect more and more information from all the sources at hand.

6.6 Big data, long term storage repositories and analysis tools

NoSQL databases provide a mechanism for storage and retrieval of data that use looser consistency models than traditional relational databases in order to achieve horizontal scaling and higher availability. In the context of FOODIE project NoSQL databases management systems are useful when working with a huge quantity of data (especially big data) when the data's nature does not require a relational model as it will be the case for the different sources of VGI collected by the system (e.g, farmers' sensor data, geo-referenced statistical data, etc.). The data can be structured, but NoSQL is used when what really matters is the ability to store and retrieve great quantities of data, not the relationships between the elements. In addition, these technologies are particularly useful for statistical or real-time analysis of growing number of records in the datasets. Other usages of this technology are related with the flexibility of the data model; a lot of applications might gain from this unstructured data model and could use this flexibility to store their data without performing changes on tables or creating generic columns in a database. These databases are also good to create prototypes or fast applications, because this flexibility provides a tool to develop new features very easily. NoSQL has also a distributed, fault-tolerant architecture. Several NoSQL systems employ a distributed architecture, with the data held in a redundant manner on several servers. In this way, the system can easily scale out by adding more servers, and failure of a server can be tolerated.

There are several well-known and proven open-source solutions available in the market, each of them with their own specific characteristics and in many cases with support for spatial features and operations. The following sub-sections present the most promising ones to be selected and integrated in FOODIE service cloud platform.

6.6.1 Storage

Traditionally, Relational Database Management Systems (RDBMS) have been used in the enterprise as the solution for storing and retrieving data. Relational databases perform transaction update functions very well, particularly handling the difficult issues of consistency during update, and have advanced querying capabilities (using SQL) allowing to perform multiple operations over the stored data. Production strength relational databases can handle the complexity of two phase commit capability, where one business transaction affects multiple databases and tables, and all updates have to be effected at the same moment.

However, relational databases apply much of the same overhead to every activity, and that can handicap them for other functions. Relational databases struggle with the efficiency of certain operations key to Big Data management (very high concurrency, very high volume of requests, etc.) and also are not suited to storing non-structured data. In contrast to relational databases, NoSQL ("Not Only SQL") databases relax some restrictions related to the CAP theorem [Brewer] to offer improved performance under some scenarios. Big Data storage tools form part of the NoSQL world.

At root, the key requirements of Big Data storage are that it can handle very large amounts of data and keep scaling to keep up with growth, and that it can provide the input/output operations per second (IOPS) necessary to deliver data to analytics tools.

Among the prominent Big Data NoSQL solutions are the following (Systems working only on-memory are excluded):

6.6.1.1 Apache Cassandra

Apache Cassandra²¹⁶ is a massively scalable open-source NoSQL database. Cassandra's technical roots can be

²¹⁶ <http://cassandra.apache.org/>

found at companies recognized for their ability to effectively manage big data – Google, Amazon, and Facebook – with Facebook open sourcing Cassandra to the Apache Foundation in 2009. From a technical point of view Cassandra's data model is a partitioned row store with tunable consistency. Cassandra is also described as a wide column store and an AP system (in Eric Brewers terminology). Cassandra is the first wide-column NoSQL database in the db-engine ranking²¹⁷.

License: Apache Cassandra is released under an Apache License (version 2.0). DataStax is a software and commercial support provider that can implement and offer commercial support Cassandra as a stand-alone database together with other products (Hadoop, Hive, Pig, and etcetera)

Main features:

- Elastic scalability – The number of nodes in the cluster can be changed with no downtime or interruption to applications.
- No single point of failure – Data is distributed across the cluster, where every node has the same role, resulting in continuous availability even in the event of a node failure.
- Linear-scale performance – Read and write throughput both increase linearly as new machines are added.
- Replication and multi data centre replication – Data is replicated across multiple data centres. Read and write to any node with all changes being automatically synchronized across a cluster.
- Transaction support – Delivers the “AID” in ACID compliance through its use of a commit log to capture all writes and built-in redundancies that ensure data durability in the event of hardware failures, as well as transaction isolation, atomicity, with consistency being tunable.
- MapReduce support - Cassandra has Hadoop integration, with MapReduce support. There is support also for Apache Pig and Apache Hive.
- Query language - CQL (Cassandra Query Language) was introduced, a SQL-like alternative to the traditional RPC interface.

Implementation language and bindings: Apache Cassandra is written in Java and has bindings for many other languages (Clojure, Python, .NET, Erlang, Go, Haskell, Node.js, Perl, PHP, Ruby, Scala).

6.6.1.2 CouchBase Server

CouchBase Server²¹⁸, originally known as Membase, is an open source, distributed (shared-nothing architecture) NoSQL document-oriented database. CouchBase is a product from CouchBase Inc., a merged company originating from the creators of Membase and the creators of CouchDB. From a technical point of view, CouchBase originated as a Key Value Store and evolved into a document store (since v2.0) akin to MongoDB. CouchBase Server is also a CP system (in Eric Brewers terminology). CouchBase is the third document NoSQL database in the db-engine ranking [DBRanking].

License: Couchbase Server is a packaged version of Couchbase's open source technology and is available in two variants: a Community Edition without recent bug fixes as Open Source (Apache 2.0 license for the source, custom license for the binaries) distribution, and an Enterprise Edition for commercial use.

Main features:

- Elastic scalability – The number of nodes in the cluster can be changed with no downtime or interruption to applications.
- Native support for JSON - Support for JSON documents along with indexing and querying
- Replication and multi data center replication – Data is replicated across multiple datacenters. Data can be replicated uni-directionally or bi-directionally with the ability to read and write to either cluster.
- Built-In Object-Level Cache - built-in object-level cache, based on memcached that lets you read and write data with sub-millisecond latency and sustained high throughput.
- Auto-Failover. Replica data is distributed across all nodes to reduce the impact of failure on a single node. If desired, Couchbase Server supports automatic failover to activate replica nodes.

²¹⁷ <http://db-engines.com/en/ranking/>

²¹⁸ <http://www.couchbase.com/>

- Hadoop and ElasticSearch support via connectors.

Implementation language and bindings: CouchBase Server is written in C/C++, Erlang and has clients for many other languages (C/C++, Python, .NET, Java, Ruby, PHP).

6.6.1.3 Apache HBase

Apache HBase²¹⁹ is an open-source, distributed, versioned, non-relational database modeled after Google's Bigtable. Just as Bigtable leverages the distributed data storage provided by the Google File System, Apache HBase provides Bigtable-like capabilities on top of Hadoop and HDFS. From a technical point of view, HBase's data model is a wide column store and a CP system (in Eric Brewer's terminology). HBase is the second wide-column NoSQL database in the db-engine ranking.

License: Apache HBase is released under an Apache License (version 2.0).

Main features:

- Linear and modular scalability.
- Strictly consistent reads and writes.
- Automatic and configurable sharding of tables.
- Automatic failover support between RegionServers.
- Convenient base classes for backing Hadoop MapReduce jobs with Apache HBase tables.
- Block cache and Bloom Filters for real-time queries.

Implementation language and bindings: Apache HBase is written in Java and has clients for other JVM-based languages (Jython, Groovy, Scala). It also has Thrift and REST client APIs.

6.6.1.4 MongoDB

MongoDB²²⁰ is an open-source document-oriented database system. Its origin lies in the development of a PaaS system by the company 10gen. In 2009, MongoDB was open sourced as a stand-alone product with an AGPL license. From a technical point of view, MongoDB's data model is a document store and a CP system (in Eric Brewer's terminology). MongoDB is the first document NoSQL database in the db-engine ranking [DBRanking].

License: MongoDB is available for free under the GNU Affero General Public License. The language drivers are available under an Apache License. In addition, MongoDB Inc. offers commercial licenses for MongoDB.

Main features:

- Auto-Sharding - scale horizontally without compromising functionality.
- Fast In-Place Updates - Atomic modifiers for contention-free performance.
- Replication - high availability and increased throughput with replica sets.
- Map/Reduce - Flexible aggregation and data processing.
- Querying and Indexing - Rich, document-based queries.
- File storage - MongoDB can be used as a file system.

Implementation language and bindings: MongoDB is written in C++ and has clients for many other languages (C/C++, NET, Python, Go, Erlang, Javascript, Node.js, Java, Ruby, Perl, PHP and Scala).

Other systems in the Big Data storage world worth mentioning are Apache Accumulo²²¹, Riak²²² [Riak], DynamoDB²²³ and Aerospike²²⁴.

²¹⁹ <http://hbase.apache.org/>

²²⁰ <https://www.mongodb.org/>

²²¹ <http://accumulo.apache.org/>

²²² <http://basho.com/riak/>

²²³ <http://aws.amazon.com/es/dynamodb/>

²²⁴ <http://www.aerospike.com/>

6.6.2 Data collection & message transportation

What has made data really big in recent years is that most new data is contained in high-throughput streams. Application logs, GPS tracking, social media updates, and digital sensors all constitute fast-moving streams that need to be stored and analysed. Although several solutions have long existed for the collection and transport of data between systems, it is just recently that some of them have evolved to address the need for collection and transport of those high-throughput streams. Among these solutions we can find Message Queuing Frameworks along specialized log collection tools. The goals are to have a reliable, efficient, scalable transport mechanism which supports batch as well as near real-time data consumers.

The prominent data collection frameworks used in the Big Data world are the following²²⁵:

6.6.2.1 Apache Kafka

Apache Kafka²²⁶ is an open-source publish-subscribe messaging framework rethought as a distributed commit log. It is a project developed by the Apache Software Foundation written in Scala that has its roots under developments at LinkedIn. Kafka is currently a subproject within the Apache Incubator. The project aims to provide a unified, high-throughput, low-latency platform for handling real-time data feeds. Kafka aims to unify offline and online processing by providing a mechanism for parallel load into Hadoop as well as the ability to partition real-time consumption over a cluster of machines.

License: Apache Kafka is released under an Apache License (version 2.0)

Main features:

- Publisher-Subscriber messaging pattern
- Messages are persistent
- Everything is distributed (producers, consumers, brokers and the queue itself)
- Focus on throughput
- Scale horizontally to handle additional data volume.
- Store configuration in Zookeeper instances.
- Fault-tolerance in the presence of machine failures
- Guarantees ordered durable message delivery
- Clients for many languages (Python, Go, C, C++, Clojure, Ruby, Node.js, Storm, Scala DSL, HTTP REST, JRuby, Perl)

6.6.2.2 Apache Flume NG

Apache Flume NG²²⁷ is a distributed, reliable, and available service for efficiently collecting, aggregating, and moving large amounts of log data written in Java. Flume NG is an evolution of the Apache Flume project to solve certain core issues. It has a simple and flexible architecture based on streaming data flows. It is robust and fault tolerant with tunable reliability mechanisms and many failover and recovery mechanisms. It uses a simple extensible data model that allows for online analytic application. Apache Flume is focused on collecting data into a HDFS.

License: Apache Flume is released under an Apache License (version 2.0).

Main features:

- Flexible data flows allowing fan-in and fan-out flows, contextual routing and backup routes (fail-over) for failed hops.
- Stream data from multiple sources into Hadoop for analysis.
- Focus on throughput, collect high-volume Web logs in real time.

²²⁵ Systems not oriented to high throughput/volume, scalability and availability are excluded (such as some full-fledged message queuing frameworks)

²²⁶ <http://kafka.apache.org/>

²²⁷ <http://flume.apache.org/>

- Insulate themselves from transient spikes when the rate of incoming data exceeds the rate at which data can be written to the destination.
- Guaranteed data delivery.
- Scale horizontally to handle additional data volume.
- Store configuration in Zookeeper instances.
- Several data sources (Avro, Thrift, Exec, Netcat, Syslog, JMS, Scribe) and sinks (HDFS, Logger, Avro, Thrift) supported out-of-the-box.

6.6.2.3 Scribe

Scribe²²⁸ is a server for aggregating streaming log data. It is designed to scale to a very large number of nodes and be robust to network and node failures. Scribe was developed at Facebook and released in 2008 as open source. Scribe is implemented as a thrift service using the non-blocking C++ server. Scribe servers are arranged in a directed graph, with each server knowing only about the next server in the graph, providing batching, scalability and high availability.

License: Scribe is released under an Apache License (Version 2.0)

Main features:

- Log entries consist of just two strings, category and message.
- Scales horizontally to handle additional data volume.
- Robust to failure of the network or any specific machine, but does not provide transactional guarantees.
- Messages are stored locally in case of network failure and resent after connectivity is restored.
- Any clients able to implement the Thrift protocol are supported.

6.6.2.4 RabbitMQ

RabbitMQ²²⁹ is open source message broker software that implements several messaging protocols. The RabbitMQ server is written in Erlang. Rabbit Technologies Ltd., developed and provided support for RabbitMQ. In 2010 it was acquired by SpringSource, a division of VMWare. It has support for different topologies and provides facilities to build systems with high-availability and fault-tolerance.

License: RabbitMQ is released under the Mozilla Public License (version 1.1). There is also commercial support.

Main features:

- Flexible routing - messages are routed before arriving to queues. Several kinds of routing mechanisms are supported out-of-the-box and it is possible to implement new ones.
- Scale horizontally to handle additional data volume through clustering and federation.
- High availability and fault tolerance through queue mirroring.
- Multi-protocol - support for AMQP, STOMP, MQTT and HTTP
- Clients for multiple languages - Java, Ruby, Python, .NET, C/C++, Erlang, Node.js, Perl, etc.
- Guarantees ordered durable message delivery

6.6.2.5 Apache Thrift

Thrift is an interface definition language that is used to define and create services for numerous languages. It is used as a remote procedure call (RPC) framework for "scalable cross-language services development". It is an open source project in the Apache Software Foundation.

License: Apache Thrift is released under the Apache 2 License.

Main features:

- Interface description language - Everything is specified in an IDL file from which bindings for many languages can be generated.

²²⁸ <https://github.com/facebook/scribe/>

²²⁹ <https://www.rabbitmq.com/>

- Language bindings - Thrift is supported in many languages and environments (C++, C#, Cocoa, D, Delphi, Erlang, Haskell, Java, OCaml, Perl, PHP, Python, Ruby, Smalltalk)
- Cross-language serialization with lower overhead.

6.6.2.6 Apache Avro

Apache Avro²³⁰ is a remote procedure call and serialization framework developed within Apache's Hadoop project. It uses JSON for defining data types and protocols, and serializes data in a compact binary format. In other words, Avro is a data serialization system. Its primary use is in Apache Hadoop, where it can provide both a serialization format for persistent data, and a wire format for communication between Hadoop nodes, and from client programs to the Hadoop services.

License: Apache Avro is released under the Apache 2 License.

Main features:

- Rich data structures.
- A compact, fast, binary data format.
- A container file, to store persistent data.
- Remote procedure call (RPC).
- Simple integration with dynamic languages. Code generation is not required to read or write data files nor to use or implement RPC protocols. Code generation as an optional optimization, only worth implementing for statically typed languages.
- It uses JSON for definitions.

6.6.2.7 Google Protocol Buffers

Protocol buffers²³¹ are Google's language-neutral, platform-neutral, extensible mechanism for serializing structured data – think XML, but smaller, faster, and simpler. You define how you want your data to be structured once, then you can use special generated source code to easily write and read your structured data to and from a variety of data streams and using a variety of languages – Java, C++, or Python.

License: Google Protocol Buffers is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution 3.0

Main features:

- Protocol buffers are a flexible, efficient, automated mechanism for serializing structured data
- Is fast, small and simple.
- Data structures are compiled to generated code for writing/reading serialized data.

6.6.3 Processing and analysis frameworks

6.6.3.1 Storm/Trident

Apache Storm²³² is a free and open source distributed real-time computation system, which allows data stream processing. A Storm topology consumes streams of data and processes those streams in arbitrarily complex ways, repartitioning the streams between each stage of the computation however needed.

Trident²³³ is a high-level abstraction for doing real-time computing on top of Storm. It allows you to seamlessly intermix high throughput (millions of messages per second), stateful stream processing with low latency distributed querying.

License: Apache Storm is a free and open source project licensed under the Apache License, Version 2.0, and currently undergoing incubation at The Apache Software Foundation (ASF), sponsored by the Apache Incubator

²³⁰ <http://avro.apache.org/>

²³¹ <https://code.google.com/p/protobuf/>

²³² <http://storm.incubator.apache.org/>

²³³ <http://thrift.apache.org/>

Main features:

- Storm is written in Clojure and Java.
- Storm integrates with any queuing system and any database system. Example queue integrations include: Kestrel, RabbitMQ / AMQP, Kafka, JMS. Integrating Storm with database systems is simply, open a database connection and read/write as usually.
- Storm topologies are inherently parallel and run across a cluster of machines. Different parts of the topology can be scaled individually by tweaking their parallelism.
- Storm was benchmarked at processing one million 100 byte messages per second per node on hardware with the following specs: Processor: 2x Intel E5645@2.4Ghz, Memory: 24GB.
- Storm is fault-tolerant: when workers die, Storm will automatically restart them. If a node dies, the worker will be restarted on another node.
- Storm guarantees every tuple will be fully processed. One of Storm's core mechanisms is the ability to track the lineage of a tuple as it makes its way through the topology in an extremely efficient way.
- At the core of Storm is a Thrift definition for defining and submitting topologies. Since Thrift can be used in any language, topologies can be defined and submitted from any language.

6.6.3.2 Akka

Akka²³⁴ is a toolkit and runtime to build correct concurrent, fault-tolerant and scalable event-driven applications on the JVM. Jonas Bonér began working on Akka in early 2009, in order to facilitate the development of Scala applications with synchronized threads and shared memory. The first public release was Akka 0.5, announced in January 2010. Now, Akka is part of the Typesafe Platform, together with the Play framework and the Scala programming language.

License: Akka is Open Source and available under the Apache 2 License.

Main features:

- Akka is written in Scala, but also working in Java.
- Concurrency is message-based and asynchronous; Akka supports multiple programming models for concurrency, but it emphasised actor-based.
- Akka has a core modular structure, which can incorporate other modules to add features.
- High performance: 50 million msg/sec on a single machine. Adaptive load-balancing, cluster rebalancing and actor migration.
- High level abstractions like Actors, Futures and Software Transactional Memory (Atomic, Consistent and Isolated)
- Integration with various third-party systems (e.g. Apache Camel, ZeroMQ).

6.6.3.3 Hadoop

The Apache Hadoop²³⁵ software library is a framework that allows for the distributed processing of large data sets across clusters of computers using simple programming models. Doug Cutting began its development when was in Yahoo! (2005), inspired by technologies released by Google, specifically MapReduce and Google File System (GFS), in order to use as the basis for a distributed search engine.

License: Apache Hadoop is released under the Apache 2 License.

Main features:

- Apache Hadoop had two principal parts: the Hadoop Distributed File System (HDFS) and MapReduce. With HDFS and MapReduce, the speed of analysis scales to the size of the cluster.
- There are no restrictions on the data that HDFS stores. Data may be unstructured and schemaless.
- MapReduce enables you to operate on the contents of a file in parallel by having an independent process read each chunk (or "block") of the file.

²³⁴ <http://akka.io/>

²³⁵ <http://hadoop.apache.org/>

- The Hadoop framework itself is mostly written in the Java programming language, with some native code in C and command line utilities written as shell-scripts.

6.6.4 Digital Libraries and preservation repositories

Digital libraries (DLs) are used to collect, manage and preserve for the long term rich digital content; usually providing its users communities functionalities on that content, of measurable quality and according to codified policies [51]. Different DL systems and frameworks have been developed, based on different architectures (e.g., federated architecture, distributed architecture, and service-oriented architecture), to provide all the functionality required. Some relevant DL systems are: Libronix DL System²³⁶, Greenstone²³⁷, OpenDLib²³⁸ and its successor gCube DL²³⁹ management system, Daffodil²⁴⁰, OSIRIS/ISIS²⁴¹, JeromeDL²⁴², dLibra²⁴³, etc. Most of these systems support well-known standards and protocols for communication and data exchange, such as RSS, RDF, MARC, Dublin Core, OAIPMH [53] and OAI-ORE [54]. It is also worth mentioning rohub²⁴⁴, a digital library system that extend dLibra with semantic capabilities for the storage and management of research objects (semantic aggregations of digital resources).

Moreover, repository systems are at the core of most digital libraries with support of protocols for data and metadata exchange like OAI-PMH. Some relevant repository systems are: Fedora²⁴⁵, DSPACE²⁴⁶, and EPrints²⁴⁷. These are frequently used to create institutional repositories for managing documents and collections within scholarly environments, hence differing from digital libraries in their scope: they are institutionally defined, scholarly, cumulative and perpetual, open and interoperable. Similar to repositories we can also find digital object preservation systems like Archivematica²⁴⁸, KOPAL²⁴⁹ and dArceo²⁵⁰.

Many of the abovementioned systems offer similar functionality, with differences in the supporting formats/protocols, search capabilities, technical support, etc. So in remainder of this section we will introduce in more detail the most relevant ones for FOODIE, which we considered the main candidates to be used, taking into account the technical features, but mainly the familiarity of partners with the systems for any technical support/information needed during the course of the project.

6.6.4.1 dLibra

dLibra is a software system for building digital libraries, which has been developed by Poznan Supercomputing and Networking Center (PSNC) since 1999. Its multitier service-oriented architecture and configurable components of end-users applications allow deploying digital library systems suited for particular needs. It is focused on storing and publishing documents although it can accept files of any format. dLibra system offers a broad scope of functions and characteristics, including:

- storage and retrieval of digital objects independent of format, e.g. PDF, DjVu, MP3, FLV, JPG,
- dedicated tools supporting import from external systems and formats (e.g. MARC, XML, BibTeX, Z39.50, RDF),
- advanced capabilities in terms of resources and metadata management,
- secure and flexible authentication (e.g. LDAP, SSO, dedicated solutions),
- advanced rights management allowing precise assignment of duties,

²³⁶ <http://www.logos.com/ldls>

²³⁷ <http://www.greenstone.org/>

²³⁸ <http://www.opendlib.com>

²³⁹ <http://www.gcube-system.org/>

²⁴⁰ <http://www.daffodil.de/>

²⁴¹ http://dbis.cs.unibas.ch/delos_website/

²⁴² <http://www.deri.ie/content/jerome-dl>

²⁴³ <http://dlibra.psnc.pl/>

²⁴⁴ <http://www.rohub.org/portal>

²⁴⁵ <http://www.fedora-commons.org/>

²⁴⁶ <http://www.dspace.org/>

²⁴⁷ <http://www.eprints.org/>

²⁴⁸ <https://www.archivematica.org>

²⁴⁹ <http://kopal.langzeitarchivierung.de>

²⁵⁰ <http://dingo.psnc.pl/darceo/>

- support for building complex digital libraries (e.g. regional), with hundreds of cooperating institutions,
- scalability of the digital library along with the growth of resources and users,
- interoperability through the information exchange, using well-known standards and formats (e.g. OAI-PMH, OAI-ORE, RDF, OpenSearch, RIS, RSS feeds).

From these, one of the most important functions of the dLibra system is the storage and the presentation of digital objects. Related to this, dLibra supports hierarchical repository structure, collections for presentation, groups of digital objects, planned digital objects and content versioning. The metadata associated to these objects include technical, administrative and descriptive aspects.

The general architecture of the system is presented in Figure 30. The core of dLibra include the following services:

- Metadata service - is responsible for management of the digital library objects and other elements of the digital library data model - composite objects, collections and directories; it also provides all functionality related to metadata of digital library elements including management of the metadata schema and dictionaries created for each metadata schema element.
- Content service - is responsible for management of the content of digital library objects (bytestreams); beside of store/retrieve functionality provides also long-term preservation support and content transformations.
- Indexing service - is responsible for building search indexes for efficient searching in content and metadata of digital objects.
- Search service - provides searching functionality based on indexes built by indexing service.
- User service - handles user accounts and authentication/authorization operations.
- Profile service - stores private profiles of users.

Figure 30 dLibra Architecture

In a typical dLibra configuration, end-users applications are deployed on top of those services. dLibra provides the following client applications: (i) Editor's and Administrator's application, which allows users to create digital repository (submit digital objects, describe digital objects etc.) and administer the repository's functions; (ii) Reader's application, which is available through web pages, enabling users („readers”) to use the digital objects stored in the repository. Readers have various functions available on the web pages such as local search (simple or advanced), distributed search, values indexes, browse via collections of objects, creating accounts and subscribe to events.

6.6.4.2 DSpace

DSpace is an open source repository software package typically used for creating open access repositories for scholarly and/or published digital content. It allows capturing data in multiple digital formats (e.g., text, video, audio, and data files), indexing digital content, so users can search and retrieve materials, distributes digital content over the Web and preserves digital materials over the long term.

Internally, DSpace is a set of cooperating Java Web applications and utility programs maintaining an asset store and associated metadata store. The asset store is maintained on a file system or similar storage system. The

metadata, including access and configuration information is stored in a relational database. The key features are:

- Out-of-the-box: easy-to-install and get up and running quickly.
- Application architecture: it is a full application, not only a framework with components (i.e. database, data model, workflows, browse/search, storage manager, front end web interface) built into the architecture. Components may be swapped or added, but there is no need to build new ones.
- Built-in workflows: the embedded data model and workflows are familiar to librarians and archivists.
- Built-in search engine: it comes with Apache Lucene, an OS indexing engine supporting full-text searching for end users. It is also possible to enable a faceted search/browse interface via Apache Solr, an OS enterprise search platform.
- File types: auto-recognition of files of any common format (e.g. TXT, DOC, PDF, JPEG, MPEG, TIFF), but accepts files of any format.
- Metadata: Qualified Dublin Core is the default metadata schema, but it can accept custom metadata schemas similar to Qualified Dublin Core. DSpace can also translate metadata from other metadata schemas such as MARC/MODS.
- Tools/plugins: It comes with management tools including batch import/ export, batch metadata editing, curation, and object backup & restoration tools.
- Security: It comes with an authorization stack or organizations may use an existing LDAP, Shibboleth, or similar protocols to link their internal systems
- Permissions: It allows controlling permissions as granular as item level, or you can set global permissions based on communities and collections.
- OAI-PMH/SWORD/WebDAV: compliance with standard protocols for access, ingest and export.
- Configurable database: Organizations can choose either Postgres or Oracle for the database in which DSpace manages items and metadata.
- Languages: It is available in over twenty languages

Figure 31 depicts the system architecture organized into three layers: (i) Storage, which is responsible for physical storage of metadata and content; (ii) business logic, which deals with managing the content of the archive, users of the archive (e-people), authorization, and workflow; and (iii) application, which contains components that communicate with the world outside of the individual DSpace installation (e.g., the Web user interface and the Open Archives (OAI)²⁵¹ protocol for metadata harvesting service).

Figure 31 DSPACE System Architecture

²⁵¹ <http://www.openarchives.org/>

6.6.4.3 dArceo

dArceo, developed by Poznan Supercomputing and Networking Center (PSNC), is a system for long-term preservation of source data (e.g. master files), primarily focused on textual, graphical and audiovisual content. It makes migration of source data possible with respect to the OAIS model. Additionally, dArceo provides conversion and source data delivery functions, which may help both to build digital libraries and access source data by advanced users. dArceo can be configured to store data in the PLATON-U4 archiving services, a service for data storage backup and archive in multiple, geographically distributed replicas, to ensure their stability, integrity and long-term availability.

dArceo architecture (depicted in Figure 32) is based on services and REST-full interfaces. There are 9 services, forming together a fully functional dArceo instance:

- **Source Data Manager (SDM)** provides functions for storage, retrieval and modification (including versioning) of preserved (source) data. It also extracts additional metadata from submitted data and metadata using FFMpeg²⁵² 0.9, FITS²⁵³ 0.5.0 and DROID²⁵⁴ 6.01. It can be configured using dedicated plugin to work with various data archiving systems, and by default it can use SFTP, FTP or local file system. To handle potentially long-lasting functions (e.g. storage/retrieval from manually operated BluRay or tape system) asynchronous invocations have been introduced. Finally, SDM uses METS format as metadata containers for descriptive, technical and administrative metadata. PREMIS is used to represent changes related to the object, e.g., migration.
- **OAI-PMH Repository (OR)** provides OAI-PMH repository interface to digital objects stored in dArceo. Two formats are supported: Dublin Core and METS.
- **Data Manipulation Services (DMS)** provide functions for data manipulation and are designed to be an extensible framework, where users can add new services and discover them using Service Register based on semantic technologies. It is possible to pipeline services, so that a particular service can be used individually, or in a more advanced data manipulation flow (e.g. several conversions). There are three types of DMSs: (i) **Data Migration Services (DMiS)**, which use transformation approach of the OAIS model; (ii) **Data Conversion Services (DCS)**, which provide lossy conversion functions, simplifying the process of building digital libraries, which primarily provide access to so called presentation versions of digital objects; (iii) **Advanced Data Delivery Services (ADDS)**, which provide means to deliver data in personalized way, including source format, e.g. by streaming or progressive download. Alternatively the data can be exposed to advanced analysis, e.g. text extraction from a/v document, and the results are then delivered to the user.
- **Services Register (SR)** is a register for all DMS. It stores metadata of registered services and enables search. Each SR can gather information about publicly available services from other (configured) SRs. As a result SR offers its users not only services registered locally, but also those available in different locations.
- **Source Data Monitor (SDMo)** monitors source data and assesses risk of data loss in the context of long-term preservation, it also verifies integrity of source data.
- **System Monitor** provides overview of the whole system, by means of reports (e.g. storage usage statistics).
- **Data Migration and Conversion Manager (DMCM)** is responsible for execution of user-defined migration plans. It communicates with other services, e.g. SR, SDM, DMS, SDMO to execute particular migration plan.
- **Rights Manager (RM)** is responsible for rights management (AA) both to digital objects and services.
- **Notification Manager (NM)** is responsible for communication between services, by means of notifications.

²⁵² <http://www.ffmpeg.org/>

²⁵³ <https://code.google.com/p/fits/>

²⁵⁴ <http://sourceforge.net/projects/droid/>

Figure 32 dArceo system architecture

6.7 Semantics and Linked Open Data

6.7.1 Linked data storage & publication

6.7.1.1 Jena

The open source framework known as Jena²⁵⁵ provides an API to interact with RDF graphs through reading from and writing to them. Jena approach represents the RDF as an abstract data model which can be loaded from several kind of sources: files, databases, URLs or a combination of these. The sources are not limited to RDF, OWL is also a possibility.

Among Jena services it is remarkable to mention:

- Data model query: Jena offers the possibility to query the data model with SPARQL and update it through SPARUL.
- RDF serialisation: It also supports the serialisation of the model to a relational database, RDF/XML, Turtle, N3.

6.7.1.2 Virtuoso

Virtuoso Universal Server²⁵⁶ is a middleware and database engine hybrid that combines the functionality of a traditional RDBMS, ORDBMS, virtual database, RDF, XML, free-text content management & full-text indexing, linked data server, web application server and file server functionality in a single system. So, instead of providing dedicated servers for each of these functionality realms, Virtuoso enables a single multithreaded server process that implements multiple protocols (see architecture diagram in Figure 33). It is designed to take advantage of operating system threading support and multiple CPUs.

Virtuoso database engine includes physical file and in memory storage and operating system processes that interact with the storage, provides dynamic locking from row to page level, support transactions as well as entity and referential integrity.

Moreover, in addition to the functionality realms mentioned above, Virtuoso implements several industry standard Web & Internet protocols, including among others: HTTP, WebDAV, UDDI, SOAP, WSDL, SPARQL and

²⁵⁵ <http://jena.apache.org/>

²⁵⁶ <http://virtuoso.openlinksw.com/>

SPARUL. It also implements a variety of industry standard data access APIs for the database (e.g., ODBC, JDBC, XMLA), and supports different standards for content syndication and interchange format (e.g., Atom, RSS, FOAF). Virtuoso also supports several query languages, including SQL, SPARQL, XQuery, XPath and XSLT.

Regarding Virtuoso RDF, key features include: an RDF triple store, SPARQL query language support, SPARQL protocol support, inline SPARQL integration within SQL, use of bitmap indices for optimizing storage and management of RDF triples, implementation of the HTTP-based Semantic Bank API²⁵⁷ that enables client applications to post to its RDF Triple Store, and several RDF insert methods, including http PUT and POST.

Virtuoso SPARQL can use an inference context for inferring triples that are not physically stored. Such an inference context can be built from one or more graphs containing RDF Schema triples. The supported RDF Schema or OWL constraints are imported from these graphs and are grouped together into rule bases. A rule base is a persistent entity that can be referenced by a SPARQL query or end point.

Virtuoso's reasoning (v6.1.1) includes support for owl:sameAs, rdfs:subClassOf, rdfs:subPropertyOf, owl:equivalentClass, owl:equivalentProperty, owl:InverseFunctionalProperty, owl:TransitiveProperty, owl:SymmetricalProperty, and owl:inverseOf.

The latest release v7.1.0 includes improvements in the Engine (SQL Relational Tables and RDF Property/Predicate Graphs), SPARQL compiler, Jena and Sesame provider performance and GeoSpatial support, among others.

Virtuoso comes in two editions: Open-source and Commercial. The difference between these two is that the Open Source Edition does not include the Virtual Database Engine and Data Replication Functionality of the Commercial Edition.

Figure 33 Virtuoso Universal Server architecture

²⁵⁷ http://simile.mit.edu/wiki/Semantic_Bank

6.7.1.3 OWLIM

OWLIM²⁵⁸ is a family of semantic repositories, or RDF database management systems:

- Based on a Triple Reasoning and Rule Entailment Engine (TRREE) - a native RDF rule-entailment engine.
- Implemented in Java and packaged as a Storage and Inference Layer (SAIL) for the Sesame RDF framework.
- Compatible with Jena with a built in adapter layer.
- Robust support for the semantics of RDFS, OWL 2 RL and OWL 2 QL.
- Best scalability, loading and query evaluation performance.

It comes in three different versions: OWLIM-Lite, OWLIM-SE, OWLIM-Enterprise. OWLIM-Lite and OWLIM-SE are identical in terms of usage and integration. Besides a few differences in configuration parameters, these editions have the same functionality and implement the same Sesame APIs. However, they use different indexing, inference and query evaluation implementations, resulting in different performance, memory requirements, and scalability.

OWLIM-Lite (previously SwiftOWLIM) is a high-performance semantic repository designed for medium data volumes (below 100 million statements) and for prototyping. The key features include:

- Customizable reasoning in addition to RDFS, OWL Horst, and OWL 2 RL support. Reasoning and query evaluation are performed in-memory.
- Reliable persistence strategy ensures data preservation, consistency, and integrity.
- OWLIM-Lite can manage millions of explicit statements on desktop hardware.
- Licensed for use free of charge.

OWLIM-SE (previously BigOWLIM) is the commercial edition of OWLIM – a high-performance semantic repository suitable for handling massive volumes of data and very intensive querying activities. The key features include:

- Customizable reasoning in addition to RDFS, OWL-Horst, and OWL 2 RL and QL support. Reasoning and query evaluation are performed over a persistent storage layer.
- Optimized owl: same as handling which improves performance and usability when huge volumes of data from multiple sources are integrated.
- File-based indices, which enable it to scale to billions of statements even on desktop machines.
- Special-purpose index and query optimization techniques, ensuring fast query evaluation against very large volumes of data.
- Clustering support brings resilience, fail-over and scalable parallel query processing.
- Geo-spatial extensions for special handling of 2-dimensional spherical data allowing data using the WGS84 RDF vocabulary to be indexed and processed quickly using a variety of special geometrical query constructions and SPARQL extensions functions.
- Full-text search support based on either Lucene or proprietary search techniques.
- High performance retraction of statements and their inferences – so inference materialization speeds up retrieval, but without delete performance degradation.
- Powerful and expressive consistency/integrity constraint checking mechanisms.
- RDF rank can be calculated for the nodes in an RDF graph and used for ordering query results by relevance, visualization and any other purposes.
- RDF Priming, based upon activation spreading, allows efficient data selection and context-aware query answering for handling huge datasets.
- Notification mechanism, to allow clients to react to statements in the update stream.
- Commercial license on a per-server-CPU basis.

OWLIM-SE can manage billions of explicit statements on desktop hardware and can handle tens of billions of statements on commodity server hardware

OWLIM-Enterprise (previously BigOWLIM Replication Cluster) is a high-performance, clustered semantic repository. The key features include:

²⁵⁸ <https://www.ontotext.com/owlim>

- Scale-out concurrent query processing allows query throughput to be scaled proportionally with the number of cluster nodes.
- Resilience in the event of hardware/software failure so that the cluster remains full functional in the event of a failure of any node.
- Automated fail-over and load-balancing keeps the cluster fully utilized at all times.
- Dynamic configuration and automatic synchronization allows nodes to be added or removed at any time.
- Notification mechanism allows clients to react to statements in the update stream for the entire cluster.
- Commercial license on a per-server-CPU basis.

Both OWLIM-SE and OWLIM-Enterprise can be obtained for evaluation first.

For FOODIE is particularly interesting the support for geo-spatial data.

6.7.1.4 Berlin SPARQL Benchmark results summary.

The Berlin SPARQL Benchmark (BSBM) compares the performance of storage systems that expose SPARQL endpoints, including native RDF stores, Named Graph stores, systems that map relational databases into RDF, and SPARQL wrappers around other kinds of data sources. BSBM is built around an e-commerce use case, where different vendors offer a set of products and consumers have posted reviews about products.

The results of the latest experiment from April 2013²⁵⁹ used the Berlin SPARQL Benchmark Version 3.1²⁶⁰ to measure the performance of different triple stores including BigOwlum (version 5.2.5524), BigOwlum (version 5.3.5777) cluster edition, Virtuoso (06.04.3132), Virtuoso (07.00.3202) and TDB (0.9.4) - a component of Jena for RDF storage and query.

One of the experiments measured the loading times for different datasets sizes for each of these systems. For relative small datasets (10M), BigOwlum was the fastest, whereas for bigger datasets (100M, 200M and 1B) Virtuoso was the fastest with a significant difference. Other experiment measured the query throughput (query per second) for 12 different queries in each system. In general, results are mixed. In the first use case, in 33% of cases Virtuoso 6 was the best performing system, and 33% TDB for medium size dataset (100M), 50% Virtuoso 6 and 33% TDB for 200M dataset, and Virtuoso 6 or 7 always for 1B dataset. In the second use case, Virtuoso 6 or 7 was in general the best performing system. Finally, results of query mixes per hour experiment showed also Virtuoso as the best performing system.

These results are very useful to decide the best triple store for FOODIE. According to results, we plan to use Virtuoso because is the best performing system, scalable and open-source.

6.7.1.5 su4j

su4j is a tool developed by CTIC foundation composed by two different libraries: *su4j sparql endpoint*, *su4j sparql client*.

The first one provides a flexible SPARQL endpoint that could be deployed on any Java EE-based application. In comparison with fuseki, this is not an embedded server, but a simple endpoint to be deployed on any custom application. The main features of this library are:

- JavaEE Servlet-based implementation of SPARQL 1.1 Protocol
- Several formats supported
 - SPARQL Results XML, JSON and HTML for SELECT/ASK queries
 - RDF/XML, N3, Turtle and JSON-LD for CONSTRUCT/DESCRIBE queries
- Named graph support
- Different implementations:
 - Jena-based implementation
 - so potentially plugged to other compatibles systems, such as Virtuoso, Oracle and others

²⁵⁹ <http://wifo5-03.informatik.uni-mannheim.de/bizer/berlinsparqlbenchmark/results/V7/index.html>

²⁶⁰ <http://www4.wiwiss.fu-berlin.de/bizer/BerlinSPARQLBenchmark/V3/spec/index.html>

- actually compatible with any Dataset²⁶¹ implementation, including TDB²⁶²
- Proxy-based implementation
 - allowing to allow access to private endpoints
- CORS enabled

The client library allows users to query a SPARQL endpoint from a J2EE application.

6.7.1.6 Elda

Elda²⁶³ is a Java open-source implementation of the open Linked Data API specification²⁶⁴, a set of best practices for publishing, sharing and linking data and information on the web.

The Linked Data API provides a configurable way to access RDF data using simple RESTful URLs that are translated into queries to a SPARQL endpoint. The key features include:

- Multiple built-in results formats including JSON, XML, Turtle, RDF/XML, and HTML.
- Configurable views control which information is returned about selected items.
- Selection and result strings can be restricted to specified languages.
- Where necessary, explicit SPARQL can be used in configuration or passed through URIs.

Additional features of Elda include:

- Possibility to write specialized formatters in Java.
- Optimized query generation using SPARQL 1.1 features.
- Ability to run in a web application container or as a standalone server.

Hence, Elda enable data publishers to exploit existing standard RDF store and SPARQL query technology available off-the-shelf, to handle application-level data formats (JSON, XML) and to broaden the reach of the data to include consumers that prefer non-RDF formats for accessing data.

This may be very useful in FOODIE to reach many types of data consumers.

6.7.1.7 Marmotta

Marmotta²⁶⁵ is an open implementation of a Linked Data Platform from Apache that can be used, extended and deployed easily by organizations who want to publish Linked Data or build custom applications on Linked Data. The Linked Data Platform specification is a set of best practices and simple approach for a read-write Linked Data architecture. It describes the use of HTTP for accessing, updating, creating and deleting resources from servers that expose their resources as Linked Data.

The key features of Marmotta include:

- Read-Write Linked Data
- RDF triple store (Kiwi²⁶⁶) with transactions, versioning and rule-base reasoning
- SPARQL, LDP (Linked Data Platform) and LDPPath query
- Transparent Linked Data Caching
- Integrated basic security mechanisms

The Marmotta project is graduating from the incubator as a new Top Level Project in the Apache Software Foundation.

For FOODIE, Marmotta will be considered as a possible alternative of Elda, although at the moment it does not seem mature enough.

²⁶¹ <http://incubator.apache.org/jena/documentation/javadoc/arq/com/hp/hpl/jena/query/Dataset.html>

²⁶² <http://incubator.apache.org/jena/documentation/tdb/index.html>

²⁶³ <http://www.epimorphics.com/web/tools/elda.html>

²⁶⁴ <https://code.google.com/p/linked-data-api/>

²⁶⁵ <https://marmotta.apache.org/>

²⁶⁶ <https://marmotta.apache.org/kiwi/>

6.7.1.8 GetLOD

GetLOD²⁶⁷ is an open and reusable tool for publishing geographic data on the Web as Linked Open Data in RDF/XML format. Such solution enables the indexing of geographic information on open data search engines and the integration with open data portals or the Comprehensive Knowledge Archive Network (CKAN), the catalogue of free dataset and projects.

It can be integrated with geoportals, Open Data Portals and Spatial Data Infrastructures based on the interoperability standard defined by the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC). Hence, GetLOD is a potentially useful tool in FOODIE to support the publishing of the project geographical information sources as Linked Open data. Moreover, in addition to RDF, GetLOD enables the publishing of data in other not linkable interchange formats (e.g. shapefile and / or GML), which may also be useful for the project.

6.7.2 Semantic tagging and data transformation

6.7.2.1 GATE

GATE²⁶⁸, General Architecture for Text Engineering, is an open source software supporting manual annotation, performance evaluation, information extraction and [semi-]automatic semantic annotation, among others tasks, and it is being used in different applications, such as cancer research, decision support, web mining, etc.

The architecture of GATE (see Figure 34) includes a persistent storage layer with support for XML, Oracle, PostgreSQL, or Java serialization, and enables I/O interoperability with many other systems.

GATE includes a set of tools for data editing and visualization, rapid application development, manual annotation, ontology visualization and editing and semantic annotation.

Key features include:

- pluggable input filters with out of the box support for XML, HTML, PDF, MS Word, email, plain text, etc.
- common in-memory data model built around stand-off annotation, documents and corpora.
- Integration support with many complementary systems for Information Retrieval (e.g., Lucene, Google search), Machine Learning (e.g., Weka, MaxEnt), Ontology support (Sesame, OWLIM), Parsing (e.g., RASP, Minipar), and others (e.g., UIMA, Wordnet, Snowball, etc.).
- Support for using taxonomical relations in annotation matching for enhancing generalization power of pattern matching.

GATE can also be used with ontologies for (i) ontology learning: automatically extending ontologies with knowledge extracted from text through Information Extraction; and (ii) Knowledge Base Population: automatically populating knowledge bases with instance data extracted from text. This is related to Semantic Annotation.

Regarding semantic annotation, i.e., the automatic and semi-automatic production of semantic metadata for text and other source, GATE identifies mentions of known concepts and instances from an ontology.

²⁶⁷ http://www.planetek.it/eng/products/all_products/getlod

²⁶⁸ <https://gate.ac.uk/>

Figure 34 Gate architecture

6.7.2.2 Annotea

Annotea²⁶⁹ is a Web-based shared annotation system based on a general-purpose open RDF infrastructure, where annotations are modeled as a class of metadata. Annotations are viewed as statements made by an author about a Web document. Annotations, described with a dedicated RDF schema, are external to the documents and can be stored in one or more annotation servers. The annotation server stores the annotations in an RDF database. Users can query a server to retrieve an existing annotation, post a new annotation, modify an annotation, or delete an annotation. All communication between a client and an annotation server uses the standard HTTP methods. Figure 35 illustrates the basic architecture of Annotea.

Annotations are collections of various statements about a document, such as comments, typographical corrections, hypothesis or ratings. The metadata of an annotation gives information such as the date of creation of the annotation, name of the author, the annotation type (e.g., comment, query, correction...) the URI of the annotated document, and an XPointer that specifies what part of the document was annotated. The metadata also includes a URI to the body of the annotation, which is assumed to be an XHTML document.

Figure 35 Annotea architecture

6.7.2.3 AgroTagger

AgroTagger²⁷⁰ is a keyword extractor that uses the AGROVOC thesaurus as its set of allowable keywords. It can extract keywords from Microsoft Office documents, PDF files and web pages, and it is used mainly for indexing information resources.

There are different services based of AgroTagger that can be accessed either as web interfaces for manual document upload or as REST web services that can be programmatically invoked. These include web services

²⁶⁹ <http://www.w3.org/2001/Annotea/>

²⁷⁰ <http://aims.fao.org/agrotagger>

AGROTAGS V3 subset²⁷¹ of AGROVOC, Full AGROVOC thesaurus²⁷², and web interfaces for manual upload of documents to extract the keywords/concepts (e.g., Hive²⁷³ and maui-indexer²⁷⁴).

6.7.2.4 D2RQ

The D2RQ²⁷⁵ Platform is a system, based on Jena, for accessing relational databases as virtual, read-only RDF graphs. Hence, it enables RDF-based access to the content of relational databases without having to replicate it into an RDF store. In particular, D2RQ enables:

- To query a non-RDF database using SPARQL.
- To access the content of the database as Linked Data over the Web.
- To create custom dumps of the database in RDF formats for loading into an RDF store.
- To access information in a non-RDF database using the Apache Jena API.

D2RQ Platform consists of the following components (see Figure 36):

- D2RQ Mapping Language, a declarative mapping language for describing the relation between an ontology and an relational data model.
- D2RQ Engine, a plug-in for Jena that uses the mappings to rewrite Jena API calls to SQL queries against the database and passes query results up to the higher layers of the frameworks.
- D2R Server, an HTTP server that provides a Linked Data view, a HTML view for debugging and a SPARQL Protocol endpoint over the database.

The supported databases include: Oracle, MySQL, PostgreSQL, SQL Server, HSQLDB, Interbase/Firebird. D2RQ can also connect to ODBC data sources (e.g., MS Access using an ODBC-JDBC bridge); however, this has some limitations and is preferred to use a dedicated JDBC driver for the particular database.

D2RQ is Open Source software, which may particularly useful in FOODIE as we may need to access from database sources.

Figure 36 D2RQ architecture

²⁷¹ <http://agropedialabs.iitk.ac.in/>

²⁷² <http://agrovoc.mimos.my:58300/agroTagger/>

²⁷³ <http://hive.nescent.org/indexing.html>

²⁷⁴ <http://maui-indexer.appspot.com/>

²⁷⁵ <http://d2rq.org/>

6.7.2.5 morph-RDB

morph-RDB²⁷⁶ - formerly ODEMapster is an RDB2RDF engine that follows the R2RML specification²⁷⁷. It supports two operational modes:

- Data upgrade, which consists in generating RDF data from a relational database according to the R2RML mapping descriptions.
- Query translation, which allows evaluating SPARQL queries over a virtual RDF dataset, by rewriting those queries into SQL according to the R2RML mapping descriptions.

morph-RDB employs various types of optimisations during the query rewriting process to generate more efficient SQL queries. Some of these optimisations are self-join elimination, subquery elimination, and left-outer join elimination. morph-RDB has been tested with the BSBM synthetic benchmark and has been successfully deployed in various projects .

The supported databases include MySQL, PostgreSQL and MonetDB.

morph-RDB has also been extended to support Google Fusion Tables in a project called morph-GFT²⁷⁸, which translates SPARQL queries posed by users into SQL-like queries that are supported by the GFT API.

It has also been extended to work with a Linked Data Platform implementation (LDP) in a project called morph-LDP²⁷⁹, which exposes relational data as read/write Linked Data for LDP-aware applications, while allowing legacy applications to continue using their relational databases (see Figure 37).

Figure 37 morph-LDP architecture

6.7.2.6 SILK

The Silk-Linking Framework toolkit was developed by Freie Universitat of Berlin, with a clear target on aiming to discover and maintain data links between sources in the Web of Data. These links that connect data sources take the form RDF triples, where the subject of the triple is an URI reference in the namespace of the first dataset, while the object is a URI reference in the other. The property linking both resources is set up by Silk applying discovering rules based on shared identifiers and resource similarity. Silk accesses data sources via the SPARQL protocol and can thus be used to discover links between local and remote data sources.

Silk framework basically has a three part architecture:

- Link discovery engine, which computes links between data sources
- Quality evaluation tool of results
- Protocol for keeping RDF links, even included data sources are subject to changes (Web of Data-Link Maintenance Protocol).

²⁷⁶ <http://mayor2.dia.fi.upm.es/oeg-upm/index.php/en/technologies/315-morph-rdb>

²⁷⁷ <http://www.w3.org/TR/r2rml/>

²⁷⁸ <http://mayor2.dia.fi.upm.es/oeg-upm/index.php/en/technologies/316-morph-gft>

²⁷⁹ <http://mayor2.dia.fi.upm.es/oeg-upm/index.php/en/technologies/331-morph-ldp>

Silks main feature is Silk-Link Specification Language (Silk-LSL), an XML-based language for specifying heuristics for deciding whether a semantic relationship exists between resources of two data sources. These link conditions can apply different similarity metrics to multiple properties of an entity or related entities, which are addressed using a path-based selector language. The implemented metrics include among others string, date, URI and a taxonomic matcher that calculates the semantic distance between two concepts within a concept hierarchy.

6.7.2.7 Tables

TABELS (Tabular Cells) is a tool to bridge the gap between tabular formats and linked data. TABELS is able to process spreadsheets, csv files, but also other tabular formats such as statistical specific ones, analysis tool formats and so on. Moreover, TABELS is more than a transformation tool. It is geared up with data-sensitive front-end widgets to facilitate end-users the exploitation of data.

The tool defines its own DSL (Domain Specific Language) to perform the transformations from data tables to RDF. This language allows describe mappings between tables and graphs and it is formed by three different parts:

- The PREFIX section: to declare the namespaces and prefixes as in the SPARQL language.
- The data tables structure section: to specify how to go through the tables according to four complementary dimensions: file dimension, sheet dimension; row dimension and column dimension. Moreover, through the language it is possible to express the process of data structures by means different kind of statements:
 - Dimension statements: to iterate through the above mentioned dimensions.
 - Conditional statements: to establish a iteration flow correction depending of certain circumstances.
 - Binding statements: to associate values to variables for further utilization.
- The RDF instantiation section: to design the RDF graph model in which variables are instantiated. Graph patterns can be separated and are expressed in N3 syntax.

6.7.2.8 R2R

Developed by Freie Universität a Berlin, R2R is a Java API that targets the data transformation between different vocabularies in the Web of Data. To perform the transformations R2R uses a set of mappings defined in a language similar to SPARQL against a set of input triples. In addition to the input triples and the mappings, the third input is the target vocabulary in which the result is described. The input data can be handled to the transformation engine in the form of file, Jena Model or SPARQL endpoint.

Two different use cases are targeted in R2R:

- Closed use case: A controlled environment where the inputs defined above are given to the transformation engine.
- Global, open use case: In this scenario, both data and transformation are published. When a Linked Data consumer faces unknown vocabularies, it can look up transformations published, thus obtaining data in well-known vocabularies of her after the transformations found are applied with R2R.

6.7.2.9 Other RDFizer tools

An RDFizer is a software or service for converting non-RDF data sources into one or more of the RDF data model serializations (e.g., RDF/XML or N3) for use with RDF tools and integration with other data.

According to SMILE project²⁸⁰, each RDFizer tries to be as specific as possible in identifying the semantics associated with the data that is being converted. For data formats that are already highly structured (e.g., EXIF information in digital pictures or MIME headers in Email messages or method references in Java bytecodes), this is possible without human intervention and the RDFizer has to decide what ontology to use to express that information in RDF. But for data formats where structure exists but the semantics associated with relationships are

²⁸⁰ <http://simile.mit.edu/wiki/RDFizers>

6.8.3 OAuth

OAuth²⁸⁵ is an open authorization standard. The main assumption of OAuth is to reduce the knowledge of client about the authorization mechanisms on server side. The server provides the single-use token to the client, by which the client could authorize himself on third party software.

6.8.4 HTTPS/SSL

The HTTPS²⁸⁶ is the encrypted version of HTTP standard. The encryption is done via SSL protocol. The SSL and its sucesor TLS²⁸⁷ ensure a secure channel between client and server.

6.9 Marketplace and e-commerce

6.9.1 OpenCart

OpenCart²⁸⁸ has an extensive amount of features that gives users a strong hold over the customization of their store. It has order management and multiple payment gateways already built in. A shop can be created without so much technical knowledge: simply install, select template, add products and ready to accept orders.

Main features:

- OpenCart is a **module-based system, which** allows users to easily extend the functionality for their needs. It comes with 11 modules (Bestsellers, cart, category, featured, latest, specials, manufactures, information, google analytics and google talk). Existing modules can be manipulated with the Layout, Position, Status, and Sort Order tools in Modules.
- The framework includes some **payment gateways** but there can be added new ones (extension).
- The framework includes some **shipping methods** but there can be also added new ones (extension).
- Three different types of **sales report** but new ones can be added downloading them from the extension section.
- Minimum requirements on the server: Apache or Windows IIS, PHP 5 and MySQL.
- OpenCart follows the **MVC** architecture.
- Support different templates and even the style of the own shop could be migrated. Users can also create their own theme.
- OpenCart functionality, as well as look and feel, is all controlled by modules and themes. If users do not find the functionality needed in the store, they can often add it as a 3rd party extension.
- There are many extension modules²⁸⁹ that could be downloaded (for free or for a certain amount of money).
- The storefront could be customized in the admin panel: the administrator can change the position of the products, disable categories, edit prices and descriptions, and upload banners.
- If some functionality is missing, an OpenCart module could be added. The new module needs to follow the MVCL design pattern to create the admin and frontend parts (it is well-documented). The easiest way to create a new module is to follow the skeleton that the DIY Module Builder²⁹⁰ provides.
- It is released under GNU GPL License.

6.9.2 Broadleaf Commerce

Broadleaf Commerce^{291 292} is an open source Java eCommerce platform based on the Spring Framework. The domain, service, and presentation layer components in Broadleaf Commerce are all fully customizable. Broadleaf

²⁸⁵ <http://oauth.net/>

²⁸⁶ <http://tools.ietf.org/html/rfc2818>

²⁸⁷ <http://tools.ietf.org/html/rfc5246>

²⁸⁸ <http://www.opencart.com/>

²⁸⁹ <http://www.opencart.com/index.php?route=extension/extension>

²⁹⁰ <http://opencart.hostjars.com/creating-opencart-modules>

²⁹¹ <http://www.broadleafcommerce.org>

²⁹² Demo instance: <http://demo.broadleafcommerce.org>

Commerce was designed to handle near linear scaling using commodity hardware. It comes in a free community edition, distributed under Apache 2.0 license, and in a commercial enterprise edition.

- One of the key advantages of this platform is that it is based on well-known technologies including Java, Spring, Hibernate, Solr and Jersey.
- No foreseen disadvantages

Main features:

- It provides a flexible framework designed to allow users to extend any Broadleaf entity, add their own custom entities, and replace or extend any service, DAO, or controller. Users can do all of this without changing the core Broadleaf libraries or source. This is possible because Broadleaf Commerce provides a unique application context merge process that allows users to override any default configurations or components and to extend or add new data entities.
- The free version (Community Edition) of the framework is declared to offer the following functionality out-of-the-box: Cart Operations, Checkout, Offers & Discounts, Personalized Ad Targeting, Promo Codes, Content Management, Product Information Management, Product Options, Multiple Currencies, Multi-Channel, Multi-Device, Multiple Languages (localization), Basic Search, Smart Search & Browse, Category Management, SEO Management, Order Status & Tracking, Basic Order & Payment History, Registration Management, Account Management, Support Provided (Forums and Documentation).
- The Enterprise Edition, for \$50,000/year, provides everything from Community plus: Workflow & Approval, Sandbox Environments, Custom Fields, Performance Improvements, 24x7 Professional Support, 4 Production Java Virtual Machines, Advanced Price Lists.
- Which version for whom?
The community edition is suggested for companies that forecast less than \$2M/year in web transactions but expect to grow. It is especially recommended for those who desire a clear path to upgrading on a leading edge technology platform.
The enterprise edition is recommended for companies with over \$2M/year in web transactions. It is especially recommended to those who regularly push site updates with multiple teams involved in the process.

6.9.3 Apache OFBiz

Apache OFBiz (The Apache Open For Business Project)^{293 294} is an open source enterprise automation software project licensed under the Apache License Version 2.0, including Open Source ERP (Enterprise Resource Planning), Open Source CRM (Customer Relationship Management), **Open Source E-Business / E-Commerce**, Open Source SCM (Supply Chain Management), Open Source MRP (Manufacturing Resources Planning), Open Source CMMS/EAM (Maintenance Management System/Enterprise Asset Management), Open Source POS (Point Of Sale), and so on.

- Advantages: very powerful framework with big potential – ready for many different use cases.
- Disadvantages: seems a heavy framework that needs a lot of effort to adjust it to specific requirements and to achieve operational state of a service.

Main features:

- Apache OFBiz offers a great deal of functionality, including: advanced e-commerce, catalog management, promotion & pricing management, order management (sales & purchase), customer management (part of general party management), warehouse management, fulfillment (auto stock moves, batched pick, pack & ship), accounting (invoice, payment & billing accounts, fixed assets), manufacturing management, general work effort management (events, tasks, projects, requests, etc), content management (for product content, web sites, general content, blogging, forums, etc), a maturing Point Of Sales (POS) module using a rich client interface, and much more all in an open source package!
- Open For Business (OFBiz) is a suite of enterprise applications built on a common architecture using

²⁹³ <http://ofbiz.apache.org/apache-ofbiz-project-overview.html>

²⁹⁴ <http://www.ofbizdemo.com/ecommerce/>

common data, logic and process components. The loosely coupled nature of the applications makes these components easy to understand, extend and customize.

- The most basic components in OFBiz are Entities and Services. Basic entities correspond to actual database structures. There is also a type of entity called a "view-entity" that can be used to create a virtual entity from other entities to combine sets of fields by joining other entities together.
- Web Framework and XML Mini-Languages. There are many useful tools in the OFBiz Core Framework that address points of difficulty in web, client-server and peer-to-peer based enterprise applications. A tool exists for simplifying the use of flat data files making it easier to integrate with legacy systems. Various tools exist for organizing and structuring web-based content and applications with a flexible separation of logic and presentation. These tools along with the standard J2EE and other Java tools make it easy for the system to communicate with human users and other systems.

6.9.4 BigFish

BigFish²⁹⁵ ²⁹⁶ is a solution that leverages the power of the Open for Business (OFBiz mentioned above) open source project. OFBiz has been downloaded hundreds of thousands of times and is the foundation for thousands of eCommerce and ERP solutions. It includes all the features necessary to quickly build a revenue generating website. BigFish is a framework with all the necessary functionality to start generating revenue online, and that can also be customized to add additional functionality if desired.

- Advantages: It is based on very powerful OFBiz framework but adjusted towards simplified installation and maintenance.
- Disadvantages: Risk that customization may involve big costs as in case of pure OFBiz framework.

Main Features:

- Registration of customers and CRM: Functions for customers to register and complete a Contact Us form; admin module functions to view and manage customers and activity.
- eCommerce purchases and order management functions: Functions for customers to purchase and check-out; admin module functions to view and manage Orders
- Home Page: Manage all aspects of the home page by leveraging BigFish and maintaining user content. Complete flexibility controlled by business experts from the users' company.
- SEO: User friendly URL's, auto-generated or user specified SEO tags. Applies to Category, Product and Static Pages.
- Navigation functionalities, including: hover over drop-downs, expandable selections, "Mega Menus", possibility to include images.
- Home Page "carousel". Maintain generic content in Content-Library. Include content in a carousel display as Home Page Spots.
- Categorization: Browse by type, brand or by how-you-like-it.
- Product listing pages: displayed and sorted based on the business requirements, Web 2.0 Quicklook feature.
- Faceted navigation. BigFish is pre-integrated with Apache SOLR. The indexing capability allows for comprehensive faceted navigation options managed by the business experts.
- Product detail page. Designed and implemented to highlight the key features of the products. Inventory aware capability to show out-of-stock for certain items. Include Recently Viewed.
- Site search. Powerful search features using Apache SOLR. Includes integration with Jazzy for spell-check. Powerful but simple to use "synonym" capability.
- Up sell and cross sell. Flexible relationships to provide you-may-also-like, complementary and alternate products.
- My account. Complete functionality supporting sign-up, forgotten password. Manage a complete address book for shipping and billing information.
- Check out. Includes Guest checkout. Options for single page checkout. Pre-integrated with Cybersource.

²⁹⁵ <http://bigfish.solveda.com>

²⁹⁶ Demo instance: <http://bigfish.solveda.com/bfDemo.html>

- Paypal capable.
- Static pages. Maintain your content. Build an unlimited number of static pages for "About Us", "Return Policies" and much more.
- International support: country Formatting (date, time), currency.

6.9.5 Shopizer

Shopizer²⁹⁷ is a complete java shopping cart and e-commerce content management software (CMS) built from ground up with performance in mind on a strong technology stack.

- Advantages: good technical documentation
- Disadvantages: Viral license (GPLv2)

Main features:

- Enables to create high end web store fronts in minutes and turn existing web sites to full e-commerce systems without specific technical skills
- Provides essential e-commerce tools for selling online: shopping cart, inventory management, payment and shipping, order management, online invoicing, e-commerce tracking.
- Compliant with JEE 1.5 and above.
- Works with Oracle, MySQL and HyperSQL databases.
- Ready for Websphere, Apache Tomcat, Jetty, Oracle Weblogic and JBoss application servers.
- Includes a set of tag libraries in the view layer exposing business entities and CMS APIs to JSP pages. 90% of the catalogue is built using Struts 2 tag libraries. JQuery plugins are used for extending UI with rich features such as modal windows and photos viewers. DWR library is used to facilitate Ajax calls with business components.
- Struts action classes are MVC entries to all functionalities, which use the service layer to create transactions and query data from the database. Shopizer uses the concept of 'module' for decoupling with the code and easing the integration with plug and play pieces of functionality. Integration with 3rd party systems such as shipping quotes and payment systems are implemented using its module framework.
- The system heavily uses Spring IOC and Transaction annotations. Business objects are Hibernate pojoes retrieved from an associated DAO, all grouped in a service facade exposed to Struts action classes and modules. Shopizer supports HSQLDB, Oracle and MySQL databases.
- The system is built on Struts 2, Hibernate and Spring. It uses Hibernate Search / Lucene for indexing and searching. Apache Commons libraries are used for doing common routines. Reports are generated using Jasper reports. JQuery ui and ajax are heavily used on the UI as well as DWR and Struts2-jQuery plug-in.
- Catalogue/Inventory: Multiple merchants, Boutique template, Multiple languages, Inventory management, Read only product options, Priced product options, Search products, Customized content (e-commerce CMS), Search engine friendly URLs, Up sell / Cross sell
- Shopping cart/Checkout: Standalone shopping cart, digital downloads, mini-cart in boutique pages
- Pricing: 1 to many prices per item, discounts, time based promotions
- Payment options: Money order / COD, PayPal Express Checkout, AuthorizeNet, Psigate, Moneris, Beanstream
- Shipping options: Fedex, UPS, USPS, Canada Post
- Order management: Capture payment, refund payment, print shipping label, PDF Invoices, customer notification by email, customer management, order reports
- Online invoicing: Send email invoice, invoice template, invoice order flow, PDF Invoices
- API: Customer authentication, customer management Web Service, customer information, Google APIs (IP Location, Maps...), Google Analytics integration, Facebook integration.

6.9.6 JadaSite

JadaSite^{298 299} is an open source content management and e-commerce system. Its philosophy is to ensure that

²⁹⁷ <http://www.shopizer.com/>, <http://shopizer.sourceforge.net>

²⁹⁸ <http://www.jadasite.com/>

JadaSite is feature-rich, easy to use and maintain, and does not require an IT Team for support and to make changes to the system.

- Advantages: easy to maintain and prepared for 3rd party modifications.
- Disadvantages: viral license (GPLv3).

Main features:

- Platform and Technology: Open source 100% Java based, including AJAX interface. It can be deployed on Unix, Linux and Windows servers, and on any J2EE application servers including Apache Tomcat, Sun GlassFish, BEA Weblogic, IBM Websphere, etc. It is compatible with MySQL, SQLServer, Oracle database server, etc., and can be easily load balanced for greater fault tolerance and scalability
- Design: Template-based, supporting easy customization of existing templates, easy configuration of items on home page. It includes a template editor to create or modify existing template with ease, and allows uploading plug-and-play templates.
- Security: Full HTTPS/SSL support with secure administrative access, including password-protected administrative access, multiple administrator logon and role based administrator security. All sensitive information is encrypted in database.
- Payment: Compatible with multiple payment gateways, supporting the usage of different gateways by currency, payment processing at time of sale or during order fulfilment, CVV2 (Security code) and cash on delivery.
- Shipping costs and tax can be calculated based on many criteria (e.g. fixed, percentage, type of product, geographic location, country etc.).
- Marketing: Search engine optimized; Coupon support; Fixed dollar amount discount; Percentage of dollar amount discount; Discount over order amount discount; Free shipping; Enable and disable coupon by start and end date; Customer order history; Top rated items; Shows customer comments and rating; Featured product on home page
- General (selected features only): multi-lingual; multi-currency;

6.9.7 Conclusion

There are many frameworks available on the market. A final choice of a specific framework for marketplace implementation should be based on specific requirements that arise during further works. The analyzed frameworks differ in many dimensions - including technology (Java vs. PHP), license, maturity, available documentation and functionality. Technology should be selected based on skills of the development team. License is a topic for Intellectual Property management activity as some of the frameworks are licensed under GPL, which is a so-called viral license. Maturity of the project is important when it comes to support the developers (bug fixes, feature requests). Similarly about documentation, which may really slow implementation, works down when it is made negligently or does not exist.

6.10 Notification mechanisms

PUSH technologies allow the establishment of client-server communications where the server initiates the request for a given transaction, as opposed to PULL technologies where the client needs to initiate each communication process. These technologies are becoming increasingly popular in the mobile development arena and are frequently used to send server-originated notifications to multiple devices.

The main difficulty associated to the creation of a push notification service is to deal with the diversity of the existing notification mechanisms on the market.

The most relevant PUSH technologies are the following:

- **GCM (Google Cloud Messaging)**³⁰⁰: GCM is a PUSH notifications service developed by Google. This service is used by Android applications and also as a communication service between Google Chrome

²⁹⁹ Demo instance: <http://demo1.jadasite.com>

³⁰⁰ <http://developer.android.com/google/gcm/index.html>

browser and its extensions and applications. This service replaces the old PUSH service used in previous versions of Android which was known as C2DM (Android Cloud to Device Messaging).

- **APNS (Apple Push Notification Service)**³⁰¹: APNS is the service created by Apple with the goal of sending and receiving PUSH notifications between their devices. It is available in every Apple mobile device since iOS 3.0. This service could also be used in Apple laptops since version 10.7 (Mac OS X Lion). Besides, since iOS 10.9 (Mac OS X Mavericks), this service is used to send notifications to the Safari browser.
- **MPNS (Microsoft Push Notification Service)**: It is the PUSH notifications service created by Microsoft and which is used by Windows Phone devices. This service is available since version 7.1.
- **BPNS (Blackberry Push Notifications Service)**³⁰²: It is the notifications service created by Blackberry to be used in their devices. Blackberry was the brand that gave relevance to this kind of services in the origin of PUSH technologies.
- **WNS (Windows Notification Service)**³⁰³: It is the PUSH notifications service developed by Microsoft to be used with the Windows 8 system.
- **ADM (Amazon Device Messaging)**³⁰⁴: It is the PUSH service notification developed by Amazon to be used with their Kindle Fire devices.
- **HTML5 Server Sent Events (SSE)**³⁰⁵ / **EventSource**: Although it is not exactly a PUSH technology, the goal of this one is the same: send information from a server to a client without an explicit request from the client. This technology is part of HTML5 and it works in all the major browsers and can be adapted to several old browsers.
- **XMPP**³⁰⁶ (**Extensible Messaging and Presence Protocol**) is a communications protocol for message-oriented middleware based on XML. Designed to be extensible, the protocol has also been used for publish-subscribe systems, signalling for VoIP, video, file transfer, gaming, Internet of Things applications such as the smart grid, and social networking services.
- **PubSubHubbub**³⁰⁷ is an open protocol for distributed publish/subscribe communication on the Internet. Initially designed to extend the Atom (and RSS) protocols for data feeds, the protocol can be applied to any data type (e.g. text, pictures, audio, video, etc.) as long as it is accessible via HTTP. Its main purpose is to provide real-time notifications of changes, which improves upon the typical situation where a client periodically polls the feed server at some arbitrary interval. In this way, PubSubHubbub provides pushed HTTP notifications without requiring clients to spend resources on polling for changes.

The next table summarizes some of the main PUSH notification mechanisms:

Mechanism	Platform	Payload (bytes)
GCM (previously C2DM)	Android	4096
APNS	iOS	256
MPNS	Windows Phone	3072
WNS	Windows 8	5120

³⁰¹

<https://developer.apple.com/library/ios/documentation/NetworkingInternet/Conceptual/RemoteNotificationsPG/Chapters/ApplePushService.html>

³⁰² http://developer.blackberry.com/develop/platform_services/push_overview.html

³⁰³ <http://msdn.microsoft.com/en-us/library/windows/apps/hh913756.aspx>

³⁰⁴ <https://developer.amazon.com/public/apis/engage/device-messaging>

³⁰⁵ http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Server-sent_events

³⁰⁶ <http://tools.ietf.org/html/rfc6120> and <http://tools.ietf.org/html/rfc6121>

³⁰⁷ <https://code.google.com/p/pubsubhubbub/>

ADM	Kindle Fire	4096
BPNS	BlackBerry	Unlimited
SSE/EventSource	Web Browsers	Unlimited

6.11 Reporting and visualization components

6.11.1 JReport

JReport³⁰⁸ is developed by Jinfonet Software, a provider of data visualization and embedded reporting solutions for the enterprise. JReport is a Java-based reporting platform that embeds into any application, while delivering reporting, dashboards and analysis via the Web and mobile devices. JReport's approach to design, deployment and interaction simplifies the work for both developers and users

6.11.2 Jasper Studio

Jaspersoft Studio³⁰⁹ is the free, open source, eclipse-based report designer for JasperReports and JasperReports Server. Create very sophisticated layouts containing charts, images, subreports, crosstabs and much more. Access your data through JDBC, TableModels, JavaBeans, XML, Hibernate, CSV, and custom sources. Then publish your reports as PDF, RTF, XML, XLS, CSV, HTML, XHTML, text, DOCX, or OpenOffice.

6.11.3 Crossfilter

Crossfilter³¹⁰ is a JavaScript library for exploring large multivariate datasets in the browser. Crossfilter supports extremely fast (<30ms) interaction with coordinated views, even with datasets containing a million or more records; we built it to power analytics for Square Register, allowing merchants to slice and dice their payment history fluidly.

Since most interactions only involve a single dimension, and then only small adjustments are made to the filter values, incremental filtering and reducing is significantly faster than starting from scratch. Crossfilter uses sorted indexes (and a few bit-twiddling hacks) to make this possible, dramatically increasing the performance of live histograms and top-K lists.

6.11.4 Highcharts

Highcharts³¹¹ is a charting library written in pure JavaScript, offering an easy way of adding interactive charts to your web site or web application. Highcharts currently supports line, spline, area, areaspline, column, bar, pie, scatter, angular gauges, arearange, areasplinerange, columnrange, bubble, box plot, error bars, funnel, waterfall and polar chart types.

It works in all modern mobile and desktop browsers including the iPhone/iPad and Internet Explorer from version 6. On iOS and Android, multitouch support provides a seamless user experience. Standard browsers use SVG for the graphics rendering. In legacy Internet Explorer graphics are drawn using VML.

Through a full API you can add, remove and modify series and points or modify axes at any time after chart creation. Numerous events supply hooks for programming against the chart. In combination with jQuery, MooTools or Prototype's Ajax API, this opens for solutions like live charts constantly updating with values from the server, user supplied data and more.

³⁰⁸ <http://www.jinfonet.com/>

³⁰⁹ <http://community.jaspersoft.com/project/jaspersoft-studio>

³¹⁰ <http://square.github.io/crossfilter/>

³¹¹ <http://www.highcharts.com/products/highcharts/>

6.12 Precision Farming systems

6.12.1 Prefarm

PREFARM® is a running system of data collection, data processing and final recommendation on GIS platform in crop production (Precision farming). The partial elements of the system **PREFARM®** are used today on an area of several hundred thousand hectares, not only in the Czech Republic, but also the neighboring countries. It is a dynamic system which is constantly developed in accordance with the latest knowledge in agronomic and technical area.

Field Record (diary) is very simple software computer instrument for easy input all set of information about fields which were using during the working operations (=records of data, informatics). Required values are archived and it can be worked with them anytime you want. Software can assort data for agronomist's needs, but for control groups as well. Prefarm diary is connected with Prefarm MapServer application, we can send information between application and we can save database up-dating.

PREFARM Map Server is a global information system, which can use users of Prefarm®. They can work with information from their fields in a Geographical information environment without using software for GIS and without perfect knowledge of GIS environment. The internet connection is required only and an internet viewer. Prefarm MapServer is not only for precision farming, it is for reasonable managing plant production. Prefarm MapServer is a tool which user has available GIS basic tools.

Main points of system **PREFARM®**

Easy work with data in central database (office, field) – Transparent of data analysis (maps and tables) – Easy data access (map view, tabs, statistic, new notes) – Multifunction level of using in farm or company (chairman, lawyer, crop manager, driver) – Traceability/complete notes (crop plan, fertilizers using....) – Possibility of another database connection (WMS, cadastral maps...)

1. Data collection

- Basic measuring by GPS (field boundary, soil sample points and other important thinks to create GIS environment for first data processing) Field information, point information, field boundaries are recorded with H-GIS software as the vehicle travels around field.

2. Data processing

- Soil test analysis
- Soil test maps
- Yield maps
- Soil electro conductivity maps
- Application maps
- Recommendation

Figure 39 The soil sampling map

Figure 40 The spatial development of the soil nutrient (a sample of the one of the set maps)

3. Data using

- Farm management
- Crop rotation planning
- Variable application of Phosphor, Potash, Magnesium, Nitrogen, Lime and other.
- Variable seedling

Figure 41 Prefarm data management system

6.12.2 DokuPlant

The system has to reflect at every time the three important dimensions within the rural area. Those dimensions are:

- Where? Where is the plot?
 - When? When have they been cultivated? When which action has been done?
 - What? What is growing? What has been done on the plot?
- Where are all the plots with a certain crop?

Geographic information systems:

The geographic information system WinGIS, is an easy to use and efficient GIS software with wide geographic application possibilities and facilities. The integration of the online map data as „embedded Module“ provides the access to worldwide available map data like satellite/aerial images, road/terrain maps and geocoding functionalities. Data exchange interfaces to/from other GIS/CAD systems and database support (WinGIS internal database or external databases) are integral parts of the software package. Images as e.g. Microsoft Bing Maps (www.bing.com/maps) in the form of orthoimages, embedded into all PROGIS technologies either online or downloaded allow to start up work for every advisor immediately. Also other maps available in the country can be used as well and also crunched with Bing Maps or worked out with local experts like RuralOSM (Open Street Map) will be implemented during the project phase. Based on that GIS system there are about 20 applications supporting agriculture, forestry, environmental caretaking and risk management as well as the integrated chain-partners. Open interfaces allow the linkage to existing other technologies: Samples are agro-sensor-stations, mobile devices, RFID technology, GPRS or UMTS communication etc.

Time management:

The entire system has to build in a way that also the time dimension has to be displayed dynamically. Whereby the user has the chance, at any time, to go back in the history as well as look forward in the future. This feature will not only display it will also affect the other two dimensions like graphic and attribute information. With one mouse click in the present, past or future the system will display What? Where? and When?

The time management for the future has to give to the end-user the chance to better plan and simulate in order to know economic and ecological the answer for his enterprise.

Display of the time:

The time has to be displayed dynamically so it is up to the user if he wants to display one day, three years or one month. (zoom into the time management)

Time management and resources:

The time management has also a strong impact on the other resource e.g. prices of the crop, price of the gas etc.. Which means for example the prices can be filled in from every user and are valid for a certain time (day, week, month, year etc...).

The **regional adaption** of PROGIS software technology “DokuPlant” is divided three parts:

1. Ortho-images
2. Expert database
3. Activity based cultivation models

The AGROOffice Admin-Version, which is part of DokuPlant – the basic documentation tool, is used for adapting and modifying the expert database of DokuPlant. System can be used by farmers, group of farmers, farm advisory services, machinery cooperatives and other organisations which adapt and modify the whole expert database at once and provide it to a number of farmer, region or country.

The expert database includes the following contents to their local request:

- Crops and varieties for crops
 - Crops will be defined with the following main property: time (from seeding to harvesting), etc.
- Resources including prices/times/contents like
 - Agricultural machines
 - seeds
 - available fertilizers
 - permitted plant protectors
- Yearly cultivation activities for crops
- Production methods

Different Production Methods give you the possibility of building different models for one crop and using them in one simulation file. By using different combinations of production methods, the user can define a huge number of

new crop models, always using the existing crops.

How many production methods should be introduced?

At least ten production methods that stand for common variations in cultivation (direct seeding, extensive plant protection, intensive fertilisation...) should be introduced. More than that, five production methods (Variante1, Variante2, Variante3, Variante4, Variante5) must be introduced, they can be renamed by the user later on.

Which production method should be the default method?

The default production method of a crop should be "empty" or "none", so no production method is assigned. That means, of course, that the crops in the main simulation file must be simulated without any assigned production method.

How can the simulation file contain more than one model of one crop?

First of all, make sure, if you really want to offer more than one model in the simulation file, or if you want to build one simulation file and other simulation files for other models. When a crop has different combinations of production methods, it is always treated like a different crop.

- Cultivation restrictions
- Nutrient values
- Public data like postcodes, communes, banks, etc.
- Extras like currencies
- Activity based cultivation models including their resources

Activity based cultivation models including their resources:

After filled expert data information you can define activity based cultivation models. Different Production Methods give you the possibility of building different models for one crop and using them in one simulation file. By using different combinations of production methods, the user can define a huge number of new crop models, always using the existing crops.

Example:

Add a crop from the selective defined crop list into the simulation window with the time management. After that you have to assign the production method, which will give you the opportunity to define different cultivation models by using the same crop.

Assign the needed activities in reference time and the appropriate resources to each activity.

CO2 approach:

On the basis of such nutrient balancing principle a model for CO₂-balancing can be designed. To each activity respectively resources can be assigned CO₂ values. Appropriate preliminaries with scientists were affected to provide basis data for each activity in consideration of natural conditions within energy and CO₂ effects as expert data. Each activity e.g. driving with tractor, fertilizing of NPK on a field with appropriate size and soil value that will be assigned with appropriate CO₂-data, a CO₂ input/output balance can be generated provable and traceable at any time at arable land. These expenses represents the same expenses you need for planning, business calculations, proof of insurance, documentation for logistic partners, subsidy accounting, precision farming etc. That means no additional expenses excluding once

- creating the expert model for CO₂ balance
- adaptation of that expert model with local partners

The main advantage for such expert model at PROGIS software is that preliminary and also post calculation analyses like CO₂ can be generated at any time for a holding/region/land. Comparisons to conventional methods can be calculated automatically by using and optimizing the production method in view of using such CO₂ models

(e.g. precision farming plus fertilization optimization, precision farming plus plant protection optimization, precision farming plus transport optimization etc.).

That method can lead to higher CO₂-sequestrating and/or to a lower CO₂-output regarding a standard situation. That CO₂ optimized situation is based on a farmer investment, thereby optimizing CO₂ situation.

It can be also a base for carbon credit financing for developing countries by using the same model and technology. The basis will be still the comparison between actual to optimized model for reducing the energy intensive agricultural production sustainable. The technology allows it with few clicks to run variants and at the end to decide for the optimum variant.

Additional possibilities logistic, smart- and/or virtual farming, environment management etc.:

Advantaging aspects and effects regarding group of farms approach like logistic, smart farming, virtual farming, environment-/ risk management application can enlarge the use cases and give for groups of farmers an additional advantage for creating new values with the setup of new services to get additional income. To realize such approach it needs one platform for all parties concerned (farmers, agricultural experts, advisors, service providers, etc.) and the technology will work only within a large number of supporting the concept and can be provided at reasonable price. The uniform access for all parties especially for small scale farmers will succeed the using of precision farming management because of the cost-benefit factor. That platform serves for all parties as communication and service portal.

Logistics is the yet largest single PROGIS project that runs already for several years with 40.000 farmers, 6 factories, 100.000 sugar beet fields and many other fields in the meantime as well as hundreds of machines organized by 25 machine cooperatives. All information is permanent online and the dispatcher can influence the process at any time to optimize the system.

Key question at the installation and setup of the system was not only the technology including communication, central unit to be replaced within the FOODIE project from one server and mobile GIS solutions but the takeholder cooperation and the business model were also of highest importance. Within FOODIE project several possible business-models for the whole processes have to be evaluated and integrated that allows a flexible setup serving the different customer groups.

Precision farming technology:

The basic principle of precision farming technology is an exact positional controlling of each cultivation activity like tilling, plant protection, fertilization, harvesting, watering by using precision farming technology. The whole process of precision farming calls for an amount of data to be collected and analyzed, which enable the control of the whole process.

It has to be evaluated if it is profitable for a farmer to use specific precision farming for his fields in whole. The following three key influencing factors are obtain data, data interpretation and the management strategy.

Obtain data:

The base for significant precision farming management strategies is the availability of data.

It has to be evaluated if there are geographic information (see links) like ortho- or satellite images in an adequate quality (high resolution) form public or private sources available. Use the orthoimages to identify the actual cultivated area, define characteristic areas such as sandy areas, poor drainage areas, weed and disease problem areas, wet areas, livestock usage etc. An alternative practical solution are public orthoimages that are directly embedded at GIS applications.

To obtain cultivation practice records an automatic collection of process data over a central data management will be advantageous for implementing precision farming. All relevant data of an ongoing process will be automatically documented and handled on a central data management. A system can automatically

document in connection with GPS and a standardized communication between machine and accessory equipment all cultivation activities on a plot on a small scale basis and in georeferenced way. All that determination of position information will be connected to data records. Using sensor for monitoring the cultivation (see links – soil science) or for optimizing the effective allocation (see links – crop information) and right time (see links - Meteorology) of resources. Another way to determine the crop information (see links) like yield maps, chlorophyll maps etc. is using satellite information.

Data interpretation:

For data interpretation it is essential to use a geographic information and analyse system. Advisors or service providers that collect, handle, analyze and interpret data use for the collected data GIS programs, which overlay geo-referenced information for further interpretation.

In future it will be necessary to make interpretation over a wide range of maps (see links – geography, soil science, meteorology, crop information etc.). Such a systems can handle all wanted maps in that way that a numerous number (maximum 4) of maps are loaded and displayed on a GIS based system, whereby only one map is aktiv for editing at time. Contains a map only a number of single attributes (measured data) it is possible via ISO modell to interpolate or to spread homogenously the attributes on the whole area (e.g. field, plot). If the map have a colour scale but no values, the attribute spreading can be carried out over import or assignment of two or more reference values. Also maps with characteristic information like last years yield, heavy weed infestation where yields are reduced and characteristic areas including specific attributes are useful for further decision making.

The system have to support to find a solution by interpreting and comparison of homogeneous and heterogeneous data distribution (e.g. in yield maps). To verify the reasons for inhomogeneous in maps by on-site inspection will lead to interpreting the variability within a map.

For creating a recommendation map the following two possibilities are available:

- Create a map via ocular comparison with each existing map and make a manual assignment to each defined management zone (colour scale area).
- The management zones including the calculation of value will be created via entering of mathematical operations (enter formula).

The recommendation map is created by appropriate totals formation for each area (field, plot). Furthermore the recommendation including geographic provides at the same time the basis for carrying out of VRT (variable rate technology).

Management strategy:

The management strategy in precision farming implies to increase the productivity and economic returns including reduced impact on the environment by optimizing cost and ecological effects in crop production. The evaluation of the right management strategy is extensive since each farm is unique and only the one solution does not exist. Furthermore the profitability review and the needed adaption is an ongoing process of a used precision farming management strategy.

To create a management strategy it has to be evaluated if there is an error in the data collection process, the data is accurate, the data from one year is sufficient enough, additional data is needed, the decision-making have influenced succeeding yield and if the creating management strategy can established on allocated data.

At present management strategies are based on one specific aspect, in general according to amount highest cost centre (fertilization and plant protection). It will be started by evaluating the data like soil and crop characteristic (ground survey, sensor, remote sensing etc.) within a field/plot. The data interpretation is realized by classification of management zones (nutrient zones with crop potentials, pest infestation). The management strategy is based on recommendation map and will be put into practice by machines and accessory equipments which support the adjusting dosing of resources to the location specific need (seed, plant protection, fertilizer, water etc.) through the variable rate technology.

Fine tune the strategy by intergrating the optimal time for the activity that boosts the potential of economic return and limit pest infestation. Prospective management strategies have to focus on timely operations.

An objective have to be a holistic approach. Each cultivation process will be scanned including external influences (like weather, diseases, timely rainfalls, sufficient drain season and hours of sunshine, climate etc.), advantaging aspects and effects regarding group of farms approach like logistic, smart farming, virtual farming, environment-/riskmanagment application. To realize such approach it needs one platform for all parties concerned (farmers, agricultural experts, advisors, service providers, etc.) and the technology will work only within a large number of supporting the concept and can be provided at reasonable price. The uniform access for all parties especially for small scale farmers will succeed the using of precision farming management because of the cost-benefit factor. That platform serves for all parties as communication and service portal.

The web platform provides the geographie (see links from private/public organisations) expert know how data (see links) including the authority input (see links) through connecting with FMIS for farmers documentation application. In retourn it receives the production specific information from the farmers. The platform can be used from public/private service providers or advisors in connection with further information like soil science (see links), meteorology (see links) and crop information (see links) provided form public/private organisations for data interpretation. A further approach for the unique platform is to supply with expert models. Expert models for e.g. activity based cultivation models, environment and risk management, time management for setting an activity etc. and a expert model which combines existing defined expert models. Expert models the decision support system for more comprehensive management strategy evaluation. That allows to work out various economic scenarios for the management strategy depending on demand and problem.

7 Sensors and communication protocols

7.1 Sensors

A **sensor** is a device that measures a physical quantity and converts it into a signal which can be read by an observer or by an instrument. There exist many kinds of sensors for surveillance and intrusion detection, such as infrared, other optical, microwave-based, or other types. They, for example, video cameras, can be effectively used to support manned surveillance. There are also video-based systems that sense changes in the image and will trigger an alert. Since every sensor used for this kind of applications can be characterised by its location coordinates (changeable) and a time component, the spatial extension and near-real-time availability of sensor-originated information layers in geospatial applications create a great potential.

Sensors are most commonly used to make quantifiable measurements, as opposed to qualitative detection or presence sensing. For the sensor selection there are four criteria:

- What we need to measure, this influenced type of sensors, sensors could measure almost anything, but every phenomena need different type of sensors
- In which environment we will measure, there are different need on outdoor and indoor sensors, and also there are specific needs on sensors working in extreme conditions
- What is required accuracy of measurement
- The question, if the whole system is calibrated or certified

These four aspects could have influence on selection of sensors, but also on the cost of sensors.

Every sensor is described by next characteristics:

- Transfer Function - the functional relationship between physical input signal and electrical output signal
- Sensitivity - relationship between input physical signal and output electrical signal
- Span or Dynamic Range - range of input physical signals that may be converted to electrical signals by the sensor
- Accuracy or Uncertainty - largest expected error between actual and ideal output signals
- Hysteresis - width of the expected error in terms of the measured quantity
- Nonlinearity - maximum deviation from a linear transfer function over the specified dynamic range
- Noise - sensors produce some output noise in addition to the output signal
- Resolution - minimum detectable signal fluctuation
- Bandwidth - response times to an instantaneous change in physical signal

When we are speaking about sensors, we usually consider both part of sensors and transducer, a *sensor* is a device that receives a signal or stimulus and responds with an electrical signal, while a *transducer* is a converter of one type of energy into another. From a signal conditioning viewpoint it is useful to classify sensors as either active or passive. An active sensor requires an external source of excitation. A passive (or self-generating) sensor generates their own electrical output signal without requiring external voltages or currents.

7.2 Wireless Sensors networks (WSN)

The future utilization of sensors technologies will be mainly based on Wireless Sensors Network which is an emerging technology made up from tiny, wireless sensors or “motes.” Eventually, these devices will be smart enough to talk with other sensors yet small enough to fit on the head of a pin. Each mote is a tiny computer with a power supply, one or more sensors, and a communication system. One is the network independent module Smart Transducer Interface Module (STIM) that contains the transducers, its signal conditioning circuitry and a standard interface. The other is a network specific module Network Capable Application Processor (NCAP) that implements the interface to the desired control network and also implements the standard interface of the transducer module. Sensor networks are receiving a significant attention because of their many potential civilian and military applications. The design of sensor networks faces a number of challenges resulting from very demanding requirements on one side, such as high reliability of the decision taken by the network and robustness to node failure, and very limited resources on the other side, such as energy, bandwidth, and node complexity.

Sensor Network Systems provide a novel paradigm for managing, modelling and supporting complex systems requiring massive data gathering, with pervasive and persistent detection/monitoring capabilities. It is not therefore surprising that in recent years, a growing emphasis has been steered toward the employment of sensor networks in various technological fields: e.g. aerospace, environment monitoring, homeland security, smart buildings. A significant amount of resources has been allocated for national (USA, France, Germany) and international (e.g. European Commission) research programs targeted at developing innovative methodologies and emerging technologies in different application fields of wireless sensor network. The main features that a sensor network should have are:

- each node should have a very low power consumption, the capability of recharging its battery or scavenging energy from the environment, and very limited processing capabilities;
- each node should be allowed to go in stand-by mode (to save as much battery as possible) without severely degrading the connectivity of the whole network and without requiring complicated re-routing strategies;
- the estimation/measurement capabilities of the system as a whole should significantly outperform the capabilities of each sensor and the performance should improve as the number of sensors increases, with no mandatory requirement on the transmission of the data of each single sensor toward a centralised control/processing unit; in other words, the network must be scalable and self-organising, i.e. capable of maintaining its functionality (although modifying the performance) when the number of sensor is increased¹;
- a sensor network is ultimately an event-driven system, so that what it is really necessary to guarantee is that the information about events of interest reach the appropriate control nodes, possibly through the simplest propagation mechanism, not necessarily bounded to the common OSI protocol stack layer;
- congestion around the sink nodes should be avoided by introducing some form of distributed processing;
- the information should flow through the network in the simplest possible way, not necessarily relying on sophisticated modulation or multiplexing techniques.
- Summarising, the fundamental requirements of a sensor network are:
 - Very low complexity elementary sensors, associated with a low power consumption and low-cost;
 - High reliability of the decision/estimation/measurement of the network as a whole;
 - Long network life-time for low maintenance and stand-alone operation;
 - High scalability;
 - The resilience to congestion problems in traffic peak conditions.

In past years in world an extensive research and development work is being done to ensure information technology use in agriculture; long range wireless sensor network creation for specific agricultural use, would ensure a PA technological leap, would solve pressing problems for agriculture and would make PA widely available for farmers, even for low scale use (cranberry fields, fruit gardens, bee-gardens etc.). However for existing solutions these problems remain:

- Existing WSN solutions are in experimental development phase; their implementation is not possible without the specific WSN technology developers' assistance.
- Existing WSNs have a short working range (ability to guarantee communication between sensors only at a range of several tens of meters); therefore their implementation in large area is very expensive.
- Existing WSN technology application programming is not possible without deep WSN operating system (open source Tiny OS, commercial ZigBee etc.) knowledge, that is possible only in specialized development centers;
- Presently known WSN physical node technologies with several hundred meters working range don't support available Operating Systems;
- Existing WSNs are not suited for climatic and geographical factors, as well as production manufacturing problems;

- Realistic WSN implementation is unthinkable without specific WSN technology that includes physical nodes, sensors, operating system, application programming environment, competence centre support.³¹²

7.2.1 Pessl Instruments³¹³

iMETOS weather stations are universal devices that can be equipped with up to 80 sensors, depending on the design and your needs. They are sturdy, easy to mount and perfectly designed for a variety of different tasks in different climate zones.

They measure precipitation, soil moisture, wind speed, wind direction, atmospheric pressure, humidity, and temperature. Depending on the application, iMETOS® can be combined with a brightness sensor and monitoring units for leaf wetness, global radiation, surface temperature, etc.

A major advantage of iMETOS® weather stations is that they operate independently of any mains supply. iMETOS uses very little energy and therefore can be run for a long time on the integrated rechargeable storage battery. It is combined with solar cells so that the battery – with its smart charging software for a long life – is constantly recharged. Even in periods of bad weather and in regions with little sunlight, the energy is sufficient to operate the device throughout the year without interruption.

7.2.2 VLITE based technologies

RFID technology with unique properties, whereby you can build a sensor networks with long-range communication, and affordable costs. Technology is internally known as VLIT. It is characterized by 868 MHz working frequency and by protocol that supports communication mode Point-To-Point, Point-To-Multipoint and the relay station of long distance over several devices. In combination with the mobile unit and the software interface being developed by The Ceske Centrum pro Vedu and Spolecnost (CCSS) presents VLIT NODE completely new and unique solution for building mobile sensor networks.

Technical specifications

- The operating frequency of 868 MHz, divided into several sub bands
- Bi-directional communication protocol of anti-collision
- Communication distance of 200 to 800 meters depending on the environment, weather and location sensors
- Different communication modes: challenge, selective call, communications event management
- Support for communication Point-to-point, Point-to-multipoint, multi - hopping
- Memory integration
- Each tag contains a unique number (physical address)
- The calculation of simple operations
- Easy connectivity measuring sensors
- Very low power consumption
- Lifetime 6 months - 5 years (depending on battery size and type of communication)
- Implementation of wireless sensor networks for collecting and transmission of data
- The ability to connect to the existing mobile solutions that ensure the collection of measurement and its transmission to the Internet environment
- Integration into the Web environment, storing data in standardized formats

7.2.3 CCSS mobile unit

The mobile gateway or computer developed by CCSS³¹⁴ (Czech Center for Science and Society) will be collecting data from machinery, sensors or sensor network and transmit the data to a Web server. The gateway will be a small computer kit based on modules compatible with the industrial standard PC104. The boards of this computer are stacked together like building blocks. Each board has mounting holes at the corners, which allow the

³¹² Karel CHARVAT, Zbynek KRIVANEK, Marek MUSIL, Jan JEZEK VLITE NODE – SOLUTION for PRECISION FARMING, IST Africa 2011

³¹³ http://metos.at/joomla/page/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=10&Itemid=29&lang=en

³¹⁴ <http://www.ccsc.cz/en>

boards to be fastened to each other with standoffs. The new standard will define electrical connections, which will be supplemented by proprietary connectors providing specific buses and power connection. The gateway will serve as the main data collector, buffer and transmitter to the outer world. The gateway will consist of power management board (powering of other boards, battery handling), processor board (AVR Atmega with SRAM and flash memory), GPRS modem board (optionally with GPS module) and RS485 expansion board. Again, it is important to develop a pluggable operating system (OS). The system will use modified open source real time operating system Ethernet (www.ethernut.de) with extensions respective to used peripherals and connected sensors. OS consists of several libraries and general API framework for user application with support of easy data acquisition via ISObus standard.

The data is sent to the server by UDP or TCP protocol and then stored into the database. Therefore, we will design several web services accessible via HTTP GET or POST protocols. Server side application will manage the database (this is implemented as Java web application). Appropriate REST services will be implemented. These services will enable client side application to query the database and retrieve output in JSON format. This format can be then easily used for AJAX based client application. The database design has to be tested with special emphasis on performance and scalability.

With the addition of a GNSS receiver, this prototype system can monitor tractor movements on a larger scale, since the path becomes less predictable and requires satellite coverage. The combined use of RFID and GNSS yields much more precise calculation of the position in those cases where satellite coverage is not available, e.g., in warehouses used to store products. The obtained geo-referenced information is then processed by the platform to be represented in a WebGIS application, allowing the workflow for analysis and operations that the case requires. In particular, for each transaction carried out, it is possible to obtain a spatial representation that identifies the areas involved and assess the subsequent operations.

- CPU – 32 bit ARM family;
- interfaces - SPI, I2C, UART, 1-WIRE, USB;
- connection to the Internet - over GSM/GPRS, WiFi, Ethernet;
- connection to WSN base station - over serial connection (UART), built in;
- position identification – GNSS module;
- firmware – real time operating system with UNIX like architecture;
- data logger funkcija, with data buffering memory feature;
- programming language - C with support of embedded assembler, debugging via JTAG

7.2.4 IMCS technologies LUMI node

Sensor node should be considered as one entity with its sensors. Without sensors node loses sense of existence. It means that requirements to sensor node mean requirements to sensors connected too. What kind of sensors is needed and what requirements are applied it is defined by application. This research deals with long range sensor network for precision agriculture especially for protection of American cranberry from radiation frosts.

Combining know how obtained from field experiment described above, research in field of WSN, engineering knowledge a state of the art functional schematics of a new (namely - LUMII WSN) node was created. This schema and mechanical engineering of node solves row of problems of AgroSeNET hardware discovered during research. Schema contains some elements that can be regarded as inventions.

To describe hardware functionality of the LUMII WSN node description should be started with logical components.

Energy harvesting and power management. Different ambient energy sources can produce electrical power. Implementation of photovoltaic energy harvesting today could be done in relatively low costs. Because of its high energy output, photovoltaic cells could be used not only to power up wireless sensor nodes, but also recharge the batteries. Main task of energy harvesting circuit is to gather maximum energy in different solar cell lighting and battery load conditions. For energy harvesting and battery charging of the node solar panel consisting of two solar cells and energy harvesting integrated circuit (IC) LTC3105 from Linear Technologies are chosen. The solution offered is dealing with two tasks; the first one is recharge of the battery, the second is a measurement of solar radiation level. Solar cells are switched in short circuit mode for solar radiation measurement by switching on analog MOSFET switch SW1. Solar cell pyranometer – the problem is that it does not measure the

whole spectrum of the sun radiation. Therefore it is advisable to use a professional pyranometer to calibrate a photovoltaic instrument.

Two SANYO Eneloop Rechargeable lite long life AAA batteries (up to 2000 cycles) are chosen.

Micro-controller. Microcontroller must have enough RAM, to execute the program, and enough flash memory, to store program and data. Microcontroller must have low energy consumption. To connect to all necessary digital sensors and radio transceiver microcontroller must have enough ADC inputs to interface with analog sensors and digital interfaces such as I2C, UART, SDI-12, SPI, 1-wire . The Texas Instruments microcontroller MSP430F2272 with 1 KB RAM and 32 KB flash memory is chosen for LUMII WSN node.

IMCS WSN platform features

Sensor node

- CPU -Texas Instruments (TI) MSP430 family;
- Transceiver - TI family;
- internal sensors - air temperature and humidity, barometric pressure, ambient light;
- external sensors - full range of sensors for environment monitoring;
- interfaces – GPIO, ADC, UART, SDI-12, 2-wire JTAG, 1-Wire, I²C;
- power source - solar panel with energy harvesting feature and long life rechargeable battery located inside the box with transparent lid;
- IP67 rated mount in polycarbonate enclosures with effective membrane filter ventilation;
- Software – operating system with UNIX like architecture.

Further development:

Easy replaceable external module including:

- Additional -sensors e.g. for surface humidity (for instance - leaves), underground water level, soil moisture measurement at different levels;
- hardware bridge from I²C bus to 1-Wire bus, standard sensor interface extensions will be added to provide features according to application requirements;
- bus line buffers to provide possibility to connect sensors over long cables;
- high impedance analog signal instrumentation amplifier with input multiplexer for different chemical element measurement by Ion selective electrodes (pH, ammonium, calcium, chloride, nitrate etc);
- development for use of transceivers for extra-long communication distances e.g. 5 - 15km.

7.2.5 Libelium

Libelium [90] delivers a powerful, modular, easy to program open source sensor platform for the Internet of Things enabling system integrators to implement reliable Smart Cities and M2M solutions with minimum time to market. The platform allows implementation of any Wireless Sensor Network, including Precision Farming applications.

7.2.6 SIEGA SYSTEM

SIEGA SYSTEM is a system based on a sensors network that together with a computer application, allows real time monitoring of a number of variables for precision agriculture [91]. A pilot using Siega System with Libelium WSNs has been deployed in a vineyard in Pontevedra, a city in the Region of Galicia in the North of Spain [92] .

7.2.7 SYNELIXIS

SYNELIXIS offers a set of products that help control farming procedures remotely. Its solutions allow monitor the environmental conditions of farms and the status of automated systems, program and control them through any kind of device. Its solutions cover open fields, greenhouses and livestock raising [93].

7.2.8 Camalie Networks

Camalie Networks' wireless monitoring and control technology offers support to precision farming. Camalie Networks System 3 provides a low cost, scalable, open system, for monitoring and control of agricultural operations. It provides an open source XBee/Arduino compatible platform on which to build specialized wireless sensing and actuation web applications. The Open architecture of this system means there will be many parties capable of supporting and extending it long term. The CS3-Terraduo weather proof, solar powered sensing station is capable of monitoring as many as 12 sensors and controlling up to 8 valves or pumps. Data is taken from the sensors as often as every 15 seconds and relayed back to a gateway and on to a webserver with a database where the data is immediately available for viewing via the internet [94]. Its installations include Stage Coach Vineyards in the Napa Valley where 17 nodes measure soil moistures at 42 locations and ambient temps and humidities at 12 locations spread out across 1.500 acres of vines.

7.3 Wireless Communication Protocols

Wireless communication in embedded systems is a growing field. It can be used in a wide range of situations where mobility is essential and wires are not practical.

Types of wireless technologies being developed range from simple IrDA that uses infrared light for short-range, point-to-point communications, to wireless personal area network (WPAN) for short range, point-to multi-point communications, such as Bluetooth and ZigBee, to mid-range, multi-hop wireless local area network (WLAN), to long-distance cellular phone systems, such as GSM/GPRS and CDMA.

Various wireless standards have been established. Among them, the standards for wireless LAN, IEEE 802.11b ("WiFi") (IEEE, 1999b) and wireless PAN, IEEE 802.15.1 (Bluetooth) (IEEE, 2002) and IEEE 802.15.4 (ZigBee) (IEEE, 2003), are used more widely for measurement and automation applications. All these standards use the instrumentation, scientific and medical (ISM) radio bands, including the sub-GHz bands of 902–928MHz (US), 868–870MHz (Europe), 433.05–434.79MHz (US and Europe) and 314–316MHz (Japan) and the GHz bands of 2.400–2.4835 GHz (worldwide acceptable).

In general, a lower frequency allows a longer transmission range and a stronger capability to penetrate through walls and glass. However, due to the fact that radio waves with lower frequencies are easier to be more easily absorbed by various materials, such as water and trees, and that radio waves with higher frequencies are easier to scatter, effective transmission distance for signals carried by a high frequency radio wave may not necessarily be shorter than that by a lower frequency carrier at the same power rating. The 2.4 GHz band has a wider band width that allows more channels and frequency hopping and permits compact antennas.

The wireless standards also address the network issues for wireless sensors. Three types of networks: star network, hybrid network and mesh network, have been developed and standardized [95].

Some of the main standards of communication for WSNs are described below.

7.3.1 Wireless LAN (IEEE 802.11)

Wireless LAN (IEEE 802.11) is a flexible data communication protocol implemented to extend or substitute for a wired local area network, such as Ethernet. The bandwidth of 802.11b is 11 Mbits and it operates at 2.4 GHz frequency.

7.3.2 Bluetooth (IEEE 802.15.1)

Bluetooth (IEEE 802.15.1) is a wireless protocol that is used for short-range communication. It uses the 2.4 GHz, 915 and 868MHz radio bands to communicate at 1 Mbit between up to eight devices. The Bluetooth is considered a cable replacement for mobile devices. It is mainly designed to maximize the ad-hoc networking functionality. The Bluetooth technology uses star networks, which are composed of piconets and scatternets. Each piconet connects one master node with up to seven slave nodes, whereas each scatternet connects multiple piconets, to form an ad hoc network.

7.3.3 Bluetooth low Energy

Bluetooth low Energy, the ultra-low-power Bluetooth technology is the simplified version of Bluetooth. It uses the same physical layer in 2.4 GHz ISM used by Bluetooth for interoperability with existing Bluetooth devices and allows 1 Mbit/s data rates in up to 10 meters range. Bluetooth low energy is designed to be very efficient at transmitting very small quantities of data at very low latencies to other devices. When compared to classic Bluetooth technology it is at maximum 15 times more efficient. It achieves these efficiency gains by optimizing three basic areas of functionality: connectable and discoverable modes, the number of packets transmitted during connections, and the size of each individual packet. In classic Bluetooth technology, for a device to be connectable or discoverable it must enable its receiver. Therefore, the only way to be responsive is to have the radio active for a significant period of time. A basic requirement for two frequency hopping devices to communicate is that they need to use the same frequency or channel at the same time, they need to be synchronized. When the devices first start communicating, they are not synchronized, and they need to search different channels to find each other. In Bluetooth technology, 32 channels are used. Searching through that many channels takes time, and in Bluetooth technology it can take up to a couple of seconds for two devices to find each other, which consumes power. In Bluetooth low energy technology, instead, there are only three channels used for advertising. This brings Bluetooth low energy to be over 17 times more efficient than classic Bluetooth. There are two other major differences between the two versions of the standard: Bluetooth low energy uses fewer channels, and the hop sequence used by the radios is different. There are two reasons why there are fewer channels: Bluetooth low energy uses a larger modulation index, meaning that its signal takes up more bandwidth, and has relaxed requirements for how steep the channel filters need to be. Because of this, Bluetooth low energy channels are spaced 2 MHz apart, rather than 1 MHz apart as in Bluetooth technology. Both of these design choices were made in order to provide lower power consumption. Another important improvement of the low energy version, is that when a slave device does not have any data to transmit, it does not even have to bother listening to the master device's communication event packets. This enables the slave device to stay in the lowest possible power mode for as long as possible, further saving significant amounts of power. However, if it does have something important to transmit, then it can wake up at the next appropriate communication event and transmit its data very quickly. This enables an excellent compromise between ultra-low power operation and low latency transmission of data. Regarding the network topology, instead, unlike Zigbee and Z-Wave, it does not support mesh networking [96].

7.3.4 IEEE 802.15.4

The IEEE 802.15.4 standard is a physical radio specification providing for low data rate connectivity among relatively simple devices that consume minimal power and typically connect over short distances. It is ideal for monitoring, control, automation, sensing and tracking applications for the home, medical and industrial environments. Features of IEEE 802.15.4 devices include:

- 868MHz band, 1 channel, 20 kbps.
- 915MHz ISM band, 10 channels, 40 kbps.
- 2.4 GHz ISM band, 16 channels, 250 kbps.
- connecting up to 255 devices per network.
- full protocol for transfer reliability.
- power management to ensure low power consumption.

7.3.5 Zigbee

ZigBee is established by the ZigBee Alliance that is supported by more than 70 member companies. It adds network, security and application software to the IEEE 802.15.4 standard. Owing to its low power consumption and simple networking configuration. The ZigBee technology uses hybrid star networks, which uses multiple master nodes with routing capabilities to connect slave nodes, which have no routing capability. Though low-powered, ZigBee devices can transmit data over long distances by passing data through intermediate devices to reach more distant ones, creating a mesh network, as a network with no centralized control or high-power transmitter/receiver able to reach all of the networked devices. The decentralized nature of such wireless ad hoc networks makes them suitable for applications where a central node can't be relied upon. ZigBee is used in applica-

tions that require only a low data rate, long battery life, and secure networking. ZigBee has a defined rate of 250 kbit/s, best suited for periodic or intermittent data or a single signal transmission from a sensor or input device. Applications include wireless that requires short-range wireless transfer of data at relatively low rates. The technology defined by the ZigBee specification is intended to be simpler and less expensive than other WPANs, such as Bluetooth or Wi-Fi. ZigBee networks are secured by 128 bit symmetric encryption keys.

7.3.6 RFID

RFID is a technology that makes use of wireless communication. The protocol was originally developed for short-range product identification, typically covering the 2 mm - 2 m read range, and has been promoted as the replacement technology for the optical bar-code found, with the use of EPC (Electronic Product Code). RFID has the ability to allow energy to penetrate certain goods and to read a tag that is not visible. There are various standards involved in RFID. In our case the reference standard is the ISO/IEC 18000, for item management air interface, defining the parameters for air interface in different frequencies: < 135 kHz, 13.56 MHz, 2.45 GHz, 5.8 GHz, 860-930 MHz and 433 MHz [97].

7.3.7 Ultrawide bandwidth radio

Ultrawide bandwidth radio is a technology which uses a UWB signal with instantaneous spectral occupancy in excess of 500 MHz or a fractional bandwidth of more than 20%. One of the UWB techniques used by WSN applications, is named Impulse Radio-UWB (IR-UWB). The IR-UWB technique relies on ultra-short (nanosecond scale) waveforms that can be free of sine-wave carriers and do not require IF processing because they can operate at baseband. The IR-UWB technique has been selected as the PHY layer of the IEEE 802.15.4a Task Group for WPAN Low Rate Alternative PHY layer. The baseline of 802.15.4a is based on two optional PHYs consisting of a UWB impulse radio (operating in unlicensed UWB spectrum) and another option operating in unlicensed 2.4 GHz spectrum, where the former will be able to deliver communications and high precision ranging [96].

7.3.8 Z-Wave

Z-Wave is a technology developed by the Danish company Zensys. It uses a low-power RF radio for low-power remote control applications. The technology has been standardized by the Z-Wave Alliance. This technology is not compatible with 802.15.4. The main advantage of this technology with respect to 802.15.4 is its operation in sub 1 GHz band. The 2.4 GHz RF band, in fact, is subject to significant interference due to 802.11 and 802.15.1 devices. On the other hand the 868 MHz ISM band used by Z-Wave is limited by European regulations to operate at or under 1%. However 1% duty cycle operation in the band can be enough for most of the control applications. Mesh topologies could be formed, however the addressing scheme used allows a maximum of 232 nodes in the network. Operable data rates are 9.6 kbps and 40 kbps [96].

7.3.9 3G/GPRS

Wireless programming is commonly used in the mobile phone industry to provide dynamic software upgrades and services to thousands of devices at once. Its use in wireless sensor networks reduces operation costs for large-scale deployments. Using 3G technology is solution for sensor applications such as Precision Agriculture where sensor nodes are located in the crop field, places that are difficult to access. The 3G/GPRS technologies allows sensor networks and M2M devices to connect to the Cloud by using high speed WCDMA and HSPA cellular networks in the same way as Smartphones do. This makes it possible for sensor nodes to send not only discrete sensor information such as temperature or humidity (which can be encoded using just a single number) but also complex streams of information such as photos and videos.

8 Conclusions

The following document provides an exhaustive list of relevant aspects that FOODIE project has to take into account for the design and implementation of the proposed agricultural service-based cloud platform. These include the alignment with national and European level policies related to agriculture such as the Water Framework Directive (WTF) or the Common Agriculture Policy (CAP) or current and past initiatives such as INSPIRE, GMES/Copernicus, SISE, GEOSS or GODAN for sharing the large amount of valuable datasets related to environment and agriculture which have been generated over the past years.

Besides, the architectural roadmaps of various projects inline with these initiatives were analysed (e.g., ENVIROFI, AgriXchange, FutureFarm, SmartAgrifood, FISpace, etc.). These projects will provide the baseline for specifying FOODIE architecture, thus ensuring that it is also aligned and compliant with the existing environmental and agricultural ICT infrastructures.

The document also reviewed several standards commonly used in the geospatial, environmental and agricultural domains to encode, access and exchange information as well as those related to the semantic tagging and publishing of datasets. In this regard, several openly available datasets and vocabularies have been identified, which can be used in the scope of the project in order to improve the semantic tagging and publication of datasets within the platform repositories as well as by enabling the provision of improved tools and advisory services for the different stakeholders (by integrating and fusing these external data with the datasets stored in the FOODIE platform).

Finally, several free and open-source technologies and software solutions were identified – many of the coming directly from the open-source geospatial community - as potential building blocks of the FOODIE service platform hub (e.g., storage databases, map visualization, data processing and fusion tools, etc.) which will allow the consortium to provide a cost-effective service-based platform for the end-users, by avoiding incurring in software licensing costs in most cases.

References

References

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- [1] Douglas Nebert (2004). Developing Spatial Data Infrastructures: The SDI Cookbook. GSDI, 2004
 - [2] <http://dublincore.org/>
 - [3] http://joinup.ec.europa.eu/asset/core_location/description
 - [4] <http://sdmx.org/>
 - [5] <http://www.thegigasforum.eu/forum/welcome.html>
 - [6] http://www.w3.org/QA/2012/06/implementing_adms_and_the_core.html
 - [7] INSPIRE (2008). INSPIRE Metadata Regulation 03.12.2008.
 - [8] INSPIRE (2009). Corrigendum to INSPIRE Metadata Regulation 15.12.2009.
 - [9] ISO/TC211 (2003). ISO 19115: international metadata standard for geographic information.
 - [10] Javier Nogueras-Iso, F. Javier Zarazaga-Soria, Pedro R. Muro-Medrano: Geographic information metadata for spatial data infrastructures - resources, interoperability and information retrieval. Springer 2005: I-XXI, 1-263
 - [11] Sven Schade and Paul Smits (2012). Why Linked Data Should Not Lead to Next Generation SDI. IGARSS 2012, Munich, Germany.
 - [12] Kaufman, Y. J. and D. Tanre (1992) 'Atmospherically resistant vegetation index (ARVI) for EOS-MODIS', in 'Proc. IEEE Int. Geosci. and Remote Sensing Symp. '92, IEEE, New York, 261-270.
 - [13] Pinty, B. and M. M. Verstraete (1992) 'GEMI: A non-linear index to monitor global vegetation from satellites', Vegetatio, 101, 15-20.
 - [14] Gower, S. T., Kucharik, C. J., & Norman, J. M. (1999). Direct and indirect estimation of leaf area index fAPAR, and net primary production of terrestrial ecosystems. Remote Sensing of Environment, 70(1), 29-51.
 - [15] Carlson, T. N., & Ripley, D. A. (1997). On the relation between NDVI, fractional vegetation cover, and leaf area index. Remote sensing of Environment, 62(3), 241-252.
 - [16] Huete, A. R., & Jackson, R. D. (1987). Suitability of spectral indices for evaluating vegetation characteristics on arid rangelands. Remote sensing of environment, 23(2), 213-218.
 - [17] Huete, A. R., & Jackson, R. D. (1988). Soil and atmosphere influences on the spectra of partial canopies. Remote Sensing of Environment, 25(1), 89-105.
 - [18] Huete, A., Justice, C., & Van Leeuwen, W. (1999). MODIS vegetation index (MOD13). Algorithm theoretical basis document.
 - [19] Richardson, A. J., & Everitt, J. H. (1992). Using spectral vegetation indices to estimate rangeland productivity. Geocarto International, 7(1), 63-69.
 - [20] Lyon, J. G., Yuan, D., Lunetta, R. S., & Elvidge, C. D. (1998). A change detection experiment using vegetation indices. Photogrammetric Engineering and Remote Sensing, 64(2), 143-150.
 - [21] Senseman, G. M., Bagley, C. F., & Tweddale, S. A. (1996). Correlation of rangeland cover measures to satellite-imagery-derived vegetation indices. Geocarto International, 11(3), 29-38.
 - [22] Marsett, R. C., Qi, J., Heilman, P., Biedenbender, S. H., Watson, M. C., Amer, S., ... & Marsett, R. (2006). Remote sensing for grassland management in the arid southwest. Rangeland Ecology & Management, 59(5), 530-540.
 - [23] Qi, J., Marsett, R., Heilman, P., Biedenbender, S., Moran, S., Goodrich, D., & Weltz, M. (2002). RANGES improves satellite-based information and land cover assessments in southwest United States. Eos, Transactions American Ge

ophysical Union, 83(51), 601-606.

- [24] Qi, J., Marsett, R. C., Moran, M. S., Goodrich, D. C., Heilman, P., Kerr, Y. H., ... & Zhang, X. X. (2000). Spatial and temporal dynamics of vegetation in the San Pedro River basin area. *Agricultural and forest meteorology*, 105(1), 55-68.
- [25] Qi, J., Chehbouni, A., Huete, A. R., Kerr, Y. H., & Sorooshian, S. (1994). A modified soil adjusted vegetation index. *Remote sensing of environment*, 48(2), 119-126.
- [26] Qi, J., Kerr, Y., & Chehbouni, A. (1994). External factor consideration in vegetation index development.
- [27] Ray, T. W. (1994). A FAQ on vegetation in remote sensing. Available via anonymous FTP at: kepler.gps.caltech.edu/pub/terrell/rsvefaq.txt.
- [28] Liu, J., Qi, J., Jiang, Z., & Huete, A. (2007). Interpretation of the modified soil-adjusted vegetation index isolines in red-NIR reflectance space. *SPIE-International Society for Optical Engineering*.
- [29] Fröhlich, B., Bach, E., Walde, I., Hese, S., Schmullius, C., & Denzler, J. (2013). LAND COVER CLASSIFICATION OF SATELLITE IMAGES USING CONTEXTUAL INFORMATION. *ISPRS Annals of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences*, 3, W1.
- [30] Breytenbach, A., Eloff, C., & Pretorius, E. (2013). Comparing Three Spaceborne Optical Sensors by Fine Scale Pixel-based Urban Land Cover Classification Products. *South African Journal of Geomatics*, 2(4), 309-324.
- [31] Laliberte, A. S., Browning, D. M., Herrick, J. E., & Gronemeyer, P. (2010). Hierarchical object-based classification of ultra-high-resolution digital mapping camera (DMC) imagery for rangeland mapping and assessment. *Journal of spatial science*, 55(1), 101-115.
- [32] Griffith, J. S. Object-Oriented Method to Classify the Land Use and Land Cover in San Antonio using eCognition Object-Oriented Image Analysis.
- [33] Myburgh, G., & Van Niekerk, A. (2013). Effect of feature dimensionality on object-based land cover classification: A comparison of three classifiers. *South African Journal of Geomatics*, 2(1), 13-27.
- [34] Laliberte, A. S., Browning, D. M., & Rango, A. (2012). A comparison of three feature selection methods for object-based classification of sub-decimeter resolution UltraCam-L imagery. *International Journal of Applied Earth Observation and Geoinformation*, 15, 70-78.
- [35] Peña-Barragán, J. M., Ngugi, M. K., Plant, R. E., & Six, J. (2011). Object-based crop identification using multiple vegetation indices, textural features and crop phenology. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 115(6), 1301-1316.
- [36] Advanced Training on Monitoring Of Crops Through Satellite Technology. A joint FAO, UN & SUPARCO publication. 2012
- [37] Matsushita, B., Yang, W., Chen, J., Onda, Y., & Qiu, G. (2007). Sensitivity of the enhanced vegetation index (EVI) and normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI) to topographic effects: a case study in high-density cypress forest. *Sensors*, 7(11), 2636-2651.
- [38] Sayar, A., Eken, S., & Mert, U. (2013, November). Registering landsat-8 mosaic images: A case study on the Marmara sea. In *Electronics, Computer and Computation (ICECCO), 2013 International Conference on* (pp. 375-377). IEEE.
- [39] Brown, M., & Lowe, D. G. (2007). Automatic panoramic image stitching using invariant features. *International Journal of Computer Vision*, 74(1), 59-73.
- [40] Alganci, U., Sertel, E., Ozdogan, M., & Ormeci, C. (2013). Parcel-Level Identification of Crop Types Using Different Classification Algorithms and Multi-Resolution Imagery in Southeastern Turkey. *Photogrammetric engineering and remote sensing*, 79(11), 1053-1065.
- [41] Mugisha S, Huising J (2002). Optimal Resolution for Large-Scale Vegetation Mapping Using Air-Borne Multispectral Data. *International Archives of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing Spatial Info. Sci.*, 34(6): 155-161.
- [42] Mugisha, S., Tenywa, M. M., & Burt, P. J. A. (2010). An improved technique for the prediction of optimal image resolution (s) for large-scale mapping of savannah ecosystems. *African Journal of Environmental Science and Technology*, 4(10), 709-717.
- [43] Alganci, U., Sertel, E., Kaya, S., & BerkUstundag, B. (2013, August). A research on agricultural mapping capabilities of

the SPOT 6 satellite images. InAgro-Geoinformatics (Agro-Geoinformatics), 2013 Second International Conference on (pp. 93-96). IEEE.

- [44] Duro, D. C., Franklin, S. E., & Dubé, M. G. (2012). A comparison of pixel-based and object-based image analysis with selected machine learning algorithms for the classification of agricultural landscapes using SPOT-5 HRG imagery. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 118, 259-272.
- [45] Johansen, K., Phinn, S., Witte, C., Philip, S., & Newton, L. (2009). Mapping banana plantations from object-oriented classification of SPOT-5 imagery. *Photogrammetric Engineering and Remote Sensing*, 75(9), 1069-1081.
- [46] Alparone, L., Wald, L., Chanussot, J., Thomas, C., Gamba, P., & Bruce, L. M. (2007). Comparison of pansharpening algorithms: Outcome of the 2006 GRS-S data-fusion contest. *Geoscience and Remote Sensing, IEEE Transactions on*, 45(10), 3012-3021.
- [47] Bhandari, A. K., Kumar, A., & Padhy, P. K. (2011). Enhancement of low contrast satellite images using discrete cosine transform and singular value decomposition. *World Academy of Science, Engineering and Technology*, 79, 35-41.
- [48] Veena, G., Uma, V., & Reddy, C. G. Contrast Enhancement for Remote Sensing Images with Discrete Wavelet Transform. *International Journal of Recent Technology and Engineering (IJRTE)*, ISSN, 2277-3878.
- [49] Mishra, R., Sharma, U., & Shrivastava, M. (2014). Contrast Enhancement of Remote Sensing Images using DWT with Kernel Filter and DTCWT. *International Journal of Computer Applications*, 87.
- [50] M. Venkata Dasu, VR Anitha, Fahimuddin Shaik and B. Abdul Rahim. An Application of Decorrelation and Linear Contrast Stretching Methods on Satellite Images. *International Journal of Electrical, Electronics & Communication Engineering*.
- [51] Candela, L.; Castelli, D.; Ferro, N.; Ioannidis, Y.; Koutrika, G.; Meghini, C.; Pagano, P.; Ross, S.; Soergel, D.; Agosti, M.; Dobрева, M.; Katifori, V.; Schuldt, H. The DELOS Digital Library Reference Model - Foundations for Digital Libraries. Version 0.98 (February 2008)
- [52] Maris Alberts, Karel Charvat, Otakar Čerba, Peteris Bruns, Premysl Vohnout, Stepan Kafka, Pavel Vlach Review of geographic resources metadata and related metadata standards SmartOpenData - Linked Open Data for environment protection in Smart Regions 2014
- [53] The Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting. Version 2.0. 2008. Available: <http://www.openarchives.org/OAI/openarchivesprotocol.html>
- [54] Open Archives Initiative Object Reuse and Exchange. ORE User Guide – Primer. Version 1.0. 2008. Available: <http://www.openarchives.org/ore/1.0/primer>
- [55] FAO, 2014. AGRIS: International Information System for the Agricultural science and technology. Available from: <http://agris.fao.org/agris-search/index.do> [4/2014].
- [56] CIARD R.I.N.G, 2014. A directory of information services and datasets in agriculture. Available from: <http://ring.ciard.net/about-ring> [4/2014]
- [57] Subirats, I., Zeng, ML., 2012. How to select appropriate encoding strategies for producing Linked Open Data (LOD)-enabled bibliographic data. Available from: <http://aims.fao.org/lode/bd> [4/2014].
- [58] Subirats, I. 2014. Linked Open Data: A Use Case in the Agricultural Domain. Available from: <http://aims.fao.org/community/blogs/linked-open-data-use-case-agricultural-domain> [4/2014].
- [59] FAO, 2014. AQUASTAT Countries, regions, transboundary river basins. Available from: http://www.fao.org/nr/water/aquastat/countries_regions/index.stm [3/2014].
- [60] FAO, 2014. FAOSTAT. Available from: <http://faostat.fao.org/> [3/2014].
- [61] World Bank, 2014. World Bank Data Agriculture & Rural Development. Available from: <http://data.worldbank.org/topic/agriculture-and-rural-development> [4/2014].
- [62] International Monetary Fund, 2014. World Economic Outlook Database. Available from: <http://www.imf.org/external/pubs/ft/weo/2013/02/weodata/index.aspx> [3/2014].
- [63] GBIF, 2014. Free and open access to biodiversity data. Available from: <http://www.gbif.org/dataset> [4/2014].

- [64] Bioversity International, 2014. Bioversity International: research for development in agricultural and forest biodiversity - Databases. Available from: <http://www.bioversityinternational.org/e-library/databases/> [4/2014].
- [65] LP DAAC, 2014. The Land Processes Distributed Active Archive Center. Available from: <https://lpdaac.usgs.gov/> [4/2014].
- [66] ESA, 2014. Earth observation data from the European Space Agency. Available from: <https://earth.esa.int/web/guest/home> [4/2014].
- [67] NOAA, 2014. The National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration. Available from: <http://www.noaa.gov/> [4/2014].
- [68] EEA, 2014. European Environment Agency - Data and Maps. Available from: <http://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps> [4/2014].
- [69] Copernicus, 2014. The European Earth observation programme. Available from: <http://www.copernicus.eu/> [4/2014].
- [70] Eurostat, 2014. Your key to European statistics. Available from: <http://epp.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/portal/page/portal/eurostat/home> [4/2014].
- [71] DATA.GOV 2014. U.S. Government's open data - Data Agriculture Catalog. Available from: <http://catalog.data.gov/dataset?groups=agriculture8571> [4/2014].
- [72] GOVERNMENT OF SPAIN 2014. Catalog of Public Information, the single point of access to data sets of the General State Administration. Available from: <http://www.datos.gob.es/?language=in> [4/2014].
- [73] GOVERNMENT OF SPAIN 2014. Data Catalogue. Available from: <http://www.datos.gob.es/catalogo/127/all/all/all?title=&order=6&language=in> [4/2014].
- [74] GOVERNMENT OF GALICIA 2014. Government of Galicia Open Data Portal. Available from: <http://abertos.xunta.es/portada> [4/2014].
- [75] GOVERNMENT OF CASTILLA AND LEON 2014. Open Data Portal. Available from: http://www.datosabiertos.jcyl.es/web/jcyl/RISP/es/Plantilla66y33/1284162103951/_/_/ [4/2014].
- [76] MeteoGalicia 2014. Weather Stations Data Portal. Available from: <http://www2.meteogalicia.es/galego/observacion/estacions/listaEstacions.asp> [4/2014].
- [77] MeteoGalicia 2014. Weather and Oceanographic Prediction API. Available from: <http://www.meteogalicia.es/web/proxectos/meteosix.action> [4/2014].
- [78] MeteoGalicia 2014. Thematic Realtime Environmental Distributed Data Service. Available from: <http://www.meteogalicia.es/web/modelos/threddsIndex.action> [4/2014].
- [79] MeteoGalicia 2014. Weather Radar Catalog. Available from: <http://mandeo.meteogalicia.es/thredds/catalog/observacion/RADAR/catalog.html> [4/2014].
- [80] Pontevedra Region Government 2014. Phytosanitary Warnings, Phytosanitary Advices and Meteorological information. Available from: http://www.efa-dip.org/es/index_es.htm [4/2014].
- [81] National Geographic Institute 2014. Aerial photos and satellite images Portal. Available from: <http://www.ign.es/ign/layoutIn/faimgsatsatellite.do> [4/2014].
- [82] Goodchild, MF., 2007. Citizens as sensors: the world of volunteered geography. GeoJournal August 2007, Volume 69, Issue 4, pp 211-221.
- [83] Dietz, C., Suh J., 2012. Volunteered Geographic Information: Selected Web Resources. Available from: <http://www.ala.org/magirt/sites/ala.org.magirt/files/content/publicationsab/VGI%20MAGIRT%20EP%2012-postfinal.pdf> [4/2014].
- [84] Esri, 2014. GeoNode: All about open analysis data and maps. Available from: <http://geocommons.com/> [4/2014]
- [85] Geonode, 2014. Open Source Geospatial Content Management System. Available from: <http://geonode.org/> [4/2014]

- [86] WFP, 2014. WFPGeoNode. Available from: <http://geonode.wfp.org/> . [4/2014]
- [87] Google, 2014. Map Marker. Available from: <http://www.google.com/mapmaker> [4/2014]
- [88] OpenStreetMap, 2014. OpenStreetMap. Available from: <http://www.openstreetmap.org/> [4/2014]
- [89] Wikimapia, 2014. Wikimapia. Available from: <http://wikimapia.org/> [4/2014]
- [90] Libelium, 2014. Libelium. Connecting Sensors to the Cloud. Available from: <http://www.libelium.com/> [4/2014]
- [91] Austen Group, 2011. Siega - Agricultural Management Expert System. Available from: <http://www.siegasystem.com/en/index.html> [4/2014]
- [92] Libelium, 2012. Smart Agriculture project in Galicia to monitor vineyards with Waspote. Available from: http://www.libelium.com/smart_agriculture_vineyard_sensors_waspote/ [4/2014]
- [93] Synelixis Solutions Ltd, 2014. We bring state-of-the-art technology to your farm. Available from: <http://syngreen.synelixis.com/index.php/en/solution> [4/2014]
- [94] Camalie networks. Wireless Agricultural Monitoring and Control. Available from: <http://99.115.132.118/html/index.htm> [4/2014]
- [95] Ning, W., Naiqian Z., Maohua W., 2006. Wireless sensors in agriculture and food industry—Recent development and future perspective. Computers and Electronics in Agriculture.
- [96] Buratti, Ch., Conti, A. , Dardari, D., Verdone, R., 2009. An Overview on Wireless Sensor Networks Technology and Evolution. Sensors (Basel)
- [97] Ruiz-Garcia L., Lunadei L., Barreiro P., Robla JI., 2009. A Review of Wireless Sensor Technologies and Applications in Agriculture and Food Industry: State of the Art and Current Trends.Sensors (Basel)
- [98] Senkler, K., Voges, U. (ed). 2007. OpenGIS Catalogue Service Specification – ISO Metadata Application Profile [online]. Open Geospatial Consortium. Available at: http://portal.opengeospatial.org/files/?artifact_id=20555.
- [99] Beaujardiere, J. (ed)., 2006. OpenGIS Web Map Server Implementation Specification. Version 1.3.0 [online]. Open Geospatial Consortium. Available at: http://portal.opengeospatial.org/files/?artifact_id=14416.
- [100] Whiteside, A. (ed). 2007. Web Coordinate Transformation Service (WCTS) Interface Engineering Report [online]. Open Geospatial Consortium. Available at http://portal.opengeospatial.org/files/?artifact_id=24314.
- [101] Schutt, P. Whiteside, A. (ed) et al. 2005. OpenGIS Web Processing Service [online]. Open Geospatial Consortium. Available at: http://portal.opengeospatial.org/files/?artifact_id=24151.
- [102] D.2.8.I.7 INSPIRE Data Specification on Hydrography – Guidelines, version 3.1. Joint Research Centre of the European Commission. Available at: http://inspire.jrc.ec.europa.eu/documents/Data_Specifications/INSPIRE_DataSpecification_HY_v3.1.pdf.
- [103] European Commission, 2012a. Copernicus. Copernicus, The European Earth Observation Programme. Available at: <http://copernicus.eu> [Accessed December 19, 2012].
- [104] HABITATS, 2011. D4.1 State of the Art of existing SDI
- [105] Erwin Goor (VITO) GIO GLOBAL LAND COMPONENT - LOT I "OPERATION OF THE GLOBAL LAND COMPONENT" Framework Service Contract N° 388533 (JRC) SOFTWARE DESIGN DOCUMENT PRODUCT DISTRIBUTION FACILITY (PDF) 2014
- [106] Hřebíček, J. & Pillmann, W., 2009. Shared Environmental Information System and Single Information Space in Europe for the Environment: Antipodes or Associates? In Proceedings of the European conference of the Czech Presidency of the Council of the EU: TOWARDS eENVIRONMENT. European conference of the Czech Presidency of the Council of the EU TOWARDS eENVIRONMENT. Prague, Czech Republic: Masaryk University. Available at: <http://www.e-envi2009.org/proceedings.pdf>.
- [107] Pillmann, W. et al., 2009. Screening of Information Sources for an Integrated Environmental Information Space.
- [108] O’Flaherty, J., 2008. Towards a Single Information Space for the Environment in Europe., Brussels, Belgium. Availa-

ble at: ftp://ftp.cordis.europa.eu/pub/fp7/ict/docs/sustainable-growth/sise-workshop-report-08_en.pdf.

- [109] Klien, E., Annoni, A. & Marchetti, P.G., 2009. The GIGAS project – an action in support to GEOSS, INSPIRE, and GMES.
- [110] Global Agricultural Monitoring System of Systems: http://www.earthobservations.org/cop_ag_gams.shtml
- [111] http://europa.eu/pol/agr/index_en.htm
- [112] Agricultural Policy Perspectives Brief, N° 5, */ December 2013, Overview of CAP Reform 2014 – 2020, http://ec.europa.eu/agriculture/policy-perspectives/policy-briefs/05_en.pdf
- [113] Water Framework Directive: http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Water_Framework_Directive
- [114] WATER FRAMEWORK DIRECTIVE: THE WAY TOWARDS HEALTHY WATERS", <http://www.umweltdaten.de/publikationen/fpdf-l/4194.pdf>
- [115] RIVER BASIN NETWORK on Water Framework Directive and Agriculture , <http://www.ecologic.eu/sites/files/publication/2013/River%20Basin%20Network%20-%20Final%20Report%20.pdf>
- [116] Habitats Directive , Document 31992L0043 <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:31992L0043>
- [117] Botts, M., Percivall, G., Reed, C., Davidson, J. 2008. OGC® Sensor Web Enablement: Overview and High Level Architecture. Pages 175 – 190. In Nittel, S., Labrinidis, A., Stefanidis, A. 2008. Lecture Notes in Computer Science. 1st edition. Berlin Heidelberg New York: Springer. 270 pages. ISBN 3-540-79995-8.
- [118] Botts, m., Percivall, g., Reed, c., Davidson, j. 2007. OGC White Paper OGC® - Sensor Web Enablement: Overview And High Level Architecture [online]. Open Geospatial Consortium. Available at: http://portal.opengeospatial.org/files/?artifact_id=25562.
- [119] ISO 19156 Geographic Information – Observations and Measurements. International Organization for Standardization: Geneva. 46 pages.
- [120] Cox, S. (ed). 2007. Observations and Measurements – Part 1 – Observation Schema [online]. Open Geospatial Consortium. Available at: http://portal.opengeospatial.org/files/?artifact_id=22466
- [121] Cox, S. (ed) 2011. Observations and Measurements – XML Implementation [online]. Open Geospatial Consortium. Available at: http://portal.opengeospatial.org/files/?artifact_id=41510.
- [122] Botts, M., Robin, A. (ed). 2007. OpenGIS® Sensor Model Language (SensorML) Implementation Specification [online]. Open Geospatial Consortium. Available at: http://portal.opengeospatial.org/files/?artifact_id=21273.
- [123] Robin, A. (ed). 2011. OGC® SWE Common Data Model Encoding Standard [online]. Open Geospatial Consortium. Available at: http://portal.opengeospatial.org/files/?artifact_id=41157.
- [124] O'Reilly, T. (ed) 2012. OGC® PUCK Protocol Standard Version 1.4 [online]. Open Geospatial Consortium. Available at: https://portal.opengeospatial.org/files/?artifact_id=47604.
- [125] Havens, S. (ed) 2007. OpenGIS® Transducer Markup Language (TML) Implementation Specification [online]. Open Geospatial Consortium. Available at: http://portal.opengeospatial.org/files/?artifact_id=19371.
- [126] Na, A., Priest, M. (ed) 2007. Sensor Observation Service [online]. Open Geospatial Consortium. Available at: http://portal.opengeospatial.org/files/?artifact_id=26667.
- [127] Simonis, I., Echterhoff, J. (ed) 2011. OGC Sensor Planning Service Implementation Standard [online]. Open Geospatial Consortium. Available at: http://portal.opengeospatial.org/files/?artifact_id=38478.
- [128] Simonis, I. (ed) 2006. OGC® Sensor Alert Service Candidate Implementation Specification [online]. Open Geospatial Consortium. Available at: http://portal.opengeospatial.org/files/?artifact_id=15588.
- [129] Simonis, I., Wytzisk, A. (ed). 2003. Web Notification Service [online]. Open Geospatial Consortium. Available at: http://portal.opengeospatial.org/files/?artifact_id=1367
- [130] Charvat, K., Horakova, S., Wolfert, S., Holster, H., Schmid, O., Pesonen, L., Martini, D., Mietzsch, E., Mildorf, T., 2012. Final Strategic Research Agenda (SRA): Common Basis for policy making for the introduction of innovative approaches to data exchange in the agri-food industry. Available from:

http://www.researchgate.net/publication/235110911_Final_SRA_%27Common_Basis_for_policy_making_for_introduction_of_innovative_approaches_on_data_exchange_in_agri-food_industry%27

- [131] Kunisch, M., Frisch, J., Martini, D. and Böttinger S. agroXML – a standardized language for data exchange in agriculture. Available from: http://www.itfoodtrace.com/dateien/EFITA_Kunisch_et_al.pdf
- [132] Pesonen, L., Fusai, B., Rehben, E., Koistinen, M. 2012. AgriXchange D4.5 Report describing the reference framework; design and verification. Available from: <http://www.agrixchange.org/results/deliverables>.
- [133] Pesonen, L., Lokers, R., Schmitz, M., Ronkainen, A., Koistinen, M., Rehben, E. and Turchi, A. 2012. AgriXchange D4.3 The basic design. Available from: <http://www.agrixchange.org/results/deliverables>.
- [134] Pesonen, L., Fusai, B., Rehben, E., Koistinen, M. 2012. AgriXchange D4.4 Information models of the three selected use cases LPIS, GeoFer-tilizer and Animal Registration
- [135] Charvat, K., Horakova, S., Wolfert, S., Holster, H., Schmid, O., Pesonen, L., Martini, D., Mietzsch, E., Mildorf, T. 2012. Final Strategic Research Agenda (SRA): Common Basis for policy making for the introduction of innovative approaches to data exchange in the agri-food industry. Available from: <http://www.agrixchange.org/results/deliverables>
- [136] Coene, Y. and Gasser, R. (2007). Joint Operability Workshop Report. Towards a single information space for Environment in Europe, Frascati. Available at: ftp://ftp.cordis.europa.eu/pub/ist/docs/environment/sise-workshop-report_en.pdf
- [137] Reference Model for Service Oriented Architecture 1.0". Committee Specification 1, 2006. Available at: <http://www.oasis-open.org/committees/download.php/19679/soa-rm-cs.pdf>
- [138] Usländer (ed.) (2007). Reference Model for the ORCHESTRA Architecture (RM-OA) Version 2.1. OGC Best Practices Document 07-097
- [139] Usländer, T. (ed.). (2009). Specification of the Sensor Service Architecture, Version 3.0 (Rev. 3.1). OGC Discussion Paper 09-132r1. Deliverable D2.3.4 of the European Integrated Project SANY, FP6-IST-033564.
- [140] Simonis, I. (ed.) (2008). OGC® Sensor Web Enablement Architecture". OGC Best Practices Document 06-021r4, Version 0.4.0. Available at: <http://www.opengeospatial.org/standards/bp>
- [141] Percivall, G. (ed.) (2003). OGC Reference Model Version 0.1.3", Open Geospatial Consortium Document 03-040. Available at: http://portal.opengeospatial.org/files/?artifact_id=3836&version=3
- [142] Object Management Group (OMG) (2007). Unified Modeling Language: Superstructure, version 2.1.1.1. OMG Document formal/07-02-05.
- [143] Percivall, G. (ed.) (2008) OGC Reference Model Version 2.0, Open Geospatial Consortium Document 08-062r4. Available at: <http://orm.opengeospatial.org/>
- [144] Usländer, T (2010). Service-oriented Design of Environmental Information Systems. PhD thesis of the Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT). KIT Scientific Publishing. ISBN 978-3-86644-499-7. Available at: <http://digbib.ubka.uni-karlsruhe.de/volltexte/1000016721>
- [145] Klopfer, M. and Simonis, I. (eds.) (2009). SANY - an open service architecture for sensor networks. ISBN 978-3-00-028571-4. Available at: <http://www.sany-ip.eu/publications/3317>
- [146] Richardson, L. and Ruby, S. (2007). RESTful Web Services. O'Reilly Media, Inc. ISBN-10: 0-596-52926-0.
- [147] Kunz, S. and Usländer, T. (eds.) (2011). Specification of the SII Implementation Architecture (second issue). Deliverable D4.7 of EO2HEAVEN. Available at: <http://www.eo2heaven.org/sites/default/files/D4.7%20Specification%20of%20the%20SII%20Implementation%20Architecture.pdf>
- [148] Fernando Ubieta Aforo Information Society and Rural Development Evaluation Scenario, <http://www.ruralwins.org/images/FernandoUbieta.pdf>
- [149] Dragan Stokic, Ana Teresa Correia, Martin John, Brian Wall, Fernando Ubieta, Vania Bicocchi, Massimo Garuti, Alvaro Oliveira, Juan Antonio Alvarez, Itziar Cuenca, Julio Font, Maria Acilu, Dimitris Kiritsis Dragan Stokic, Ana Teresa Correia, John Martin Agri-Food Roadmaps, IST-2001-37258, Roadmap based on business demands for each sector

-
- [150] GIGAS Project Final Report, Publishable Summary, <http://www.thegigasforum.eu/cgi-bin/download.pl?f=530.pdf>
-
- [151] A5.2-D2 [2.0] Specification Introduction and Overview, http://www.esdi-humboldt.eu/files/0906-a5_2-d2_specification_introduction_and_overview-fhg-igd-002-final.pdf
-
- [152] D-4.1 State of the Art of existing SDI, HABITATS, CIP- ICT-PSP-2009-3-250455, Social Validation of INSPIRE Annex III Data Structures in EU Habitats, 2010
-
- [153] D4.1.3 Operational System V3, A service platform for aggregation, processing and analysis of urban and regional planning data, 2014
-
- [154] Karel Charvat, Pavel Gnip, Premysl Vohnout, Karel Charvat jr VISION FOR A FARM OF TOMORROW, IST Africa 2011
-
- [155] Edward Nash (UR), Raimo Nikkilä (TKK), Sascha Kluger (Agrocom), Kai Oetzel (Agrocom), Liisa Pesonen (MTT), Ilkka Seilonen (TKK), Jens Wiebensohn (UR) Machine-readable encoding for definitions of data required to assess compliance to agricultural management and crop production standards FUTUREFARM Integration of Farm Management Information Systems to support real-time management decisions and compliance of management standards, 2010
-
- [156] Hans Schaffers, Javier García Guzmán, Mariano Navarro de la Cruz, Christian Merz at all Living Labs for Rural Development Results from the C@R Integrated Project, Published by: TRAGSA and FAO, ISBN-13: 978-84-693-0040-4
-
- [157] K. Charvat junior, P Gnip, Karel Charvat COIN – Module for Tactical planning of agriculture production. EFITA/WCCA 2011, Praha
-
- [158] Eva Pauknerova, Interconnecting eGovernment and INSPIRE, Czech Office for Surveying, Mapping and Cadastre, Prague, Czech Republic
-
- [159] Jan Ježek, Michal Kepka, Server-side solution for sensor data, in ICT in Agriculture, Food and Environment – Where we are? Where we go? In Press
-
- [160] LAUN, Wolfgang. A JAXB Tutorial [online]. 2008, 14. 4. 2011 [cit. 2011-04-30]. WWW: <http://jaxb.java.net/tutorial/>.
-

Table 7 References